

**The Impact of ‘Face Culture’ on Chinese International Students’
Developing Identity as Learners and Speakers of English**

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Abstract

Globalization in higher education has led to an increase in a large number of international students moving to and studying in English-speaking countries, with Chinese international students making up a significant proportion of that number. This study explores the relationship between ‘face’ culture, a key facet of Chinese social dynamics, and the evolving identities of Chinese international students as English language learners and speakers. The concept of ‘face’, deeply rooted in Chinese culture and people’s daily lives, represents Chinese Confucian values and emphasizes social reputation, harmony, and preservation of dignity. In the context of English language acquisition, this cultural element of ‘face’ can have a profound influence on how Chinese students perceive, adopt, and adapt to the English language and its associated educational environment.

This research employs a qualitative approach: a pilot study as well as semi-structured interviews to collect data and analyse the contents in order to unravel the multilayered connections between ‘face’ culture and the linguistic and socio-cultural identities of Chinese international students in their social and academic life in the UK. Through the perspectives of Chinese international students and the lecturers who have or have had experiences with teaching Chinese students in the UK, and analysis of relevant literature, this study explores how ‘face’ culture impacts Chinese international students as English learners and speakers. It also examines how ‘face’ affects their interactions with the lecturers, as well as their participation in classroom activities and discussions. Moreover, the research also delves into the influence of ‘face’ culture on Chinese international students’ development of intercultural communication skills, which play a vital role in fostering effective cross-cultural exchanges and shaping their own identities.

The findings of this study highlight the complex relationship between ‘face’ culture and Chinese international students’ perceptions towards it. Chinese international students may find themselves struggling with a tension between the cultural norms of self-confidence in Western academic contexts and their innate tendency to maintain ‘face’ or not ‘lose face’”. As a result, their learning experience in the UK may have more challenges that extend beyond simple language competence, and gender can also be considered as one of the challenges. The desire to ‘maintain face’ or not ‘lose face’ can lead to a preference for more passive language use, hindering authentic engagement in communication within or outside of the classroom and limiting opportunities for linguistic development. Moreover, the fear of ‘losing face’ may discourage students from seeking help or clarification from their peers or lecturers, inhibiting their comprehensive language development.

Conversely, ‘face’ culture can also function as a motivational factor. Chinese international students might strive for linguistic excellence to enhance their social standing and pursue approval from other Chinese students and native speakers in the UK. Some Chinese international students may also feel ‘face’ has minimal or no influence on them. This dual role of ‘face’ culture in language acquisition underlines its impact on learners’ identities and highlights the need for educational approaches that recognize these cultural differences. Educators or lecturers can play a crucial role in creating classroom environments, as also noted and agreed by many of the participants in this research, where they should be aware of diverse cultural perspectives, fostering a safe environment for students to navigate the challenges posed by ‘face’ culture.

In conclusion, the intertwining of ‘face’ culture and the development of Chinese international students’ identities as English language learners and speakers can be a challenging phenomenon, but also full of opportunities. The researcher intends that the findings of this thesis will underscore the importance of awareness and promoting cultural sensitivity in English language education, enabling a more encouraging and effective language learning experience for Chinese international students. By acknowledging the involved interaction between ‘face’ culture and identity, lecturers and institutions can foster a safer environment that encourages students to embrace academic and social challenges while honouring their cultural differences.

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Author's Declaration

I hereby declare that this thesis is the result of the researcher's own work except for citations and quotations, which have been explicitly acknowledged in the text, and that this work has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

This chapter provides a brief introduction to the study and also presents and discusses the background and rationale of the study. It then introduces the research questions, aims and the research approach chosen for this study, methodology of this thesis will be introduced as well. In addition, the implications of the study and a short conclusion are presented at the end of this chapter.

This study aims to explore Chinese international students' perceptions of 'face' culture and whether it has an impact on their study and life in the UK. It investigates the challenges related to 'face' culture that Chinese international students may encounter in developing their identity as English learners and speakers. This research focuses on students who have already graduated from the MEd TESOL programme, and who are also members of student groups whose classes were delivered fully online as a result of the restrictions around the recent period of the Covid-19 pandemic.

1.2 Structure of the thesis

The thesis consists of seven chapters. The first chapter provides a justification for undertaking this study along with the rationale for conducting thesis research and its aims and questions. Then chapter two provides the context and background of the study, with a particular focus on the perceptions of Chinese international students regarding 'face' culture and their experiences related to 'face' culture during their social life and studies in the UK. Chapter three presents and discusses the relevant existing literature and key concepts which underpin this study. The concept of 'face' and related theories of 'face' culture, as well as 'China English' are examined in detail. The concepts of culture and identity are also discussed, as is the role of gender although is not the centre of the thesis. Additionally, this research presents and discusses the theoretical framework that forms the foundation of this study. It examines the theory of Goffman's (1955,1967) work, the politeness theory of Brown and Levinson (1978,1987), as well as Mao's (1994) work on 'face' culture, which combined forms the basis of the theoretical framework of this study. Chapter four discusses the research methodology chosen for this study. It covers the philosophy underpinning this approach, the research paradigm, research methods, and the development of the research questions and aims, as well as recruitment of participants, data analysis procedures, and ethical considerations. Chapter five presents the findings of this study, with discussions and analysis of Chinese international students' perceptions of 'face' and their 'face' related experiences from both academic and social contexts as well as their use of 'China English'. Finally, Chapter six summarises this research, and concludes the findings in the context of the questions raised as part of the study. This study's contributions and implications for non-Chinese international students and teachers and universities in both the UK and China are presented and discussed. Moreover, the current study's limitations along with recommendations for future research with a similar interest in this area are discussed in this final chapter.

1.3 Research background

This study examines the impact of ‘face’ culture on the development of self-identity for Chinese international students; it intends to contribute to preparing them for the transition of studying and living in the UK and the practicalities of learning English in an authentic environment. Specifically, the purpose is to investigate whether and to what extent ‘face’ affects Chinese international students’ developing identity as learners and speakers of English as well as discussing the impacts of their experiences of learning and social contexts in the UK. Indeed, Chinese students may encounter challenges while studying English as a second language, which may impede their learning autonomy (Bakar, 2013) and thus affect their learning experience and language development. These challenges could arise due to various factors such as differences in language structure between their first and target languages, and also in terms of the differences in cultural background. It will be interesting to investigate these issues throughout the thesis. Additionally, differences in educational systems, such as teaching methodologies, assessment methods and academic expectations, may require students to adjust their learning strategies, as their previous experience in these areas may be insufficient. These potential obstacles could limit the students’ capacity to take control of their learning process and become self-directed learners. It may be that ‘face’ culture and issues related to it, are one of the potential challenges that Chinese international students encounter in the UK. This should be recognized and addressed to enhance their learning experience, thus improving their learning environment and promoting autonomous learning. This research aims to contribute to the studies around Chinese ‘face’ culture as it explores the impact of ‘face’ culture on the specific context of experiences of Chinese international students studying abroad. Moreover, this current study intends to help lecturers and support staff in universities and other non-Chinese students in the UK to have a better understanding of Chinese ‘face’ culture, both to better understand and to support Chinese international students in developing their language skills to a level that supports them in every context while studying abroad. The discussion around the findings and conclusions of the study will be presented in the following chapters.

1.4 Research rationale

When I first came to the UK to study, especially when I arrived in Scotland, I found that I could not understand what the local people were saying. Although I had achieved the IELTS score required for postgraduate study at a UK university and my spoken English level was sufficient for basic daily communication, the reality was that I could not freely communicate with the locals or with my classmates. It seemed that some of my fellow Chinese students were experiencing similar issues. In contrast, the other international students in my class appeared at ease and did not seem to be troubled by the language and cultural barriers. This led me to wonder why Chinese students, despite studying English for nearly a decade prior to arriving in the UK, still struggle to use it effectively. Individual language proficiency might be one aspect, but there were also other, less obvious reasons for this. Through self-reflection and discussions with other Chinese students, I concluded that it might be the Chinese concept of ‘face’ that hinders our language development. Fear of ‘losing face’, fear of bringing shame to China, or simply a lack of confidence often makes us anxious and fearful about communicating with native speakers. Could there be deeper issues behind this? With this question in mind, I began this research for my thesis. I hope to make a small contribution to the lives of Chinese

international students who are studying abroad or intending to study abroad, helping those who have been as confused as I was to better adapt to life in a different culture.

Most Chinese learners study English for many years in a non-authentic language learning environment (Gil, 2008). In other words, the majority of Chinese students studying English as a second language have limited exposure to real-life English language contexts and interactions which is because their English language education mainly takes place within a traditional classroom setting that lacks linguistic authenticity. The latest study shows that there is an obvious gap in the current situation of English education in China, in terms of the urban and rural differences (Peng, 2024). Peng (2024) further argues that rural primary school students face extra challenges and obstacles when learning English due to limited educational resources, a lack of language-rich environments, insufficient teacher support, and the negative impact of family-related factors. According to Peng (2024), students in urban areas have better access to an authentic English environment. In contrast, students in rural areas generally do not learn English in an authentic environment. The use of English is much lower, and opportunities to practice the language are limited.

Universities in China emphasise the literature and the grammar of English as important throughout every English language programme which aims to test students' knowledge and level of English throughout their education; however, this method of education does not concern itself with nor develop authentic communication (Hwang, 2005). Shan (2020) argues that researchers often take a deterministic view, seeing Chinese students as a homogenous group influenced by Confucianism, contrasting them with Western educational principles. According to Shan (2020), Chinese students value active and reflective thinking, deep understanding, and inquiry, however, their active reflection may not be recognized by Western higher education. Chinese international students are also seen by Western scholars as less autonomous in their learning practices and as having difficulties and challenges in classroom behaviours and communication. Therefore, Chinese international students may come to the UK to study without being fully prepared to use language in authentic contexts, particularly lacking authentic language practice and may not be able to function in terms of speaking and engaging in class or in everyday situations. This teaching approach used in China may not provide the students with enough opportunities to practise and develop their spoken communicative abilities, which are just as essential for meaningful language use as reading and writing. As a result, students may struggle to apply their theoretical knowledge to practical situations, which could limit their ability to communicate effectively in real-life settings. This may lead to a result, that Chinese students' pragmatic competence is considerably low (Gu, 2014), and it is also possible that the lack of experience in speaking and engaging in classroom activities is compounded by the Chinese 'face' culture. Online learning has become essential for university students in China, especially during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, using online technology to engage in real-life activities in English is a crucial skill for Chinese university students in today's increasingly globalized world (Lian, Chai, Zheng and Liang, 2021). Their study shows that authentic language learning tasks with technology positively impact students' confidence and self-efficacy in using English (Lian, Chai, Zheng and Liang, 2021). This suggests that Chinese international students' language competence can be enhanced through the structuring of authentic language learning, especially in the context of online learning environments during and beyond the pandemic. It will be interesting to find out whether participants in this study benefit from online learning or not.

It has been claimed that the concept of 'face' defines the nature of Chinese culture and affects how Chinese people identify themselves (Jia, 2001; Zhu, 2003); if we want to have a deeper understanding of Chinese international students, then, first of all, we need to know what 'face' culture is. 'Face' is owned by an individual or group, it represents self-image and reflects respect and confidence others have in themselves (Goffman, 1972; also in Qi, 2011). 'Face' is accompanied by feelings and emotions like pride, honour, relief, embarrassment, and shame which depend on whether they "gain/save face" or "lose face" (Forbes, 2019). Furthermore, during an interaction, people may run the risk of threatening and damaging the face of those involved, which may inhibit spoken interaction and is the key focus of this study. The concept of 'face' is deeply embedded in various aspects of Chinese people's daily life and it is worth examining whether 'face' continues to have an influence on Chinese international students, both academically and socially, as they study in the UK; and whether it affects the development of their language skills and their linguistic identity.

After years of studying in Scotland, I gradually noticed a change and development in myself. Initially, I was very resistant to interacting with local people, but now I no longer worry about making language mistakes or saying the wrong things. Am I still aware of the effects of 'face' culture even after all those years in the UK? The answer is absolutely yes, I believe the topic of 'face' culture will always be central to the experience of Chinese students in the UK, but I feel that I have the courage to face it now. This gradual shift in my identity began through repeated interactions with people of a variety of cultures and backgrounds.

Moreover, I have been complimented on my English level more than once, and I believe people speaking to me meant it as a compliment; despite my English level being higher than my partner's, some of the people still chose to talk to my boyfriend, instead of me. I was completely ignored by them as if I did not exist. Being a young Chinese female, I was treated just like many other young females, unfairly, and being Chinese seemed to make it worse. Therefore, despite the happiness and joy of being acknowledged, I also felt a tinge of offence. It seemed that the overall English proficiency of Chinese international students was perceived to be quite low, and I appeared to be representative of what people expected. As a Chinese person, seeing my fellows bound by this stereotype and hearing negative comments based on their own identities or gender made me feel irritated. I, as a young Chinese woman, feel the responsibility to stand up and reach out to other girls and boys, and together, we may be able to change the situation even just a little bit.

I hope that by sharing my experiences, I can relate to other international students who have had similar experiences. I also hope that our voices will be heard by more people. Many Chinese students come to the UK at a very young age, leaving behind their familiar environment, family, and friends. I hope my research can help them become a better version of themselves or help give them the courage to confront unfair perceptions due to stereotypes. In addition, I hope it can change the perceptions of non-Chinese people towards Chinese international students, giving them the tools and encouraging them to be more understanding and supportive.

1.4.1 The impact of ‘face’ on Chinese students’ learning experience

According to (Zhang, 2020), compared to other international students, Chinese international students have reported facing more challenges in interacting with both British students and other international students which suggests that they may not be understood by other non-Chinese students due to linguistic or cultural differences; specifically, because of their experience of ‘face’ culture which is an example of language that essentialises the Chinese and is related to linguistic differences in societies. Moreover, Chinese international students suggest that the challenges concerning social interaction rather than academic adjustment (Spencer-Oatey & Xiong, 2006); those challenges may cause them to lose confidence when meeting language challenges and eventually may lead to a sense of ‘loss of face’. However, previous research on Chinese students studying abroad has primarily concentrated on academic aspects, such as classroom participation and the difference in learning approaches between Chinese and Western classrooms, as discussed by Wu, 2015; Wang, 2018; Zhang, 2020. There have been limited studies on the social interaction of Chinese international students with individuals from different countries (Spencer-Oatey, Lifei, Dauber and Jing, 2017), especially research related to ‘face’ culture-related research. Therefore, the focus and the aim of this research is to fill the gap in the current literature. It may be that Chinese international students lack confidence, and they are too focused on their own anxieties around ‘face’ to engage in classroom discussion; that is, they may be anxious about other class members being aware of their own perceived limitations as learners and the fear of ‘face’ culture that is embedded in their approach to studying and interacting in class.

Therefore, it is necessary to investigate how Chinese face culture impacts Chinese international students in their social and academic contexts. This study also aims to help other non-Chinese people to have a better insight into Chinese ‘face’ culture.

1.4.2 Face related challenges

International students may encounter many challenges while adjusting to a new cultural environment (Su, 2010), and there are studies suggesting that a lack of confidence in their language competence may hinder students’ participation in class (Robertson, Line, Jones and Thomas, 2000). As a result, international students may experience a sense of confusion and isolation, which could affect their overall academic performance and social engagement. This could stem from a fear of making mistakes or being misunderstood by their peers or instructors which may lead to ‘losing face’ in public. This lack of participation could limit the student’s ability to fully engage with the material, ask questions, and contribute to classroom discussions, which could affect their learning outcomes and academic development. It is also worth researching how Chinese international students manage to overcome or fail to deal with these challenges, as well as exploring ways in which they can be supported in both social and academic contexts. Even though Chinese students expect to make friends with local students the misunderstandings and limited opportunities for social interactions may make it hard to do so (Brown & Holloway, 2008a). In addition, there has been a unique situation over the last few years because of the Covid-19 pandemic which has resulted in the requirement for many classes to be delivered online and Chinese students missing opportunities to extend their authentic English usage. According to Shan (2020), more Chinese students are choosing to study within the UK higher education system, which emphasises the need for them to develop as

autonomous and reflective learners capable of independently understanding and interpreting knowledge (Shan, 2020). During this transition from learning in China to learning in the UK, Chinese international students may encounter challenges in both social and academic contexts, and the process of transition or the development of learner identities related to Chinese international students' autonomy and motivation has been discussed in much of the literature (Shan, 2020), however, the challenges related to 'face' culture have been neglected. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the impact of 'face' culture on Chinese international students' developing identity as English learners and speakers.

In addition, Chinese international students appear to face more challenges in interacting with local and other international students than students from other countries (Zhang, 2020), and the reasons can be various, one of them being 'face'- related. Moreover, negative stereotypes held by other non-Chinese students regarding Chinese international students are not helpful, such as that Chinese students are passive learners, do not sufficiently participate in class, and they do not think critically, which are very common misconceptions (Zhang, 2020). In addition to these challenges, Zhang (2020) believes that negative stereotypes held by other non-Chinese students such as that Chinese international students have low English proficiency, talk too loudly, and are rude (Ruble & Zhang, 2013) are not helpful, because they can also undermine Chinese students' experience and confidence as learners in the UK and indeed limit their opportunities for social interaction. Therefore, this research aims to clarify, discuss and counter these misunderstandings and stereotypes around Chinese students and aims to help universities create an open and friendly environment for both Chinese international students and non-Chinese international students.

While studying in the UK, I reflected on my master's study and social life and wondered how I could help Chinese international students understand the impact of 'face' culture on their studies and life in the UK while helping other non-Chinese students and lecturers understand the impact of Chinese 'face' culture on Chinese international students. As Greggo (2001) indicates, Chinese students lack confidence in their English competence and the anxiety of making mistakes can hold them back from developing their language competence. In other words, Chinese students may suffer a sense of "losing face" or become embarrassed when they communicate or speak English; the main issue may be that the students do not want to use English in the first place (Jackson, 2002). Furthermore, language issues and unfamiliarity with the cultural norms of the host country may prevent Chinese international students from interacting with local or other non-Chinese students (Andrade, 2006; Su, 2010). This is especially related to the previous experience of education that Chinese students have had which in the main has been rote learning in which the learning is teacher-centred.

According to Su (2010), "the Western cultures of teaching and learning encourage students to analyse, question and critique ideas" (p.91), and Chinese international students are expected to be more independent which is a very new learning approach for them when studying abroad, in the UK. Chinese cultures of teaching and learning have more focus on reciting knowledge, therefore, the different teaching and learning methods can cause challenges for Chinese international students who are unfamiliar with these approaches. In other words, Chinese teaching and learning methods are teacher-centred. The education system in China has an impact on 'face' because Chinese students may not have had an opportunity to truly contribute to class as they have been trained to obey teachers; but in the UK, they are expected to engage

and share their views which may exacerbate the ‘face’ issue. Su (2010, p. 92) citing Hu (2002b, pp.98-99):

The teacher selects points of knowledge from authoritative sources,... and delivers knowledge for the students to memorise, repeat and understand... the focus of teaching is not on how teachers and students can create, construct, and apply knowledge, but on how extant authoritative knowledge can be transmitted and internalised...

The Chinese teaching approach emphasises understanding and obtaining basic concepts of knowledge and in the Western teaching approach, the emphasis is on how to apply knowledge to an authentic situation. Learning within different cultures implies the possible challenges Chinese international students may meet while learning and living in the UK. However, findings from Shi (2006) suggest that students from metropolitan cities like Beijing or Shanghai may have positive interactions with teachers as they have had more opportunities and experiences with “native” English teachers, unlike the participants chosen for this study. Teaching and learning methods in China are shifting in order to create a better learning environment for students, but “traditions” may cause students to still feel the need to hold the view that teachers should be able to know all the answers and thus support the needs of students (Su, 2010). Therefore, Chinese international students may face more academic challenges with the UK teaching approach, because of the unique issue involved with ‘face’ culture and related expectations. The above discussion will be developed in detail in the Findings Chapter and Conclusion Chapter where the participants for this study have been interviewed and their responses analysed.

1.5 Research questions

The research questions below, along with the literature, will enable the researcher to create a set of interview questions which will enable the interview process, and thereafter analyse the findings. These questions are also designed to reveal whether there is an impact of ‘face’ culture on Chinese international students and their experiences with ‘face’ in both academic and social contexts. It is planned that this will result in enabling a profound understanding of the impact of Chinese ‘face’ culture on students’ studying and lives in the UK. It plans also to fill the gap in the current literature. These research questions are:

1. In what ways do Chinese international students perceive Chinese ‘face’ culture?
2. In what ways does the role of ‘face’ culture contribute to the developing identity of Chinese international students as English learners and speakers?
3. To what extent does ‘face’ culture affect Chinese international students' perceptions and use of language in both academic and social contexts while studying in the UK?
4. How do Chinese international students perceive the diversity of language and especially their perceptions of “China English” when they are in the UK?

1.6 Research aims

The following aims to support the research questions will be:

- To analyse what ‘face’ culture is and the ways in which it can affect Chinese students’ development of identity as English learners and speakers.
- To explore how Chinese international students perceive ‘face’ culture in the context of the UK.
- To examine the key factors arising from their perceptions that may affect their developing identity as international students and English learners.
- To explore whether Chinese international students’ use of language is influenced by and related to their experience of ‘face’ culture in both social and academic contexts.
- To examine the impact of teaching methods in both China and the UK on Chinese international students’ awareness of ‘face’ culture.
- To explore ways in which UK universities can help Chinese students overcome ‘loss of face’ and encourage them to become confident international students.

1.7 Research approach

A qualitative methodology will be adopted and the reasons for choosing a qualitative approach will also be discussed. The Methodology chapter will present and discuss the pilot study which aims to identify the potential challenges and inform the development of the main study. It gives details of participant recruitment, interviews, data collection, and data analysis. The participants were recruited through emails and interviews conducted through online meetings due to the restrictions caused by the recent Covid-19 pandemic. Ethical considerations and reliability will also be discussed in the Methodology chapter. Data collected from the participants are analysed and will be presented and discussed in the Findings chapter along with the themes that arose from analysis.

1.8 Significance of the study

According to Zhang (2020), the transitional experience of Chinese postgraduate students in the UK has not been fully researched and the limited studies are not helpful in identifying the challenges that Chinese students have met or the challenges they have overcome or failed to overcome. In this study, the challenges related to ‘face’ culture are the focus of investigation; as explored and discussed earlier ‘face’ culture is embedded in every aspect of Chinese people’s daily life. Therefore, it is important to explore Chinese international students’ perceptions of Chinese ‘face’ culture and their experience with ‘face’ in the UK in order to help other non-Chinese people have a better understanding of ‘face’ culture and the experience of Chinese international students. The significance of this study is clear. It would be helpful for non-Chinese people to better understand what ‘face’ is, since there are more and more Chinese international students who choose to study in the UK and understanding ‘face’ culture can help those who are not Chinese to understand Chinese international students’ classroom and social behaviours. As for Chinese international students, ‘face’ is embedded in their daily life, but they may not be aware of it and this study may offer an opportunity for them to reflect on whether it has an impact on them and the significance of that. Both non-Chinese and Chinese international students would benefit from an understanding of how ‘face’ may limit Chinese

students and lead them to behave in a certain way; specifically, an understanding of Chinese international students' developing identity and their perception of 'face' culture within the academic and social contexts would benefit young Chinese international females just like me, by informing them and supporting them to understand the challenges they may encounter in the UK. In addition, it is important for teachers and universities in the UK to be aware of 'face' and notice how 'face' can create a unique atmosphere in the classroom and how Chinese international students' learning experiences and engagement can be enhanced.

In summary, this study will explore how Chinese students can overcome the impact of 'face' and build confidence in their learning and themselves; it is equally important for this study to contribute to a better understanding of how universities in the UK can develop better support for Chinese international students. This study also can help universities and teachers in China, even Chinese students themselves who have the intention of going abroad, to prepare them for learning abroad and help them understand what they should be expecting, the challenges they may have and more importantly, the opportunities they can have.

1.9 Conclusion

In summary, this study is designed to explore the perceptions around whether 'face' culture has an impact on Chinese international students' learning and social experience. To fill in the gaps in the related previous research field, the researcher will discuss and provide a valuable understanding of 'face' culture and Chinese students' experience in both learning and social contexts. In addition, the researcher will explore their perceptions of 'face' culture and 'China English' by conducting a qualitative study, in order to discover how 'face' affect their study and social life in the UK. A detailed discussion of the context which underpins this study will be presented in the next chapter.

Chapter 2: Context

2.1 Introduction

Chinese ‘face’ culture is a complex set of social norms and behaviours that are deeply embedded in Chinese society (Qi, 2017). In other words, the concept of ‘face’ has a long history in China, as referenced in Confucianism and other traditional philosophies. ‘Face’ is a complex concept that includes one’s reputation, social status, and honour, among other things (Forbes, 2019). It is earned through one’s actions and behaviour, and ‘losing face’ may lead to serious consequences. Therefore, in order to better understand what ‘face’ culture is, how it extends throughout society in China, and its influence on the educational system in China, a discussion of what ‘face’ culture is, how ‘face’ culture is perceived by Chinese international students in the UK will be presented. This chapter will provide an overview of the challenges related to Chinese ‘face’ culture and English language learning in China. It will begin by exploring the historical roots of ‘face’ culture in China and its current state in modern society.

This chapter will then examine the challenges that Chinese learners of English may have in merging the norms and values of ‘face’ culture with those of the English-speaking world. Additionally, it will explore how the use of English can affect one’s ‘face’ in Chinese society, including the potential challenges that may arise when traditional notions of ‘face’ conflict with the expectations of English-speaking contexts. This chapter investigates the differences in the perception of ‘face’ in both the UK and China. In addition, it explores Chinese international students’ learning and living experiences in the UK in relation to their educational background in China and explores whether or not ‘face’ has an impact on them even when they are living and studying in the UK.

Therefore, the first section will discuss the concept of Chinese ‘face’ culture and Confucianism on Chinese students’ learning and social life and how it impacts English language learning and teaching in China. The second part will provide the Western view of ‘face’ culture and the ways in which it differs from the Chinese concept of ‘face’. This chapter will also present numerical data on Chinese international students studying and living in the UK, as this data can help the researcher to understand the enormous number of Chinese students who may experience the challenges of Chinese ‘face’ culture and English language learning in a completely new and different foreign country. The third section will discuss Chinese international students’ learning and their living experience and the challenges they may have in relation to ‘face’ culture in the UK. The researcher then will investigate potential challenges that a lifelong experience and awareness of ‘face’ culture might bring to this new learning and social context or environment.

2.2 Chinese face culture and English language in China

‘Face’ is one of the most essential concepts in Chinese culture (André, 2013). If one wants to understand Chinese culture properly, then the concept of ‘face’ should not be ignored (Zhu, 2003), this is because the concept of ‘face’ culture exists almost in every aspect of life in China. Zhu (2003) also argues that the notion of ‘face’ contains all sorts of emotions (honour, shame, anger and guilt, etc.), which can function both as motivations for gaining or losing ‘face’ and the associated consequences of gaining or losing ‘face’. As will be discussed in relation to the experience of Chinese students interviewed for this study, Chinese students may act in a certain way to avoid ‘losing face’ or to ‘gain face’ during their study period in the UK, just as they do

in China.

'Face' is the "harmony of individual behaviour with the judgement of the community" (Yu, 2003, p.1685); when people act based on the accepted social conventions, 'face' is gained, and if they act against the accepted social conventions, then 'face' is lost. This is a situation that the author of this thesis has experienced and understood and thus, she is aware that this may cause difficulties for Chinese international students studying in the UK; this is one significant area that this study aims to investigate. The reason for exploring 'face' related issues around Chinese international students is that Chinese international students studying in the UK may encounter challenges related to 'face' culture, which is a significant aspect of Chinese "unspoken" social rules and communication norms.

In Chinese culture, 'face' refers to a person's reputation, and status, which is highly valued by Chinese people. In the UK, social norms and interactions may be different from those in China, which could result in misunderstandings or challenges for Chinese international students who are used to the norms of their home country. For example, in the UK, direct communication and expressing one's opinions freely are often valued, whereas, in China, indirect communication and the ability to 'save other's face' and not 'lose face' are often more important. In other words, indirect communication is used in China, and it refers to the use of subtle and implicit ways to convey messages rather than being direct. This style of communication is often used to avoid causing offence or embarrassment to others which may lead to 'losing face', especially in hierarchical relationships where it is important to show respect to those in positions of authority. The concept of 'saving face' is also important in Chinese culture. It refers to the desire to avoid causing embarrassment or humiliation to oneself or others and to maintain a positive and accepted public image. In China, 'saving face' is seen as a way to maintain social harmony and avoid conflict. It is often considered rude or disrespectful to directly criticize or confront someone in public, as this may cause them to 'lose face'. Indeed, in Chinese culture, both indirect communication and the concept of 'saving face' or avoiding 'losing face' are deeply rooted and valued. They are seen as important ways to maintain harmonious relationships and to show respect for others. However, it is important to note that these values may differ from those in other cultures, where direct communication and open criticism may be more valued which may be the case in the UK.

Furthermore, in Chinese culture, maintaining the appearance of harmonious relationships and avoiding conflict is important, which could lead to Chinese students being hesitant to speak up in group discussions in class or other social situations, as they may not want to feel that they are in a situation where their opinions differ with others and which may cause conflicts with other students, and this behaviour may be seen as a lack of confidence or willingness to engage by their peers or teachers. However, it is important to note that not all Chinese international students will experience the same difficulties related to 'face' culture, as some Chinese international students in the UK may feel that although they are fully aware of 'face' culture, they find it does not affect them or has little effect on their study and social life in the UK, while others may be deeply affected by 'face' culture. The reason for exploring this is that this research intends that one of the outcomes may give guidance to teachers, students and their peers in order that they may be aware of these cultural differences and provide support and understanding to help Chinese international students improve their experience of studying abroad and have the confidence to face any challenges they may encounter.

Indeed, 'face' is something that belongs to an individual or a group, however, it is not directly determined by the individual or group: 'face' may be given to the individual or group or taken away from them based on a complex set of social interactions within Chinese society (Qi, 2011),

which refers to showing respect, admiration, or appreciation for someone. It can take many different forms, such as giving compliments, showing deference, or expressing gratitude. For example, if someone invites you to their home for dinner, it is considered 'giving face' by complimenting the food, finishing the food on your plate even if you have had enough, and expressing appreciation for the invitation. Similarly, in a formal or work setting, showing respect to a person in a position of authority, such as a boss, can also be seen as 'giving face'. On the contrary, if you offer a difference of opinion to your boss in front of other employees, your boss will be seen as "losing face" and you, yourself, will be seen as rude and disrespectful.

Qi (2011) further suggests that another way of 'giving face' is that if a person 'gains face' from others or groups, they may feel honour, pride, and dignity; if they 'save face' which means they prevent themselves from 'losing face', then they may feel secure or relieved within social interactions. In Chinese culture, 'gaining face' refers to actions or behaviours that increase one's status or reputation. It can be achieved through various ways, such as receiving recognition or praise or being associated with successful people or events. For example, if a student gets top grades in school, they may 'gain face' by being praised by their teachers, especially in public. 'Gaining face' is an important aspect of Chinese culture as it reflects one's personal achievements, abilities, and social standing; it is seen as a way to earn respect and admiration from others and to enhance one's reputation. However, it is also important to maintain modesty and avoid arrogance, which may be seen as a way to 'lose face'. If a person loses their 'face', then depending on the situation, it may lead them to experience a range of feelings and emotions changing from embarrassment or incompetence (in minor cases) to shame and inferiority (in more severe cases) (Qi, 2011), which is a very common part of social interaction in China that almost everyone experiences. For example, if a student gets a low grade, and they are criticised by teachers or parents then it may be seen as a minor case which leads to embarrassment and 'losing face'. However, if a student is caught cheating in an exam and they are criticised by teachers or parents in front of the class or even noticed by the whole school, then it will be seen as a more severe case of 'losing face'; it may cause worse outcome than simply 'losing face', as there is the embarrassment or even humiliation of being reprimanded in front of the class which may lead to a serious impact on one's learning experiences and one's confidence.

According to Bedford and Hwang (2003), the sense of shame prompted by 'losing face' can affect how a person feels about oneself and his personal identity. In other words, when a person feels shame in a wider social setting, then their identity or how they see themselves and how others see them may be questioned by the person themselves and also by other people and the shame can be seen as 'losing face' within Chinese society. This experience of 'losing face' can have a significant impact on how a person views themselves and their personal identity. When a person 'loses face', they may feel insufficient or imperfect, and their sense of self-worth and confidence can be diminished. This sense of shame can also affect their personal identity, as it may cause them to question their values, actions and even their existence. For example, if a student fails a test, they may feel ashamed and embarrassed, which may lead them to question their intelligence and ability to succeed. This experience can have a lasting impact on their personal identity, as it may affect how they view themselves as a student and as a person.

Therefore, trying to 'save face' is a mechanism for Chinese society to promote social harmony (Qi, 2013), that is, to ensure that everyone feels their 'face' is not threatened during social interactions, since unity in terms of behaviour takes precedence over individual experience and behaviour over any diverse experience. Moreover, in China, the collective experience is more important than the individual. As a result, individual shame, disgrace, and losing 'face' are the

price of breaking this social harmony: if someone rejects the prevailing Chinese cultural norms and acts differently, then those people who are connected tightly to them, especially their families, will also feel ashamed, which is unimaginable to many people in Chinese society. In other words, if an individual's behaviour violates the cultural norms, then not only themselves but also their family will feel shame and lose 'face'.

'Filial piety' is a central value in traditional Chinese culture: it means the virtue of respect for one's parents, elders and even ancestors (Ikels, 2004), and bringing shame on one's family is a sign of disrespect for one's parents and the older members of the family. The behaviour of making one's family lose 'face' is considered to be in opposition to filial piety and is reprimanded in Chinese culture. Thus, this makes it clear that the notion of 'face' goes deeper than the effect on the individual. Even if individuals do not wish to do so, there will be pressure to conform to, and maintain behaviours that are seen to be helpful to social harmony and stability (Forbes, 2019). These unspoken conventions are central to social harmony in Chinese society; even if individuals do not wish to behave in a certain way, to support the continuance of social harmony, there can be pressure to behave which helps to maintain social harmony and stability, especially in cultures where collective values are emphasized, as in China. In Chinese culture, maintaining social harmony and avoiding conflict is highly valued, and individuals are often expected to show humility and respect and prioritize the needs of the group over their individual needs and desires. These expectations can be particularly strong for Chinese international students who may feel a keen sense of responsibility to represent their country and culture in a positive light while studying abroad, which may be the case in this study and which the researcher wishes to explore further. As a result, some Chinese international students may feel pressured to obey these cultural rules even if they may disagree with the "unspoken" rules or even find themselves uncomfortable when obeying them; and some may even feel an internal conflict between their personal values and the wider cultural or community values, even when studying in another country. This study then will explore whether Chinese students still feel the need to maintain social harmony while studying in a smaller social unit, or classroom unit, in the UK or whether they feel under pressure not to make other Chinese international students 'lose face' while they are studying in the UK and whether the 'face' pressure has an impact on their classroom behaviours.

Indeed, 'face' is in line with the Confucian ideal of social harmony which is an important Chinese value that deeply affects all Chinese people (Fan, 2000; Hsu & Huang, 2015). Confucianism profoundly influences the Chinese educational system both outwardly and in "unspoken" ways (Bush & Qiang, 2000), and it still has an impact on Chinese educational procedures and beliefs today. Confucianism has influenced the Chinese educational system in a number of ways: it places a strong emphasis on the significance of complying with traditional values and ways of life as well as honouring authority figures, including parents and teachers (Bush & Qiang, 2000), which implies that there is not an equal relationship between parents and children or between students and teachers. Overall, Confucianism has had a big impact on how the Chinese educational system operates, and it still has a significant impact on Chinese education and certainly on every Chinese student. The concept of 'face' in Chinese culture emphasizes maintaining social harmony and showing respect for others which is closely related to the idea of Confucianism. In Confucian thought, respect for authority and deference to others are considered important virtues that contribute to a stable and harmonious society. The idea of 'face' reflects this focus on social harmony, as it is a way of showing respect for others and avoiding conflict or embarrassment. Furthermore, Confucianism places great emphasis on personal moral character and the cultivation of virtues such as humility, loyalty, and filial piety. The concept of 'face' can be seen as an extension of these virtues, as it is a way of showing

respect for others and establishing one's own moral character. It will be worth finding out whether Chinese international students interviewed for this study are still under the influence of Confucianism, especially 'face' culture, when they study in the UK.

The hierarchical structure of the Chinese educational system, which gives teachers and academics a lot of power over students, reflects this emphasis on respect. In other words, 'face' along with Confucianism affects how students learn and gain knowledge and how teachers teach students, and these values have existed in the Chinese educational systems for thousands of years. Chan (1999) argues that teachers are the centre of the Chinese classroom, which means teachers control classroom activities and even students. In other words, teachers have more power above students, and they can make decisions for students rather than considering students' feelings about those activities. An example of the unspoken "power" is that students gain knowledge through rote learning rather than critical thinking, which is in opposition to the ways in which learners are encouraged to think when learning in Western countries. This teaching method is influenced by 'face' culture and Confucianism, which ensure that students are the followers, teachers are the leaders in the classroom, and students are passive learners. Xu (2013) suggests that students must obey the teachers, otherwise, they will be punished and will also 'lose face' in front of their classmates.

2.2.1 English language learning in China

English is one of the compulsory subjects in Chinese schools at all levels, which is taught ever since primary school, and almost every student in China has had 9 years of formal English education before they start university (Sun, Wu, Yi and Zhang, 2022). There are two different courses for students of higher education: College English, general English for non-English major students and specialist English for English major students (Xu & Fan, 2017), and students must finish English studies in the first two years of university (MOE, 2007; 2016). According to MOE (2007), all undergraduates in China are also required to learn English which illustrates the importance of English throughout the Chinese education system. However, despite the high status of English learning in China's education, there is still a mismatch between how English is taught in China and the "English that students need and use in their life outside the classroom" (Jenkins, 2014, p.156). In other words, Chinese students who learn English aim to pass an exam or be able to read, but their ability to use and speak English is greatly overlooked. One of the purposes of English teaching based on College English Requirements (2007) is:

To enhance their ability to study independently and improve their general cultural awareness so as to meet the needs of China's social development and international exchanges' (Ministry of Education, 2007, p.1).

This means that English in Chinese classrooms is not taught for authentic use, and students may not be able to use authentic English outside the classroom. With the fear of 'losing face' and the teaching method in China that may not fully prepare students for studying in the UK or using authentic English, students in China may not be able to use English as a tool for communication. Moreover, Chinese language education systems place a significant emphasis on formal instruction, focusing on grammar, vocabulary, and academic writing. However, this approach may fail to prepare English learners to effectively communicate in authentic situations where English is used as a way of communication, especially for those students who have the intention of studying in the UK. Therefore, the English that students or learners need

and use in their real daily life may differ significantly from what they learn in traditional language classrooms. Students may struggle to understand and communicate with native English speakers, who often use informal expressions and language that are not typically taught in formal language classes. English learners often need to develop skills such as listening and cultural awareness (Richards, 2008), which are essential for effective communication in real-world settings. These skills may be overlooked in China's traditional English language education, which tends to focus more on grammar and vocabulary. Additionally, students who want to study abroad may also not be well-prepared, as they may not have an awareness of Chinese 'face' culture, and they may not be ready to deal with the 'face' related challenges that may occur in the UK.

Therefore, this study aims to find out if Chinese international students are aware of the impact of 'face' culture on their study or social life in the UK, especially when they go abroad to the UK. In addition, this research will discuss when the experience of Chinese international students coming to the UK, and whether they have ever experienced a moment of 'losing face'; 'losing face' can happen momentarily when someone challenges you during a discussion or in class. Therefore, it may be a huge pressure for Chinese international students, particularly when they are abroad and do not have families or friends to support them.

2.2.2 Chinese face culture in the context of China

There is a famous Chinese proverb: "As a tree needs bark, so a man needs face" (cited in Forbes, 2019) which shows that 'face' is fundamental to Chinese culture. This study will explore whether 'face' culture can still have an impact on Chinese international students' developing identities while they are living and studying in the UK. It aims to discover whether an understanding of Chinese international students' experiences with 'face' culture can help Chinese international students learn more effectively. In addition, avoiding 'losing face' or 'gaining face' is very important in Chinese people's daily life, which is reflected in their actions, decision-making, and social interactions (Wang & Spencer-Oatey, 2015); it would be interesting for me to find out whether this happens while Chinese international students have been removed to another completely different social context. The researcher herself has studied in this context and has become aware of the pressure on young Chinese international students studying abroad and would like this study to contribute to exploring whether 'face' culture still has an impact on Chinese international students' learning and living in the UK. It has been observed at both national and individual levels that the pursuit of 'gaining face' is a common strategy for status-building among Chinese people (Faure & Fang, 2008; Qi, 2011; Wang & Lin, 2009; Wang & Spencer-Oatey, 2015). The pressure on young Chinese international students studying abroad can be significant, and it may be exacerbated by the cultural value placed on 'face' in China, especially on how Chinese international students perceive their academic performance, relationships with peers and teachers, and overall well-being while studying abroad. For example, Chinese international students may feel pressure to perform well academically to 'gain face' and maintain their reputation and the reputation of their families so that they will not 'lose face' or make their parents 'lose face'. They may also feel pressure to conform to not yet familiar social norms and expectations in their interactions with peers and teachers in the UK, which also may reduce their confidence. This pressure can be intensified by the fact that these students are studying in a foreign country where they may feel like outsiders and consistently worry about 'losing face'. Moreover, they may feel the need to present themselves in a certain way to their peers and teachers, to avoid 'losing face' or being perceived as disrespectful. They may also feel pressure to participate in additional activities or

social events to build their social status and reputation so that they can 'save face'. In the context of academic studies, if a Chinese student 'gains face', it means that they have achieved something that enhances their reputation or social status. For example, if a student earns a high grade on an exam, they may 'gain face' among their peers, teachers, and family members; 'gaining face' can provide a sense of accomplishment and pride. On the other hand, if a Chinese student 'loses face', it means that they have done something that damages their reputation or social status. For example, if a student failed to give the right answer to questions in class, they may 'lose face' among their peers and teachers. The pressure to 'maintain face' can be significant for Chinese students studying abroad, particularly in Western countries where cultural norms and expectations may differ from those in China. The fear of 'losing face' can lead to anxiety, stress, and even hesitancy to seek help. This may also be the situation in the UK where Chinese international students may still pursue 'face' and be afraid of 'losing face'.

Forbes (2019) suggests that Chinese people can be very polite and friendly when dealing with acquaintances and strangers, as they all follow the unspoken rules of 'face' in order to ensure that others do not lose their 'face'. Forbes (2019) further suggests that Chinese people can be very direct with those close to them, but also indirect with people they are not close to; they may rarely refuse others' requests, as they do not want to make others lose 'face'. Indeed, many Chinese people believe that if you directly refuse someone, you will make them lose 'face' which would result in social consequences such as damaged relationships or a negative reputation. In other words, as a result, Chinese people often avoid directly refusing someone to prevent them from feeling embarrassed or 'losing face'. Instead, they may use indirect language or nonverbal communication to deliver their message (Forbes, 2019), otherwise, the person who has been refused may feel ashamed, humiliated, and may lose confidence. Additionally, others in the community may view them negatively, leading to a loss of social status or credibility within their immediate social environment. Therefore, to avoid this outcome, Chinese people may use indirect language, such as saying "maybe" or "next time" instead of "no"; they may also use nonverbal communication, such as avoiding eye contact or pretending they have something else to do and they are in a hurry to avoid an actual conversation. By using indirect language or nonverbal communication, they can decline the request while still maintaining the other person's dignity and social status, which is a way of 'giving others' face'.

Thus, under most circumstances, most Chinese people will do whatever they are asked to do, even if they do not want to. However, they can also be very direct with other people in a social context, as this is the way to show intimacy; only families or really close friends do not need to 'give you face', that is by being direct. In other words, only when you are close to someone, you do not need to "give them face" which is a sign of intimacy. However, whether Chinese international students are able to develop this intimacy with other people in the UK, or they feel close enough to other people will be difficult to find out because it is a very personal issue. It may be that Chinese international students find it difficult to make intimate friends in the UK, therefore, it closes off a whole area of experience that they have been used to.

There is also evidence that shows the impact of 'face' culture on Chinese international students which also has been discussed in Forbes's (2019) research. Some of the participants in Forbes's (2019) research suggest that their parents will "have face" if they send their children abroad, which is also discussed in Qi's (2017) research that having a child studying abroad is in itself an important source of 'face'. Chinese parents will compare not only themselves, but they will also compare their children; for example, if one's children have great marks in school; if the children can speak three different languages; if the children win a championship in a

competition, all these things are related to 'face', as these will make the parents gain 'face'. Therefore, the core of the 'face' concept is that one person cannot directly give themselves 'face', but 'face' depends on the image in others' eyes (Qi, 2011), thus, parents may 'gain face' from their children. Therefore, it is worth exploring whether Chinese students still follow the rules of 'face' during interactions with non-Chinese people when they are studying in the UK, as this may affect their behaviours in class and out of class and to discover issues in relation to 'face' while they are living and studying in the UK, and whether this has an effect on them.

2.2.3 The concept of face in Western culture

'Face' is not limited to China. The work of Goffman (1972) contributed to the development of a universal understanding of 'face'. According to Goffman (1955, p.213), "face is the positive public image you seek to establish in social interactions". Later, Chinese anthropologist, Hu (1994) introduced the concept of 'face' semantic analysis to Western countries in 1994 as a part of her research (Hong & Yu, 2018, p.1325). Initially, "'face' was used by the English community in China, to refer to the continual devices among the Chinese to avoid incurring or inflicting disgrace" (Hong & Yu, 2018, p.1325). Goffman (1955) discussed 'face' in detail in his work and since then Western researchers have referred to the Chinese terms "Lian" and "Mian" as 'face' during their discussion and analysis of 'face'. The most discussed aspect of 'face' in Western literature is in intercultural social interactions where 'face' affects both Chinese people and Westerners: there are unwritten rules in social interactions with any Chinese speakers, and if you break these rules, you will lose 'face' (Yu, 2003; Zhu, 2003). According to Forbes (2019):

Both Western and Chinese scholars agree that face can be lost, saved and given, and research on face from a Western perspective focuses on saving face, particularly related to the context of politeness. (Goffman, 1967; Brown and Levinson, 1978; Spencer-Oatey, 2015)

In any society, the focus on definitions of 'face' can be various, for example, in social contexts, linguistic, and interpersonal, but they all share some commonalities. First, 'face' is based on a social or interactive context, "face exists in response to the presence of others and interactions with others" (Thompson, 2014, p.4). Second, 'face' is an image we present to others. Third, the requirements of the situation or a certain context can affect the image of 'face' that we present (Thompson, 2014, p.4). This study wants to examine a particular context of Chinese students living and studying in the UK and to explore how they negotiate 'face' specific within their educational and social interactions.

Goffman's definition of 'face' can be seen as the foundation for 'face' theory in sociolinguistics research and applied linguistics and which focuses on the interaction between individuals and the social world. The conceptualization of 'face' by Goffman emphasizes how individuals connect with society and its institutions, which is also discussed by Brown and Levinson (1978) who define 'face' as "the want to be unimpeded and the want to be approved of in certain respects" (p. 63). Brown and Levinson (1978) believe that when people interact, they recognize each other's desires to support each other's 'face' and provide such confirmation and this "approval is generally reflected in the way that other people respond to us" (Thompson, 2014, p.6) which is showing respect and honour to others. The interesting point about this is that even in the UK, all these "rules" of conversation are generally unspoken. Craig, Tracy and Spisak (1986) argue that 'face' is "the self-image they present to others" (p. 440) and Cupach and Metts (1994) also argue that 'face' is "the conception of self that each person displays in

particular interactions with others” (p. 3). All these definitions emphasise ‘face’ and interaction as a way to seek confirmation and support from others no matter what culture the speaker comes from. This study, therefore, wants to investigate whether a particular social interaction in a specific context may affect Chinese students living and studying in the UK.

Brown and Levinson view ‘face’ in terms of two components which are ‘positive face’ and ‘negative face’. ‘Positive face’ is defined as “the want of every member that his [her] wants to be desirable to at least some others” (1987, p. 62), which means ‘positive face’ represents the need to be accepted and approved by the people in the group. ‘Negative face’ is “the want of every ‘competent adult member’ that his actions be unimpeded by others” (p. 62). In other words, if an adult's behaviour is not approved by others or an adult is criticized and opposed by others, this will make the adult ‘lose face’. It is clear that the Western concept of ‘face’ is focused more on people as individuals rather than the concept of ‘face’ as societal which exists in the Chinese context. Later Lim and Bowers (1991) extended the work of Brown and Levinson (1987) and proposed an example of an alternative ‘face’ which they termed ‘fellowship face’, ‘competence face’ and ‘autonomy face’:

Fellowship face is the want to be included which inherently reflects a desire for acceptance by others. Competence face is a want to have one's abilities respected by others; in essence, we want people to value what we can do. Autonomy face is a want to not be imposed on and is a type of ‘negative face’ (Redmond, 2015, p.7)

This suggests that people often have different needs and desires related to how they want to be perceived by other members of the group. ‘Fellowship face’ represents the need to feel included and accepted by a group; while ‘competence face’ reflects the desire to have one's skills and abilities recognized and valued by others. ‘Autonomy face’, on the other hand, is about the need to maintain independence and control over one's own decisions and actions which is a form of ‘negative face’, which means it involves the desire to not have one's freedom or autonomy impeded by others. However, the influence of ‘face’ on politeness is different in Chinese society and Western society; this will be discussed in the following paragraphs.

2.3 Differences in the perception of face between Chinese and Western culture

Although ‘face’ is received as a universal concept, it is particularly prominent in Chinese culture” (Faure and Fang, 2008; Forbes, 2019, p.135). According to Qi (2017), in Chinese culture, what distinguishes ‘face’ is the quantity and quality of relationships within Chinese society which reinforces the power of ‘face’, which means that ‘face’ is a concept that is closely tied to social relationships. In other words, the number and quality of one's social connections reflect a person's social status, influence, and ability to build and maintain relationships. In Chinese society, relationships play a crucial role in the acquisition and maintenance of ‘face’; the more relationships a person has, and the more high-status those relationships are, the more ‘face’ they will have. Qi (2017) further suggests that each person has their own ‘face’ and is responsible for maintaining it, and in Chinese society, one's ‘face’ is highly dependent on the person with whom one is connected, that one has a duty or even a social obligation to protect the ‘face’ of those they are connected with (Qi, 2011), such as one's parents, as discussed above. This suggests that Chinese culture places a strong emphasis on maintaining harmonious relationships and avoiding conflicts. ‘Losing face’ is considered a major threat to social

harmony and can cause a person to lose social status and respect. Therefore, people in Chinese society are highly conscious of their actions and behaviour, especially in public settings, to avoid offending others or causing a 'loss of face'. Conversely, 'face' is more dependent on one's own actions rather than those of others in Western culture (Forbes, 2019). Qi (2017) also found that Chinese people often associate themselves with the country's 'face'; that is, they clearly view themselves as citizens of a larger social group and believe that each Chinese person represents not only themselves but also the country. In her study, several Chinese international students explained that they felt very stressed because they feared that if they (as individuals) behaved inappropriately overseas then the entire Chinese people would lose 'face'. Chinese international students believe they represent not only themselves but also their country and their family, which may be because of the issue of 'face' (Qi, 2011); Chinese international students come from a tightly connected society where 'face' is deeply rooted in people's mind and their life. However, 'face' culture is not unique to China, Forbes (2019, p.56) argues that:

Face is not an exclusively Chinese practice, the use of face as an object consciously sought after through pursuing various strategies further distinguishes the Chinese practice of face from Western practices (Qi, 2017).

This may be a potential issue for Chinese students studying in the UK, as when Chinese students and other Western international students are in the same classroom, 'face' can mean different things to them, so it may lead to misunderstandings. This and other related experiences will be discussed with the participants of this study in terms of their own experiences.

From a Western perspective, Brown and Levinson (1987) proposed their concept of politeness and 'face' which focuses on the perspective of individualism: a person enhances their 'face' by using polite behaviour and speech. While the politeness of Chinese people is to realize and mutually enhance each other's 'face' (Yu, 2003). Thus, the difference between Chinese 'face' culture and the politeness-focussed Western concept of 'face' is that the Chinese 'face' culture is much broader and "more interpersonal and consequently much more prevalent and important in Chinese society" (Forbes, 2019, p.137). In other words, the Western-based concept of 'face' focuses more on the personal and individual, while the Chinese concept of 'face' emphasises the connections between each other and the group. In addition, in Chinese society, 'face' has a fundamental appeal and an explicit goal of social relations, which is further different from the Western concept of 'face' (Qi, 2011), which means that 'face' is the priority concern in Chinese social interactions but not in the Western context. However, it will be interesting to investigate, in this study, whether Chinese students may behave differently since they have come to live and study in a specific context where 'face' is not a priority concern in the UK.

During the recent Covid-19 pandemic, I also found a similar situation: many Chinese international students were criticized and blamed by some Chinese people because it was believed that their return from their host countries would greatly increase the risk of infection among Chinese people. In addition, they felt that they were discriminated against as Asians by some of the local people of the UK. BBC NEWS (3 May 2021) reported that an Asian student was beaten on a street in London by a group of men who told him: "I do not want your coronavirus in my country". Also in 2020, there was much discussion online of Donald Trump's reference to coronavirus as the 'Chinese Virus' and these prejudices have even been found in the mainstream media, for example, *Le Courrier Picard*, a regional French newspaper, published the headlines 'Alerte Jaune' (Yellow alert) and 'Le péril Jaune?' (The yellow peril?) (BBC NEWS, 2020), referring to the rather racist notion that Chinese people have yellow skin which is very outdated and very racist. Therefore, many Chinese international students felt lost and stressed, even terrified as they were stuck in the desire to return home and the fear of being

accused of losing Chinese people's 'face' collectively because of their decision to return and also because of what were perceived to be inappropriate behaviours in the host country. This is an example of how the interdependent structure within Chinese society enhances and amplifies the value of 'face' (Forbes, 2019) so that it becomes an issue for collective discussion rather than individual discussion. Qi (2011) further suggests that when members of society behave in a socially acceptable way, social harmony and stability are strengthened. However, Zhu (2003) argues that this may have a positive side for society but also has a negative side: "While harmony and order are encouraged at the expense of conflict and disorder, these goals of harmony and stability can encourage the toleration of unsatisfactory situations such as injustice" (Forbes, 2019, p.56); this could relate to the situation of Chinese students above, who wanted to return to their host country during the pandemic but were prevented by social pressure.

2.4 Higher education in China: background to the study

The data from this study began to be collected in 2020. According to 'The Guardian,' the number of Chinese students at British universities increased significantly, with more Chinese students enrolled than from any other country (Adams, 2020). This is essential for discussions about Chinese international students in the UK and whether 'face' culture is relevant. In 2020, the Higher Education Statistics Agency reported that the number of Chinese students in the UK exceeded 120,000, making up over a third of non-EU students. The number rose from about 89,500 in 2014-15 to more than 120,300 (Adams, 2020). The increasing number of Chinese students highlights the importance of addressing their challenges in the UK. Yu and Moskal (2018) assert that Chinese students are vital to the financial health of UK universities, highlighting their significant role. With their numbers surpassing those from other countries, the importance of China as a source of international students is clear. Therefore, UK university teachers need to understand the context, social, and educational backgrounds of Chinese students to enhance classroom integration and support. This understanding is beneficial not only in classroom practice but also in tutorial sessions and for international student support staff.

In light of this issue around the specific needs of Chinese international students, this research seeks a deeper understanding of the experiences of a group of Chinese international students in the UK, with two related purposes. Firstly, it seeks to analyse 'face' culture and its impact on Chinese students' identity as English learners and speakers. The fear of 'losing face' may lead students to try to avoid mistakes, appear incompetent, and thus potentially hindering language development. This fear also contributes to a lack of confidence and unwillingness to engage in class, further impeding progress. Secondly, the study explores how Chinese students perceive 'face' culture in the UK, affecting their academic and social experiences. Some may find 'losing face' less significant in the UK than in China, while others may feel the opposite. Academically, maintaining performance to 'save face' may cause stress and anxiety. Socially, fear of making mistakes can lead to isolation and difficulty forming relationships. Understanding 'face' culture's influence can help UK teachers and institutions create a more supportive and inclusive environment, aiding Chinese students' development as English learners and speakers.

The main focus of all relevant literature consulted and analysed for this study on the experiences of international students discussed in the Literature Review Chapter is related to Chinese students' English learning motivations and expectations, challenges with adjustment, and international student learning (Hu, 2017), but there is much more literature on international

students in the US rather than in the UK (Hu, 2017). It does not exactly relate to the experience of Chinese international students studying in the UK; however, it is situated in another English-speaking country, and it may be that some of the information is relevant. Although there is some research on cultural differences and culture shock (Hu, 2017), I found no literature on the impact of Chinese ‘face’ culture on Chinese international students in the UK context. Therefore, the researcher intends to fill the gap by exploring Chinese international students’ experience related to ‘face’ culture in the UK which will help Chinese international students, as well as university teachers, be aware of the impact of Chinese ‘face’ on their study and their life in the UK; since ‘face’ culture has been deeply rooted in Chinese society and people’s daily life, it may still affect Chinese students even when they are studying in the UK. It would be informative to investigate how ‘face’ culture impacts Chinese international students’ academic and social experiences, as the findings of such research could benefit both students and universities in the UK. Moreover, by gaining a better understanding of ‘face’ culture and potential issues related to it, universities and teachers in China can better prepare students for studying abroad, ultimately improving their learning ability to study and live in a foreign academic and social environment.

The challenges of cultural differences related to classroom behaviours faced by all international students seem to be the most discussed problem by academics (Hu, 2017). One cultural difference that may affect the behaviour and class engagement of Chinese students in class is ‘face’ culture. Due to the rule of ‘face’ culture, Chinese students may keep silent and be hesitant to share their views during class discussions, because they may feel different views can cause disputes which will lead them to a ‘loss of face’; and they may not want others to feel their ‘face’ is threatened, while other students, however, may consider Chinese students to be passive learners based on Chinese students’ behaviours in class; it may be the situation for Chinese students studying in the UK which this study will further explore and investigate.

Owens (2003) claimed that international students feel more comfortable speaking their mother tongue and are reluctant to integrate into the culture of the host country because they believe that no matter how long they stay in the host country, they will never feel or be treated as being local. It may be the situation for Chinese international students in the UK, as they may prefer to spend time with other Chinese students because they can relate to each other’s cultural background; they may also have the fear of making friends with locals as they worry about not being understood or being perceived as incompetent in English, which could result in ‘losing face’. This study will also investigate whether Chinese international students have similar feelings to those what Owens (2003) claimed; however, there can be many reasons for Chinese international students to feel that they may not be able to integrate into the host country (Owens, 2003), among which the influence of Chinese traditional culture cannot be ignored, especially ‘face’ culture. Several studies (Liu, 2002; Ruble and Zhang, 2013) suggest that it is a common phenomenon for Chinese international students to have a strong desire to be polite in order to receive social approval (‘positive face’) (Zhu and Bresnahan, 2018). This may be due to ‘face’ culture, as Chinese international students may be concerned about ‘losing face’ in public and this may have an impact on their confidence and their developing identity as English learners and speakers in the UK.

2.5 Experiences of Chinese international students in the UK

It has been widely accepted that more prestigious higher education institutions attract more Chinese students (Cebolla-boado et al., 2018; Fang & Wang, 2014). However, little attention

has been paid to the fact that the desire to be associated with the world's most famous and prestigious institutions is not merely a means to another end; it is an end in itself (Cebolla-boado et al., 2018; also cited in Forbes, 2019, p. 139). Another reason some students choose to come to the UK is their inability to get into a top Chinese university, so studying abroad is better for their job prospects than attending a second-tier Chinese university (Cebolla-boado et al., 2018); for students and their parents, going to a less prestigious university in China can be considered a 'loss of face'. However little attention has been paid to the fact that the desire to be associated with the world's most famous and prestigious institutions is not a means to another end, it is for the students and the family to gain prestige.

Wang and Spencer-Oatey (2015) suggest that 'face' management (to gain, lose and give) is a common strategy among Chinese people in an intercultural context. In an academic context, 'face' concerns may affect Chinese international students' participation in-class discussions (Hwang et al., 2002; Liu, 2002; Wen & Clément, 2003). The 'face' concerns may also affect Chinese international students in a social context, as they may not want to encounter disapproval from others (Zhu and Bresnahan, 2018), which may affect Chinese students' social behaviour while they are in the UK. Wang (2012) also suggests that 'face' is deeply rooted in Chinese people's daily life, and it is seen as the core of social interaction (Qi, 2017). Therefore, Chinese international students may choose to not participate socially with others from non-Chinese backgrounds to save their 'face' (Liu, 2002), as they do not need to worry that they may not be understood or make any grammar mistakes. In Forbes's (2019) research, some participants who are Chinese international students also claim that they are worried about causing trouble for others, in other words, they are worried about making others 'lose face' if they act in a way that is not in accordance with social rules. Forbes (2019) concluded that:

In a Western context, many Chinese students are also courteous, polite and considerate to others, partly due to a desire to avoid the loss of face. However, even in this aspect, the effects of face are amplified in Chinese culture (p.137).

The following is an example of 'face'-related behaviour by Chinese overseas students in the UK. In the year 2023, the British Museum sparked controversy for using the term "Korean Lunar New Year" in an online post as more than a billion people around the world celebrated the Chinese New Year. The British Museum's Twitter account posted: "Join us in celebrating the Korean Lunar New Year and enjoy the magical performance of the Silla Orchestra"; many Chinese people questioned whether "the British Museum was "misappropriating culture" by labelling the Chinese lunar year with Korean" (BBC News, 2023). After seeing The British Museum's post, many Chinese students in the UK organized activities on their own; they found literature on the Chinese New Year, recommended documentaries and made posters to let foreigners know about the Chinese New Year. Girls dressed in Hanfu (traditional clothing of the Chinese Han Majority) to promote traditional Chinese culture. This caused a great reaction on the Internet, with the result that many Chinese netizens became proud of these Chinese international students in the UK. A lot of comments online mentioned 'face': "it is giving Chinese people face" and "We are proud of you girls, those Culture thieves should feel ashamed, it's losing their country's face": they believed it was an appropriate gesture to show the world that Chinese people have zero tolerance for cultural appropriation. This cultural confidence appears to be strengthened in the new generation of young Chinese people, as they feel positive and confident in Chinese culture. Similarly, during the Covid-19 pandemic, Chinese students were afraid of losing Chinese people's 'face', because their decision to go back to China was seen to be bringing the Covid virus back and putting Chinese people in danger, but they were praised later and considered to be saving Chinese people's 'face' in this "Chinese New Year"

event as they spoke out against what they perceived as unfair treatment.

In a closely connected society like China, where a person's 'face' depends on the behaviour of those with whom they have social connections, Qi (2017) also argues that Chinese international students also feel obligated to perform according to the proper manner and socially acceptable actions, rather than just to consider their own 'face'. Qi's (2017) research also suggests that the participants who are overseas students shared one expression that was: "I cannot lose Chinese people's face" (p.11) which was further discussed by Forbes (2019, p.137) in his research. This shows that Chinese international students are aware of the concept of 'face' and some of those students also feel that they are deeply affected by it, even when they are abroad. Thus, whether 'face' culture may impact their developing identity as English learners and speakers will be one of the areas focused on in this study. No doubt that the risk of 'losing face' in the tightly-knit Chinese culture, coupled with the Chinese value of filial piety, may pressure Chinese international students and this may cause them to behave in a certain way (Forbes, 2019). It is interesting that the literature on Chinese international students' mobility has so far overlooked the impact of 'face' on the experiences and development of Chinese international students' identity. Although there is a lack of focus on the impact of 'face' culture on Chinese international students in the literature, this study aims to reveal how 'face' can affect Chinese international students' developing identity as English speakers and learners in the UK. It will investigate whether the participants feel pressure to behave in a certain way in the classroom.

2.6 Conclusion

This chapter has introduced the concept of Chinese 'face' culture, and the English language background in China and has discussed the differences in the perception of 'face' between Chinese and Western cultures. This study notes that English as a subject has played an important role in China's education system which is discussed in this chapter. It has also explored the number of Chinese international students studying and living in the UK and their reasons for choosing UK universities, and also illustrated the experiences of Chinese international students in the UK. Chinese international students may still feel the impact of 'face' in the UK, and they may also have suffered the pressure of 'losing face'. The definitions of 'face' culture and related areas which will inform this study will be further discussed in the literature review chapter.

I am aware that Chinese students have grown up with an understanding of 'face' in the particular Chinese culture, however, many non-Chinese students and teachers in the UK are not familiar with the concept of 'face' culture. Therefore, it is important to make them aware of 'face' culture so that they can better understand Chinese international students. I also intend to help Chinese students adapt to their studies and life in the UK more easily. The remaining literature pertaining to this study will be discussed in the following literature review chapter.

Chapter 3: Literature Review

3.1 Introduction

In order to explore the impact of ‘face’ culture on Chinese international students’ developing identity as learners and speakers of English, this literature review discusses the issues around ‘face’ as follows: the concept of culture, the concept of ‘face’ culture; the effect of ‘face’ culture in the Chinese context; ‘face’ culture and Chinese learners’ pragmatic proficiency; ‘face’ culture and stereotypes of Chinese students in Western countries; the Western concept of ‘face’; Brown and Levinson’s politeness theory; ‘face’ culture and identity. This chapter further discusses ‘face’ culture and China English and the perceptions of Chinese students towards China English.

‘Face’ is not unique to Chinese or East Asian people (Forbes, 2019); it is a universal concept (Qi, 2017). Indeed, the effects of ‘face’ along with the unspoken rules of ‘face’ on social interactions are shared by both Chinese and Western people which is also the most discussed aspect of ‘face’ in Western literature (Forbes, 2019). However, the impact of ‘face’ on Chinese international students’ developing identity has been overlooked in the literature related to Chinese international students’ learning experiences in the UK. Therefore, this research aims to explore how Chinese international students perceive ‘face’ culture and how their own development of their identities are impacted as English learners and speakers in the UK.

3.2 Identity

Indeed, identity is a complex and multifaceted concept that shapes how individuals perceive themselves and are perceived by others (Block, 2007). Over the years, scholars have developed various principles to understand and explain the dynamics of identity within social interactions involving processes through which identities are negotiated, constructed, and performed.

Bucholtz and Hall (2010) proposed the following 5 principles to locate and discuss identity in language:

1. ‘The emergence principle’ means that identity is not fixed but rather emerges through the language of social interactions. It focuses on how individuals negotiate and construct their identities through ongoing interactions with others.
2. ‘The positionality principle’ suggests that individuals temporarily adopt specific roles and perspectives during interactions, influenced by their cultural backgrounds, social statuses, and relational dynamics, at a specific time and in a specific context. For example, a person may exhibit different aspects of their identity when interacting with family members, colleagues, or friends, reflecting the contextual nature of identity expression.
3. ‘The indexicality principle’ suggests that individuals make explicit or implicit references to identity roles and labels during interactions, shaping how they are perceived by others and how they perceive themselves.

4. 'The relationality principle' highlights how individuals define themselves with reference to others and how these relational dynamics shape identity negotiation and expression.
5. 'The partialness principle' which reveals the incompleteness and ongoing nature of identity formation (p.19–26) (cited in Preece, 2016, p.5).

These principles of identity have helped me as a researcher to understand the experiences of Chinese international students as English learners and speakers in the UK. Chinese international students' identity as English learners and speakers develops through interactions with native speakers of English and other international students. They may come across language barriers, cultural differences, and academic challenges, which can lead to the growth of their linguistic and cultural identities, or in some negative cases, hinder their development. Moreover, their interactions with peers, lecturers and locals shape their sense of belonging and cultural identity within the UK context, as they navigate this new context in which they live. Examining how identity is placed and interacts within the context of language learning and intercultural communication, enables me, as the researcher, to have insights into the complex process of identity development among Chinese international students in a multicultural setting. This relates specifically to 'the emergence principle' (Bucholtz and Hall, 2010) refers to the fact that identity flows and emerges. This may be what Chinese international students experience and have to negotiate when they move from one social context to another. Just as Gu (2009) argues, for Chinese students, in their unique intercultural environment of living and studying, the evolution of their identities has become intertwined with their maturation and intercultural growth. They may experience culture shock involving cultural adaptation which relates to personal growth, while they may also need to face the challenge of navigating their identities between Chinese culture and the UK culture during social and academic contexts. They may experience a sense of belonging to the new cultures while simultaneously feeling like outsiders.

As Blackledge and Pavlenko (2001) note:

Multiple identities are constructed and negotiated through language and are themselves in need of explanation, secondly, linguistic forms and strategies have multiple functions and cannot be directly linked to particular identities outside of interactional contexts" (p.244).

In other words, identity is not fixed but fluid and shifting, even constructed through language and the linguistic needs of different contexts. Chinese international students are moving from one linguistic context and its set of rules to another. Hall (1996) argues that many students may "have a unified and stable identity and become fragmented, composed, not of a single, but of several, sometimes contradictory or unresolved, identities" (p.598). Therefore, Chinese international students may become confused about their identities when they first come to the UK, as language and its association with specific identities can vary depending on situational, cultural, and relational factors. For example, the same linguistic behaviour may be interpreted differently by different interlocutors or in different social or academic settings, leading to shifting and complex understandings of identity, which may be the situation for Chinese

international students as English learners and speakers in the UK. They need to face the challenges which they might encounter not only from their studies and different social contents but also their shifting linguistic identities by using Chinese, English or both, depending on the context. This is connected to how Chinese students and their emergent identities in this new social and academic context are viewed by others, which to my knowledge is an area that has not been fully researched.

Thus, in discussions concerning the developing identity of Chinese international students, particularly in relation to ‘face’ culture, it is important to examine thoroughly the influence of culture, especially considering the weight that it holds in an analysis of ‘face’ culture.

3.3 Culture

Said (1993) claimed that culture is a multifaceted concept that extends beyond mere economic, social, and political dimensions. Culture does not only refer to entertainment but also serves as a reflection of a society’s values, beliefs, and aspirations. Additionally, Said (1993) suggests that culture encompasses a refining and elevating aspect, serving as each society’s repository of the finest knowledge and ideas. Said (1993) provided an understanding of the nature of culture, by emphasizing that culture is essential to society. Chinese international students initially may experience culture shock which is a common reaction to experiencing a different culture, and this very often happens when they attempt to embrace cultural diversity and exchange ideas within the UK culture. Chinese ‘face’ culture is one of the cultural differences that people in the UK may not be aware of and Chinese international students themselves may not even recognize. Therefore, this research aims to find out how Chinese international students perceive ‘face’ culture and whether it has an impact on their developing identity as English learners and speakers in both social and academic contexts.

However, Pennycook (1998) claimed that “culture is not taken to be some artistic domain but rather the much broader field of how we make sense of our lives” (p.165). Pennycook (1998) proposed the concept of cultural fixity, emphasizing its significance in understanding cultural constructions. Hence, this is very important in considering the experiences of Chinese international students in the UK.

However, the studies of Pennycook (1998) and Said (1993) were written before the development of China as a key role in global society. Pennycook (1998) further suggests that cultures held by students are often described as “fixed, static and deterministic, in terms of Asian, or Japanese or Hispanic etc. students having certain characteristics as if these emerged from some preordained cultural order” (p.188). In other words, the cultures attributed to students are often described as fixed, and unchanging, with labels such as “Asian”, “Japanese”, or “Hispanic” implying inherent characteristics that stem from a fixed cultural framework. This may be the attitudes which Chinese international students experience in the UK in terms of how they are perceived by others as English learners and speakers, and indeed, how they perceive themselves in terms of culture. Moosavi (2022) argues that East Asian students have to face the negative evaluations of mainstream society because they are often described as

foreign “others”. Indeed, Chinese international students may encounter challenges and stereotypes in both social and academic contexts; for example, Chinese international students often are referred to as passive learners, and their behaviours and expressions can also be constrained due to the different expectations of others, which can be a hindrance to their identity development as English speakers and learners in the UK.

Borghetti (2019) suggests that the term “culture” includes a range of material, social, or subjective traits collectively shared by members of a particular national or ethnic group, including elements such as history, traditions, social practices, communication norms, religion, and value systems. This understanding was rooted in the conventional approach to the language-culture connection, where the relationship between a language and its speakers was primarily associated with a specific national or ethnic community. In other words, Borghetti (2019) is questioning the approach to the initial discussion of culture made by Said (1993) and Pennycook (1998).

In this study, Chinese international students come from a certain ethnic group where ‘face’ is an unspoken social rule. Therefore, when they are living and studying in the UK, they may experience cultural shock and conflicts between different cultures; as above, their initial reaction to the culture they think they understand may be very different, because it is so wide-ranging. Moosavi (2022) believes that there is a common generalization about East Asian students: that they experience culture shock and difficulties in Western education. This generalization often views East Asian culture as static and overbearing and blames East Asian culture for hindering students’ progress. Sometimes, Confucianism is specifically mentioned to explain the perceived obedience and passiveness of East Asian students (Nield, 2004). Indeed, in some cases, East Asian students may be seen as having characteristics shaped by Confucianism, distinct from Western education. However, this misrepresentation of Confucianism can make the teachers or peers ignore the individuality of East Asian students. Therefore, the real question should be whether the West fosters an educational environment conducive to East Asian students demonstrating their abilities.

Borghetti (2019) further argues that culture can be seen as the developing characteristics recognized by members of a specific human group, whereas identity represents a personal, contextual, and dynamic process of aligning with various groups, whether large or small. This can bring additional challenges for Chinese international students, as they may need to navigate their identities in more fluid ways in relation to the culture in which they are living. Chinese international students need to negotiate and shift their identities in different contexts, which is in line with the work of Borghetti (2019) who argues that cultural belonging may not always be perceived as significant by individuals, who may experience shifts in identification based on various factors defining the specific communicative context they are engaged in (e.g., physical environment, participants, goals). They may need to selectively adopt aspects of Western culture such as their behaviour in the classroom, a different way of dress, or food to eat to find a sense of belonging, while still maintaining their Chinese cultural heritage, resulting in complex identity development or negotiations. This relates to the work of Moosavi (2022), who argued in academia, there is a tendency to generalize East Asian students as homogenized learners, while these academics see them as “saviour academics” who rescue East Asian

students from their 'deficiencies'. This may also explain why Chinese international students are often perceived as passive learners, with no critical thinking or hardly engaging in classroom settings. Moosavi (2022) argues that critical thinking is essential in navigating challenges across cultures which is often viewed in culturally relativist terms. East Asian students' perceived lack of critical thinking is attributed to East Asian cultural characters emphasizing where knowledge is supposed to be memorized and rote-learning, hindering students from offering their own or different perceptions. There is existing literature (Atkinson, 1997) claiming that East Asian students are seen as being constrained by a culture that prevents them from asking questions or thinking independently or critically but they can be "rescued", as Moosavi (2022) discusses. The idea that East Asian students struggle with critical thinking (Hammersley-Fletcher & Hanley, 2016) often implies that Western students are naturally good at it. However, Pu and Evans (2019) argue that East Asian students have the same critical thinking skills just as Western students, that Western students are not inherently better at critical thinking, and language proficiency should not be connected with critical thinking ability.

Borghetti (2019) further suggests that the traditional definition of "culture" has lost its relevance in describing contemporary reality, largely due to the impacts of globalization, such as migration, mass tourism, and the Internet. The increased ease of interaction among people today allows individuals greater autonomy in choosing which cultural groups they wish to engage with in general. Therefore, Hannerz (1992) argues that "cultures are no longer cohesive systems" passed down with minimal variation from generation to generation (p.8).

With the rapid development of Chinese society, the younger generation may choose to engage with different cultures freely via social media or books, and their perceptions of cultural heritage are changing as well. They see themselves as international students who belong to Chinese society but also to the global society. Moreover, these changes in the understanding of culture due to globalization can have significant implications for Chinese international students in the UK, as highlighted by Borghetti (2019). Chinese international students may encounter a diverse range of cultural experiences within the UK which can lead to a deeper understanding of cultural diversity and may challenge traditional notions about their own culture and others' culture which they have grown up with.

Borghetti (2019) believes that "individuals' cultural realities are expressed through acts of identity via the use of language (p.7)", while "Risager (2007) repeatedly stresses that the relationship between language and culture "does not emerge clearly" (p. 127), is "contradictory" (p. 147) or appears "heterogeneous and conflicting" (p. 156)." In other words, we express culture through language and there is a core relationship between language and culture that may appear conflicting and may be difficult for Chinese students to access initially.

In this research, the relationship between culture, identity and language needs to be discussed, as it not only reflects how Chinese international students perceive themselves, negotiate with others in a different language and social settings, and how cultural differences may impact them, but also how they are perceived by others. Chinese international students including myself as the researcher, use English as a tool for communication to express our identities while interacting with others and even seeking approval from others in the classroom or outside of

the classroom, as the use of language plays a crucial role in signalling the identity an individual wishes to be acknowledged (Borghetti, 2019).

3.3.1 Cultural identity and language

Borghetti (2019) outlined three different frameworks for conceptualizing “identity” within the context of intercultural language education, which is Norton’s (2006) work: “a sociocultural conception of identity” (pp. 24-25); Bucholtz and Hall’s core framework- “the relationship between identity and language”, “where identity is assumed as being produced in interaction” (p.4); and Zimmerman (1998) who distinguishes between “discourse,” “situational,” and “transportable” identities (p.4).

The first framework, proposed by Norton (2006), emphasizes identity’s dynamic nature across time and place, its complexity and multifaceted nature, its relationship with power dynamics, its connection with classroom practice through self-reflexivity, and its construction by language. In relation to this research, Chinese international students may experience significant transitions in their sense of belonging as they adapt to a new language and cultural context, they may need to navigate their academic and social environments in the UK. This is evidence of the dynamic nature of culture, Chinese international students as referred to earlier in terms of culture shock, cannot simply fit in, they have to adjust their behaviours to the new cultural context.

Bucholtz and Hall’s framework (2005) focuses on the discursive construction of identity, which emphasizes the emergence of identity in interaction, the influence of temporary roles on identity formation, the connection of identities to broader ideological structures, their relational nature, and their partiality in specific contexts. Just as Chinese international students negotiate their identities in interaction with others, both within their academic institutions and in broader social settings, this negotiation may involve adopting temporary roles or positions. For example, they need to present themselves as international students or peers, while navigating power dynamics with lecturing and university administrators within these contexts and negotiating these shifts in their self-perception and different social relationships.

Zimmerman (1998) offers a third framework distinguishing between discourse, situational, and transportable identities. In relation to Chinese international students, transportable identities may refer to how they view themselves in the move from being Chinese, and children of their parents in terms of social and educational experience, to a very different new environment. Zimmerman (1998) suggests that transportable identities refer to more stable yet contextually relevant aspects of identity, which are often linked to language use in interaction and to negotiation or resistance in discourse, illustrating individuals’ performance of “acts of identity” through language to maintain their “local identity line”. Chinese international students may need to switch between Mandarin and English, adapting their language use to different social situations. This language adaptation is not just about communication but also about performing their identity in various contexts. For example, speaking Mandarin with fellow Chinese students can enhance a connection to their home culture, while speaking English in academic

settings may help them integrate into the UK culture. This framework provides insight into how Chinese international students may navigate their identities in the UK; and the negotiation of identity may occur in various social interactions, such as classroom discussions and social contexts, especially in environments where they feel their cultural identity is misunderstood. They may avoid or restrain certain characteristics of their identity, such as “face-related” behaviours and in relationship to their cultural background, depending on the situational context and interactional dynamics. In other words, they bring their experiences of ‘face’ into a much more fluid, wider and international society, they have to negotiate the shifting identities not only their identity in culture but also their own experience and understanding of ‘face’ culture.

According to Spencer-Oatey (2015), both Western and Chinese scholars agree that ‘face’ can be lost, saved, and given, research from a Western perspective focuses more on ‘saving face’, specifically in the context of politeness. Brown and Levinson’s politeness theory on ‘face’ emphasizes an individualistic perspective where one uses polite language and behaviour to enhance their own ‘face’ (Forbes, 2019). However, in Chinese culture, politeness is more about being aware of and mutually enhancing each other’s ‘face’, as Yu (2003) described and discussed. This suggests that in Chinese culture, politeness may not just be about individual behaviour but also involves the consideration of others in social interactions. Forbes (2019) further suggests that in the Western context, the concept of ‘face’ is often limited to the context of politeness and ‘saving face’, while in Chinese culture, the concept of ‘face’ is broader and more interpersonal, which makes it more prevalent and important in Chinese society. This means that in Chinese culture, ‘face’ is not just about individual behaviours, but also involves mutual respect and social harmony, which may continue to be the situation for Chinese international students in the UK where they may worry about ‘face’ or make others ‘lose face’ during social interactions.

In Chinese society, the notion of ‘face’ is extremely significant (Hinze, 2005, p.171; Qi, 2011, p.280), and there are various expressions in the Chinese language to explain certain social phenomena and people’s behaviour which all are linked to the ‘face’ concept. The results from an online survey in 2006 indicate that 83.3% of Chinese people believe that ‘face’ is important and cannot be ignored in social interactions (Kinnison, 2017). Therefore, to investigate the impact of ‘face’ culture on Chinese international students’ developing identity as learners and speakers of English, the concept of ‘face’ needs to be explored and understood. To further compound the challenges, gender is another one of the factors that may shape Chinese international students’ identities, therefore, needs to be investigated and explored in a broader discussion of identity and in relation to face culture.

3.4 Gender

Butler (1999) suggests that gender identity is socially constructed, politically charged and informed by a socio-historical context of a male-dominated society and other social laws (Yaghoubi-Notash et al., 2019). In other words, gender identity is not something people are born with or naturally possess, but rather something that is constructed by many external factors.

Butler (1999) argues that how we understand and perform gender is deeply influenced by social norms, politics, social context and the historical context in which we live. When Chinese international students come to the UK, they may encounter different cultural expectations regarding their understanding of gender expression and identity in general. Butler's work provides an understanding of the complex interplay of gender, culture, power, and identity which they may become aware of, but also through which they themselves may be viewed by others. It is especially important to be aware of such 'face' culture-related challenges encountered by Chinese female international students in navigating their academic and social experiences in the UK.

Butler (1999) argues that given the prevalent cultural environment in which women's lives have been either misrepresented or not revealed at all, these various societal expectations have seemed essential. In many contemporary non-Western cultures, women are further away from the prestige norms of society (Holmes and Meyerhoff, 2003, p.109). In other words, women are considered by many cultures to have a lower status, even in 2024. Holmes and Meyerhoff (2003) also discussed how individuals use language to convey their gender identity and navigate their place within society. Gender exists with other aspects of our identity, like race, and class, as previously discussed. It also explores how language can challenge or reinforce traditional gender norms, and how gender with other social factors like race, ethnicity, sexuality, and class affect individuals' language use. It is for this reason that I chose to investigate the context in China, from which participants in this study have come and where the traditional culture is valued, especially 'face' culture. It emphasises that gender is not experienced in isolation but interacts with these other aspects of identity, which means gender and identity are intertwined and closely tied, which may be a challenge for young Chinese women in the UK. The continuing evolution of language and gender dynamics, connected with shifting societal attitudes towards gender should not be ignored. However, to my knowledge, I was not able to find any literature specifically on how Chinese 'face' culture and gender are linked. Therefore, this would be an area of interest for me and any further research.

Holmes and Meyerhoff (2003) note that "language is not simply a passive reflector of society, it also creates it. There is a constant interaction between society and language" (p.112). Language is how we express ourselves, but it is not just a tool for communicating with others. Language also reflects the values and beliefs of our culture, and it is helpful to discuss within this study that this includes values and beliefs around gender and its specific roles. In every culture, there may be "unspoken" rules about how men and women are supposed or expected to speak and indeed behave, which determine everything from the words we choose to the tone of our voice. Kamran (2021) suggests that "In Pakistan, a good woman consents to these norms and is docile, obedient, soft-spoken and well-mannered. She is oriented towards the home and avoids participating in the public sphere (p.4)". These linguistic differences and fixed stereotypes reflect and reinforce traditional gender roles and power dynamics, just as Yaghoubi-Notash, Mohammad and Soufiani (2019) argued "According to Butler, people are compelled to act out our expected gender identities to become signified in society". Therefore, within this context, Chinese international students, and in particular, female students, there is need to

develop their identity as English learners and use their ‘voice’ in a way that counteract and overcome any negative stereotypes they may encounter.

3.4.1 Gender and language

Butler (1999) suggests that by performing linguistic acts, people are continuously using language to practise and reiterate its power, which means performativity becomes absolute power. In other words, in the context of gender, linguistic acts are particularly effective in enforcing and repeating traditional gender roles and expectations. The absolute power embedded within linguistic performativity shapes not only individual identities but is also woven through societal structures, which affects how Chinese young women in the UK develop their identities and how they are influenced by traditional gender norms and cultural stereotypes in relation to the expectations, both academic, linguistic and societal imposed upon us. Yaghoubi-Notash et al. (2019) argue that linguistic patterns in everyday interactions reflect issues of performance and power; just as gender is defined by simplistic labels “girl” or “boy”, a person’s gender identity can develop in society, and this is often what Chinese international students experience as they become aware of how they are viewed by others in the UK. In other words, people’s perceptions of how they should behave may and do influence their behaviours.

Chinese international students come to the UK with the labels “Chinese”, and “second language users”, however, additional perceptions around them being ‘male’ or ‘female’ are often made by other students and even teachers while their own identities have been developed through living and studying in the UK, this can be a difficult process for them to navigate.

Butler (1999) has studied language from the perspective of gender and believes that feminine and masculine identities can be shaped through gender acts and language (Yaghoubi-Notash et al., 2019). In other words, Butler (1999) believes that language plays an essential role in shaping the individual’s identity. Whenever language is used, the gender embedded in language can take on several forms since “language patterns” are so closely related to “social patterns” (Yaghoubi-Notash et al., 2019), that is, what is normal in UK society but not in Chinese society. In this study, Chinese international students in the UK may thus encounter differing cultural expectations around gender roles and identities compared to those in China. For example, English is gendered in terms of pronouns, such as ‘he’, and ‘she’ while spoken Chinese is not, as in Chinese (tā) is used for both ‘he’ and ‘she’, although it should be noted that written Chinese does distinguish genders. Even potentially simple linguistic issues such as these, have to be navigated by Chinese international students.

Bulter (1999) further argues that “gender is not always constituted coherently or consistently in different historical contexts, because gender intersects with racial, class, ethnic, sexual, and regional modalities of discursively constituted identities” (p.40). Indeed, Chinese international students’ experiences may be further complicated by factors such as race, ethnicity, and class, as language use and pattern are influenced by all of these, which is discussed much further by radical feminists (Lewis, 1989; Hall and du Guy, 2011; Lindqvist et al., 2021). This research does not aim to explore this specific topic, other than to acknowledge the complexity of gender

within a broader context of identity, and how universities in the UK can better support Chinese international students.

Early sociolinguistic studies of gender often assumed that gender should be studied where it was most salient, and that gender was most salient “in cross-sex interaction between potentially sexually accessible interlocutors, or same-sex interaction in gender-specific tasks” (Brown and Levinson 1983, p.53). However, Holmes and Meyerhoff (2003) argue that there are at least four significant, and increasingly controversial, theoretical assumptions about gender embedded in this recommendation: (1) gender is closely wedded to sex, and the study of gender is closely wedded to the study of heterosexuality; (2) gender is an attribute; (3) the study of gender is the study of individuals; and (4) gender is best studied where most salient (p.22). There were assumptions made in early sociolinguistic studies regarding gender research and the theoretical controversies arising from them in the past, but they have been challenged and changed within the development of modern society. As discussed above, gender research should not only focus on individuals but should also consider the societal and cultural influences and interactions on the development of attitudes toward their gender. In general, the difference between gender and sex is within physiological and sociological contexts, however, in this research, gender is used and considered as a sociological term, not a physiological term.

Holmes and Meyerhoff (2003) further suggest that the difference between sex and gender is a key idea in Western feminist thought, which challenges the belief that differences and inequalities between women and men are solely because of biology or being male or female. In other words, the sociobiological view simply merges gender into ‘sex’. Some researchers think gender is just based on biology (like being male or female), while others see it as more about how society and culture shape our ideas of what it means to be a man or a woman. Feminists argue that while there are biological differences between men and women, these differences do not decide how people act or think (Beauvoir, 2015; Bulter, 1999; Hooks, 2015). Holmes and Meyerhoff (2003) believe that society plays a key role in shaping gender and intend to explore how gender is connected to our biology and our social environment. It is important to explore how attitudes toward gender have developed and to consider how it is influenced by different cultures and societies.

In this study, it is interesting to note that Chinese international students have come from a particular culture and Chinese institutions, and their related language has constructed them as silent, and obedient (Hwang et al., 2002); however, there are even more expectations associated with the behaviours of women, which is also central to traditional Chinese ‘face’ culture. These specific expectations can be considered along with Butler’s (1999) argument that society assigns certain roles, behaviours, and expectations to individuals based on their perceived gender. It means that Chinese students in general, have to negotiate many challenges, however, for Chinese females, the challenges are even bigger, as we are expected to be even more silent and obedient. Therefore, it is important to discuss the influence of ‘face’ culture within which gender dynamics may also play a crucial role in shaping their identities as English learners and speakers in the UK.

3.4.2 Gender and context

Context plays a crucial role in understanding language use and its relationship with gender, which means understanding how the environment influences the way people use language to talk about gender and indeed perceive others' use of language. I am concerned with the focus on the participants in this study as young Chinese women and their issues or experiences, and the layers of power which has informed these experiences.

This is a vital part of the overall discussion because context embraces factors such as culture, and society, within the specific situation, and all of these may affect how language is used and understood. This discussion is about how much control individuals have in using language within the power structures which are woven through society that influence how language is used and thus is relevant to a discussion of language and face culture. People use language within contexts which are informed by a certain 'power', for example, gender in relation to assumed or perceived roles and stereotypes, that can shape how language is used, particularly in this context, which focuses on how power shapes the language choices of Chinese women but also how they are perceived.

In summary, it has been helpful to explore and discuss in relation to the area of gender within this research, even though it is not central to this study. This section explores the relationship between gender, language, identity and culture, particularly focusing on the experiences of Chinese female international students studying in the UK. Furthermore, the research underlines the importance of considering broader societal and cultural contexts in analysing gender dynamics.

However, gender is not the focus of this research, and in this chapter, I will focus on consulting and discussing the 'face' culture-related literature which will enable me to analyse the issues raised in the previous chapter; to answer the research questions discussed in Chapter 1 and, at the end of this chapter, develop the interview questions for the participants in this research.

3.5 The concept of Chinese face culture

'Face' culture is a major principle, and it is deeply rooted in Chinese culture which can be explained as honour, respect, or even status (Carr, 1993). That is, in Chinese society, the expressions related to 'face' are connected with a person's honour and the related respect that one gives to her/him or even the person's status in the society. As discussed earlier in the Context chapter, 'face' culture is closely tied to Confucianism and China is still influenced by Confucian culture. The Confucian culture encourages people to "pay great attention to propriety, righteousness, honesty and shame, which are the four dimensions of the country" (Hong and Yu, 2018, p.1325), and if all have been thoroughly considered and fulfilled, it is believed that the nation will be prosperous and powerful, and its citizens will all behave politely and follow social conventions. Hong and Yu (2018) further suggest:

Confucius also held the opinion that if one does not know the rites, he then has nothing to support himself, as a result, he cannot have his own foot stand on the world (p.1325).

This means that everyone should act and behave based on social conventions and if not, they will 'lose face' and other people will not respect them.

The most commonly cited definition of 'face' is from Goffman (1967), who is considered the first person to attempt to clarify the universal meaning of 'face' across cultures which is not specified in the Chinese context. People's behaviour is influenced by their understandings and feelings of 'face' in various cultural contexts (Hong & Yu, 2018). For instance, if someone is afraid of 'losing face' or makes others 'lose face', they may be hesitant to speak what they think out loud, even if they disagree with what is being said by others in the group, which may be the case in the context of China. Alternatively, someone who places less importance on 'face' may feel more comfortable speaking their mind, which may be the situation in Western countries. In other words, the concept of 'face' from a Western viewpoint reflects Western culture and values, whereas the 'face' view of China represents Chinese cultural and societal features. Goffman (1967) argues that 'one's 'face' and the 'face' of others are constructs of the same order which is determined by the rules of the group', thus, the key to 'gaining face' or 'losing face' depends on whether people follow the social behavioural rules of a particular society or not, and very often these social rules are unspoken but are understood by everyone in the society. This made me wonder whether Chinese international students still feel the need to follow these rules for 'gaining face' or 'losing face' while studying in the UK, which was the impetus for this study.

Qi (2017) argues that an instance of knowledge transfer where existing native Chinese concepts were largely overlooked, and a set of foreign theories was directly applied to an unfamiliar or exotic context. This means that understanding distinctively Chinese cultural attributes, such as 'face', was simply missing. While the notion of face varies across cultures, the experience of being embarrassed or gaining pride through the actions of someone else is not limited to a specific culture. It is a widespread phenomenon. The theories and concepts developed in one sociocultural context may not be meaningfully applied in other socio-cultural contexts, in general (Qi, 2017). Thus, issues around 'face' may not be easily compared across societies. As discussed, a narrow concept of 'face' that comes from Chinese culture to Western culture is not applicable. Therefore, the analysis for this particular study, has broadened to enable an exploration of the structure of Chinese society, as it informs how 'face' culture is understood by students studying in both China and the UK.

According to the 'face negotiation theory', "face is tied to the emotional significance and estimated calculations that we attach to our social self-worth and the social self-worth of others" (Ting-Toomey, 2005, p. 73), which means 'face' is woven through everyday interactions. 'People in China who have no power, wealth or status may still care about their 'face' and even desire 'face' from others' (Di, 2011, p.73). In other words, people's social status does not affect their desire for 'face'. Lu (2006) expresses a very similar idea:

Face not only belongs to the middle class and the people above them. When it comes to the face issue, even pedicab drivers and the illiterate still strive to maintain their face at all costs and in all circumstances (p.398).

Bond (1991) argues that behaving in a right and proper way is important, and people may feel a 'loss of face' if they fail (p.24); that is, the thought of pursuing individual morality is embedded in Chinese people's lives, and they are conscious of their performance and judgements by others in a group or community. This study aims to discover the use of 'face' and the perceptions of 'face' within Chinese society but also wants to find out whether Chinese international students are also affected by 'face' culture in the UK.

Bedford (2004) claims that there are four types of shame in Chinese face culture: *diu lian*, *can kui*, *xiu kui* and *xiu chi*. Bedford (2004) further explains that *diu lian* can be translated as 'loss of face' which is a long-lasting painful process; *can kui* is more like a disturbing thought which exists in one's mind and can be seen as the combination of regret and shame; *xiu kui* is a strong feeling of shame which "is the violation of a self-expectation that results in harm to others"(p.14); *xiu chi* is the strongest of the emotions, which normally equals to 'deep shame' in English (Bedford, 2004). This shows that there can be different levels of 'losing face' which often come with different emotions, and which may restrain Chinese international students' behaviour and affect their developing identities in both academic and social contexts.

Bedford (2004) further describes the feeling of embarrassment or shame felt by observers when a woman behaves in a certain way, for example, wearing a very short skirt that is perceived as strange or improper by others in China. In other words, this feeling of *xiu chi* is not necessarily directed towards the individual who is embarrassed but towards the woman who is perceived to be violating the social norm. It highlights how individuals may feel embarrassed on behalf of others and especially how a woman is expected to behave, and how this can be perceived, in Chinese society.

Chou (1996) argues that the extension of 'face' culture can be divided into personal and social areas comprising self-esteem, social desirability, and interpersonal relationships. Zhang (2017) suggests that 'the uniqueness of Chinese 'face' is that an individual would take action to maintain their 'face' or so that they do not 'lose face' and even 'gain face', not only for the 'face' of themselves but also for the 'face' of the greater self' that is the wider society. However, the definition of 'the greater self' can be different depending on individuals, as each individual is different and 'the greater self' is closely linked to the 'face' of the family (Zhang, 2017). In other words, 'face' is related not only to the individual but to the family and society.

This is also in line with Nathan and Scobell's (2012) view that 'face can be used to explain the uniqueness of Chinese diplomacy' (p.25). Although this observation refers to political diplomacy, it also refers to "individual diplomacy" because individuals can be diplomatic and interact with others; they do not want to cause situations that make themselves and others feel bad and lead to a 'loss of face'. Any factor that may damage one's social status cannot be sustained and may cause him (or her) to 'lose face' (Hwang & Han, 2012). However, it is essential to understand that this connects to 'face' being a family issue but also a societal issue. If one person makes an error, this reflects badly on that person's family but also the wider society. This is key to understanding Chinese students' behaviours in certain situations because even in classroom settings there is an awareness of a person's social status which can be a linguistic status or cultural status, and this will be discussed later in detail.

3.5.1 Chinese classroom culture

Classes serve as the main place in which students to gain knowledge and essential life skills(Zhu and Li, 2020). They are the foundation of a student’s educational journey, providing vital opportunities for learning and personal growth. Within the school environment, students not only acquire academic knowledge but also foster their worldview, life perspective, and values which will profoundly influence their future integration into society. However, Lin (2024) suggests that conventional English teaching in China aims to enhance students’ vocabulary and understanding of texts and memorise moral values to pass exams (Lu and Gao, 2004). As a result, it has little focus on “promoting students’ virtues as civic and global citizens” (Lin, 2024, p.1).

In 2020, the Ministry of Education of China introduced an educational reform requiring the development of moral education, known as “*KeCheng SiZheng*” into all fields taught at colleges and universities (Lin, 2024). This highlights a shift towards encouraging students’ moral compass alongside academic learning, which is the exploration of students’ values, principles, and attitudes.

Zhu and Li (2020) argue that a positive class culture can contribute to fostering an environment that enhances students’ capacity to adapt to societal changes and supports their learning, personal development, and their ability to navigate the complexities of the world around them. Zhu and Li (2020) further suggest that the characteristics of Chinese classroom culture can be reflected in three aspects: collective, social and normative. In other words, Zhu and Li (2020) believe that class in China operates as a collective unit where every student and teacher should contribute to the development of class culture and requires that all actions from the common interests and perspectives of the group. Moreover, class is viewed as “to make schools a microcosm of society and to form a close connection with society (p.62)”. The goal is to enable students to grasp the needs and values of the larger community within the school environment. Therefore, class culture is a reflection of the collective thoughts, and interests of its members, particularly playing a normative role in guiding the behaviour and attitudes of both teachers and students. Therefore, it is necessary to have a basic understanding of the current Chinese classroom culture and students’ behaviour, and it may help the researcher myself, have a better understanding of Chinese international students’ classroom behaviour and expectations.

3.5.2 Face culture and education in China

Wang (2023) argues that “learning is situated in both social and cultural contexts” (p.1), both of which can affect students’ learning experiences. Wang (2023) argues that the exam-focused education system remains an important role in Chinese pedagogical practice and students’ experience of learning. This focus is often attributed to Confucianism, which despite its much richer account of education emphasises the interconnectedness of individuals’ identities and learning. Although there have been attempts to change the education system, it is still considered to be the most reliable and suitable method of university selection. Students who come from areas where there are limited cultural resources (Dello- Iacovo, 2009; Zhao, 2015;

You, 2019; Wang, 2023) are not, therefore, disadvantaged, by their being exam result-based selection system instead of a subjective interview-based selection system. As China's society and Education system develops, it is interesting to explore whether 'face' culture still has an impact on the student's learning process, especially for Chinese international students overseas.

A case study by Wu (2009) suggests that the educational practices in Chinese schools, where there is a strong emphasis on reading comprehension and grammar while Oral English skills are frequently neglected in classroom teaching, leads to many students struggling to speak English proficiently despite years of learning. Moreover, Wu (2009) argues that Chinese international students in the UK still worry about 'losing face': they will choose not to express their ideas in class until they understand the exact meaning of a classroom discussion topic, unlike other international students. Wu's (2009) study suggests that the fear of making mistakes, or 'losing face' in public, especially in front of peers, is a significant hindrance for many Chinese international students in the UK. It is even more challenging for more experienced visitors like teachers or visiting scholars in the UK, many of them feel under pressure to have "good enough" English (Wu, 2009). In other words, a person's social status or how they perceive themselves may greatly affect their perception of 'losing face' culture, their behaviours, identities and indeed the related issues of 'face' culture. Therefore, it will be interesting to introduce one method of measurement to examine the level of people's face concern and how people's identity, self-image or their social status are influenced by that.

The following section will introduce the 'Loss of Face Scale' which may help to bring a clear understanding of 'face'. This means, that to understand the position of Chinese students in the UK and to understand any issues they may have with identity and 'face', it is very important to analyse the nature of 'face' in Chinese society. Therefore, analysing and exploring the difference between the Western view of 'face' and the Chinese view of 'face' may help teachers and students in order to fully capitalise on the positive role of 'face' and benefit all students in an educational context.

3.5.3 Development of the Loss of Face Scale (LOF)

Zane and Yeh (2002) developed the Loss of Face Scale (LOF) to assess individuals' level of 'face' concern. That is, the LOF is used as a measurement to examine people's concerns about their own image, and whether people are worried about 'losing face' and 'gaining face'; this knowledge and experience of 'face' are embedded in Chinese students' behaviour and interactions. After an extensive review of the literature on the concept of 'losing face', Zane and Yeh (2002) developed a project library that listed 45 'face-related' behaviours. In terms of this study, the most important considerations are that they found the most common 'face-threatening' situations (Hu, 1944; Ho, 1976; Hwang, 1987) to be related to 'social status, ethical behaviour, social propriety, social behaviour and self-discipline' (Zane and Yeh, 2002, p.126); these are key to understanding Chinese students' behaviour, such as keeping quiet during class discussions.

Hu (1994) indicates that 'face concern' exists in every culture. In other words, the need to maintain social dignity and respect is present in every society. However, the degree of importance placed on 'face' may vary across cultures. "Face is important in traditional Chinese culture but esteemed in varying degrees by generations in the US less steeped in the old ways" (Chen-Louie, 1981, p.232), which means that in the United States, the notion of 'face' may be perceived differently by different generations, and it has developed across generations; the older generation may be much more aware of being diplomatic in social interaction, so as not to offend other people, while the younger generation may be more lack of these social skills. Thus, this research focuses on Chinese international students in the UK, but it is clear that there is also an understanding of 'face' and an awareness of 'face' in other cultures as well. However, "the salience of 'face' in the social interactions of individuals from East Asian cultures has been well-documented" (Zane and Yeh, 2002, p.127), as opposed to issues around 'face' in other cultures.

The result of their research suggests that LOF is an effective measurement in the field of psychology, particularly in the study of human behaviour. The study of human behaviour is an area which is closely related to the focus of this research which is how Chinese students behave in a very different social and study context in which the unspoken rules of 'face' are very different. Meanwhile, the LOF further illustrates the extent of the influence of 'face' culture on China, and indeed the whole world in many aspects of life. This prompted further investigation of how the concept of 'face' culture may have evolved. Although it was noted that the LOF is an effective tool for the study of human behaviour, this was not investigated in detail in this thesis, though it presents an interesting area for further research. In particular, exploration was done to determine whether 'face' still has an impact on Chinese international students' experience in the UK classrooms, social behaviour and developing identity in the context of studying in the UK or not.

Shan (2020) argues that Chinese students tend to be quieter than non-Chinese students in class discussions. One of the reasons is that they want to be precise and fully prepared before sharing their ideas, however, there can be many other reasons that influence their intentions to speak Wu (2009), for example, claims that "temporary quietness" usually occurs as students navigate a "complex process" (p.9) in the UK classroom, as students are actively processing the question, grasping the concept, and formulating a response. However, there may be a gap between knowing what to say and understanding how to express it correctly in English and this often results in missed opportunities to participate in class discussions. This is in line with Shan's (2020) work which claims that it is the fear of 'losing face' or lack of confidence that stops Chinese international students from speaking in public rather than the lack of ideas. This is exactly what may happen in a classroom discussion, where Chinese international students may be seen as not engaged in class, but they may just need time to process and overcome the fear of 'losing face'. Even though they are viewed as passive learners (Shan, 2020), in fact, they may hold high expectations for themselves in contributing to engaging in-class activities. Thus, Chinese international students may encounter challenges in expressing themselves effectively in English, particularly in academic settings where precise communication is essential. Chinese international students may also hesitate to participate in class discussions due to concerns about

their language proficiency and the potential for public embarrassment, as ‘face’ can highly influence international students’ behaviour in the classroom.

Wu (2009) underscores the significance of social dynamics, particularly within the context of Chinese cultural norms, in classroom participation. He suggests that Chinese students present a greater concern for the opinions of their fellow Chinese peers or colleagues compared to non-Chinese individuals. An example in Wu’s (2009) study highlights this phenomenon: a Chinese student stops talking in a discussion after being interrupted and having his language corrected by another Chinese classmate. This sensitivity to maintaining ‘face’ among fellow Chinese students can influence their behaviour, as evidenced by students’ cautious participation in class discussions when other Chinese students are present. In contrast, it is interesting to note that observations by Wu (2009) showed when the classroom environment only involves one Chinese international student, this student’s participation increases. Therefore, just as Shan (2020) argues Chinese international students are not passive learners but may indeed be the opposite. However, their concerns over possible errors in spoken English and the need to properly prepare their words may cause a tendency to avoid being outspoken in public, or perhaps simply miss the chance to speak as they took too long to formulate their words in their heads, due to the believed requirements of ‘face’ culture as well as a lack of confidence in speaking English.

3.5.4 Face measurement models

Berger and Heath’s (2007) research shows that people usually behave similarly to those who are around them. However, sometimes people’s behaviour can be very different from others’ behaviour because of the identity signalling effect, which means that people would act differently due to their aims and needs (Chan, Berger and Van Boven, 2012). Identity signalling means that some people’s behaviour is triggered by the belief that certain of their own behaviours can deliver particular information about them as an individual to the self or others (Gal, 2015). This means that in certain contexts, the way you behave or the things you say gives information to other people that you may not want them to have. This is a worldwide phenomenon, not only in the West but also in Eastern countries, such as China (Shi, Kuang and Yang, 2017). Shi, Kuang and Yang (2017) state that people in Eastern cultures are more concerned about the way in which ‘face’ and social identity are linked compared with those in the West. This is also discussed by Li and Su (2007), who have found that the Chinese are particularly concerned with others’ opinions and the social impact of their actions; that is, the way in which this social effect manifests itself as ‘face’ (Li and Su, 2007). This is related to how people behave in certain situations and what clues other people get from them in social situations. Shi, Kuang and Yang (2017) argue that the study of ‘face’ has attracted many scholars, and yet there is still no conclusion on the dimension and meaning of ‘face’ and there is no universally accepted definition.

Thus, researchers tend to use their own measurements to explain ‘face’. Bao and Zhao (2009) developed three dimensions of individual need for ‘face’, which are “ability-based”, “relationship-based”, and “morality-based”. In other words, they believe that ‘face’ can be

explained in accordance with these three dimensions. Later, Shi, Fan and Ye (2012) extended Bao and Zhao's (2009) work and highlighted three dimensions of 'face' which are "ability-based", "relationship-based", and "morality-based". Among these, 'morality-based face' normally starts with self-restraint: in China, the expectation is that an individual's character and morality can be recognized by other people. Therefore, initially, people may be less open in interactions if they feel they are being judged according to their character and morality. In other words, it is based on the belief that people's actions and behaviour reflect their inner morality, which can be perceived by others. Moreover, self-restraint is an essential aspect of 'morality-based face', as it reflects an individual's ability to control their behaviour and actions in a way that aligns with their moral values. The other dimensions suggest that 'face' needs to be 'given' by members of external society, rather than controlled internally by one person. This implies that an individual cannot solely control how they are viewed by others but must rely on the perceptions and judgments of the external society. In other words, an individual's 'face' is not entirely under their control but is partly dependent on the opinions and attitudes of the people around them. Their research on the 'face' measurement models focuses on integrating the concept and dimensions of 'face' and proposes a more universal definition of 'face'. However, the focus of this thesis relates to the 'face' concept in the Chinese context and the UK context, as Chinese international students who are studying in the UK will be the participants of this research. Therefore, the definition of 'face' by Chinese scholars, for example, by Mao (1994) will also be discussed.

3.5.5 Mao's concept of face

Mao (1994) argues that self-image is not valued so much in China; due to the culture, Chinese people focus on public image rather than self-image. The concept of 'face', also known as "Mian Zi" in Chinese, first appeared in the early Ming Dynasty [1368-1644] (Di, 2011, p.89), and "originally means the front of a human face, the surface and appearance of the objects" (Hong & Yu, 2018, p.1324). The meaning of "Mian Zi" then developed and extended to 'face' and 'face value' (Hong & Yu, 2018).

The concept of 'face' also played a critical role in social interactions among Chinese populations (Ho, 1976, 1980; Hu, 1944). In the Western context, 'face' is employed in only a small number of fixed expressions, such as "to save face", "to lose face", and "to put on a good face" (Yu, 2003, p.1686). On the contrary, in the Chinese context, 'face' can have a more flexible and diverse set of meanings.

Mao (1994) argues that 'face' is referred to as "Lian Mian" in Chinese, which does not refer to either positive or negative 'face'. According to Hong and Yu (2018), the history of the word "Mian" is far longer than the word of "Lian". The word "Mian" is seen as a symbol which refers to the connection between society and an individual (Hong & Yu, 2018). "Mian" or "Mian Zi" represents one's pursuit of reputation in public (Mao, 1994). Indeed, one's actions do not just reflect on the person themselves but also on the community as a whole, whether it is positive or negative (Buckley, Clegg, and Tan, 2006). However, Hong and Yu (2018) suggest that the word "Lian" can be explained in a medical sense which is "the front of the head or

from the forehead to the chin” (p.1324). According to Hong and Yu (2018), the reason that “Mian” represents more interpretations than “Lian” is that one has no more than one “Lian” but has many “Mian”: “the good one, the bad one, the real one, the fake one, the honest one, the disguising one and the tricky one” (p.1324). In conclusion, Mao (1994), and Hong and Yu (2018) illustrate the origins and meanings of the Chinese concept of ‘face’ or “Lian Mian”. The term “Lian” originally referred to the physical face, but the word “Mian” is associated with concepts such as dignity, reputation and one’s social status. Thus, the concept of ‘face’ in Chinese culture is closely tied to social relationships and reputation. Overall, the concept of ‘face’ in Chinese culture reflects the importance of social relationships and reputation and has a long history of evolving meanings and associations.

Mao’s (1994) concept of Chinese ‘face’ culture can be regarded as an extension of Goffman’s (1967) work but has more emphasis on the Chinese context. Since Chinese international students grow up in a very different environment from students in the UK, where ‘face’ culture may play an important role in their life and study, it is essential to try to understand the concept of ‘face’, and for the researcher myself, to find out whether ‘face’ affects their life and study. However, it is necessary to understand the structure of Chinese society, and I will return to further discuss Mao’s (1994) concept of Chinese ‘face’ in section 3.12.3 below.

3.5.6 The effect of face culture in the Chinese context

To have a full understanding of ‘face’ culture, one must consider the complex cultural background of China (Zhang, 2017), as ‘face’ is one of the important elements of it. One way to explore Chinese culture is to explore Chinese philosophy where Confucian ethics has been the most influential among all the Chinese philosophies in people’s daily lives dating to the Spring and Autumn and Warring States periods (770-221 BCE) (Benavides, 2019) which remain influential across China and East Asia to this day. According to Jia (2001), ‘Confucianism played a crucial role in making the Chinese concept of ‘face’ become a more pervasive, more deeply rooted, more dominant form of life and government in Chinese society’ (p.20). Under this influence of Confucianism, ‘Chinese people are not only concerned about gaining or losing ‘face’ of one’s “small self” but also about gaining or losing ‘face’ of one’s “big self”’ (Hwang & Han, 2010, p.479). In other words, Chinese people are concerned about how ‘losing face’ and ‘gaining face’ may affect not only themselves but also their image which is presented to the public. Tian (2014) suggests that Chinese people tend to be indirect in communication because the philosophy of Confucius, which is deeply rooted in Chinese people’s culture, advises people to maintain a relationship with each other during an interaction. Directly refusing people seems to be a very impolite behaviour and can be a way of “not giving them face”. Thus, they prefer to express their refusals very implicitly by using explanations and reasons (Tian, 2014). Hong (2011) also suggests in her study that those people who tend to be indirect normally use explanations and apologies.

In addition, ‘face’ also influences Chinese consumer behaviour, such as conspicuous consumption, luxury, and exclusive consumption (Zhang, 2012). These purchases manifest the need for social status and social approval among Chinese people, especially during social

interactions. If the Chinese are or appear to be wealthy then they will receive a ‘positive face’ from others (Jap, 2010). This behaviour may be related to the participants in this research; I have noted that many Chinese international students like to wear luxury clothes. This may suggest that they want to receive ‘positive face’ from others, and the impact of ‘face’ on Chinese international students studying in the UK may be bigger than the researcher suspected.

3.5.7 Face culture and Chinese learners’ pragmatic proficiency

Language pragmatic proficiency is defined as the ability to properly express one’s intentions in a communicative situation and to interpret the intentions of others, either explicitly or implicitly (Thomas, 1995). In other words, language pragmatic proficiency means the ability to use a language effectively in social contexts.

‘Face’ contains the requirement of evaluation of others. Thus, it needs to be analysed in an interactive context (Spencer-Oatey, 2007). In this sense, English language pragmatic proficiency is an important element in English-speaking social interaction. English language pragmatic proficiency is considered to be a crucial part of students’ competence in adapting to a new cultural and academic environment (Machado, 2018). There are other key elements to improving one’s second language (L2) pragmatic competence which can be related to cultural differences and awareness of pragmatics. Therefore, Tian (2014) suggests that it may be necessary for teachers in China to pay attention to the language pragmatics of respect, linguistic ability, and also cultural differences. In other words, Tian (2014) believes that Chinese teachers should teach language in context, as it may increase learners’ awareness and development of pragmatic skills and also help L2 learners reduce the negative transfer of language from the first language (L1) to L2.

According to Carroll and Ryan (2005), lecturers in China would be more flexible and possibly willing to adjust their teaching methodologies to different teaching styles, if they realised the potential differences between the content of course textbooks and the development of authentic pragmatic language, which could help students develop their authentic language competence. If lecturers can apply this teaching method and focus on learners, they may foster diversity and encourage students to participate in classroom learning.

3.6 Face culture and stereotypes of Chinese students in Western countries

Goffman (1967) argues that ‘face’ is related to value judgements, especially the judgements from others. Chinese students are the largest group among all the international students in the UK, more than a quarter (27%) of all non-EU students in UK universities are Chinese (ICEF GmbH, 2023), and they may encounter challenges in this respect. It appears that Chinese students may be challenged by academic, psychological, and social adjustments at the same time, but the study abroad experience may also give students a chance for their individual growth (Wang, 2018). However, Chinese learners coming from overseas may feel isolated and lonely. The main factor is communication issues or a limited ability to use English effectively

in contexts where Chinese students may feel misunderstood and stereotypes of Chinese learners held by other learners may lead to their isolation (McCormack, 1998; Poyrazli & Lopez, 2007). In other words, other learners in the classroom may have preconceived prejudices and stereotypes, and if Chinese learners cannot communicate properly and effectively, then those existing stereotypes may make them even more isolated than they are. One of the main challenges for Chinese students in adapting to the host culture is that many have low-level English proficiency or communicative proficiency. As discussed, the learning environment in the host country can make Chinese students feel confused because it is very different from that in China (Han, 2007; Jin & Cortazzi, 2006). This points out that the learning environment in the host country can be very different from that in China, which can make it difficult for Chinese students to adapt. This can lead to confusion and disorientation, as well as difficulties in learning and interacting with peers and teachers. Chinese students may even suffer from discrimination because of their limited English or accent (Poyrazli & Lopez, 2007).

3.6.1 Culture and Stereotypes

Hill and Zhou (2023) argue that many students may experience discrimination at high school based on their gender, race and language. Moosavi (2022) argues that sometimes, Western perceptions of East Asians as “outsiders” or “others” who belong to an ‘inferior’ culture can escalate into a threat against them, just as with all forms of racial stereotypes:

This construction of East Asians as outsiders has escalated to them being represented as a threat as is common with all forms of racialised stereotyping. This manifests, for example, in the cultural icon of the ‘Chinese villain’ which is a character found within Western popular culture of an East Asian ‘evil genius’ who cannot be trusted due to their ominous intentions combined with their treacherous use of powerful knowledge (p.5).

For Chinese international students in the UK, this can significantly impact their learning experiences, especially when our culture cannot be understood, and they may feel like minorities or “outsiders”. Moreover, they often start their educational journeys with hopes of personal and academic growth, so encountering cultural discrimination can be particularly frustrating. It not only damages their educational experience but also impacts their overall well-being and sense of belonging in the UK.

Moosavi (2022) suggests that existing literature on East Asian students often fails to acknowledge their individual complexities, diverse personalities, and varied experiences. Instead, it tends to rely on outdated stereotypes and generalizations, enabling narrow and limited perspectives. Moosavi (2022) further highlights that even among students of the same ethnicity or nationality and similar cultural background, such as Chinese students from different regions, there can be significant differences and even negative stereotypes. In other words, individual differences need to be recognised which challenges the assumption that all Chinese students share the same cultural background or experiences. This may lead to misunderstandings and stereotypes among peers even teachers from different cultural

backgrounds. Thus, for Chinese international students, navigating these differences can be challenging; they may encounter stereotypes or expectations associated with their nationality, while also dealing with cultural tensions between students from different regions within China. This can create a sense of isolation or identity conflict which further adds issues around ‘face’ means that Chinese international students may encounter several related challenges, especially at the beginning of their study.

This highlights some of the challenges that Chinese students may face when studying in a foreign country, particularly in an English-speaking environment. Furthermore, these challenges may arise from a variety of factors, including differences in previous learning environments, language barriers and even discrimination based on their limited English proficiency or accent. This can further intensify their feelings of isolation and create additional barriers to success in academic or professional environments. Moreover, teachers and students in China lack opportunities and resources to hear and practise with native English speakers which can cause communication challenges when students come overseas (Liu, 2005). Thus, language barriers can be a significant obstacle for Chinese students, particularly if they have limited opportunities to practice speaking and listening to English with native speakers. This can be the situation for Chinese international students in the UK. Their previous learning experience in China can make it challenging for them to communicate effectively in academic and social settings, which can lead to feelings of isolation and frustration.

Another likely cause is that the knowledge of the target language’s social and cultural customs could also be the reason that affects learners’ pragmatic competence which determines their ability to use English authentically (Halenko and Jones, 2011). This means that there may be differences between how second language learners choose to use language to express themselves and to achieve the intention of this spoken interaction (Alemi and Tajeddin, 2014). As discussed above, many reasons can be considered as the causes of learners’ pragmatic differences in communicating effectively which may relate to pragmatic ability (Wyner and Cohen, 2015), and thus, inhibit authentic communication, or a lack of confidence in interacting with peers in the classroom.

America and other Western countries put more focus on class discussions and emphasise English listening and speaking, while Chinese educational policies and systems prefer to pay more attention to learning English grammar, reading, and writing (Zhang-Wu, 2018). Therefore, even though students have high performance on English languages proficiency exams such as TOEFL (Test of English as a Foreign Language) and IELTS (International English Language Testing System), Chinese students tend to be not well-prepared for using authentic language when they are in the host country (Xue, 2013). As already discussed, this can lead to other students reinforcing negative stereotypes, because Chinese students are, at times, not understood by other students. Moreover, Spencer-Oatey (2007) claims that people’s evaluative judgments of their own ‘face’ may be influenced by individual value constructs. In other words, individuals have different values and so they may bring their prejudices about Chinese students to this context. International students, especially Chinese students, are currently facing two main challenges upon their arrival in the host country, one is how to get used to and engage in an authentic English-speaking environment, and the other one is how to conquer the

unfavourable stereotypes against their linguistic competence which may come from native speakers (Xie et al., 2019).

Zhu and Bresnahan (2018) have discussed the unwillingness of Chinese students to communicate in public and avoid communication situations that may be linked to cultural reasons rather than a problem of language competence. In other words, Chinese students may misunderstand situations, because words that are polite in some contexts may not be polite in others. Liu (2002) also finds that many researchers believe Chinese students' silence is due to their lack of communicative competence. Ruhi (2007) states that there are three aspects of the notions of self-politeness including self-confidence, present independence, and displaying impoliteness. Ruhi (2007) adds that expressions of individualism and self-confidence are more related to Western cultures, while Eastern cultures such as Chinese and Japanese are described as humble and modest (Farrokhi and Arghami, 2017). Therefore, to find out for his study whether a lack of understanding of behaviours and language behaviours influences Chinese students' experience in the UK, Han (2013) compared request strategies adopted by native British English speakers and Mandarin speakers. There is one controversial area for Chinese students which is their silence and the obvious 'avoidance of eye contact' in the Western classroom, as this may lead to the perception based on stereotypes that Chinese students' language competence is low by some other non-Chinese students (Zhu and Bresnahan, 2018). This study aims to find out whether 'face' or 'face threat' and the related issue of stereotypes held by other students may have an impact on Chinese international students' developing identity.

Therefore, in the context of the classroom and indeed socially, 'saving face' or not 'losing face' may prompt Chinese international students to only make friends with other Chinese students, because they share the same cultural values, and they understand the notion of 'face' (Wang, 2016). They may choose to stay modest and quiet (Jiang, 2014), instead of interacting with native speakers or other learners (Cheng and Erben, 2011). This may be the situation when Chinese international students study in the UK, and it is also the key aim of this study, to find out whether 'face' culture impacts their study and their identity as English learners and speakers.

3.6.2 The Western concept of face

This section explores 'face' in relation to the Western perspective and focuses on how 'face' is understood in Western societies, which is distinct from the Chinese perspective. Brown and Levinson (1987) define 'face' as a public self-image which refers to the social and emotional sense of self that each person possesses and expects others to recognize (Hong and Yu, 2018). This suggests that 'face' in Western countries reflects people's desire for individual needs and actions.

Brown and Levinson's notion of 'face' contains both 'negative face' and 'positive face', and "though susceptible to cultural variation and elaboration, embody two valid social needs that transcend cultural boundaries" (1987, p.13,61-62; cited in Mao, 1994, p.452). 'Positive face' means that every member of society wants to be approved, respected and praised by others

which is the fundamental claim to boundaries, the right to act free from restriction (Brown and Levinson, 1987). ‘Negative face’ on the other hand, refers to a person’s right to freedom of action and their requirement to not be forced upon by others (Brown and Levinson, 1987). In other words, individuals have the desire to maintain their positive ‘face’ or image, which involves seeking support and respect from others. This ‘positive face’ can be seen as a person’s public self, or the image they want to present to others. ‘Negative face’ refers to the desire to be free from imposition or interference from others. This can be seen as a person’s private self, the desire to maintain their freedom of action. Brown and Levinson (1987) argue that:

People don’t want to be forced by others in any forms and in anytime, their behaviour is free from interference and hindrance, and they have the freedom to choose their own actions (p. 62) (cited in Hong and Yu, 2018, p.1325).

This may be the situation for Chinese international students in the UK, during social interactions that they may feel the need to balance their positive and negative ‘face’. An example will be: when someone is asked for a favour, the requester is imposing on their ‘negative face’ by imposing on their time, or personal space. This can create a feeling of pressure, or obligation on the requester, which can be uncomfortable and undesirable, while also making an appeal to their ‘positive face’ by highlighting the significance of the request and expressing gratitude for their assistance. Similarly, when giving feedback or criticism, the speaker may undermine the other person’s competence while at the same time trying to maintain their ‘negative face’ by giving suggestions for improvement in a respectful way.

The image of ‘face’ can be damaged, lost, maintained or enhanced by others, hence, in interpersonal interaction, a person must continually pay attention to ‘face’ (Brown and Levinson, 1987), which includes being mindful of how one’s actions and words might impact their own and others’ ‘face’, avoiding actions that might lead to ‘loss of face’, and actively seeking ways to enhance one’s ‘face’ through positive social interactions. As others can damage a person’s ‘face’ by publicly criticizing, insulting, or disrespecting them, this can lead to ‘loss of face’. Alternatively, others can enhance a person’s ‘face’ by praising, respecting, or acknowledging them, which can lead to maintaining or even increasing one’s ‘face’. Moreover, people can also maintain their face by avoiding situations that might lead to ‘loss of face’, such as conflicts or confrontations. It suggests that the focus of Brown and Levinson’s notion of ‘face’ is the effect of ‘face’ on individuals rather than on the whole society which is the opposite of the experience of and focus on ‘face’ in China.

In addition, Brown and Levinson (1987) used the notion of the Model Person (MP) to refer to someone “with the ability to rationalise from communicative goals to the optimal means of achieving those goals” (Watts, 2003, p.85). In other words, the MP possess the ability to analyse their communication goals and make rational decisions about the best ways to achieve them. Although the notion of the MP seems to fit well with Brown and Levinson’s concept of ‘face’, Watts (2003) questions whether Brown and Levinson’s MP model “can be seen as an attempt to formulate a theory of how individuals produce linguistic politeness, that is, a production model” (Watts, 2003, p.85). In other words, Watts is concerned that Brown and Levinson have developed a theory based on an “ideal person”, but it is important to consider how well this

“ideal person” matches the reality of how people actually behave during social interaction. Watts (2003) further suggests that the MP may need to assess the risks of endangering other participants’ ‘face’ (and hence their own) and then act with appropriate strategies in order to minimise ‘face threats’. This may be the situation for the participants in this study where Chinese international students may take necessary communicative strategies in order to ‘save face’ or avoid ‘loss of face’.

3.6.3 Face and culture shock

This study discussed how Chinese international students can feel the pressure of ‘face’ consistently which also can lead to their developing and changing identities and the way they perceive themselves; their behaviours and development of their learning may also be affected. Chinese international students come to a new cultural environment in the UK; it is normal to feel overwhelmed and it may not be easy for them to adapt to living in the host country; some of them may behave based on the principle of not ‘losing face’. Therefore, culture shock is one of the challenges that Chinese international students may encounter, and this has been frequently discussed in related literature (Oberg, 1960; Locke and Feinsod, 1982; Furnham & Bochner, 1986; Shen & Chen, 2020). The concept of culture shock was first proposed by Oberg (1960) who holds that “cultural shock is caused by the anxiety resulting from losing all our familiar signs and symbols when we move to a new environment in advance (p. 14).”; then it was discussed in two parts: intercultural shock and intracultural shock. The culture shock experienced by Chinese international students is normally referred to as ‘intercultural’ shock (Xia, 2020). It will be interesting to investigate whether Chinese international students feel ‘face’ related culture shock is a challenge to their study and in the UK where the concept of ‘face’ can be very different.

3.6.4 The differences in the concept of face between Western countries and China

According to Hong and Yu (2018), there are differences in the concept of ‘face’ between Western countries and China. ‘Positive face’ refers to the desire to be appreciated and respected by others, and this is seen as similar between the East and the West. However, ‘negative face’, which refers to the desire for autonomy and freedom from imposition by others, is seen as more important to Westerners than the Chinese. Hong and Yu (2018) use an example of giving up one’s seat on public transport to illustrate this difference. In China, it is seen as perfectly normal to give up one’s seat to those in need, for example, pregnant women or disabled people, as it is a sign of kindness and respect. However, in Western countries, such behaviour may be viewed as an imposition on the person being offered the seat, as it may be seen as a sign of perceived weakness or disrespect. Western people, therefore, may be more likely to ask if they can help, rather than simply offering help outright (Hong and Yu, 2018). It may be the situation for Chinese international students in the UK that those differences between Chinese and Western societies can influence their social behaviours and the importance placed on different aspects of ‘face’. Therefore, understanding these differences in the concept of ‘face’ is important for effective communication and avoiding misunderstandings. In addition, Hong and Yu (2018)

highlight how differences in ‘negative face’ can manifest in different cultural practices, such as eating habits. Hong and Yu (2018) claim that Chinese hospitality involves constantly serving food and urging guests to eat more, which can be seen as imposing on the guests’ freedom and preferences in the context of the West. In contrast, Western people tend to offer more freedom in food choices and may simply say “Help yourself” as a way of showing respect for the guests’ autonomy (Hong and Yu, 2018). This suggests that Chinese international students in the UK may be affected by ‘face’ culture in how people interact and communicate with each other socially, especially with people who are unfamiliar with the concept of ‘face’. This is related to theories of politeness which are discussed below.

3.7 Brown and Levinson’s (1987) politeness theory

3.7.1 Politeness

Politeness is a universal concept and Hill et al. (1986) state, “it is also one of the constraints on human interaction, whose purpose is to consider others’ feeling, establish a level of mutual comfort and promote rapport” (p.349). Brown and Levinson’s (1978, 1987) politeness theory contain three basic notions: face, face-threatening acts (FTAs), and politeness strategies. According to Studies and Istifci (2017), speakers use verbal and non-verbal devices in social interaction and communication. The devices are ‘acts’, which means that under some circumstances, we may act in a way that can threaten ‘face’. These acts are called ‘face-threatening acts’ (FTAs), which can be categorised into two kinds: FTAs that threaten ‘negative face’, which means the speakers hope their actions will not be hindered by others and acts which threaten their ‘positive face’ (Brown and Levinson, 1987). Moreover, ‘face threats’ and the resulting IN Chinese students’ confidence may affect whether Chinese students contribute to class discussions or not (Wang, McConachy and Ushioda, 2002).

Brown and Levinson (1987) also propose three strategies of politeness comprising positive politeness, negative politeness, and off-record politeness. ‘Positive politeness’ may tend to focus on directness, where the speaker gives truthful responses based on facts and their intention to be friendly and encouraging, while ‘negative politeness’ may tend to attach importance to maintaining social distance and ‘saving face’ (Studies and Istifci, 2017). Both politeness strategies are linked closely to one critical element which is ‘face’ (Tian, 2014). ‘An individual's face consists of two desires: the desire to be approved of by others (termed ‘positive face’) and the desire to be unimpeded by others in one's actions (termed ‘negative face’)’ (Brown and Levinson, 1987). Both can be threatened by face-threatening acts, for example, ordering or offering from others and according to Ernawati (1996), ‘FTAs that threaten ‘negative face’, by wanting their own actions to be unimpeded by others, and FTAs that threaten ‘positive face’, by wanting to be desirable to at least some others. (p.80)’ which refers to notions of politeness. In other words, off-record politeness is an implication politeness strategy (Brown and Levinson, 1987), which means that users imply what they are saying or expressing indirectly, and such implications may be a challenge for Chinese students to interpret. This may be due to cultural differences in communication styles and the expectations for directness in language use. Chinese communication tends to be more indirect and reliant on

context, while Western communication tends to be more direct and explicit. Therefore, this suggests that the use of off-record politeness may be challenging and difficult for Chinese students to interpret accurately, as it relies on indirect and implicit messages. This can lead to misunderstandings or misinterpretations in communication, which can affect interpersonal relationships.

However, some studies suggest that Brown and Levinson's (1987) politeness theory fail to explain the Chinese concept of 'face' (Mao, 1994; Gu, 1990; Hu, 1944; Ho, 1975). Matsumoto (1988) questions that the politeness theory of Brown and Levinson (1987) has not yet addressed discourse practises in Chinese cultures where the fundamental interactional focus is on group identity rather than individualism (Mao, 1994). Furthermore, Mao (1994) argues that "Brown and Levinson's theory lacks a culturally unbiased conceptual framework for objectively and empirically evaluating their politeness universals" (p.452). In other words, Brown and Levinson's (1987) theory of politeness is based on the assumption that there are certain universal principles of politeness that are shared across cultures. Thus, Mao (1994) argues that their theory has a Western bias and does not consider the diversity of cultural norms and values. Therefore, it is difficult to apply their theory universally without considering cultural variations. In addition, Mao (1994) suggests that Brown and Levinson's theory may not have an objective way of evaluating their politeness universals, as evaluating politeness involves subjective judgments and perceptions which can vary between individuals and cultures. Gu (1990) argues that "Brown and Levinson's model is not suitable for the Chinese context. Although Brown and Levinson's (1987) politeness theory further explain the concept of 'face', this politeness model is not suitable as a theoretical framework for this research as it does not fully explain the place of Chinese 'face' in Chinese culture. The reason will be discussed in the theoretical framework section of this thesis.

3.7.2 Communication strategies

People may use different communication strategies in terms of the degree of threats to others' 'face' so that they may lower the risk of potential 'face threats' (Brown and Levinson, 1987). In order to avoid being offensive, most people may choose to speak indirectly to avoid threatening speech acts (Farrokhi and Arghami, 2017), which means they tend to be polite and use indirect speech acts. For example, Chinese students may choose to communicate with their teachers privately, rather than directly requesting more information in class. However, different languages and cultures have various features that influence the usage of language pragmatic rules (Leech, 1983). In other words, actions that are considered polite in one language and culture may not or even be rude in another language and culture (Farrokhi and Arghami, 2017). For example, one of the communication strategies regards to politeness is to give a compliment, as the speaker tries to establish or maintain rapport with the person complimented by expressing agreement, approval, and praise (Wolfson, 1986).

Brown and Levinson's view on compliments, is that they see them as potentially threatening to both the positive and negative 'face' of the person receiving the compliment. This can create tension in social interactions, as the person may feel pressured to respond in a certain way in

order to maintain their 'positive face'. However, Mao (1994) argues that this view of compliments is negative and does not consider the positive effects of compliments in social interactions. Furthermore, Brown and Levinson focus on the ways in which individual wants may limit the universality of their theory of 'face'. Despite the fact that Brown and Levinson's theory of politeness offers insightful analysis of social interactions, it is important to consider its potential biases which may cause them to ignore the wider cultural and social issues that affect politeness and 'face'. To develop a more thorough and cultural knowledge of 'face', additional research will be discussed and analysed in this study.

Yu (2003) proposes that during social interactions and communication, it is normal to encounter compliments and problems in responding to compliments. The use of compliments varies from culture to culture; and English learners may choose to use strategies that they use in their first language (Farrokhi and Arghami, 2017), but such strategies would have to be accurately expressed in English for mutual understanding, too. Moreover, non-native speakers of English often have trouble giving and receiving compliments when they have social interactions with native speakers. Therefore, Chinese international students in social contexts may use improper expressions and cause misunderstandings, which may lead to 'losing face', as they may not be able to communicate properly and effectively.

Since compliments may be considered to be an act of judgement or a comment on someone and can be threatening some person's 'face', some people from non-Western countries may feel disturbed and uncomfortable about receiving a compliment and find it difficult to respond to compliments appropriately, which makes it difficult for them to respond to compliments appropriately (Knapp, Hopper & Bell, 1984). In other words, Chinese students grow up in a very different social environment from Western students and therefore, in certain social contexts, they may not understand the compliments of Western students and even respond improperly. This may reinforce the stereotypes held by other Western students and may influence Chinese students' experiences in the UK.

Research on compliment responses has shown that compliment responses may have different functions (Farrokhi and Arghami, 2017). According to some studies and research, Chinese people have been found often to use rejection-type responses to compliments, thus it is believed that Chinese society prioritizes modesty over agreeing (Cai, 2012; Chen & Yang, 2010). Chen (1993) proposes research about the comparison of compliment responses between Chinese learners of English and native speakers. "Chinese non-native speakers prefer to reject compliments while native speakers tend to accept and appreciate them. (p.59)" Chinese people are modest which is a key character in traditional Chinese culture, which means sometimes Chinese people would use false modesty to maintain and even enhance their image. Yu (2003) also suggests that modesty is a cultural value which is also an expression of 'face' and politeness. However, the modesty of Chinese students may not be understood by other international students, as they may hold prejudices against Chinese students and think Chinese students lack language competence. This study, therefore, will explore whether Chinese students will maintain their 'face' and politeness even when they feel confused and lack an understanding of the unique position of giving and receiving compliments in English and the associated issues around politeness in the context of the UK.

3.8 Redmond's face-related principles

Redmond (2015) argues that although it was not initially conceived as a formal theory, the concept of 'face' has progressed into a more structured and organized framework over time. Then Redmond (2015) proposed three 'face' related principles based on the work of Goffman and also Brown and Levinson to have a better understanding of 'face':

Principle 1: The faces people take are contextually bound (the situation, the culture or society, and other participants) and produce a ritual process of orderly but constrained interaction.

Principle 2: We depend upon other people to accept and validate our face through a process called facework.

Principle 3: Numerous strategies are utilized in facework. We have strategies for managing face-threatening acts and repairing or restoring face (p.30).

3.8.1 Principle 1: faces are bound

Redmond (2015) further explains that an individual's 'face' in a classroom setting would differ from that in a social environment or while interacting with family and friends. According to Tracy (1990), people present different 'faces' based on various situational factors such as the nature of the task, their assigned role, the location, and cultural expectations. Once an individual adopts a particular 'face', they are bound by a sense of obligation to maintain that identity in subsequent interaction (Redmond, 2015). In this sense, the 'face' that an individual adopts may constrain them, as they feel forced to behave with the 'face' they present (Redmond, 2015). It is worth exploring whether Chinese international students may find themselves in a very similar situation where 'face' restrains their behaviours and actions and their developing identity while they study and live in the UK.

According to Redmond (2015), culture is a crucial element which can affect the 'faces' of people present and constrain their behaviours. This suggests that Chinese culture may have an impact on Chinese international students' developing identity as English learners and speakers. Redmond (2015) believes that in social interactions, individuals are expected to present and maintain their 'face' by following the rule of 'face' and politeness, which involves behaving in a manner consistent with the expectations of supporting each other's 'face'. In other words, 'face' needs to be recognised by both parties in order to maintain the relationship and more importantly, to keep each other's 'face'.

Goffman (1955) identified four stages that occur when a face is threatened and needs to be corrected: challenge, offering, acceptance, and thanks (cited in Redmond, 2015). The first stage is when a person, who is referred to as the offender, engages in behaviour that poses a threat to the 'face' of the other person, who is the partner (Redmond, 2015). The partner then challenges this bad behaviour. For example, if someone accidentally insults their friend in a conversation, the offender may offer an apology to offset the 'face' threat and restore balance to the interaction, which is stage two (Redmond, 2015). The apology serves as an offering to the

offended friend to repair the damage done to their ‘face’ and maintain the relationship. Stage three is the friend accepting the offering; final stage, the offender says “Thanks” to restore balance (Redmond, 2015). This example is a microcosm of the broader rituals that exist in everyday social interactions, where individuals present their ‘face’ and others support their ‘faces’. These rituals are not only essential to social contexts but also to academic contexts as they allow individuals to navigate social and formal interactions and maintain their social identities or what is referred to as ‘face’.

3.8.2 Principle 2: facework supports individuals’ face

Redmond (2015) suggests that individuals’ ‘face’ only exists in social interactions and relationships with others, and we may put on a particular ‘face’ due to different social circumstances and expect others to recognise and accept that ‘face’ we present. In other words, we are seeking others’ approval of our social identity or ‘face’ during social interactions. According to Brown and Levinson’s politeness theory, it is important to keep a balance between the necessity for clear communication (to achieve your goals) and the requirement to use ‘facework’ to protect your own ‘face’ and other person’s ‘face’ (Redmond, 2015).

In general, both individuals are involved in ‘facework’, where they behave in order to support each other’s ‘face’. This is in line with Kennedy (2002) who describes that in the Chinese classroom setting, students need to support teachers’ work and behaviour modestly and keep quiet and stay focused, not talk to each other. It may be seen as challenging teachers’ ‘face’ by interrupting lecturing or talking to each other, which is a ‘face-threatening’ act. It will be worth finding out whether Chinese students will still follow the unspoken rules of ‘face’ and avoid ‘face-threatening’ acts in the classroom while they are studying in the UK.

3.8.3 Face-threatening acts and management

Goffman (1955) noted that “In trying to save the face of others, the person must choose a tack that will not lead to loss of his own; in trying to save his own face, he must consider the loss of face that his action may entail for others (p. 217) (also cited in Redmond, 2015, p.17)”. Redmond (2015) further argues that however, there are occasions when we have to choose between keeping our ‘face’ or losing the other person’s ‘face’, or the opposite.

According to Brown and Levinson (1987), when it comes to potentially threatening another person’s ‘face’, such as challenging or criticizing, there are three factors to consider (Redmond, 2015):

First, is the degree to which we feel a need to communicate the failure or misconduct; second, the degree of urgency or need for efficiency; and third, the degree to which we want to protect the face of the other person. As we weigh these three factors, we decide among four general options for handling the issue (p.17).

The four options for dealing with the issues are: “not do the face-threatening act”, “off record”, “on-record with redress”, “on-record without redress” (Redmond, 2015). “Not do the face-threatening act” means not asking for anyone to help with anything, only doing it yourself. “Off record” suggests that we are aware there can be a ‘face’-threaten act but do it more indirectly by making jokes or hints (Redmond, 2015). “On-record with redress”, on the other hand, refers to the fact that we are fully aware that ‘face’ is threatened but still communicate directly with each other and try to restore ‘face’. Finally, “on-record without redress” involves the behaviours of direct talk and without trying to save others ‘face’. Individuals may take different actions to handle ‘face’ related issues during social interactions which may lead to various results, such as ‘losing one’s face’ or ‘keeping one’s face’. Therefore, this study intends to discuss whether Chinese international students may encounter these ‘face’-threatening situations in both social and class contexts, and whether ‘face’ has an impact on their developing identity as English learners and speakers in the UK.

Redmond’s ‘face’-related principle was used as an extension and complementary to Brown and Levinson’s (1987) work. This model was used analytically, as Brown and Levinson’s work was conducted in 1987, and Redmond’s work updates it. Further discussions are in the generated themes in the Findings Chapter.

3.9 Face culture and identity

As Haugh (2009) argues, “face and facework involve issues broader than simply politeness” (p.3); facework in this context refers to the interpersonal abilities or techniques required to maintain or improve, and in some cases, impede, others’ perceptions of a person’s right to and worthy of respect (Fletcher, 2016). In other words, facework is how people engage with the notions of ‘face’ or how people negotiate ‘face’ in their spoken interactions with others. “Face and facework” do not only relate to politeness, but they may also reflect identity issues.

Blackledge and Pavlenko (2001) suggest that several studies like Cutler (1999), Lo (1999), and Rampton (1995, 1999c) convincingly proved that often, individuals do not conform to the expected stereotypes based on their demographic background. This suggests that people may hold certain expectations of others during their social interaction, which can lead to a fixed opinion and stereotypes of a certain group of people, in this case, how Chinese students are viewed. The meaning and impact of language choices of all involved in an interaction depend on the specific communicative context, stressing the impact of language use in shaping and expressing identities. Chinese international students may find themselves struggling with language usage and stereotypes; they may feel afraid of using the wrong words that can make others feel offensive and impolite, and they certainly can be very sensitive about their identities as Chinese. With the fear of being impolite or lack of confidence, even ‘losing face’, the development of their language skills may be restricted. This may be the situation for Chinese international students interviewed for this research, in which the interlocutors’ reactions and responses are vital to their understanding and communication; as long as they feel it is a positive and relaxed environment, they may be more willing to try to develop the conversation instead of focussing on perfect English grammar or choosing their words carefully. Therefore,

researchers such as myself should focus more on “local and constructed—rather than expressed—aspects of identity” (Blackledge and Pavlenko, 2001, p.244). In other words, this emphasizes the importance of considering the social and cultural contexts that may shape individuals’ identities, as identity is not fixed or predetermined but is actively created and negotiated by individuals through their interactions with others. Instead of simply observing how individuals present themselves externally, researchers should explore the meanings and interpretations behind these expressions and consider the broader social and cultural influences that may shape individuals’ identities. In this study, by focusing on the local and constructed aspects of identity, I, as the researcher can gain a deeper understanding of the complexities of identity dynamics and how Chinese international students participate in shaping identities within the social and academic context.

Chambers (1995) argues that “people are taken to express— rather than negotiate— identities” (p.244). which emphasises that people tend to speak in ways that align with societal expectations based on their class, sex, age, and region (pp.100 –101). In other words, language is seen as a means of expressing one’s identity rather than actively negotiating their identity. This may explain certain behaviours of Chinese international students in classroom discussions. For example, some Chinese international students tend to keep quiet and silent when they sense that their ideas and thoughts are different from others, so that they may avoid conflicts and arguments by simply not talking, as the Chinese social convention focuses on harmony. This can also be seen as a way of ‘saving each other’s face’.

As Blackledge and Pavlenko (2001) argue:

Eight identity domains are seen as crucial for everyday interactions, including cultural, ethnic, gender, personal, role, relational, facework, and symbolic interaction identities. It is posited that individuals experience identity, security and emotional safety in a culturally familiar environment. In contrast, in a culturally unfamiliar environment, individuals may experience identity vulnerability or insecurity because of a perceived threat or fear. Satisfactory identity negotiation outcomes in conversational interaction include the feelings of being understood, valued, supported, and respected, despite the intercultural differences that may surface in the process (p.244).

The role of cultural awareness in providing individuals with a sense of identity, security, and emotional well-being may also explain why some Chinese international students tend to stay together with other Chinese students instead of attempting to make friends with other non-Chinese international students. This further suggests that in a culturally unfamiliar environment, Chinese international students may encounter potential challenges, not only related to language but also to “face” related challenges. Understanding, support, and respect are thus essential to enable Chinese international students to negotiate such potential challenges around identity successfully, despite any intercultural differences and lack of understanding that may emerge.

Blackledge and Pavlenko (2001) further discuss the “hidden symbolic power” “which underpins an ideological drive towards homogeneity, a drive which potentially marginalizes or excludes those who either refuse or are unwilling, to conform” (p.248). This may refer to the unspoken tensions which exist when Chinese students use language, in which they may be

perceived by others as being unwilling to speak or conform. Their research also reveals that in multilingual settings, both groups and individuals adjust their identities in reaction to dominant language ideologies that promote uniformity. These highlight various examples in different countries where language plays a critical role in access to identity, and self-expression. Moreover, language is more than a tool for communication; it intertwines with issues of identity, societal integration and indeed power. In other words, this “hidden symbolic power” (Blackledge and Pavlenko, 2001) refers to the subtle but effective power woven throughout the whole society. It is normally implicit but exists in cultural norms and language, and it may not be very obvious, but it shapes people’s perceptions, and behaviours in significant ways, just as the “unspoken rules” of ‘face’ culture affect Chinese people. This can create barriers in language use, especially for those who face challenges in language development, who may find it even harder to use or speak a language, which can be the case for Chinese international students who struggle with the coexistence of multiple identities as English speakers and Chinese students just like myself, as the researcher. Holding the joint identity of an English learner and a Chinese international student can make me, for example, feel very emotional, struggling and pleased at the same time when I am in different contexts. For example, I felt accepted and acknowledged by local people when I received compliments about my language proficiency, however, I also felt sensitive and offended as people assumed my English was bad just because I am Chinese. My shifting identity can make me feel that I struggle, as I try to fit into a completely new environment as a Chinese international student in the UK and “identity only becomes an issue when a person’s sense of belonging is disrupted (Preece, 2016)”. This is echoed by Bauman’s (2004) classic sociological text, in which Bauman tells his migration story and suggests that he always felt (or was made to feel by others) ‘out of place’ (Preece, 2016), which allows him to establish ‘new’ identity from the ‘old’, which is in fact, what we Chinese international students are experiencing when we move from one context to another: we develop our identities.

Blackledge and Pavlenko (2001) claim that “identities are understood as the interplay between reflective positioning, that is self-representation, and interactive positioning, whereby others attempt to reposition particular individuals or groups” (p.249). Thus, individuals have the desire to shape and express their identities in a variety of ways. Reflective positioning acknowledges the power of self-representation, enabling individuals to claim their identity in a way that aligns with their own experiences, values, and understanding, which underlines the fluid and multifaceted nature of identity. Individuals may navigate and construct their identities based on personal experiences, cultural influences, and more importantly, their self-awareness which involves adaptation, resistance, and potential conflicts. The concept of interactive positioning underscores the role of external forces, especially for Chinese international students in the UK, who may face challenges such as different societal norms, and cultural expectations. They may also need to face situations in which others may attempt to reposition them as individuals based on their perceptions or stereotypes related to a particular cultural group. In the meantime, maintaining the current state of their relationship with others in both social and academic contexts is a part of daily “facework”. Goffman (1967) also suggests earlier that ‘face’ can be found in interacting events, and only appears when people start evaluating these events, which means that the notion of the ‘face’ will only appear when people may fear ‘losing face’

during the interactions or they desire to gain ‘face’ from others. In other words, ‘face’ is often neglected by people until they realize they have a need for ‘face’, such as seeking others’ approval in social interactions. These interactions, which include the need to evaluate others or be evaluated, can be a deterministic characteristic of ‘face’ (Lim, 1994). In other words, ‘face’ exists in social interactions and the actions of pursuing ‘face’, ‘gaining face’ from others or avoiding ‘losing face’ are the key features of ‘face’. As Lim (1994) continues to explain:

Face is not what one thinks of oneself, but what one thinks others should think of one’s worth. Since the claim of the face is about one’s image held by others, one cannot claim face unilaterally without regard to the other’s perspective. The face claim is the claim that the other should acknowledge, whether explicitly or implicitly, that one possesses the claimed virtues (p.210) (cited in Spencer-Oatey, 2007, p.7).

This suggests that ‘face’ refers to one’s social status, reputation, and dignity; it is not something that individuals can claim for themselves, but rather, it is a reflection of how others perceive them. In addition, Lim (1994) claims that one has ‘face’ is based on the idea that others should acknowledge one’s positive qualities or virtues, such as honesty, or success. In other words, ‘face’ requires consideration of others’ perspectives which is not enough for an individual to believe they possess certain virtues; these qualities must also be recognized and valued by others. In the context of Chinese students in the UK, the cultural transition of living and studying from China to the UK may make it even more difficult for them to adjust to a new environment, not to mention trying to fit into a very new and different culture where they do not understand the unspoken rules of conversation, and where the expectations about ‘face’, ‘giving face’ and ‘losing face’ are not embedded in the UK culture. Therefore, they may need to navigate their identity and their use of language within specific face-related contexts in the UK.

Imahori and Cupach (2005) claim that “it is this intrinsic social factor that distinguishes ‘face’ from identity” (p.196). Richards & Schmidt (2013) argue that identity is “a person’s sense of themselves as a discrete, separate individual, including their self-image and their awareness of self, and an important concept in sociocultural theory.” In other words, identity is treated as an individual phenomenon, while ‘face’ is treated as a relational phenomenon, as the notion of ‘face’, especially in China is related to social interaction. Moreover, people’s views about themselves both as a person or an individual and in relation to other people are highly dependent on their own sense of identity (Richards & Schmidt, 2013). On one hand, people may develop relatively stable and persistent cognitive representations of who they are. On the other hand, they also construct and negotiate their identity through social interaction (Spencer-Oatey, 2007). Thus, when Chinese students attend any social events or indeed are in the classroom, they may, expect people to understand their behaviours as well as their attempts at speaking the target language.

Similarly, Arundale (2005) argues that ‘face’ is not equal to identity, but that both relationships and identity arise, and are maintained and changed, through communication. Arundale (2005) further notices that “however, a relationship, and hence ‘face’, is a dyadic phenomenon, while identity is an individual (and much broader) phenomenon” (Arundale, 2005). In other words,

'face' is related to interactions and can be divided into 'negative face' and 'positive face', however, identity embraces much more than that and focuses on individuals themselves. A few years later, however, Arundale (2010) claimed the two notions are very different and are not comparable. "Face is co-constituted in interaction; it is a non-summative phenomenon, whereas identity is a summative individual phenomenon" (Arundale, 2013, p.110). In other words, 'face' is located in interactions and relationships while identity is considered to be an individual phenomenon; this is discussed below as Spencer-Oatey (2007) believes that both involve a set of attributes and 'face' is treated as a social phenomenon and based on interactions. The concept of 'face' emphasises the value of interpersonal relationships and how others can affect how we see ourselves. 'Face' is treated by Arundale (2005) as a social phenomenon, because it needs that interactive communication for the notion of 'face' to be developed and understood. However, some people in the UK may not understand the notion of 'face', so they only see just one side of individual identity which is the gap between 'face' and identity. Indeed, Bedford (2004) argues, "as with Western shame, the central issue of Chinese shame is identity" (p.22), but it is much more pronounced among Chinese people, and therefore, Western academics may have difficulty in understanding Chinese students properly which may have an impact on Chinese students' experiences of studying and living in the UK.

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, President Xi of China claimed that the challenges faced by countries like the US and other Western nations include high COVID-19 infection rates, racial tensions and various other related issues, while Chinese people should be proud in their nation's culture, political system, and most significantly, its global power(Xue, 2023). Moreover, with the development of China's material power, President Xi claimed that Chinese people demand that their country demonstrate a qualified image of great power in the international community because it can provide a heightened level of face(Xue, 2023). In other words, Chinese people had confidence in the Chinese government's policies during the pandemic and their attitudes towards Chinese development in a global community are positive. They even have a sense of 'gaining face' globally from the developing status of China.

This phenomenon can also be observed in a classroom context in the UK: Chinese international students have a desire to uphold and enhance their reputation and social standing, as their behaviour is also related to the 'face' of China and notions of collective responsibility (Wu, 2009). This may also explain why Chinese international students tend to keep quiet in classroom discussions because their language proficiency may lead them to lose their face and indeed China's face. This may also serve as a powerful motivator for Chinese international students' classroom involvement, as Wu (2009) argues that active participation in classroom learning, beyond merely passive engagement, is intricately linked to the concept of face among Chinese students. Seeking to gain face, students may be encouraged to contribute actively to discussions, share insights, and demonstrate their knowledge and competence. Their drive to maintain a positive image within the academic context can also be seen as a way of improving their face and China's face.

3.9.1 Face and social attributes

The second aspect of 'face' discussed by Goffman (1967) is the concept of social attributes. Spencer-Oatey (2007) believes that "people only make 'face' claims concerning positively valued social attributes" (p.643). He believes that 'face' and identity are very different, as the identity attributes of a person involve negative, positive, and neutral factors, while the 'face' attributes only involve positive characteristics, and 'losing face' comes from other people's perceptions (Kennedy, 2002; Hwang, 1987, Chang and Holt, 1994) which is negative. The statement suggests that 'face' and identity are different concepts and operate in distinct ways. Identity attributes refer to the different aspects of a person's social identity that can be positive, negative, or neutral, such as personality traits, abilities, beliefs, and values. These attributes are inherent to the person and do not depend on others' perceptions or evaluations. On the other hand, 'face' attributes are the positive characteristics that a person wants to maintain or enhance in their social interactions. These attributes are mostly based on others' perceptions and evaluations of the person's behaviour, status, and reputation. It will result in 'losing face' when these attributes are negatively impacted by others' perceptions, evaluations, or judgments of the person's behaviours or actions. Therefore, 'face' and identity differ in that 'face' attributes are based on external evaluations, while identity attributes are inherent to the person. The former focuses only on positive characteristics, while the latter includes both positive, negative, and neutral factors.

Although previously Arundale (2005), Imahori, and Cupach (2005) argue that 'face' and identity are completely different, in fact, some theorists think they are related. According to Goffman (1967), 'face' is a self-image and an accepted social attribute. In this respect, Goffman's concept of 'face' is very similar to the psychological concept of identity as they both involve a set of attributes (Spencer-Oatey, 2007). Locher (2008) also argues that similarly to 'face', identity can be regarded as a relational concept which is relational and negotiable. "Face-work, relational work, identity work, and rapport management have the same referent: the negotiation of relations and identities in interaction" (Locher, 2008, p.533). Spencer-Oatey (2007) concludes that from a cognitive perspective, 'face' and identity are similar because both are related to the concept of self-image which includes individual, relational, and collective self-construction, and both contain multiple self-aspects or attributes.

In the context of Chinese students in the UK, they may choose to avoid social interactions in order to 'save face' as they may be afraid of making mistakes while speaking English. Some Chinese students may choose to interact with local or other international students when they feel confident about their spoken English so that they can gain 'face' for themselves and even for their Chinese classmates, as it is a way for them to show that Chinese students can speak English fluently (Liu, 2002). Thus, it is important to have an understanding of the relationship between identity and language.

Blackledge and Pavlenko (2001) further argue that "languages are not permanent"; rather the idea of a permanent or fixed language may emerge and evolve through the imagining of the nation-state (p.252). This suggests that nationalism does not simply arise from language; instead, nationalism itself fosters the perception of distinct languages, or rather, nationalist

ideology shapes the belief in language distinctions (Billig, 1995). In other words, languages are not fixed but can even be products of nationalist ideology, which can be a challenge to the traditional views on the relationship between language and nationalism. It suggests that the concept of distinct languages may be more a result of political and cultural motivations than a natural and inherent characteristic. This viewpoint emphasises the role of social, cultural, and political factors in shaping linguistic identity. For Chinese international students in the UK, their learning process as English learners and speakers can also be seen as a process of finding and reforming their identity, the conflicts of a new culture with Chinese culture, and language challenges which may hinder the development of both their language and related personal growth.

Forbes and Rutgers (2021) argue further that language is how we recognize ourselves and others. “Yet, we live in an increasingly multilingual world where many individuals have multiple languages in their repertoire” (p.399). The role of language can be seen as a foundational element of human identity and affects interpersonal interaction. It not only enables us to express ideas and thoughts but also reflects how we perceive and are perceived by others. There has been a shift from considering language as a distinct marker of ethnic, cultural, or national identities for specific groups, to recognizing language as part of a broader range of linguistic and other multimodal resources used for communication and identity formation (Rymes, 2010). Through language, we can express our thoughts, emotions, and experiences, shaping our identities. Moreover, the language we use can also reflect our social background, values, and beliefs, influencing how others perceive and understand us. Chinese international students in the UK, speak both Chinese and English or even more languages; they may be aware of the fluid nature of languages, therefore, they may choose their languages and expressions more carefully, as languages can represent not only their thoughts but also their identities as Chinese English speakers. Moreover, with the ‘face’ culture deeply rooted in their experience, they may choose to cater to and satisfy others’ needs and hardly express their true thoughts in order to avoid damaging their public image or indeed to save ‘face’; this particular behaviour can have an impact on their developing identity.

During language learning, students may have challenges dealing with the complex relationship of language-related tensions intertwined with their existing and developing social identities. These tensions as discussed above come from the conflict of different cultural or educational backgrounds, different societal expectations, and personal motivations. Negotiating these tensions becomes vital and cannot be ignored, as it can impact the development of their language and proficiency. This struggle can lead to feelings of a lack of belonging, or self-doubt. Additionally, others’ perceptions or expectations of their language use may also influence students’ self-confidence and lead to a ‘losing face’ situation. Zotzmann and O’Regan pointed out (2016):

The concept [of identity] sensitises us to think about the reasons for and the conditions under which people use language, the way they are perceived by others as users of language, the meanings they want to convey in particular situations and the resources they draw upon in order to do so (p.113).

For instance, Chinese international students often struggle with their language levels or proficiency, and accents. Especially when Chinese international students first come to the UK, they may find, for example, the accents in Scotland can be very strong and difficult to understand, which may make them question their language proficiency and lose confidence when they cannot understand the local people and their accents; also, they may feel their own accents cannot be understood by the locals. This is how language plays a role in Chinese international students' identity as English learners and speakers which is in line with Norton's (2013) argument:

It is through language that a person negotiates a sense of self within and across different sites at different points in time, and it is through language that a person gains access to – or is denied access to – powerful social networks that give learners the opportunity to speak. Thus, language is not conceived of as a neutral medium of communication but is understood with reference to its social meaning (p.45).

Consistently balancing different expectations can potentially cause internal identity conflict and affect students' motivation and confidence to continue learning new or multiple languages. Furthermore, Chinese students at the same time may navigate conflicting expectations from their families, peers, teachers, and even educational institutions, which is additional pressure on their identities as language learners in the UK.

The concept of identity, especially in the context of language and multilingualism, has been viewed as multiple, fluid, and situated (Miller and Kubota, 2013), which suggests that individuals possess complex and dynamic identities that can be influenced by various social and cultural even educational factors. This suggests that as individuals navigate different linguistic contexts, they also navigate different facets of their identity. This interaction is influenced by both past experiences and present circumstances of the language learners.

Norton (2013) claimed that identity refers to 'how a person understands his or her relationship to the world, how that relationship is constructed across time and space, and how the person understands possibilities for the future' (p.45). The past experiences with language, culture, and environment shape the individual's current linguistic repertoire and self-perception, while the present linguistic interactions further shape and refine this identity. The past informs the present, which, in turn, influences the future linguistic and cultural paths of the learners. In the context of participants in this study, Chinese students have been learning English in China for over 10 years, and while they may not have much pragmatic experience until they come to the UK and use it in an authentic language environment, they are required to embrace new languages and cultural influences in the UK, thus continuously renegotiating and reconstructing their identities over time. This is in line with the work of Preece (2016), which suggests that such identities are constrained, constructed, constituted, negotiated, accomplished and/or performed through the types of social spaces and relations (or discursive spaces in which language learners inhabit) (p.3).

Usually, our self-image or identity is reflected in people we are close to, for example, our classmates, colleagues, friends and families. But when we come to a very new and different environment or social context where no one understands the issue of 'face', it may be very

difficult to have valuable and truthful relationships in or out of the classroom. Spencer-Oatey (2007) also argues as follows:

However, face is only associated with attributes that are affectively sensitive to the claimant. It is associated with positively evaluated attributes that the claimant wants others to acknowledge (explicitly or implicitly), and with negatively evaluated attributes that the claimant wants others not to ascribe to him/her (p.644).

In other words, 'face' is closely tied to the emotional response of the individual claiming it, which means that 'face' is not just about having certain positive qualities or virtues, but also about how others value and perceive those qualities. Furthermore, 'face' is associated with positive and negative attributes, and 'face' can be subjective and vary across cultures and social contexts. What one person values as important for 'face' may not be the same for another person or group. Therefore, the attributes associated with 'face' can be fluid and changing depending on the social environment and individuals involved, which may be the situation for Chinese international students in the UK. They may find what they value the most about 'face' is not understood by other non-Chinese people. Therefore, this research will explore and discuss Chinese international students' perceptions of 'face' culture and whether they meet any 'face' related challenges in the UK.

Ruble and Zhang's (2013) study suggest that Chinese international students have a strong desire to gain a positive 'face' or social approval. This also addresses their concerns about receiving 'negative face' in the UK. Chinese students in the UK may feel inferior to non-Chinese students due to differences in language and academic background (Liu, 2016; Wang et al., 2017). They do not want to be criticised and judged or 'lose face'. Also, they do not often feel confident or positive about social interactions or even in class. This means when Chinese students are in very different contexts, 'face' may not always be positive but can be negative depending on how Chinese students perceive themselves. In other words, the impact of 'face' may influence how Chinese students perceive themselves and therefore, it may also affect their developing identity in the UK.

However, different people may have different views on 'face' attributes; that is, some Chinese people may think it is shameful to be approved by their groups. The concept of 'face' in Chinese culture can be complex because it contains multiple dimensions, including dignity, social status, group reputation, and national status, which can lead to varying understandings and reactions among different people. For example, Wang and Tian's (2022) study of 'face' culture and consumers' consumption suggests that the older generations or traditional values believe that maintaining or gaining 'face' from the group is a source of honour and respect, while younger generations view group approval as conforming to societal pressures, which means people may hold great expectations of them, and they need to work even harder to maintain their status and 'face'. Moreover, for some Chinese people, group approval may reinforce their social identity and provide a sense of belonging and security, while, for others, especially those with a strong desire for independence, group approval may harm their own identity, which can lead to a sense of shame and damage their self-worthiness. In contrast, some other Chinese people may believe that being recognized by their group is 'gaining face'. For example, some Chinese students

may feel those students who interact with teachers and express their ideas and interrupt teachers are disrespectful and do not give teachers 'face' (Zhang & Xu, 2007). Chinese students may feel that they are 'gaining face' if they are considered very smart by teachers and peers (Spencer-Oatey, 2007), which can be a problem faced by many Chinese students in the UK. Chinese students may think of themselves as valued by their peers; a 'positive face' may help Chinese students feel more self-confident. However, the culture of 'face' in some areas of education in the UK appears to be the opposite. If a teenager in a UK high school seems to be too clever, then they may not be valued highly by peers (Spencer-Oatey, 2007), which is how 'face' can cause difficulties, anxieties, and stress for Chinese students and it may make them feel it is a challenge to study and live in the UK. This raises another aspect of 'face' which appears to agree with Goffman's (1967) research, that 'face' is vulnerable, hence it is related to emotional reactions and affective sensitivity. As Goffman (1967) points out:

If the encounter sustains an image of him that he has long taken for granted, he probably will have few feelings about the matter. If events establish a face for him that is better than he might have expected, he is likely to 'feel good'; if his ordinary expectations are not fulfilled, one expects that he will 'feel bad' or 'feel hurt'(p.6).

This suggests that if one's social status or reputation has been enhanced, one may feel validated by the positive evaluation of their value and one is likely to feel positive emotions, such as satisfaction or pride. If the individual's face does not meet their expectations or appears more negative than what they had hoped for, they are likely to feel negative emotions, such as disappointment or embarrassment. This is because their social status or reputation has been diminished, and they may feel that their value has not been acknowledged or valued. Overall, the emotional response to changes in 'face' is closely tied to the individual's self-perception, expectations, cultural background, personality, and the specific social context in which the encounter takes place.

Krashen's (1981) Affective Filter hypothesis argues anxiety, self-confidence, motivation, and learners stress can impact the acquisition of language; similarly, MacIntyre and Gregersen (2012) also suggest that students who have more negative emotions are more likely to limit their language development. In other words, if Chinese students have more negative emotions while living in the UK, their development of authentic English learning and studying may be negative.

The notion of affective sensitivity raises another distinction between 'face' and identity. Although people evaluate identity attributes as positive, negative, and neutral, people are not necessarily sensitive about them (Spencer-Oatey, 2007), particularly UK lecturers and students who may not be as sensitive to these as Chinese students are. According to De Vita (2000), Chinese students always are viewed by lecturers from the UK as quiet and do not often welcome student-centred learning or feel comfortable with multicultural participation activities (De Vita, 2000), which may explain where those stereotypes come from and why Chinese students seem to be passive learners; and it may also be because lecturers from the UK may not be aware of 'face' culture.

Spencer-Oatey (2007) clarifies that ‘face’ is closely related to the self-construal of a person, “self as an individual or individual identity, self as a group member (group or collective identity) and self in relationship with others (relational identity)” (Spencer-Oatey, 2008, p.14). This means that Chinese students may understand their place very clearly as individuals and in a group, but lecturers and other students may not understand this. This may lead to misunderstandings which may impact Chinese students’ experiences of studying in the UK. Students studying in the UK can be very different in terms of background and culture. Face-to-face and cooperative learning-based teaching methods may conflict with not only the experience but also the values of Asian students (Phuong-Mai, Terlouw, Pilot and Elliott, 2009, p.858). Thus, Chinese students may need to adjust their learning and communication styles to adapt to the UK learning style (Holmes, 2004). There is no doubt that this adjustment combined with the traditional cultural values of China can be a great challenge for Chinese international students. Nevertheless, Goffman’s (1967) initial conceptualization of ‘face’ also involves both ‘face’ and identity, which implies that ‘face’ and identity are closely connected. In other words, to learn more about ‘face’ culture, the influence of identity needs to be considered, especially how Chinese students identify themselves as English learners and speakers in the UK, which is also the focus of this study.

3.9.2 Identity and English learning

Before exploring how Chinese international students identify themselves as English learners and speakers in the UK. It will be helpful to have a basic understanding of the status of English in China and the ways in which this may affect Chinese learners’ identity.

According to Wang, McConachy and Ushioda (2021), English is assigned practical and functional significance in both social and individual discussions in China. This emphasizes the unique role of English in foreign language education within China. English has become the dominant foreign language learned and used across various contexts in China, as supported by research (Gil and Adamson, 2011). Moreover, scholars such as Lam and Wang (2008), O’Sullivan (2016), and Pan (2011) have also underlined the influential and practical value attributed to English in both societal context and individual development. No doubt the high status of English can affect Chinese international students’ identity as English learners and users in the UK. First, a student’s English proficiency becomes a central aspect of Chinese international students’ identity while studying in the UK. Their ability to communicate effectively in English may influence their sense of belonging within both the academic and social contexts of the UK, which can also become a hindrance or challenge for them, due to the impact of ‘face’ culture as discussed in this study. Secondly, living and studying the English language and Western culture in the UK may lead to shifts and development in the cultural identity of Chinese international students. They may be required to navigate between their Chinese culture and the cultural norms and practices they encounter in the UK, leading to a complex and evolving sense of cultural identity. Moreover, language proficiency and cultural adaptation can affect how Chinese international students perceive themselves and are perceived by others within the UK society. Their ability to interact confidently in English and engage

with local communities may shape their social identity. Furthermore, Chinese international students often navigate between multiple cultural and linguistic contexts especially in a multilingual classroom, leading to the development of a transnational identity. They may maintain connections with their home country while simultaneously adapting to the cultural and linguistic norms of the UK, resulting in a mixed identity that reflects their personal experiences.

While there is a growing interest in studying language acquisition within the Chinese context, current research has highlighted the impact of contextual social factors (Wang and Zheng, 2019). There is a lack of comprehensive research on simultaneous multilingual learning in China, necessitating a more thorough and targeted investigation (Wang, McConachy and Ushioda, 2021). The emerging interest in researching language learning within the Chinese context highlights the increasing recognition of China's significance and status in both economic and cultural contexts.

Moreover, the rapidly changing of China along with globalization and technological advancements impacts even more of the language learning dynamics. For instance, the increasing use of Internet resources may influence how Chinese language learners engage with different languages and cultures, both inside and outside of China, especially for Chinese international students in the UK, who have access to more information that they may not have been able to before, and this can affect how they perceive the world and themselves.

Oshima and Harvey's (2017) work shows that during the transition to tertiary education, the way language learners view language learning and its personal relevance can significantly influence their motivation for learning. This stresses that there can be many reasons that affect language learning outcomes not just 'face' culture; for instance, the importance of learner attitudes, perceptions, motivations and personal experiences. Understanding how learners perceive language learning and its connection to their identities can provide valuable insights for educators and teachers/lecturers.

Oshima and Harvey (2017) argue that starting university can be challenging for students, particularly for those who move to a completely new environment, because the shifts in their social and educational surroundings may present challenges to their perception of both their present and future selves (Mercer 2011). Students viewed university as a preliminary phase for their future. However, once they commenced their studies, conflicting discourses regarding the purpose of language learning emerged in their consciousness, causing identity tensions as they tried to merge these conflicts (Wang, McConachy and Ushioda, 2021). This may be particularly challenging for Chinese students as they cross cultures.

Wang, McConachy and Ushioda (2021) argue that during multilingual learning, students encounter language-related tensions tied to various social identities and negotiating these tensions impacts the evolution of their motivation, they further suggest in their research:

After commencing study in Shanghai, the students from provincial areas became acutely aware that they had been relatively disadvantaged in terms of access to resources for learning foreign languages compared to their Shanghainese peers. This brought about identity tensions for them as they sought to adjust to university life in

Shanghai and integrate with local students. When asked if she was satisfied with her English proficiency at the beginning of her university life, QQ said that her level of English was not sufficient in Shanghai (p.424).

This suggests that multilingual learning has the potential to bring about identity tensions for learners, that learners need to balance between their identities as Chinese nationals and as second language learners, and that their identity as non-local FL learners in metropolitan cities like Beijing and Shanghai. Preece (2016) claimed that identity has become significantly more complex due to the mobility and diversity arising in both physical and digital social realms as a consequence of globalization in late modernity, and this change in thinking about identity is often discussed in terms of ‘essentialism’ and ‘non-essentialism’ (p.3) which will be discussed later in this section. This is exactly what Chinese international students in the UK experience, in attempting to deal with the tensions between two different cultures and even the shock of different education systems. All the challenges can cause potential tensions in their identity shifting and shaping, as Bucholtz (2003) points out:

The attributes and behaviour of socially defined groups can be determined and explained by reference to cultural and/or biological characteristics believed to be inherent to the group. As an ideology, essentialism rests on two assumptions: (1) that groups can be clearly delimited; and (2) that group members are more or less alike (also cited in Preece, 2016, p.3).

This suggests that the term “essentialism” can be explained as people in certain groups have certain qualities and their acts or behaviours have arisen from their culture. In this study, Chinese international students can be seen by others as the ‘group’, which may lead to certain stereotypes. Other non-Chinese people may assume they are all alike, for example, assuming that Chinese international students’ language proficiency is low, or they are all passive learners. In contrast, Hall’s (1996) definition of identities is:

About questions of using the resources of history, language and culture in the process of becoming rather than being: not ‘who we are’ or ‘where we came from’, so much as what we might become, how we have been represented and how that bears on how we might represent ourselves (cited in Preece, 2016, p3), and that is how non-essentialism viewed identity (p.4).

This emphasises the growth, potential, and critical evaluation of representations in shaping our identity. It focuses on considering the transformative power of history, language, and culture in developing our identities and more importantly, shaping our future selves. Indeed, a new environment like the UK can bring challenges but also opportunities for Chinese international students. It depends on the angle from which people view identity. These are the potential challenges and opportunities discussed above that Chinese international students may encounter in the UK, and this research will discuss the challenges along with the opportunities that may affect Chinese international students’ developing identity as English learners and speakers.

According to Wang, McConachy and Ushioda (2021), Chinese students felt a social obligation to study foreign languages and secure a promising career or pursue higher education. This influential motivation is deeply rooted in students' minds and heavily influenced by Confucian ethics, where societal success symbolically reflects on one's family and broader relational networks. "The learners' significant others work as mediators between their individual values and attitudes and the macro social discourses" (Wang, McConachy and Ushioda, 2021, p.10). Indeed, the concept of 'face' culture is deeply rooted in Confucian ethics which may influence students' attitudes towards foreign language learning. In contexts where 'face' culture exists, such as China, there is a strong emphasis on one's social roles and responsibilities, particularly regarding education and career success. For instance, students perceive foreign language learning as not just personal but also as a societal expectation tied to their social role or identity as students and children of their parents which are central principles of 'face' culture. Moreover, success in society serves not only as an individual achievement but is also related to one's familial honour and 'face', which raises the pressure on students and their language learning and can increase the tensions between language learning and students' developing identity. The role of others, such as family members and teachers become essential, as constructive feedback on their achievement can encourage students to keep learning, while unconstructive feedback may bring stress and make students question themselves and even impact their learning results. The influence of 'face' culture underlines the complex relationship between cultural norms and social expectations in shaping students' attitudes, motivations, and behaviours towards language learning.

In conclusion, Block's (2006) definition of identity emphasizes the relationship between an individual's sense of self and their language use within specific social contexts, which highlights the nature of multilingual identity and emphasises individuals' understanding and perception of how their linguistic choices shape, construct and negotiate their identities and especially their interactions with others. Furthermore, individuals' identities are not fixed but evolve as they encounter new experiences, come to new environments and engage with different linguistic communities. The participants in this study, Chinese international students come to a completely new language environment in the UK, in which it is very likely that they will encounter those challenges but also opportunities and 'China English' may be one of them. Their learning experience or process highlights the nature of how identity is formatted and the ongoing process of identity negotiation. Therefore, it will be interesting to investigate how language acquisition and identity are intertwined, and the important role of 'face' culture in this process.

3.10 Face and China English

In the 19th century, as the term 'China English'(CE) was becoming well-known all over the world, English was no longer just a communication tool but also represented Chinese culture and customs (Chen & Hu, 2006). 'China English' is different from 'Chinese English'. The term 'Chinese English', also referred to as Chinglish, is listed in the book "International English Usage" authored by British scholar Todd and American scholar Hancock (1986) who

expound on Chinese English relating to the aspects of phonology, lexicon, and grammar (Hancock and Todd, 2005). The definition of 'China English' is quoted by Kirkpatrick and Xu (2002):

China English is based on standard English, expresses Chinese culture, and has Chinese characteristics in lexis, sentence structure, and discourse but does not show any L1 interference (p.269).

The term 'China English' (CE) was proposed by Chinese linguist Ge (1980). Later, Wang (1991) defines CE as having the core of standard English but with Chinese characteristics, which has some unique features used by Chinese English speakers. Since some Chinese expressions and phrases with unique features are very difficult to translate accurately into English, normally these words in CE are directly transliterated from Mandarin or Cantonese, "these words within Chinese regional culture, do not belong to the Western people, and they also never use them (Ge, 1980)." Chinese students may find it difficult to translate their Chinese ideas into English during social interactions and class. This particularly may be the case for Chinese international students in the UK, where they may find their ideas difficult to express in English in social interactions and class, or their translation may not be accurate. In that case, the impact of 'face' may affect how Chinese students use English or even speak English, which is also one of the reasons for the aim of this study, to find out whether the impact of 'face' may affect Chinese students' life and study as English learners and speakers in the UK.

Some researchers argue that 'China English' can be used as a functional tool. Grzega (2005) brings up the concept of 'bridge language' to assist learners' acquisition of English, which means before learners fully acquire the target language, there will be a phase where learners tend to use their first language to help them express their ideas. However, Bolton (2003) argues that English in China has developed from a tool for communication to a variety of forms, "it also bears symbolic weight conveying Chinese identities with Chinese features and cultures" (Du, 2009, p.43).

Jiang, Yang, and Zhou's (2017) research show that Chinese international students prefer to speak English quietly when they make formal public speeches in the classroom whether individually or in group work, so that their non-standard accented or pronunciations may not be noticed by other students. Jiang, Yang and Zhou (2017) note that some Chinese students feel embarrassed about their Chinese accent, and they are concerned about not being understood, or not conveying correct meanings. Thus, some Chinese students may find it difficult to express themselves when they speak which may lead to a vicious circle of low self-esteem, as they may use the wrong expression and cause misunderstandings and they may feel bad about this. In other words, Chinese students may feel they 'lose face' when they do not receive 'positive face' in a social context or even in class, because of their accent and expressions, even their CE. Thus, in this study, the researcher also wants to find out if CE will affect Chinese international students' identity while studying and living in the UK.

Moreover, students perceive the English language as a part of something bigger; for example, English as a language may also represent the culture and history of a country, such as the UK and the US. Wang (2015) argues that those Chinese students who prioritise communication and

express their cultural identity, rather than having to follow strict standards of expected communication behaviours were more accepting of CE accents. This acceptance extended even to those who didn't meet the unspoken standards of native English speakers in terms of speaking. This means that Chinese students may be willing to accept CE, if it effectively serves the purpose of communication, despite the potential possibility of an individual who uses CE 'losing face'. Thus, this study aims to find out whether 'face' and issues around 'face' may have an impact on Chinese international students' identity while learning and living as English speakers and learners in the UK.

3.10.1 Chinese students' perceptions of China English

In 2015, Wang conducted a study on the attitudes towards CE among university students and English teachers in different areas of China. The study involved sending out questionnaires to 1589 university students, which included 785 males, 802 females, and 2 unspecified genders. Additionally, 193 university English teachers also participated in the study. From the total of 1782 participants (which included both students and teachers from different universities), 31 students (15 males and 16 females) and 33 teachers (7 males and 26 females) were selected for further questioning. They were asked to provide justifications for their attitudes towards CE. Wang's (2015) research shows that the majority of participants (exceeding 96%) had no problem understanding expressions with CE features, but only 30.8% chose to accept them. Nearly half of the participants (48.9%) regarded these features as unacceptable and another 20.3% were ambivalent towards them (p.64).

Joseph (2004) argues that some people consider CE to be "wrong" English because they identify mistakes and errors within its language, and they uphold the belief that only "standard" English is "right". It suggests that some other Chinese students believe that learners of English should learn English by using the rules of "correct" grammar instead of using CE. Wang's (2015) research also suggests that his participants were relatively accepting of CE accents; however, they were resistant to communicating with other Chinese people who use a mixture of English and China English expressions, as well as English that violated the unspoken grammar rules of native English speakers.

According to Wang (2015), Chinese students' views about CE are very complicated, and their attitudes towards CE can be ambivalent. On one hand, they wanted to use English that was familiar and relevant to their local context. On the other hand, they also felt the pressure to conform to society's expectations and use English that was socially recognized as standard (Wang, 2015). This constant tension between using English with Chinese linguistic characteristics and meeting socially recognized standards constrained their choice of preferred English. Therefore, their unwillingness to accept CE accents may not have been due to a lack of understanding of the value of CE for informal interactions. Instead, it could be because the major perceptions towards CE in Chinese society have been very strong, and the use of CE may lead to a 'loss of face' that made it challenging for them to speak English as they wished. In this research, it will be interesting to find out whether Chinese international students have

an awareness of ‘face’ and whether will they still follow the unspoken rules of ‘face’ in relation to CE spoken in class and social contexts, in the UK.

Jiang (2003) points out that CE is easier for Chinese people to understand, as it can also help Chinese students learn and expand their vocabulary. Graddol (2006) suggests the stereotype of ‘standard’ English is interrupted by CE; he suggests that CE is being accepted positively. However, the experiences of some Chinese international students may be different. Some Chinese international students may speak CE, and as it is not perceived as ‘standard English’ by their classmates, they may feel judged and ‘lose face’ when what they say is difficult for others to understand. This is linked to the aim of this study to explore whether ‘face’ has impacted Chinese students’ experiences in the UK as English learners and speakers.

3.11 Summary

In conclusion, a discussion of the literature which underpins this study focusing on ‘face’ has highlighted a gap in the literature in relation to ‘face’ culture and the impact of ‘face’ on Chinese international students in the UK that this research can fill, specifically in relation to face, identity, the place of gender therein, and culture. In other words, there is a need for this research into the area of ‘face’ and “face threat” and how these affect Chinese international students’ identity as English learners and speakers while they are living and studying in the UK. This analysis of the literature has helped the researcher in choosing the theoretical framework that supports this study.

3.12 Theoretical Framework

This section sets out the theoretical framework of this study. The definition of a theoretical framework is “the structure that can hold or support a theory of a research study. The theoretical framework introduces and describes the theory that explains why the research problem under study exists” (Abend, 2008, p.173-199). In other words, the theoretical framework is a theory or concept which defines and underpins and informs the thesis. I selected Goffman’s (1967) concept of ‘face’ theory to underpin the impact of ‘face’ culture on Chinese international students’ developing identity as learners and speakers of English. However, as this research specifically focuses on the impact of Chinese ‘face’ culture on Chinese international students, Mao’s (1994) concept of Chinese ‘face’ will also be introduced and discussed as an extension of Goffman’s (1967) concept of ‘face’ which is particularly focused on Chinese ‘face’ culture. Although Brown and Levinson’s (1978, 1987) politeness model further explain the concept of ‘face’ and became a major focus in academic research (Haugh, 2009), it is not suitable as an underpinning theory for this study and the reasons for that will be discussed below.

3.12.1 Goffman’s concept of face theory

The concept of ‘face’ was first developed by Goffman (1955,1967) to explain certain social behaviours by illustrating how and why ‘face’ is lost and maintained in non-Chinese contexts, which he defined as ‘the positive social value a person effectively claims for himself by the

line others assume he has taken during a particular contact' (Goffman, 1955, p.213). In other words, 'face' is a self-image that people present to the public through their actions, words, and appearance. However, there have been criticisms and controversies by other researchers such as Gu (1990) and Mao (1994) of Goffman's definition of people's role in Chinese society and whether the 'face' issue has positive social value; that is, whether issues around 'face' are considered positive as well as negative in Chinese society. Qi (2011) questions that Goffman's claim does not fully capture this variability and the nature of 'face'. Goffman believes that the social value a person claims must be positively approved by others. This view of Goffman might be too narrow. "Positive social value" should not just be about standardized approval (whether society considers something good or bad). Instead, 'face' should be viewed as a socially shared and current evaluation that varies across different times, situations, and social groups. Goffman's interpretation does not fully address this dynamic and social dependent nature of face. His interpretation may have overlooked how social approval and value can change based on time, situation, and social group. Qi (2017) argued that Goffman's conceptualization of 'face' does not address the complex factors that determine an individual's face state or the responsibility of another person's behaviour in relation to that individual's face state. Individuals can lose face due to the behaviour of others they are associated with. Likewise, individuals can also gain face through the achievements or status of others they are connected with. However, Qi (2017) suggested that studies on face from the Western view often focus on how an individual's behaviour and how it is perceived by others determine their face state. This means face is seen by Western scholars represented by Goffman, Brown and Levinson as a direct result of one's own actions, while Chinese scholars such as Mao, and Qi believe that an individual's face is also influenced by the behaviour of people they are related to or connected with (face-related others). In China, 'face' usually is not considered to have a positive quality or any positive indication (Zhang, 2017). This will be further discussed in section 3.12.3 in detail, where Mao (1994) suggested Goffman's definition of 'face' and people's role may not be fully considered in China.

Indeed, Goffman's definition may be too static, because it does not consider that Chinese society and culture are evolving, and the concept of 'face' takes a key role in Chinese society. Younger generations in China are adopting more diverse and moderate views, influenced by global trends. Issues like gender equality and individualism are becoming more and more trending in societal discourse (Zheng, 2022). Moreover, overseas Chinese students are actively promoting their culture through cultural festivals (Times, 2023), and media. This cultural diplomacy aims to enhance China's power and improve its global image. With the changing status and repaid development of China and how China is perceived on the global stage, 'face' is gradually extending from representing honour and dignity to ensuring that China is respected and perceived as a great power by other countries (Xue, 2023) This development has led to increased interaction with other countries, influencing Chinese society and culture through the exchange of ideas, values, and practices. In other words, China's evolution as a responsible great power reflects its deeper incorporation into global society. The country's leaders and people are increasingly aware that to maintain and enhance 'face', 'face' not only refers to a person's social standing in a historical context but also evolving and representing national identity and global image. 'Face' now includes maintaining national pride and unity; externally, it also involves meeting the expectations of other nations and contributing to global stability.

Overall, China's society and culture are experiencing a dynamic transformation, balancing tradition with modernity and increasing its global influence while adopting internal social changes.

Goffman (1955) was a sociologist who largely emphasizes the interaction between individuals and the social world, and his definition of 'face' focuses on how individuals fit into society and its institutions (Thompson, 2014). Goffman's Face Theory aims to help people understand 'face': why and how people create their public images or 'face', especially during social interactions; what strategies they will use to maintain their 'face' and what they will do if their 'face' is threatened by others or indeed lost completely.

According to the pioneering research by Goffman (1955,1967), studies that focus on what people may think of us are normally classed as 'face (work)' in academic research (Haugh, 2009). In other words, Goffman's (1955) definition of 'face' emphasizes how one views one's contribution to a certain social environment or community:

Just as the member of any group is expected to have self-respect, so also, he [she] is expected to sustain a standard of considerateness; he [she] is expected to go to certain lengths to save the feelings and the 'face' of others present, and he [she] is expected to do this willingly and spontaneously because of emotional identification with the others and with their feelings (p. 215).

According to Goffman (1955), people are aware that they need to support each other's 'face' performance as they are all a part of the community: if a person does not contribute to others' 'face' protection then he cannot expect others to cooperate in protecting his own 'face'. In addition, people may feel positive about themselves if other people give them 'face', or their 'face' is saved while they may feel bad if their 'face' is threatened by other people or even lost during a spoken interaction. Some people's feelings and emotions are tightly related to their 'face', that is, they become stressed whenever their 'face' is being threatened by others. Goffman (1967) sees 'face' as an image "located in the flow of events" rather than "a private property", which involves others' judgments and is approved by "impersonal agencies in the situation" (1967, p.7). This means he believes that 'face' flows within social events and interpersonal relationships, it is given by others, and you will be judged by others as to whether you are worthy of it. 'Face' becomes a public image that individuals "borrowed" from society, and "that will be withdrawn from them if they prove unworthy of it" (1967, p.10). In other words, people's status will be removed if they do not follow the unspoken rules of 'face'. People will do 'face-work' to maintain this public image, their actions will keep "whatever they are doing consistent with 'face' (1967, p.12), and they will try to "save their own 'face' as well as others' 'face' (1967, p.14) and more importantly, not make themselves or others' 'lose face'. 'Face' is an element of the unspoken rules of social behaviour, and everything that Chinese people do in terms of 'face' is not just connected to themselves, but to the community at large.

Goffman (1967) further suggested two types of 'losing face' to describe circumstances where an individual's efforts to maintain their desired 'face' are threatened or damaged, which are to "be in the wrong face" and "be out of face" (Cupach and Metts, 2008). An example of "be in the wrong face" is when a student delivers a presentation and despite being well-prepared, the student experiences a moment of forgetting what to say due to the stress of the situation. This example suggests that someone is well-prepared and everyone, even themselves expects the

presentation to be “perfect”, but still one tiny mistake or a stressful situation can lead to a person’s ‘loss of face’ as they fail to achieve the expectations of others and themselves, or in this case, “be in the wrong face”. An example of “be out of face” is when a student is caught cheating in an exam and the whole school knows about it and it is in one of those circumstances that people do not know what to say or how to act (Cupach and Metts, 2008). In other words, when people lose their ‘face’, they will feel embarrassed or even offended, as their public image or their social status is questioned by others; they will realize that they may not be able to maintain their public image, and in order to maintain their public- image or ‘face’ people will need to do ‘face-work’.

Goffman (1955) proposed the term ‘facework’ to describe the act of ‘giving face’, and “attributes it to the Chinese notion of helping people take on the given face they desire” (Redmond, 2015, p.12). For example, in China teachers are often expected to project an image of authority, wisdom, and professionalism and to fulfil this role, a teacher needs to be confident and knowledgeable in front of their students, even if the teachers may be facing challenges or uncertainties; students meanwhile, need to show respect to their teachers. This behaviour aligns with the concept of ‘taking on the given face’ and highlights how cultural expectations may influence the way individuals present themselves in specific roles or contexts. Goffman (1955) defined the concept of ‘facework’ as “the actions taken by a person to make whatever he [she] is doing consistent with face (p. 216)” (cited in Redmond, 2015, p.12); in other words, the actions or behaviours individuals employ to align with and maintain their desired social image or reputation during social interactions. This is especially true in the context of China where people work hard to maintain the veneer of respectable communicative interactions in most circumstances, but with families, partners and really close friends, it can be very different, as individuals may be more relaxed. Goffman (1967) suggested that ‘face-work’ can be divided into two processes: the “avoidance process” (avoiding potentially ‘face-threatening’ acts) and the “corrective process” (performing a variety of redressive acts) (1967, p.15-23). The “avoidance process” means that people will act based on the unspoken rules of ‘face’ during social interactions, which will avoid ‘losing face’; for example, a Chinese student may remain quiet and silent when she/he is not confident about what she/he is going to say during a class discussion, so she/he will not make mistakes which may lead to her/him ‘losing face’. Thus, the “corrective process” means when people realize they may ‘lose face’, they will change their behaviours to ‘save face’ or ‘maintain face’. For example, when a student has made a mistake, and it was pointed out in front of their peers, they may find an excuse to justify what happened. Those two processes are later referenced by Brown and Levinson as “maintenance strategies”, and they incorporated this concept of ‘face’ into their ‘face’ model, which helped me fully explore and understand all the issues related to ‘face’ culture which may affect Chinese international students living and studying in the UK.

In summary, ‘face’ is a complex and multifaceted concept that is shaped by social interactions and the contexts in which they occur. While there may be variation in how ‘face’ is defined, the commonalities among the definitions suggest that it is a fundamental aspect of human communication and interaction (Redmond, 2015). Goffman’s (1955) ‘face’ theory serves as the foundation for the ‘face’ concept and focuses on the way individuals fit into society, which also underpins this study’s theoretical framework.

3.12.2 Brown and Levinson's politeness theory

Goffman's (1955,1967) 'face' theory did not get much attention from academic researchers at first until Brown and Levinson's (1978, 1987) influential work on politeness. The politeness theory of Brown and Levinson (1978, 1987) affects researchers who work on social interaction and communication, and it also emphasizes the importance of 'face' in social interaction (Haugh, 2009). Brown and Levinson claim that the study of 'face' has universal features that transcend cultural and ethnic boundaries. Brown and Levinson (1987) define 'face' as:

The public self-image that every member wants to claim for himself, encompassing the want to be unimpeded ('negative face': the basic claim to territories, personal preserves, rights to non-distraction) and the desire to be appreciated and approved of ('positive "face": the positive consistent self-image or 'personality') (p.61).

Brown and Levinson (1976) describe 'face' as something that we desire from others; "the want to be unimpeded and the want to be approved of in certain respects (p. 63)." Brown and Levinson (1978) claim that individuals engaging in social interactions acknowledge each other's desire to maintain their 'face' and normally offer approval of it by showing respect and honour (Redmond, 2015).

Lim and Bowers (1991) built upon the work of Brown and Levinson (1978) by proposing that 'face' not only contained two desires but rather three. They offer alternative labels for the types of 'face', which are "fellowship face", "competence face" and "autonomy face", in order to make the concept of 'face' clear and understandable (Redmond, 2015). "Fellowship face" represents the desire to be included and accepted by others. Redmond (2015) proposed an example: "If a group at work is going to lunch, you want to be invited along since this demonstrates that others accept and respect you" (p.7). "Competence face" reflects the desire to have one's abilities recognized and valued by others. Another example from Redmond (2015): "If you see yourself as a good student, you want instructors to acknowledge that, usually by giving you good praise, positive feedback on papers, and good grades" (p.7). In addition, both fellowship and competence 'face' are types of "positive face" since they represent the desire to be perceived positively by others. Redmond (2015) further argues that it is important to note that one can possess one type of face and not the other, such as being viewed as competent but not included in the group or included in the group without acknowledgement of one's abilities. According to Redmond (2015), "autonomy face" represents the desire to not be imposed upon which is a type of "negative face" that is distinct from the broader concept of "negative face". "Autonomy face" also holds the desire to maintain the current status of the conversation or a relationship; while losing a relationship or deciding not to invest in a relationship in terms of communication may provide more autonomy and thus, be viewed positively (Redmond, 2015). However, it could also represent an undesirable change that threatens one's "negative face" (Redmond, 2015), which means that people may decide not to maintain a relationship which may not 'give them face' or provide 'face' to another person. That is, it is not worth the effort. Overall, Lim and Bowers' (1991) proposal of three types of 'face' provides a more comprehensive understanding of the concept of 'face' in general, by identifying the different desires of people have to maintain in social situations.

Although 'face' has become an essential part of the study of social interaction, especially the study of politeness, the conceptualization and application of 'face' in research have always

been a controversial topic (Haugh, 2009) because two major issues have arisen about 'face' as it was proposed by Brown and Levinson. The first issue is that some people believe 'face' is based on a Western interactive perspective and therefore it is ethnocentric, which means that the approach of Brown and Levinson to 'face' is exceedingly Western individualistic (Haugh, 2009; Mao, 1994; Matsumoto, 1988), which means that people are more selfish in their interactions with other people. Haugh (2009) argues that it ignores "the rich socio-cultural milieu from which the metaphor of 'face' originally emerged" (p.2). In addition, Asian linguists represented by the Japanese linguist Matsumoto (1988) and Chinese linguist Mao (1994) argue that Brown and Levinson's (1987) model of 'face' is not suitable for Eastern cultures where an individual is considered to be less important than the social group. When Chinese international students first come to the UK, they may notice everything in this "rich socio-cultural milieu" is very different from what they have known in China in both academic and social contexts. Therefore, this study aims to find out whether 'face' culture has an impact on Chinese international students' lives and study in the UK. The second issue is that the discussion around 'face' and 'face-work' was not the main focus of Brown and Levinson's (1987) politeness theory, as it covered a much wider range of issues around politeness (Haugh, 2009; Arundale, 1999; Spencer-Oatey, 2000, 2005), which do not link specifically to the previous discussion within this thesis.

This study concentrates on the issues around 'face' and 'face-work' especially around Chinese international students, rather than politeness, which means Brown and Levinson's (1987) theory is not enough for this research to have a thorough and deep understanding of 'face'. Therefore, in order to have a better understanding of the Chinese concept of 'face' and also discover the impact of Chinese culture on Chinese international students' developing identity in the UK, it is essential to refer to and discuss the study of Chinese linguists, represented by Mao (1994) for this study.

The concept of 'face' is one of the most distinctive features of Chinese people's social behaviour in their daily life'; 'face' as an unspoken role is understood by everyone in China where it largely affects Chinese people's social behaviours with other community members in social interaction (Long and Aziz, 2022), and everyone is aware of it. Furthermore, Qi (2011) defines 'face' as "the social anchoring of self in the gaze of others" (p.280), which means people present a public image or so-called 'face' to impress others and convince other people that they are worthy social interactants. That is, 'face' reflects how people want others to perceive themselves. However, there are scholars such as Zhang, Pearce, and Chen (2019) who also consider the concept of 'face' to be different in Chinese and Western contexts.

3.12.3 Mao's conceptualization of the Chinese 'face'

I discussed Mao's concept of Chinese 'face' culture early in section 3.5.5. This is to further develop this in line with the theoretical framework.

Smith (1894) and Macgowan (1912) state that 'face' was considered an important element of Chinese culture. Domenici (2006) highlights the values of Chinese culture's original use of 'face' which reflects what they defined as the "desire to present oneself with dignity and honour (p. 10)." Therefore, in order to understand Chinese people's interactions and the concept of

'face', Mao (1994) proposes a different concept and discussion of 'face', which he claims could embrace cultural differences in the concept of 'face' – "the relative 'face' orientation":

The relative 'face' orientation may be defined as an underlying direction of "face" that emulates, though never completely attaining, one of two interactional ideals that may be salient in a given speech community: the ideal social identity, or the ideal individual autonomy (p.472).

Mao (1994) emphasizes in his argument that the concept of the Chinese 'face' (Lian or Mian Zi) does not imply the concept of 'negative face' as identified by Brown and Levinson (1987); whose discussion is solely related to the positive aspect of 'face'. Moreover, Brown and Levinson's (1987) argument does not cover the discourse behaviours in other non-Western cultures (Mao, 1994), as noted by Mao (1994). This is particularly evident in the criticism by De Kadt (1998), who further argues that Brown and Levinson's theory has incorrectly interpreted Goffman's original concept of 'face' by ignoring 'face' in the context of China, while Gu (1990) and Mao (1994) also claim that the notion of 'face' in Brown and Levinson's theory is different from the Chinese concept of 'face'. According to Gu (1990) and Mao (1994), the Chinese face consists of 'Lian' and 'Mianzi'. "Mianzi stands for prestige or reputation, which is achieved through getting on in life" (Hu, 1944, p.45; cited in Mao, 1994, p.457). In contrast, 'Lian' refers to "the respect of the group for a man with a good moral reputation"; it represents "the confidence of society in the integrity of ego's moral character", and it is "both a social sanction for enforcing moral standards and an internalized sanction" (Hu, 1944, p.45; cited in Mao, 1994, p.457). In other words, 'Lian' needs to be earned, while 'Mianzi' is given by others. However, the differences between 'Lian' and 'Mianzi' failed to be discussed or considered in Brown and Levinson's theory which means their theory cannot represent the concept of 'face' in the context of China.

According to Mao (1994), two main differences exist between the Chinese concept of 'face' and Brown and Levinson's interpretation of 'face'. The first relates to their overall conceptualization of 'face'. Brown and Levinson define 'face' as "the public self-image that every member wants to claim for himself" (1987, p.61), which means the focus of this definition is individual where 'face' represents a self-image. According to Ji (2000), 'face' is valid as a reflecting self-image, because 'face' provides the essential motivation for everyone to care about it in a community; and a successful social interaction requires people to take proper care of their self-image as well as others'. In other words, 'face' as a self-image is only effective when everyone in the community is aware of it and pays attention to it. Brown and Levinson's recognition of 'face' requires everyone in social interaction to be aware of the importance of 'face', as it motivates people to be respectful of their image and also others' self-image. In other words, for everyone to adopt Brown and Levinson's (1987) positive or negative politeness strategies in social interaction, caring about 'face' and the desire to not 'lose face' need to be the most fundamental reasons for people to have successful social interactions. However, 'face' in China is less about one's own desire to 'have face' but more about how one is viewed by other members of the community, and it emphasizes the supremacy of the community or group in the society; therefore, the importance of meaningful interactions is the priority within Chinese people's social interactions. Furthermore, Trommsdorff (2009) claims that Westerners are taught to make their own decisions by themselves, while Chinese people are brought up to accept and respect the ideas and expected behaviours of their families. Embedded in Brown and Levinson's concept of 'face' is a cultural belief that "a person is an

independent, self-reliant, and self-oriented being” (Carbaugh, 1988; Hsu, 1973; cited in Chang, 2008, p.301) who “interacts with other people as unique and self-contained individuals” (Brown and Levinson, 1978, 1987; cited in Chang, 2008, p.301). In other words, interactive communication in the Western context values individualistic ‘face’ which contains the culture of respecting independent personality, and which is in accord with Brown and Levinson’s theory. However, the Chinese concept of ‘face’ is not an individual ‘face’ or unique ‘face’, it emphasizes the relationship people share with their social network (Chang, 2008). In addition, Chang and Holt (1994) argued that the Chinese ‘face’ is deeply bonded with relations, it is shared by other members of the group or family “or by people in specific social situations” (Chang and Holt, 1994, p.101; cited in Chang, 2008, p.302). Consequently, Mao’s concept of ‘face’ explains the link between Chinese people and their social network, which also suggests that Mao’s concept of ‘face’ can better explain Chinese ‘face’ culture than Brown and Levinson’s theory.

Chinese ‘face’ culture encourages people to represent a good image when individuals communicate with others in a specific community where they can claim their reputation (Mao, 1994), and presenting a good image reflects the confidence of the society in a person; if a person presents a good image to others, it normally means he wants others in the community to consider him as a valued social interactant. This is closely related to the perspective and judgments of the community towards an individual’s behaviours; people in China will expect others to respect them if the community admits their social status which makes them feel ‘face’ is gained and honoured; otherwise, people will feel ‘loss of face’. Mao (1994) further argues that the Chinese ‘face’ emphasizes not the accommodation of individual ‘wants’ or ‘desires’ but emphasizes the harmony of individual conduct with the views and judgement of the community” (p.460). In other words, ‘face’ as a public image depends on and is determined by others in the community and affects an individual’s behaviours, actions and even words. Therefore, the notion of Chinese ‘face’ is different from the Western concept of ‘face’ in that “it is other-directed rather than self-oriented, it is communal or relational rather than individualistic” (Ho, 1976, 1994; Chang & Holt, 1994; Hwang, 1976, 2000; Jia, 1997; cited in Chang, 2008, p.303). In Chinese society, a person is not only responsible for his own ‘face’ but also for others who are closely related to him which is in accord with Mao’s concept of ‘face’, while Brown and Levinson’s theory emphasizes more on the independent individual ‘face’. Mao (1994) further argues the failure of Brown and Levinson (1987) is that they were unable to identify the original source of ‘face’ and “the impact upon their formulation of ‘face’, it has consequences for the theory’s universality” (p.454). The original Chinese concept of ‘face’ as expressed by Lian and Mianzi was not included in Brown and Levinson’s (1987) ‘face’ theory, which is not a worldwide representation: it may reflect the Western concept of ‘face’, but it certainly cannot represent Chinese concept of ‘face’.

According to Mao’s argument, the second difference between Mao’s concept of ‘face’ and Brown and Levinson’s ‘face’ is about “the content of face” (Mao, 1994, p.460), which means that “the Chinese concept of ‘face’ does not contain a component of ‘negative face’” (Ji, 2000, p.1060). According to Brown and Levinson (1987), ‘face’ consists of the ‘negative face’ and ‘positive face’, and “an individual’s ‘face’ consists of two desires” (Ji, 2000, p.1060). ‘Positive face’ means people have the desire to be approved (Ji, 2000) and admitted by others, while ‘negative face’ means people have the desire to not be impeded by others. ‘Negative face’ “refers to, and values, an individual’s need to be free of external impositions” (Mao, 1994,

p.460), however, Chinese ‘face’ (Mian Zi, Lian Mian) shows that Chinese people need public recognition to enhance their prestige or reputation. In other words, Mao’s second argument suggests that ‘MianZi’ and ‘Lian’ identify Chinese people’s need to secure public acknowledgement of their reputation which only refers to ‘positive face’ (Ji, 2000). In effect, by adjusting their behaviour to this desire of seeking others’ approval, the Chinese are surrendering to external impositions as they hardly refuse any requirements from others even if it may damage their own interests, “and thus, willingly or unwillingly, impair their ‘negative face’” (Mao, 1994, p.460). Mao (1994) further suggests that “an individual is presumed to seek the respect of the group or the community, but not to satisfy the desire for freedom”. In other words, Chinese people desire to contribute to their group or community and seek others’ approval, which resembles ‘positive face’ rather than ‘negative face’, suggesting that Mao’s concept of ‘face’ does not contain ‘negative face’. Mao’s second argument pointed out that Brown and Levinson’s (1987) ‘negative face’ does not apply to Chinese ‘face’ culture, as has been discussed above.

This study aims to explore whether ‘face’ has an impact on Chinese international students, which means the data will be collected based solely on Chinese students’ experiences and perceptions. Mao’s (1994) two arguments were discussed above which suggested the inadequacy of Brown and Levinson’s (1978,1987) politeness theory in relation to this study as it failed to explain the concept of ‘face’ in the context of China, therefore, Brown and Levinson’s ‘face’ model is unsuitable as a contribution to the Theoretical Framework for this study because it may not be able to reflect the Chinese concept of ‘face’ properly. In addition, in order to fully understand the content of ‘face’, Zhang, Cao, and Grigoriou (2011) suggest that the concept of ‘face’ should be measured by both ‘gaining face’ and ‘saving face’ (Long and Aziz, 2022), which has been discussed in the Literature Review chapter of this thesis. According to Zhang, Cao, and Grigoriou (2011), ‘gaining face’ and ‘saving face’ are different but not the opposite results of social interaction, which means during social interaction, people can ‘gain face’ if they are accepted and approved by others and it has no conflict with ‘saving face’ which refers to avoiding embarrassment or keeping others from losing respect for oneself. People may not all care about ‘gaining face’ but most people would avoid ‘losing face’ (Long and Aziz, 2022) and they will also ‘save face’ if they sense their ‘face’ is threatened (Wang, Fu, Wu, 2020); this is in accord with Mao’s concept of ‘face’: that it only contains ‘positive face’ not ‘negative face’.

In conclusion, Brown and Levinson’s (1987) concept of ‘face’ represents people who have the desire to be alone to enjoy their “territorial integrity” which focuses more on the individualistic ‘face’; whether a person interacts with others or gets respect and approval from others in the community becomes less important than their own satisfaction to be independent, and successful. In contrast, the notion of Chinese ‘face’ emphasizes that a person depends on the social recognition of his social status and the existence of his reputation, “and subsequently, on society’s endorsement of one’s bragging about it” (Mao, 1994, p.461), which means that Chinese people depend on their social network, and they seek respect from others. Thus, the Chinese concept of ‘face’ underlines others’ recognition of one’s reputation and social status. Chinese ‘face’ is other-oriented, while the Western ‘face’ is more self-oriented. The work of Mao (1994) can be seen as a development of Goffman’s concept of ‘face’ as it focuses more on the Chinese context, which is also the main focus of this study.

Brown and Levinson's (1987) model of 'face' is not universally applicable, and it is certainly not thorough enough for this study, which focuses on Chinese students and Chinese 'face' culture. Brown and Levinson's (1987) model of 'face' cannot represent Chinese 'face' culture. According to Mao (1994), Brown and Levinson's (1987) theory lacks a culturally unbiased conceptual framework to evaluate their politeness universals objectively and empirically. The theory of Mao (1994) sets out and discusses the Chinese concept of 'face' and I aim to know the impact of the Chinese 'face' culture on Chinese international students. Thus, both theories influence and underpin this study's theoretical framework. In the next chapter, Methodology Chapter, I will focus on how to answer the research questions and associated aims, and also develop interview questions.

Chapter Four: Methodology

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the research design, and research process, and also discusses the pilot study which informed this research. This section also sets out the research rationale, participant recruitment, the data collection methods, how the data analysis is conducted, and the ethical issues underpinning the study.

Firstly, this chapter presents the aims and research questions to clarify the nature of this study. Secondly, it provides a general discussion of three different research methods: quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods. The advantages and disadvantages of these three methods are evaluated and the use of qualitative methodology proposed for this study is explained, especially during the restrictions around the Covid-19 pandemic; some methods of data collection may not have been available to me during the time of the restrictions and I discuss how I dealt with that, such as by online communication (Newby, 2010). Thirdly, the philosophy of the research is set out and discussed. The processes of data collection and analysis are discussed. Finally, this section concludes with a summary of the reliability and ethical considerations related to this study.

4.1.1 Research questions and aims

The research questions discussed above are based on the purposes of this research and have been informed and shaped by the literature review. The restating of these questions and the aims of this study below is intended to support the reader in relation to understating the methodology selected for this study.

These research questions are:

1. In what ways do Chinese international students perceive Chinese ‘face’ culture?
2. In what ways does the role of ‘face’ culture contribute to the developing identity of Chinese international students as English learners and speakers?
3. To what extent does ‘face’ culture affect Chinese international students’ perceptions and use of language in both academic and social contexts while studying in the UK?
4. How do Chinese international students perceive the diversity of language and especially their perceptions of ‘China English’ when they are in the UK?

The following aims to support the research questions that are:

- To analyse what ‘face’ culture is and the ways in which it can affect Chinese students’ developing identity as English learners and speakers.
- To explore how Chinese international students perceive ‘face’ culture in the context of the UK.

- To examine the key factors arising from their perceptions that may affect their developing identity as international students and English learners.
- To explore whether Chinese international students' use of language is influenced by and related to their experience of 'face' culture in both social and academic contexts.
- To examine the impact of teaching methods in both China and the UK on Chinese international students' awareness of the 'face' culture.
- To explore ways in which UK universities can help Chinese students overcome 'loss of face' and encourage them to become confident international students.

The research questions above focus on the specific ways in which Chinese international students' experiences and perceptions are influenced by 'face' culture within the context of studying in the UK. These questions explore aspects that have not been thoroughly examined in the existing literature. Previous studies (Forbes, 2019; Goffman, 1967; Qi, 2017; Spencer-Oatey, 2015) might have widely discussed 'face' culture from different contexts in both Asian and Western perspectives, but less attention has been paid to how Chinese international students perceive and adapt 'face' culture in a Western environment on both academic and social contexts. Most research has focused on the general challenges faced by Chinese international students (Shan, 2020; Liu, 2005; Halenko and Jones, 2011; Alemi and Tajeddin, 2014), such as language barriers and cultural adjustment, without exploring in depth the specific cultural constructs like 'face' and how they are perceived in a new learning context. These questions connect the concept of 'face' culture to the identity formation process of Chinese students as English learners and speakers. Furthermore, the research on 'China English' is still developing (Jiang, Yang, and Zhou, 2017; Wang, 2015). This question asked for this research may provide more data on how Chinese students perceive these issues in a Western context, which can offer new perspectives on how language use can affect learners' developing identity. While identity development among international students has been studied (Moosavi, 2022; Blackledge and Pavlenko, 2001; Wang and Zheng, 2019), the specific impact of 'face' culture on this process, especially in the context of learning and using English, remains under-researched; therefore, these questions intend to fill the gap in the current literature.

4.2 Research paradigm

The following research paradigm presents the researcher's methodological choices and sets out the data collection methods.

John (2016) notes that "A research paradigm is a framework for thinking about how research ought to be conducted to ascertain truth" (p.71), which can be very helpful for providing a mental picture or pattern of thought. Trochim and Donnelly (2006) define the research paradigm as "the collective set of attitudes, values, beliefs, procedures, and techniques that create a framework of understanding through which theoretical explanations are formed." Guba and Lincoln (1994) and Orlikowski and Baroudi (1991) suggest that there are four dominant paradigms: positivism, post-positivism, constructivism, and critical theory and their dimensions of epistemology and methodology. The word 'paradigm' originally comes from the Greek 'paradeiknyai' which means to show side by side and is a pattern or example of something (Klein and Myers, 1999), and this research paradigm is interpretivism. A research paradigm defines for the researchers the nature of their study, as well as "a set of basic beliefs

that deals with ultimate or first principles (Guba and Lincoln, 1994, p.107). John (2016) argues that “different researchers may choose different terminologies when discussing research paradigms, due to the various perspectives from which they analyse” (p.71). Schwandt (2001) defines the paradigm as a shared worldview that represents the beliefs and values in discipline and that guides how problems are solved. In other words, a paradigm can be viewed as a worldview that defines its owners, the nature of the world, and the place of the individual in it (Schwandt, 2001). Hesse-Biber (2009) states a paradigm is “a theory or hypothesis”, and a framework on which a theory is built. It fundamentally affects the way you see the world and determines your perspectives and for a researcher, it also shapes the understanding of how elements of the study relate to each other. In addition, holding a certain worldview may influence one’s behaviour, even one’s professional practice, and the position taken on a research subject (Aliyu, Singhry, Adamu and Abubakar, 2015).

According to Johnson and Christensen (2012), quantitative research, qualitative research, and mixed research are the three main research paradigms. A qualitative approach has been selected for this study, and the data to be collected is personal and may be unstructured, as they discuss experiences and perceptions (Farrow, 2020). Conversely, quantitative research seeks facts, prediction and generalization of findings and determination, while qualitative research focuses on understanding (Hoepfl, 1997). A quantitative method is used to analyse and collect numerical data while qualitative research focuses on non-numerical data and in-depth insights (Kothari, 2004, p.2). In this research, I aim to explore Chinese international students’ perceptions of Chinese ‘face’ culture and whether it has an impact on them in both academic and social contexts. In order to collect trustworthy data from the participants, a pilot study and semi-structured interviews are used in this study for data collection. Data in this research will be collected from the experience and perceptions of participants which focuses on understanding participants’ thoughts instead of statistical data. I am seeking to understand and analyse the in-depth perceptions of Chinese international students towards ‘face’ culture and related issues; therefore, this study used a qualitative research method rather than a quantitative research approach as discussed below.

4.3 Philosophy of Methodology

According to Aliyu, Singhry, Adamu and Abubakar (2015), research philosophy emphasizes a detailed study based on beliefs, values, and principles. It involves thinking about the questions, making explanations, experimenting with ideas, thinking about possible arguments for and against them, and thinking about how concepts work (Ruona, 1999). Moreover, Paul (1993) and Honderich (1995) state that it provides a framework for thinking which helps develop thinking abilities and improve the consistency of one’s thoughts and actions. The philosophical foundation of a research method has three elements which are Ontology, Epistemology, and Axiology (Crotty,1998; Gube & Lincoln, 1994; Heron & Reason, 1997). Cresswell (2003) identifies “four sets of assumptions that are related to what is reality/knowledge?” (Aliyu, Singhry, Adamu and Abubakar, 2015, p.11)

1. How to know it is true? (a question of ontology)
2. What values go into it? (a question of epistemology)
3. How to write about it? (a question of axiology)

4. The process of studying it (a question of rhetoric or methodology), (Cresswell, 1994; Gioia and Pitre, 1990, Kuhn, 1970).

For researchers, it is important to understand the ontological and epistemological orientation within the research paradigm (Hussey and Hussey, 1997), as it can determine the entire course of the researcher's project (Aliyu, Singhry, Adamu and Abubakar, 2015). Merriam (2002, p.3) also suggests: "The key to understanding qualitative research lies with the idea that meaning is socially constructed by individuals in interaction with their world."

In philosophy, ontology normally refers to basic questions involving the nature of existence (Farrow, Iniesto, Weller and Pitt, 2020). Teddlie and Tashakkori (2009) define ontology as a standard of conceptualization, and the study will conceptualise the students' notions of their own existence. Strauss and Corbin (1998) define ontology as the theory of objects and their relationships; this study seeks the participants' view of the nature of their own existence as Chinese international students. Aliyu, Singhry, Adamu and Abubakar (2015) suggest that "ontology provides criteria for distinguishing between various types of objects (concrete and abstract, existent and non-existence, real and ideal, independent and dependent) and their ties (relations, dependencies, and predictions)" (Aliyu, Singhry, Adamu and Abubakar, 2015, p.15). In this study, I am aware that Chinese 'face' culture has been researched before in the business field, however, no researchers have studied the influence of Chinese 'face' culture on Chinese international students' identity while studying in the UK. Aliyu, Singhry, Adamu and Abubakar, (2015) state that "the subject of ontology is the study of the categories of things that exist or may exist in some domain" (Aliyu, Singhry, Adamu and Abubakar, 2015, p.15). The product of such a study is referred to as ontology which is a catalogue of the types of things that are supposed to exist in a domain of interest (Aliyu, Singhry, Adamu and Abubakar, 2015); this is exactly what I intend to do, and is also why the qualitative method is chosen.

4.3.1 A social constructionist ontology

This research is supported by a social constructionist perspective, which views reality as socially constructed through shared meanings and interpretations within a given cultural context. Within the framework of investigating the impact of face culture on Chinese international students' developing identity as English learners and speakers, a social constructionist ontology enabled me to explore how social norms and cultural values, seen through the lens of gender, shape individuals' perceptions of themselves and their language learning experiences. By examining the socially constructed nature of identity and language, this study aims to explore the ways in which face culture influences the construction of identity among Chinese students studying English as a second language in the UK.

Individuals such as participants in this study who are Chinese international students living and studying in the UK are developing their identity as English learners and speakers by using language through daily social and academic interactions. This process aligns with Joseph's (2004) argument, which claims that "Our identities inhere in our voices, spoken, written or signed" (p.21). Therefore, as Chinese international students interact in English daily, they are not just learning a language but also constructing their identities as English learners and speakers, and indeed, how we use language is a fundamental part of who we are.

4.3.2 Research methods

For this study, I aimed to explore and understand participants' perceptions and experiences, thus, I would focus on understanding why people have different experiences and how these lead to different meanings and eventually understand the social reality (Kent, 2007; Thanh and Thanh, 2015). The research philosophy is rooted in interpretivism, which emphasizes understanding social phenomena through the subjective experiences and interpretations of individuals. In the context of studying the impact of face culture on Chinese international students' developing identity as English learners and speakers, interpretivism enables me to investigate deeply the complex relationship between cultural norms, personal experiences, identity and language acquisition. By exploring the complexities in human behaviour and communication, this research aims to discover an understanding of how face culture may influence the identity development process of Chinese students within both academic and social contexts.

Teddlie and Tashakkori (2009) note that in terms of methodology, researchers consist of the following three types:

1. Quantitatively oriented social and behavioural scientists (QUANs) primarily working within the post-positivist/positivist paradigm and principally interested in numerical data and analyses.
2. Qualitatively oriented social and behavioural scientists (QUALs) primarily working within the constructivist paradigm and principally interested in narrative data and analyses.
3. Mixed methodologist scientists working primarily within the pragmatist paradigm and interested in both narrative and numerical data and their analyses (p.4).

Quantitative research is used when finding out the facts of a concept and also used when collecting factual evidence. Qualitative research is subjective, which means it has an emphasis on meanings, experiences, and descriptions; however, the reason why participants have behaved or thought in certain ways will not be analysed. Moreover, according to McCusker & Gunaydin (2015), qualitative methods intend to understand the experiences and attitudes of participants and to answer questions about the 'what', 'how' or 'why' of a phenomenon, while quantitative methods focus on 'how many' or 'how much' rather than that (McCusker & Gunaydin, 2015). This research intends to investigate how 'face' culture contributes to Chinese students' developing identity as learners and speakers of English; in other words, this study will explore how participants feel about 'face' culture and why they feel that way. I intended to find out how a community or individuals within it perceive a particular issue, then qualitative methods are often more appropriate than quantitative methods (Baruch, 1999, p.421-438). Qualitative research attempts to address how and why choices are made by participants in social situations within the process of interaction (Pen, 2012; Creswell and Poth, 2018). This is exactly what this research explores: social interactions in which speakers are interacting face to face with non-Chinese speakers in which they receive no clues about each other or 'face' culture. Burton & Bartlett (2009) argue that qualitative researchers desire to understand and describe the participants' perceptions and comprehension of a particular event or situation. In this research, I intended to do exactly that, to understand and analyse participants' perceptions.

The qualitative method is the preferred method to study these phenomena related to Chinese international students' experiences in the UK and "interpretivism as a research paradigm is

often accompanied by constructivism as an ontological and epistemological grounding” (Farrow, Iniesto, Weller and Pitt, 2020, p.16). Interpretivism refers to the fact that “knowledge in the human and social sciences cannot conform to the model of natural science” (Farrow, Iniesto, Weller and Pitt, 2020, p.15), for the reason that there are certain features of human experience that cannot be objectively “known”, which may include emotions: feelings, understandings and other meaningful aspects of the human being (Farrow, Iniesto, Weller and Pitt, 2020). The aim of interpretivism is not to find “truth”, but to find understanding, the understanding of humans and human behaviours (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). The evaluation criteria of interpretivism are ‘trustworthiness, credibility, transferability and confirmability’ (Denzin and Lincoln, 2005, p.24). In this research, in order to explore how Chinese international students perceive ‘face’ culture and to investigate the way in which ‘face’ culture can affect Chinese students’ developing identity, interpretive phenomenology will be selected as the research paradigm and supports the qualitative approach. This concentration on participants’ perceptions and their experiences situates this research in interpretivism. Therefore, semi-structured interviews will be used for data collection and to analyse and gather information from online conversations between me and participants, that is, to explore the perceptions and ideas of participants. Data collection for this study then is not focused on numeric data but on gathering participants’ experiences and perceptions, which means a qualitative research paradigm, therefore, has been selected for this research.

Myers and Avison (2002) argue that the social sciences have developed qualitative research methods that enable researchers to study social and cultural phenomena which relate to this study. Similarly, Bahari (2010) points out that those social actors who are concerned with their existence create constructivism which is the approach used to support the interpretive paradigm in this research. Denzin and Lincoln (2011) suggest that interpretive approaches rely on naturalistic methods such as interviews, and observation. In addition, according to Myers and Avison (2002), “Qualitative data sources include observation and participant observation (fieldwork), interviews and questionnaires, documents and texts, and the researcher’s impressions and reactions,”. This research aims to discuss and understand the participants’ perceptions of ‘face’ culture and their developing identity, and the use of a qualitative approach also fits with Hussey and Hussey’s views (1997) who defined qualitative research as “a subjective approach which includes examining and reflecting on perceptions in order to gain an understanding of social and human activities” (p.156). The data from participants’ feelings and thoughts will be collected through semi-structured interviews where constructivism fits into this study and which is consistent with the interpretive philosophy. Moreover, the research method fits the interpretive paradigm by interpreting the participants’ perceptions of a certain context, that is Chinese international students’ experiences of how ‘face’ culture affects Chinese international students’ perceptions and use of language in both academic and social contexts while studying in the UK.

4.3.3 Epistemology

Epistemology answers the question ‘what knowledge is’, while methodology asks about how to acquire valid knowledge (Aliyu, Singhry, Adamu and Abubakar, 2015). Therefore, the methodology is the study of methods (Stenbacka, 2001), which analyses the different methods

used in research. The most important distinction between methods is between quantitative methods and qualitative methods, which will be discussed as follows.

The approach chosen for this study is aligned with constructivism, which suggests that knowledge is actively constructed by individuals through their interactions with both the social and cultural environments. In this research, I acknowledge that the understanding of identity and language learning is not fixed but rather emerges and is fluid through dynamic interactions between individuals and their sociocultural environment. By adopting a constructivist stance, I acknowledged the importance of identifying the diverse perspectives and experiences of Chinese international students as they navigate the complexities of identity development within the context of English language learning contexts in the UK.

The rationale for adopting the qualitative method as opposed to the quantitative approach is based on the premise that the relevant data, in this case, the Chinese international students' responses will offer more depth to the study. Firstly, as the topic of Chinese 'face' culture contributes to Chinese students' developing identity as learners and speakers of English are under-researched, I intended to explore this area and reveal the relations between 'face' culture and identity, which is "more focusing on exploring and seeking details as much as possible" (Blaxter, Hughes and Tight, 2006, p. 61), which is the approach used in this study. Thus, this study aims to explore using qualitative methods and interpretive phenomenology selected because the research investigates Chinese international students' use of language related to Chinese 'face' culture in both academic and social contexts. This research relies on interpretivism, which will be reflected in participants' perceptions of 'face' culture and the use of language.

Thus, it is helpful to discuss the reason why I selected qualitative research methods for this study and also the advantages and disadvantages of using a qualitative approach will be discussed. Sears (1992) points out that: 'qualitative research is a willingness to engage and to be engaged, the ability to momentarily stop internal dialogue and to engage reflectively in a search for the meanings constructed by others and ourselves' (p.152). Qualitative research helps the researcher to closely engage and communicate with the participants and probe their ideas, as different participants may feel differently about how 'face' culture may contribute to their identity. According to Silverman (2017), quantitative research is more appropriate for exploring social facts or the cause of a phenomenon, while the qualitative approach is more suitable for topics that include understanding how people perceive contextual situations or respond to social interactions (Hennink, Hutter and Bailey, 2011). The first research question in this study intended to explore how Chinese international students perceive 'face' culture and the second research question aims to investigate how 'face' culture can affect Chinese students' developing identity. In other words, these questions concerned the participants' experience of both learning and living in a new, different social and academic environment. Similarly, the emphasis on qualitative research is context and process. According to Bryman (2016), qualitative studies focus on providing details of the feelings of people and this research intended to investigate how the participants reflect on their experiences, and questions were asked based on responses. I discussed their responses, reflections, comments, and experiences with participants, and then interpreted and analysed these responses for this study. Therefore, a qualitative approach was more appropriate for answering the research questions in this study and exploring the participants' responses to the research questions.

Edwards (1985) argued that educational research must not only explore the cognitive aspects of learning but also investigate the social and affective issues related to education. In this research, through qualitative research, the participants' perceptions of whether 'face' culture affects their learning and social interactions or not will be revealed and discussed. Creswell & Clark (2007) and Charmaz (2006) point out that qualitative research attempts to understand the meaning of the discussion provided by participants about a phenomenon inductively. This will be the approach used in this study, and the initial exploration will come from a pilot study which will be discussed later. Tymms (2012) also suggests that the qualitative method is effective in collecting information to start defining and locating the problem (p.231). This is the aim of this study, which is to collect information about the perceptions of 'face' culture from the participants so that I can define and discover the problem in this research. The use of the qualitative method is, therefore, essential to explore all aspects of the data and review the perceptions of Chinese students about 'face' culture and how it contributes to Chinese students' developing identity as learners and speakers of English in depth.

4.4 Sample

In this study, purposive sampling was used to recruit participants. According to Pulparampil (2011), purposive sampling is usually used to probe information from specific respondents in specific fields, for research purposes. Flick (2014) also suggests that purposive sampling gives access to those who have a deeper knowledge of the research area and questions. Additionally, a purposeful sampling method can be employed during the interview process to select participants with rich and valuable information, thus, enhancing the quality of the content (Suri, 2011).

Participants in this study referred to "teachers" as "teachers" in their responses to interview questions, therefore, I used the term "teachers" for consistency throughout the thesis. In this research, I aimed to investigate Chinese international students' perceptions of 'face' culture and their developing identity, which means that the research participants were recruited with a certain purpose, to represent key criteria which were: the participants had to have been to either recent Chinese graduates or currently studying in the universities in Scotland, and also the teachers of these two universities in Scotland who had have the experience of teaching Chinese international students (Ritchie, Lewis, Elam, Tennant, & Rahim, 2014). This sampling is commonly used in qualitative research where "participants are selected deliberately for their specific characteristics that are of importance to the study" (Crinson & Leontowitsch, 2006) and it can help me to control the selection process to achieve precise requirements (Barbour, 2001). Newby (2010) suggests that low response and limited resources can influence the sampling strategy (p.260), and this will be an issue discussed in the limitations section of this study.

I aimed to recruit students from two universities in Scotland. The reason for choosing these two universities was due to the approachability and convenience of accessibility, as well as the possible rich data related to the potential target participants studying here. Master's or recently graduated master's students were contacted as participants of this study. All participants were (or had been) Chinese international students who shared a similar educational background before arriving in the UK.

In addition, the teachers from these two universities who have taught Chinese international students were contacted and interviewed, as to whether they were aware of Chinese international students' unique cultural backgrounds ('face' culture) and whether the results of the study might help them to be better aware of Chinese 'face' culture and have a better understanding of Chinese international students' classroom behaviours. However, due to the restrictions of the COVID-19 pandemic, I only managed to interview two teachers from the same university. The reason for choosing only 2 teachers is that I wanted to have more voices from students as they are the focus of this research. In addition, while working within the restrictions of the COVID-19 pandemic, snowballing sampling was also used, as it was difficult for me to recruit suitable participants in person. According to Bryman (2016), snowballing sampling means researchers first recruit participants who then come up with other potential participants with similar experiences or characteristics. Based on these conditions, Chinese international students from two different universities were recruited and put into two groups. Initially, the programme leaders for doctoral programmes were contacted by me, and all participants were then recruited via email. The programme leaders introduced this researcher and the nature of the research, as well as clarified the criteria for potential participants. The researcher's contact details were given to the programme leaders of both universities and all participants, and WeChat was chosen to be a communication tool, as it is a commonly used application among Chinese students. Other potential participants currently in China were recruited by myself, as I had many classmates who were Chinese international students and had completed their master's degrees at the University of the West of Scotland and other universities in the UK. As they had been here for over a year and have been back in China since they finished their study, they might bring some fresh and interesting ideas about the development of their identity as international students; also, they were highly educated, and they might have a better understanding of 'face' culture in relation to social interactions and themselves. This accords with Bakar's (2013) view about the primary focus of sampling strategies in interviews, which is to obtain relevant, possibly expert-level information from the participants, and it can be determined by their level of knowledge and understanding of a given research area (p.100).

John (2016) claims that a purposive sample is created to meet a very specific need or purpose, and it is a "non-representative subset of a broader population" (p.79). Therefore, in line with the qualitative research design, this study focused on understanding participants' perceptions rather than using them to collect objective data statistically. The initial plan was that I would contact them via email and that the sample would be eight participants who were English Language Education major students, and the others would be non-education major students. However, due to the restrictions of the COVID-19 pandemic, I only managed to contact eight participants who were studying in TESOL programmes at two different universities, all of whom were female Chinese international students. Three of them were master's students during the year 2017-18, which means they did not have Online class experience, and the rest of them had. Further details related to the participants are in the table below:

Semi-structured interview	Participant	Programme	Gender	University	Had Online Class	Current Status	Nationality

Interviews	1	TESOL	Female	A	No	Graduated	Chinese
	2	TESOL	Female	A	Yes	First Year	Chinese
	3	TESOL	Female	A	No	Graduated	Chinese
	4	TESOL	Female	A	Yes	First Year	Chinese
	5	TESOL	Female	B	Yes	First Year	Chinese
	6	TESOL	Female	B	Yes	First Year	Chinese
	7	TESOL	Female	B	No	Graduated	Chinese
	8	TESOL	Female	B	Yes	First Year	Chinese

I, as the researcher, am also aware of this special situation that I am a young Chinese woman who interviewed other young Chinese women; I am aware that I understand their contexts, but the readers of this thesis may not. I specifically ensured that I engaged in ‘small talk’ at the beginning of each participant interview to relax the participants in this study and to create a safe and comfortable environment for the participants to express their ideas and thoughts freely without worrying about ‘face’ or the stress that might affect them from issues relating to gender that they may not have encountered previously. The sample of participants comprised young women, which worked well for the study because I as a young woman made an effort to engage with them in an unthreatening environment. Thus, in this study, there were only female participants sharing their learning and living experiences in the UK, but this may raise an interesting area for further research.

4.5 Research instruments

4.5.1 Pilot study

A small-scale pilot study was conducted with a sample of two Chinese PhD students and two teachers who have experience with teaching Chinese international students to test the clarity and appropriateness of the interview questions. Feedback from the pilot study participants was used to make a few adjustments and revisions to the questions: the two PhD students from the pilot study barely had Online learning experiences and therefore there might have been a limitation in relation to comparing the online learning experiences with face-to-face learning experiences. Moreover, questions asked about Chinese international students’ social experiences were not available from teachers’ responses in the pilot study. More details are discussed below:

Pilot study	Participant	Discipline	Gender
Interviews	1	Lecturer	Female

	2	Lecturer	Male
	3	PhD student	Female
	4	PhD student	Female

According to Jairath, Hogerney, & Parsons (2000), a pilot study is a small-scale method trial to prepare for the main study and ensure the feasibility of the methods. In other words, a pilot study may help specific methods and practical issues and make adjustments for the main research which can enhance the credibility of the qualitative research. In addition, if interviews are to be used, “the questions may be tested to make sure that they make sense” (Haralambos, Holborn and Heald, 2000, p.998). According to Kim (2011), a pilot study may also help identify potential participant recruitment problems or give some suggestions for interview questions. Thus, this pilot study aimed to support the research by discovering if there were any interview questions that needed to be reviewed for the main study.

In this pilot study, two teachers and two PhD students were interviewed, and I coded their interviews: please see Appendix B. Two main themes were generated from the coding process of students’ interviews which are ‘*“face” as a challenge, the positive nature of China English and supporting students.*’ The themes and subthemes that were based on this study’s research questions are discussed as follows.

‘Face’ as a challenge to learning, language development was the most common theme raised by the participants that underpin several subthemes discussed by the student participants. Two student participants suggested that several challenges caused by ‘face’ prevent them from learning; these are language development, self-identity development and building self-confidence. In addition, they both highlighted that the teaching method is very different here from in China; students are expected to be more independent and show critical thinking. They both agree that universities and teachers here and in China can do more to help students from China studying in the UK, in terms of pre-arrival courses.

As for the teachers’ pilot study, two teacher participants were interviewed. There were three main themes generated from the coding process of their interviews which are “*challenges to learning and language development and self-confidence; essential factors for the development of learning, language and self-confidence; and support for students’ improvement.*” The themes and subthemes arose from this study’s research questions and are discussed below.

“*Challenges to learning and language development and self-confidence*” is the most common theme that underpins several subthemes discussed by the two teacher participants. Two teacher participants discussed several challenges that prevent students from learning a language and building self-confidence in class. For example, how students’ levels of English were initially assessed for placement in classes and different teaching approaches. Participant A suggested that “students are expected to interact with teachers but also with each other... students are surprised that they are expected to contribute to the classroom”. Participant B said that “students without previous experiences of studying in the UK can be surprised by the teaching methods here, they expect me to give the answers... the expectations are different.” The perception that Chinese international students tend to be passive learners is discussed by the two teacher participants as noted in the subtheme. They also suggested that Chinese students lack confidence in their oral English, that they are worried about their English level which

makes them reluctant to engage in classroom and group discussions. They also highlighted that losing ‘face’ and Chinese ‘face’ culture hinders students from participating in group discussions and presentations. Moreover, they both discussed that Chinese international students tend to see China English as a bad thing: participant B suggested that “Students try to avoid China English, they see China English as a bad thing...focus on grammar and oral English is their weakness.”, which can be one of the reasons that Chinese students appear not to be engaged and reluctant to speak. Further discussions suggested that China English can be a pressure on Chinese students in the classroom that they may not engage in class or group discussions just to avoid speaking China English.

This pilot study helped me to better explore the aims of the study and also to reframe the research questions. It helped me assess the feasibility of these questions and identify potential problems. This pilot study aimed to test the possibility of my initial focus on ‘face’ culture, the notions of politeness and students’ attitude towards ‘China English’, rather than achieve any substantive findings (Peat, Mellis, Williams and Xuan, 2002). The results of this pilot study were encouraging, which helped me identify key themes and subthemes for the main research. Some questions did not function as well as expected and did not allow student participants to fully disclose their thoughts and experiences of the participants. Hence, I amended some of the interview questions based on the participants’ responses in order to explore more information. Furthermore, although the discussions in the pilot study were encouraging and very interesting, I still found that participants were not able to provide all answers to these questions, because they lacked relevant experiences. For example, one interview question asked teachers to talk about their students’ social life, to which they could not respond, as they had no information on their students’ social life. Thus, in-depth qualitative interviews were needed to probe participants’ thoughts on the culture of Chinese ‘face’ and ‘Chinese English’.

The results of the pilot study enabled me to narrow the research questions for this study, and also to explore the participants’ perception of ‘face’. This pilot study also allowed me to realize that the semi-structured interview can impede the expressive capacity of participants; and that the student participants for the main study would be more engaged if they saw these planned semi-structured interviews as informal conversations. Thus, the semi-structured interviews with the participants were conducted in a somewhat informal manner, while maintain as much formality as possible to conform to formal research. Interviews conducted as part of the pilot study confirmed that this was an appropriate method for developing responses to the ‘face’ culture questions; as well as for providing guidance and exploring questions in depth.

4.5.2 Online interviewing

Due to the restrictions of the Covid-19 pandemic, meeting participants face to face was not an option, therefore all interviews were conducted online. One of the advantages of online interviewing is that it is very flexible, has no limitation on place or time (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018) and is safer than meeting in person, which might avoid potentially and possibly becoming Covid positive during this pandemic. However, internet stability might be one of the potential problems for online interviewing, which should be checked and confirmed before the online interview starts (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018). In this research, I planned to interview participants in China and online interviewing could save on travel costs and inconveniences of travelling back to China, which were the difficulties only with face-to-

face interviewing (Denscombe, 2010). In addition, online interviewing also makes it “more beneficial to participants who are shy or introverted, allowing them to feel more comfortable opening up in front of a screen” (Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown, 2016, p.11). However, even with computer cameras on, it is difficult to see and read participants’ non-verbal body language and that can still be one of the disadvantages of online interviewing, and this was discussed in the limitations section.

4.5.3 Semi-structured interviews

The original interview questions for Chinese international student participants were designed in English and were asked in English, but participants were given the flexibility to answer in Chinese (Mandarin), their mother tongue, in order that I could have accurate and clear responses to the research questions. According to Jiang (2014), some Chinese students may find it challenging to speak what is considered by some to be “real English” or authentic English (cited in Zheng, 2021). This could be the situation in this study where the participants found that speaking Chinese allowed them to focus more on their thoughts and ideas rather than language grammar and the accurate expressions of English. In addition, they were afraid of not being able to express their ideas and thoughts fully and correctly in English or they had their own understanding and definition of the chosen words in interview questions, which means some interviewing skills needed to be considered for use. Therefore, in order to better support the participants in this research, participants and I started with their first language, Chinese (Mandarin), and then I let the participants decide if they were comfortable speaking English, which allowed participants to relax and gave reliable answers to the research questions. Participants in this research speak both English and Chinese, which means some of the data was in Chinese and I needed to write and analyse it in English. English and Chinese were intertwined in this study. According to Holmes et al.’s (2013) framework of researching multilingually, the relational aspect considers “which languages are in play” (p. 296):

The participants used complex cognitive and affective processes to describe their intercultural communication experiences in English: e.g. perceptions and emotional experiences; the researcher-researched relationship, which included deference to the researcher in some instances and participant agency in others; presentational strategies of the self; and ‘face strategies’. They were also negotiating the meaning of the interview questions vis-à-vis the research topic and aims, and the importance and significance of their own narratives and responses in meeting these aims.

All participants and I naturally spoke Chinese (Mandarin) at the beginning of the interviews; although the participants and I were all able to speak English, it might have been uncomfortable for participants to speak English when they could speak Chinese, and the English-speaking competence of participants could be quite different. In addition, according to Wan (1996), some Chinese students still have difficulty in English, they feel their “spoken English is inadequate” (p.9). In this study, I created a comfortable interviewing environment, and the participants could speak English or Chinese freely. Meanwhile, I ensured the participants were not under any pressure to use English or Chinese and were able to give detailed and trustworthy answers to the interview questions. Furthermore, some of the participants in this research suggested that

they would not speak out their ideas if they were not confident about their expressions. The pilot study offered me some fresh ideas and could also help me review and make adjustments to interview questions; so, I was able to find out useful information for this study.

Semi-structured interviews were used in this research to collect data and information from participants. Semi-structured interviews are designed to determine people's subjective responses to specific situations or phenomena they have experienced (McIntosh and Morse, 2015). Dunn (2005) explains that interviews are "verbal interchanges where one person (the interviewer) attempts to elicit information from another person (the interviewee)" (p.79). Seidman (2006) also suggests that "interviewing, in most cases, may be the best avenue of inquiry" (p.11). Interviews are a qualitative research method, usually in the form of conversations, in which information is acquired by asking questions (Farrow, Iniesto, Weller and Pitt, 2020). The advantages of interviews include "flexibility and the ability to collect data about the non-verbal behaviour and spontaneity of the respondent" (Farrow, Iniesto, Weller and Pitt, 2020, p.48). Denzin and Lincoln (2011) also suggest that through in-depth interviewing, the perspective and experience of participants can be achieved. Due to the restrictions of the Covid-19 pandemic, face-to-face interviews were not an option, as many students chose not to come to the UK, therefore, online interviews through Skype or WeChat were the methods that could help me access many people and participants. It allowed me to probe and discuss any further issues around 'face' culture with participants, in order to ask follow-up questions and clarify meaning.

There are three types of interviews which are structured, unstructured, and semi-structured (Mussardo, 2019). Dunn (2005, p.80) further explains:

Structured interviews follow a predetermined and standardised list of questions. The questions are always asked in almost the same way and the same order. At the other end of the continuum are unstructured forms of interviewing such as oral histories . . . The conversation in these interviews is directed by the informant rather than by the set questions. In the middle of this continuum are semi-structured interviews. This form of interviewing has some degree of predetermined order but still, ensures flexibility in the way issues are addressed by the informant (cited in Longhurst, 2003, p.105).

Semi-structured interviews, however, are probably one of the most commonly used qualitative methods (Kitchin and Tate, 2001, p.213). Semi-structured interviews are conversational and informal in tone, and this approach allows participants to give open answers in their own language rather than a "yes or no" type of answer (Mussardo, 2019), which is appropriate for this research. Semi-structured interviews use a more detailed interview guide and schedule, which can be used when there is sufficient objective knowledge of experience or phenomenon but lacks subjective knowledge (Morse and Field, 1995). The structure of the semi-structured interviews is constituted by these interview questions which focus on the participants' responses (McIntosh and Morse, 2015). Participants were able to answer these questions based on their own experience; these questions were open-ended which helped me to probe the participants' responses which were appropriate to this research, as this research aimed to explore participants' perceptions of 'face' culture. Bartholomew, Henderson and Marcia (2000) argue that this framework and flexibility of the responses constitute semi-structured interviews and that is why it makes semi-structured so different from other interview methods; it not only

provides the topic but also ensures that the researcher is responsive to the participants. Interviews can be very flexible and allow interviewers to record participants' body gestures and their emotions, even their feelings change in terms of their tone (John, 2016). In this study, I intended to probe the depth of their responses, and also to examine participants' perceptions of Chinese 'face' culture and whether it affects their developing identities as English learners and speakers. This type of information as discussed above, could be very challenging to be observed in a focus group or achieved through questionnaires, which means semi-structured interviews were a more suitable approach for this research. In conclusion, semi-structured interviews were chosen to allow the participants(interviewees) to feel free to explain their thoughts and to highlight areas of particular interest and knowledge while enabling certain responses to be questioned in greater depth (Scapens, 2004, p.340).

4.6 Interview Questions

A thorough review of the existing literature on face culture, culture and identity among Chinese international students enabled me to have a general understanding of the key concepts and identify gaps in the literature that the interview questions could address. Throughout the process of planning the interview questions, there was ongoing reflection on the research aims and goals, as well as consideration of the potential impact of the questions on the participants. This reflective process helped me to ensure that the research aims were supported by the questions.

4.6.1 Reflection and Limitations

Even with efforts to ensure cultural sensitivity, there may still be aspects of the interview questions that could be perceived differently by participants due to cultural differences between China and the UK, especially within the context of 'face' culture. Language proficiency might affect participants' ability to fully articulate their thoughts and experiences during the interview, despite the fact that they were free to choose to respond in either English or Chinese. Efforts were made to use clear and straightforward language in the questions, but this limitation was taken into account during data analysis. The interview questions were developed based on the research aims, as well as the existing literature. However, the perspectives and experiences of the participants might differ, and the sample might not fully represent the diversity within the population of Chinese international students; especially considering all participants were in fact, young Chinese women. Although I made efforts to maintain objectivity in the formulation of interview questions, my own experiences, perspectives and biases might unconsciously influence the questions.

4.7 Thematic analysis

Thematic analysis is used as an analytic approach within qualitative data for identifying, analysing, and interpreting patterns of meaning which are referred to as 'themes' (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Braun and Clarke (2006) provide a six-step coding process: "Step 1: Become familiar with the data, Step 2: Generate initial codes, Step 3: Search for themes, Step 4: Review themes, Step 5: Defining and naming themes, Step 6: Write-up, producing the report"(cited in

Maguire and Delahunt, 2017, p.3354). Themes will be identified through coding, as Namey et al. (2008, p.138) suggest:

Codes developed for ideas or themes are then applied or linked to raw data as summary markers for later analysis, which may include comparing the relative frequencies of themes or topics within a data set, looking for code cooccurrence, or graphically displaying code relationships” (Cited in Ibrahim, 2012, p.40).

Thematic analysis allows the researcher to code and categorises data into themes (Ibrahim, 2012); in this study, it also allows the researcher to explore the perceptions of participants (Ibrahim, 2012). Therefore, after reading and becoming familiar with the original data, initial codes and themes were provided and reviewed then grid detailing the themes (see Appendix 5) was produced (Braun and Clarke, 2006), the data collected from two universities in the UK were organized into themes. The initial themes were revisited to develop the data, ensuring it aligned with the research questions and the background literature. This information on themes enabled this researcher to answer the research questions: to investigate whether the Chinese student participants’ perceptions of ‘face’ has an impact on the social and academic contexts in which they live and study. The relevant quotations from participants were collated on grids in relation to each theme (see Appendix 5). During this phase, I was guided by the research questions, the theoretical underpinnings and the themes emerging within the data from participants’ interviews. Some of the themes were merged into larger categories, specifically personal perceptions and experiences. For example, the codes “face-related perceptions of academic life in the UK”, “face-related perceptions of social life in the UK” were grouped under the category of “Chinese international students’ views of ‘face’”; and “perceptions of Chinese teaching and learning method” and “perceptions of the UK teaching and learning method” were grouped under the category of “Different teaching methods in the UK and China.”. In the meantime, the connections between themes were also considered to make sure that they informed and answered the research questions and aims. Finally, the findings arising from the data collection and analysis were related to the aims of this research and were discussed in the Findings chapter.

4.8 Data analysis

Qualitative data come in different forms (Thorne, 2000), and the process of data analysis allows the researcher to “develop an increasingly detailed knowledge of the topic being studied” (Creswell, 2007). In qualitative research, data analysis requires preparing and organizing the data then reducing the data into themes through coding and finally representing the data in a discussion (Creswell, 2007). The data in this study was collected and analysed based on the participants’ experiences gathered from interview transcripts.

I transcribed each interview and analysed them by using thematic analysis as the principal form. Thematic analysis was used to analyse classifications and patterns that relate to the data (Ibrahim, 2012b). Thematic analysis is able to “detect and identify factors or variables that influence any issue generated by the participants; good qualitative research requires to be consistent with the collected data” (Ibrahim, 2012, p.40). In this study, thematic analysis was selected to identify the themes which emerged from the interviews in order to get a general understanding of the participants’ insights; which is in accord with Braun and Clarke (2006)

who note that thematic analysis is identifying, analysing and reporting patterns within the data and describing data in rich detail' (p.79). Therefore, in this study, participants' perceptions of Chinese 'face' were recorded and transcribed and then analysed by me. Moreover, this refers to how researchers explore and interpret language and gender. It is important because each person or interlocutor has their own ideas and biases, and these can affect how they perceive language and gender; thus, researchers need to be aware of their own biases and be careful to approach the data objectively, as I have done in this study.

I read through all notes and all recordings from semi-structured interviews several times and then completed all the transcriptions and re-read the data many times to check the accuracy of the transcriptions. Ibrahim (2012) suggests that "thematic analysis allows the researcher to determine precisely the relationships between concepts and compare them with the replicated data" (p.41). This process allowed me to develop a better understanding of the thematic data and helped me to have great reflections on the original recordings.

4.9 Trustworthiness

In qualitative research, reliability can be very challenging and epistemologically counterintuitive (Carcary, 2009). Therefore, the nature of the reliability of qualitative research is based on consistency (Leung, 2015), while validity in qualitative research refers to the "appropriateness" of the tools, processes, and data (Leung, 2015). However, the different epistemological foundations of qualitative research and quantitative research, statistical measures of reliability and validity do not apply to qualitative research (Ritchie & Lewis, 2013). Rather, "the trustworthiness of a research study lies at the heart of issues conventionally discussed as validity and reliability" (Seale, 2003, p. 172). Therefore, trustworthiness is important for evaluating qualitative research (Bryman, 2016). According to Guba and Lincoln (1994), there are four criteria of trustworthiness which are credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability.

4.9.1 Credibility

According to Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2018), credibility refers to whether the participant's thoughts and feelings are represented accurately by the researcher, and whether the methods produced the results the researcher wants to find out. Credibility means "whether there is a correspondence between researchers' observations and the theoretical ideas they develop" (Bryman, 2016, p. 384). Transferability refers to "the degree to which a study can be replicated" (Bryman, 2016, p.383), which means whether the results of a study can be generalized to other situations. In order to address credibility, the researcher of this study consulted a similar process which was applied in John's (2016) study:

First, employ established research methods, including specific data gathering procedures and data analysis techniques derived from successful previous projects to ensure the incorporation of accurate operational measures for the studied concepts. Second, familiarize yourself with the participating organization's culture and take the chance of being an insider within the institution prior to the initial data collection. Finally, examining previous

research findings helps assess the similarity between the project's results and those of previous studies (p.97).

In this study, I followed the principles of good practice and ensured all participants were not influenced, and their personal information and the answers to interviews were maintained confidentially and got all relevant permission from the participants. Moreover, one of the most important principles for measuring the quality of qualitative research is the researcher's capacity to link their findings to an existing body of knowledge (Silverman, 2011; John, 2016). Hence, the literature on 'face' related and Chinese international students' learning experiences in UK higher education topics has been studied, as well as works of earlier research conducted in related areas.

Bryman (2016) suggests that the credibility of the results can be supported by good practice and by validating the data, and qualitative research requires examinations of the trustworthiness of the data. I intended to validate the data by sending the interview transcripts to participants. In addition, I shared the same cultural background and similar experience with the participants, which were the advantages to understanding participants in this research, which can help collect data.

4.9.2 Transferability

According to John (2016), the degree to which research findings can be applied or transferred outside the parameters of the study is referred to as transferability. In this study, I was concerned about whether it was challenging for the discovery of the study to be used in a wider range of related research. It might not have been possible to prove that the findings of this study applied to other circumstances, because the research results were specialised to a very limited number of specific Chinese backgrounds and groups. However, John (2016) argues that each case serves as an example within a larger group, hence the possibility of transferability should not be excluded, even though each case may be unique.

4.9.3 Dependability

Dependability means evaluating the quality of data collection, data analysis, and theory generation processes; it requires providing detailed descriptions of the study's procedures to enable potential future replication, even if the results may differ (John, 2016). The question of dependability is whether the findings of a study would be replicated if the investigation were repeated with the same or similar participants in the same or similar context (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). John (2016, p.102) aims to offer a better understanding of the research methodology employed and its outcomes, by addressing the following aspects:

- a) The research design and its implementation, providing a detailed account of the strategic planning and execution involved at a high level.
- b) The operational details of data gathering, delving into the specific procedures and actions undertaken in the field.
- c) Reflective commentary, which critically evaluates the effectiveness of the inquiry process itself.

Dependability, therefore, requires researchers to be confident with no doubt and reliable in the findings of their research; the study's results are valuable, and other researchers can use them in similar circumstances (Lincoln and Guba, 1985), as discussed in the further section of this thesis.

4.9.4 Confirmability

Confirmability refers to the accurate and unbiased presentation of study findings, achieved by remaining to the necessary standards and requirements throughout all stages of the research project (Bryman, 2008; Creswell, 2009; Kekeya, 2021). Confirmability implies the potential for agreement between two or more independent individuals in terms of the correctness, relevance, or significance of the data. (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). In qualitative studies, the researcher also discusses the study's results with the participants to confirm the data's accuracy and that the interpretations of meaning are verified (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2011; Kekeya, 2021). Therefore, I checked constantly to make sure that the findings of this study were true results of participants' experiences and thoughts, rather than my own opinions.

4.9.5 The use of two languages

After the data had been collected from the semi-structured interviews undertaken for this study; I ensured that the transcripts were translated into English as accurately and fully as possible. However, the debate over whether to assess a translator's quality (Nolan, 2005; Chen and Dong, 2010) by considering whether they are a native speaker of the source text, or the target text is controversial; I was aware that the true meaning of the transcripts could potentially be lost during translation. Therefore, to ensure the credibility and confirmability of this study and maintain the reliability of the participant's answers to the interview questions, the data was translated by me as precisely and properly as I could. Furthermore, my supervisors helped to ensure that there were no difficulties in understanding the translated texts. In summary, I strived for clarity of meaning and understanding throughout the translation process.

In conclusion, all participants of this study were young Chinese females, including myself, who were studying and living in the UK. This focus on females highlights the necessity of understanding those potential cultural biases or misrepresentations of gender or specific issues related to cultural background that they might have encountered during their studying and living in the UK; it is the lens through which women are viewed and it was essential for me as the researcher to be aware of this. For me as a young Chinese woman, this refers to how Chinese women are perceived in relation to expectations about how they behave in class or how they look in the UK. Although this thesis did not set out to examine gender-related issues, all participants were in the TESOL programme and were women, which made me feel the need to discuss this relationship between gender and identity, especially within the influence of the Chinese cultural context which may be an interesting area for future study which I or some other researchers can work on. Therefore, I checked that all my participants who received the Participant Information Sheet had an initial understanding of the purpose of this study, and they signed the consent forms. All participants were informed that they were free to withdraw from the study at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences, if they wanted to. During the whole interview schedule, I made sure that the environment was positive

and safe, and that they did not feel pressured to answer my questions. Since they were all young Chinese women around the same age as me, it was natural and easy to establish a good interview 'vibe', and therefore, trustworthiness was ensured by me.

4.10 Ethical considerations

Ethical issues involve the researcher's sensitivity to the principles of the rights of participants (Bulmer, 2001), which means the confidentiality of participants' information and privacy need to be considered and assured. During a study, researchers should be aware that their actions may affect participants (Bulmer, 2001). According to Patton (2002), qualitative research should not pry into other people's privacy which would be very unethical.

I used emails to recruit participants with the assistance of the programme leaders of both universities and the study aims were introduced. WeChat was used to send messages about the research aims and only recruit participants who were interested in this study. Then, after I had recruited enough participants for this study, all participants were asked to provide informed consent before they were interviewed, and I made sure the identity of all the participants was kept confidential and used numbers to represent each participant in the written transcripts of the interview. Webster, Lewis and Brown (2014) suggest that all participants should be provided with adequate information before deciding whether to participate in the study. All information relating to participants was viewed by me and my supervisors and saved on my personal laptop which is password-protected. The paper documents were safely stored in my drawer with a lock and only accessed by myself. The initial recordings of all interviews and electronic files were stored securely on a password-protected device and only retained until the research project was completed, then they will be deleted permanently. The names of the participants did not appear in the transcripts of the interviews, or in any other publications resulting from the research. Instead, they were identified by codes, such as Participant 1, and Participant 2. I ensured that any identifying characteristics of participants or settings were carefully concealed or excluded. All participants were referred as participant 1,2,3... without using their real identity, from the beginning of the interview process which helped me identify each participant's data if needed. The data was only accessible to me, my supervisors, assessors, and possibly an external examiner. When presenting the data in the Findings Chapter of this thesis, I included references to and direct quotations from the interview transcripts, all while maintaining their anonymity through the use of given codes and without including any identifying information in the quoted content.

According to Schostak (2006), "one way to overcome the ethical issues is encouragement and informed consent with participants" (p.136). Informed consent will be received from all participants before the study progresses. This study is based on qualitative research, which means this may cause privacy and sensitivity issues when doing interviews (Newby, 2010; Simon and Barbara, 2007), thus, I avoided these issues and was reflective, also if the participants were concerned about their privacy, they could choose not to answer the questions. In addition, participants were informed that they could withdraw from this study at any time they wanted without any prejudice and that participation was entirely voluntary.

4.11 Positionality

According to Savin-Baden and Major (2013), positionality “reflects the position that the researcher has chosen to adopt within a given research study” (p.71). Rowe (2014) suggests that it can influence the conduction of the research and even outcomes and results. This study is considered to be a piece of “insider” research, as participants and I “share a similar cultural, linguistic, ethnic, national and religious heritage” (Ganga and Scott, 2006). Merton (1972) defines insiders are the members of specified groups and collectives or occupants of specified social statuses: outsiders are non-members” (p.19). An outsider, in contrast, is a person or a researcher who does not have enough understanding and knowledge of the research groups (Holme, 2020). In this research, the potential participants might have been my former classmates as they studied at the same university. This research aims to find out how ‘face’ culture affects Chinese international students, which means the participants were all Chinese. According to Clifford and Marcus (1986), our “insider” status can easily make us accepted by the group, but it may also affect how others see us in this relatively closed social world. As for insiders, it is easy to take closeness to society and the possibly beneficial consequences for granted, however, the most important thing should be how this state gives us and our participants greater access to ourselves (Crang, 2002). In other words, this particular research involved an “insider” researcher myself working with peers that I used to study with. Moreover, it is important to note that the boundaries between the “private self” and the “public self” are different when conducting insider research than outside research (Ganga and Scott, 2006), as this was the purpose of this research. However, Manohar et al., (2017) warn:

During data collection, for example, ethnic background can be very helpful. Ethnic researchers can have privileged relations with immigrant groups, which can facilitate access to the field. Similar advantages arise from familiarity with the languages and the physical space of the researched group. On the other hand, such closeness between a researcher and his/her subject can also harm the research process (Bousetta, 1997).

In other words, the “insider” status might have influenced my objectivity, and more importantly, it could have influenced the result of the qualitative interviews in this study. Thus, no matter what the research is, it is beneficial to reflect on how one’s positionality influences this research, and therefore, positionality is viewed as a research tool (Einstein, 2012). Since our identities evolve and change over time (Naples, 2003), thus our positionality also involves many complex layers (Day, 2012). According to Holme (2020), “positionality is normally identified by locating the researchers about three areas: (1) the subject under investigation, (2) the research participants, and (3) the research context and process” (p.2). Certain aspects of positionality are usually considered fixed, such as gender, and nationality, and on the contrary, some aspects are considered more fluid, such as one person’s life experience (Chiseri-Strater, 1996). Moreover, these fixed aspects may lead to a particular point of view (Holme, 2020), which can affect perceptions of certain things and cause a result which is not objective. Mullings (1999, p.337) suggests that “making the wrong assumptions about the situatedness of an individual’s knowledge based on perceived identity differences may end... access to crucial informants in a research project”. Thus, self-reflection and a reflexive approach are essential in a study so that the researcher can “identify, construct, critique, and articulate their positionality” during the whole research (Holme, 2020, p.2). In other words, a study requires researchers such as me to have a clear self-consciousness and self-assessment of their positionality, as it may influence the design and the research data findings (May & Perry, 2017). Bryman (2016) also suggests

that reflexivity requires the researchers' sensitivity to their cultural, political, and social context, as a person's ethics, social values, and even abilities can affect the research (Bourke, 2014). Malterud (2001, p.484) suggests:

Reflexivity starts by identifying preconceptions brought into the project by the researcher, representing previous personal and professional experiences, pre-study beliefs about how things are and what is to be investigated, motivation and qualifications for exploration of the field, and perspectives and theoretical foundations related to education and interests (cited in Darwin Holmes, 2020).

Thus, researchers should always be reflective and aware of their positionality so that it ensures the study can be carried out effectively. Further, Foote and Bartell (2011, p.46) argue:

The positionality that researchers bring to their work, and the personal experiences through which positionality is shaped, may influence what researchers may bring to research encounters, their choice of processes, and their interpretation of outcomes (cited in Darwin Holmes, 2020).

This suggests that positionality is crucial, and it can affect the whole process of a study, so researchers should always keep this in mind and pay attention to it, in this research, I knew some of the participants, and thus it needed to be very careful in dealing with the relationships between me and the participants. There are advantages, for example, I and the participants shared a similar cultural background, and it was easier for them to understand each other. However, there are also disadvantages, for example, I may be subjective and make assumptions about participants' perspectives and their perceptions or categorize participants based on my own thoughts.

In conclusion, the insider perspective doubts outsiders' competence in understanding the experiences of the inside group; the outsiders, on the other hand, question whether insiders are capable of detaching themselves from the group and conducting their research without prejudice (Kusow, 2003). In this study, I considered myself to be an "insider", as the research interviews were carried out with participants who were former classmates of mine. Therefore, I was aware of my positionality and made sure the study was objective and trustworthy with careful design and conscious care during the interview process.

4.12 Summary

Chapter Four discussed the design of the study, the research method which was selected based on the research questions, the instruments used to collect data, and the limitations of data collection, particularly due to the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on this research. Qualitative methodology was selected as the most suitable method for this study compared with other methods; interpretivism was selected as the paradigm which arose from the content and focus of the research questions. Moreover, this chapter discussed the recruitment of my eight participants. Four were from one university, four from another, and all were TESOL Chinese international students. All were female, five of them were in their first year of master's study, while the others graduated from a master's programme the previous year. The author chose to include graduated students in order to discuss whether their experiences in terms of 'face' were different from each of those students whose learning took place from 2020-2021,

who might have had fewer face-to-face learning opportunities due to the effect of the restrictions resulting from the Covid-19 pandemic. Furthermore, semi-structured interviews were also introduced as the research tool as well as a discussion of a pilot study. The sample selection tools were also explained. At the beginning of the interviews, I started with short, informal chats with all participants in Chinese to create a safe and relaxed atmosphere. During the interviews, some of them chose to speak English and others chose to speak Chinese, as discussed above. The trustworthiness of this research and ethical considerations were also illustrated, and the researcher's position as an 'insider' researcher was also discussed.

The following chapter will present the findings from the data which will be analysed and also discussed in relation to the research questions and the literature consulted and discussed for this study.

Chapter Five: Findings

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the data from the semi-structured interview will be presented and discussed, also analysed in detail. In addition, throughout there is a discussion of the relationship between students and lecturers who are referred to as “teachers” because the participants used the term for the interviews of this study.

After collecting and analysing the data, several major themes emerged. These themes and their associated issues are related to the differences in the education systems in China and the UK, and the important role of teachers within these systems. The different education systems in China and the UK, which led to the need for international students to adjust to the differences in both academic practice and social life in the UK, have already been discussed by the participants in this research, during the data collection. Therefore, this chapter will discuss the following separate related but interlinking themes.

5.2 Themes identified from the thematic analysis

Redmond’s (2015) face-related principle highlights the importance of maintaining social harmony and personal dignity in social interactions, as discussed in the Literature Review Chapter. These principles provide an understanding of ‘face’ culture and suggest that ‘face’ may significantly influence the behaviour and experiences of Chinese international students in the UK. During the data analysis, several themes emerged, informing the influence of these principles on both the learning social contexts of Chinese international students and their identity development.

First, “views of face”. Redmond’s principle emphasizes the challenge of maintaining ‘face’ and self-image. In this research, I intend to discuss how ‘face’ can be a challenge for Chinese students in a foreign environment. The fear of ‘losing face’ can lead to anxiety and unwillingness to engage in class discussions, ask questions, or participate in social interactions. This theme was distinct in the data, where students often discussed their concern about making language mistakes or being judged by their peers and locals. The cultural emphasis on ‘face’ contributed to their hesitation as evident in the participant responses, impacting both their learning and social life.

Secondly, “The perceptions of China English”. The theme of the positive nature of China English was informed by Redmond’s (2015) principle that students’ awareness of their unique linguistic identity can either enhance or threaten their ‘face’. For many Chinese international students as participants in this research, receiving positive feedback on their English skills could be a double-edged sword; while it increased their confidence, it also highlighted the low expectations and stereotypes held by others regarding Chinese students’ language proficiency. Indeed, I as the researcher, share this feeling. This reflects the delicate sense of balance that Chinese students need to maintain ‘face’ while navigating a foreign language. The data revealed that the pressure to ‘maintain face’ often resulted in students avoiding situations where they might appear incompetent, thus hindering their language development and academic progress.

Finally, Redmond's (2015) face-related principle significantly informed the themes generated during the data analysis, providing a deeper understanding of the cultural factors that may influence Chinese international students' experiences in the UK. Recognizing the impact of 'face' culture on challenges to learning, language development, and self-confidence, as well as the essential factors for their identity development. Each theme will be discussed as follows.

The following themes emerged from my thematic analysis of my participants' responses and related to my research questions. A summary of the themes which arose from the analysis which are presented below:

- Issues around independent learning (IL)
- Different teaching methods in the UK and China.
- Chinese international students' views of 'face'.
- Chinese international students' perceptions of pressure related to face.
- Chinese international students' experiences with online learning.
- Chinese international students' different perceptions of China English.
- 'Face' as a challenge to Chinese international students' identity development.

The following subheadings arise from the themes and are presented fully in Appendix 5.

5.3 Theme 1: independent learning

In a collectivist society such as China, acquiring and repeating the knowledge of tutors has been deeply embedded in students' minds (Cortazzi & Jin, 2011; Reyes & Zhang, 2020). This also seems to be the situation in this study, as all participants in this research suggested they have experiences with repeating and acquiring knowledge from tutors. According to Parris-Kidd & Barnett (2011), arguments exist around the differences between individualistic and collectivistic cultural norms, suggesting that these differences lead to students' reluctance to engage in academic and social interactions with non-Chinese tutors and students, and may explain the participants' responses below. Academically, Chinese learners are generally regarded as diligent but passive learners with a learning method that is more focused on rote memorization and repetition and less creativity (Li & Cutting, 2011). The Western teaching system emphasizes the development of students' independent learning and critical thinking skills (Reyes & Zhang, 2020); while Chinese international students are more focused on the results-driven education system (Parris-Kidd & Barnett, 2011) in which they have studied previously. According to the data collected from the TESOL major participants' interviews for this study from both University A and University B, their independent learning was described as follows: Participant 1 noted that:

Teachers expected students to be independent and have their own ideas. In class, teachers want to hear more different ideas rather than we all agree on just one idea.

In the pilot study, teacher Participant B also shared a similar view:

Students without previous experience of studying in the UK can be surprised by the teaching methods here, they expect me to give the answers... the expectations are different.

Teacher Participant A also suggested that students are expected to interact with teachers but also with each other, however, Chinese students are surprised that they are expected to contribute to the classroom, as Participant A noted:

Students feel embarrassed and don't want to contribute to the class... working with peers or groups... maybe because of the levels of language?

Participant A suggested that Chinese international students' lack of class engagement might be attributed to their "levels of language", which could be a common assumption among many teachers in the UK. This perception may affect Chinese international students' developing identities by making them feel undervalued in the academic environment, potentially leading to a diminished sense of belonging regarding their academic abilities and language proficiency.

Grimshaw (2007) and Reyes & Zhang (2020) explain that this way of learning is very unusual for Chinese students because most teaching modes in China are based on the "empty container" model, where teachers simply inject knowledge into students' empty minds or containers, while on the contrary, students in Western countries have more autonomy in learning knowledge. Participant 2 also responded:

Teachers here will not teach a lot or have lots of 'formal' textbooks, they were trying to help students to explore knowledge on themselves.

This reference to the lack of "formal" textbooks indicates that participants needed to take responsibility for their own learning process and engage in self-directed learning outside of formal educational settings in the UK. This is an experience which could be different from studying in China. Therefore, it was natural that when Chinese international students first came to the UK, the new learning system in the UK could be a potential challenge to them. However, Reyes & Zhang (2020) argue that Chinese students can and are willing to adjust to different teaching styles, which concurs with Participant 8's idea:

It is nice to learn in a different way, it opened my mind, and let me know that I need to think critically, which was new to me.

The difference in the way of learning may mean that Chinese international students need time and help to adapt to the new learning style. This alternative UK approach to learning may have a positive impact on the participants, as it can expand their understanding and make them realize the importance of thinking critically which is different from the Chinese traditional or conventional methods of learning.

Moreover, Participant 3 noted that:

We learn things through sharing ideas and experiences, and independent learning is required.

By sharing thoughts and insights with others, individuals can gain a deeper understanding of the subject matter which implies that this participant's learning ability may be enhanced through the exchange of ideas and personal experiences. Participant 4 further explained:

At the beginning, I had a hard time adapting to the teaching mode here...

All participants pointed out independent learning as a significant difference between the Chinese and the UK teaching model. Whilst most of them found different teaching styles did not affect their learning and they seem to be open and positive in adjusting to the new teaching method in the UK, as noted by the participants above, however, there can be some students who still struggle with the differences in teaching styles.

An additional challenge may be Western teachers' lack of familiarity with the Chinese learning model (Harris, 2012). Whilst Chinese international students may expect teachers to explain textbooks in detail, teachers in Western educational systems expect students to be more independent, learning through group discussions and interactive communication with their peers (Reyes & Zhang, 2020). Teacher Participant A in the pilot study noted that some students are initially confused by the teaching methods and the way that classes are organised in the UK, which may be different from their experience of learning in China. Participant B also suggested that teachers should encourage students to apply their knowledge of English to real-world contexts.

The data from this study shows that teachers in the UK noted that Chinese students are initially confused by the teaching methodology in the UK and have different expectations of the learning process. Thus, a lack of understanding of the difference between the Chinese and UK teaching methods can be a challenge for both the teachers and the students as it impacts the learning process, and they may need time to adjust to the more independent and interactive learning environment. This study reveals the need for understanding and support to bridge the gap between different expectations and teaching methodologies, enabling Chinese international students to successfully adapt to the learning process in their new educational setting.

For other non-Chinese international students who have a similar (Western) learning background, it can be easier to adapt to studying in the UK (Zhang, 2020). However, students from different educational backgrounds, in this case, students from China, can find the experience difficult and confusing. As Participant 7 explained, such discursive interactions between teachers and students are very new and even confusing:

There are many discussions between teachers and students, and between students and students, which are rare in China. In China, we have rarely been asked about our ideas, so I was lost and confused, I did not have any ideas...

Student Participant B in the pilot study also echoed:

I was worried about losing 'face' at first because other students (Non-Chinese) seemed to know what to do, but we don't ...

Participant B emphasised that issues around 'face' affected her study but not her social life. In order to not lose 'face', participant B worried about the rank of the University in both China and the UK, her grades and marks, and getting a good job after graduating. In China, your status is a way to give yourself 'face'; if your status is considered low then you will feel as if you are losing 'face'.

Furthermore, Reyes & Zhang (2020) suggest that most Chinese international students feel uncomfortable in such interactive classroom activities. This implies that the more participatory and discussion-based nature of Western educational systems can be unfamiliar and potentially unsettling for Chinese students. This discomfort may be because of cultural differences, as

Chinese education traditionally emphasizes teacher-centred instruction and rote learning. In addition, culture and identity are strongly connected (John, 2016), which may affect Chinese international students' learning experience in both social and academic ways and their identity as English learners and speakers in the UK, as learning a language also enables the learners to access the target culture. This is in accord with the work of Steely (1984) which claimed that the target language and the culture of the target language are inseparable, as it carries cultural meanings, values, and norms. In other words, language reflects and shapes culture, and culture influences the development and use of language. The way people communicate, express ideas, and interact with each other is deeply influenced by their cultural background. This may be the situation for Chinese international students in the UK and certainly for the participants above, where they may find that cultural differences exist, especially in relation to the understanding of 'face' culture in both academic and social contexts. Durkin (2011) also noted that Chinese international students have been used to listening and obeying teachers in China and studying in more active and interaction-based learning environments may cause tension for them. This tension may arise from the need to adapt their learning style and communication approach to fit the expectations of the new educational setting. Cortazzi & Jin (2011) suggest that Chinese international students find it hard to transition from a teacher-centred to a learner-centred learning approach. In a teacher-centred approach, the teacher plays a central role in imparting knowledge and directing the learning process, while a learner-centred approach emphasizes student autonomy, critical thinking, and collaborative learning. This has a subsequent effect in relation to the observation of Parris-Kidd and Barnett (2011) who indicated that most Chinese international students tend to be passive learners, who always keep quiet with their heads down, and are afraid of speaking out in public. The transition from one approach to another can be challenging for Chinese students who are much more familiar with a passive role in the classroom.

Chinese international students can also struggle with culturally diverse-related issues, and they are more used to hearing standard American or RP English, rather than the English with a strong local accent (Wu, 2015) encountered when living in places such as Glasgow or other university locations. Participant 1 discussed this issue:

At first, I could not completely understand what the tutors or classmates were saying, and the same happened in my social life...different accents also make it harder for me to understand.

This particular participant struggled both in the classroom and in her social life to understand what she was not familiar with: the local accents. This situation was also observed by Teacher Participant B who suggested that:

Students can be very scared with teaching practice and doing presentations...it is easier to just hang out with other Chinese students.

Language is a central and fundamental aspect of international students' experience, as it serves as the foundation for their interactions with others (John, 2016). These challenges in understanding accents can impact various aspects of a student's academic and social experiences. In academic settings, it may hinder their ability to fully engage in classroom discussions, follow lectures, or participate in group activities that require effective communication in English. Socially, it may make it more challenging for Chinese international students to engage in conversations or establish connections with English speakers who have strong accents. This in turn reduces Chinese students' confidence to ask questions in class,

which in their experience is very different compared to the Western way. “Chinese students are more concerned about losing face in front of others or putting others into a potentially challenging situations” (Reyes & Zhang, 2020, p.198), which may eventually, lead to a ‘loss of face’ situation. This could explain why Participant 1 does not ask her peers or teachers to rephrase or explain what they have said, even when she does not fully understand.

Furthermore, Reyes & Zhang’s (2020) research suggested that Chinese international students struggle to adapt to a new culture and new environment, while they also experience “a series of interpersonal and intrapersonal challenges, such as barriers to effective communication and acculturative stress, are particularly difficult for Chinese international students” (p.198). This supports the data collected from this pilot study, in which participants also refer to the challenge of communication in class.

As discussed above, some of the participants further noted that, to begin with, social life in the UK was not easy, and communication with other non-Chinese people can be a big challenge. Participant 1 noted that:

In everyday social life, when I go shopping, and I have trouble communicating with others, even after the staff explained many times and I still cannot understand it, that is one of the situations I feel losing face.

This participant was certainly aware of ‘face’ and could feel the impact of ‘face’ in her social life. Other participants also suggested that ‘face’ affected their learning and social life, as Student Participant A in the pilot study also said:

So as to not to lose ‘face’, I chose not to communicate or interact with other non-Chinese students here...

Student Participant A emphasised that ‘face’ has an impact on her social life but not on studying. She also suggested that she felt that the fear of making mistakes while speaking English made her lose ‘face’. The anxiety of losing ‘face’ hindered the participant from making friends with native speakers and other non-Chinese students.

However, two students shared different experiences about the ways ‘face’ affected them. Savignon and Sysoyev (2002) claim that our language usage has the potential to shape how others perceive us, and John (2016) believes that language shapes our identity. English as a second language is used by Chinese international students in the UK and their ‘face’ may be threatened under these circumstances discussed above, which accords with Participant 1’s perspective, that is, it may have a further impact on their developing identity as learners and speakers of English. Therefore, in the next section, the author will discuss how Chinese students perceive the ways in which issues around ‘face’ have affected their learning and socializing.

5.3.1 Chinese students’ perceptions of issues around face

‘Face’ is a universal concept, and exists in all cultures (Qi, 2017). However, ‘face’ is deeply rooted in traditional Chinese cultural values (Fan, 2000); the Chinese concept of ‘face’ can be very different from the Western concept of ‘face’, which does not permeate every aspect of

interaction in society. Participant 6 further explained:

If you are not well behaved in front of other people then your parents will consider you “lose their face” ... and your teachers will also accuse us of “losing her/his face” if our grades are not as good as those of other classes ... ‘face’ is everywhere...

Participant 6 suggested that ‘face’ is embedded in almost every aspect of Chinese society, which is related to not just the person herself but also the people around her, for example, her friends, family, and even teachers. This accords with Holmes and Meyerhoff’s (2003) research, which noted that society plays a key role in shaping gender. Moreover, society can also influence how people express and perceive gender-related concepts through their use of language and culture. I am particularly concerned with how the young Chinese women in this study navigate their unique ‘face’-related issues and experiences, especially considering the various layers of power and its influence that shape these experiences.

Forbes (2019) notes that “in Chinese culture, ‘face’ is of primary concern in social interactions rather than a side issue” (p.137). Even when Chinese students study abroad, the impact of ‘face’ culture on Chinese students’ life and study cannot be underestimated, as the ingrained effect of ‘face’ continues to impact them. However, it is important to note that the awareness and the influence of ‘face’ can vary depending on the Chinese students’ own experience. Participant 7 commented:

My awareness of ‘face’ or “face culture” begins very young...even when I came to the UK, I still noticed that most Chinese students are afraid of teachers may ask them to answer questions, and they may not have the “right” answer, and I was one of them...

This is echoed by Teacher Participant B in the pilot study who claimed that:

Ask students to reflect critically... that is when ‘face’ is really important to Chinese students... they are worried if they show the teachers their negative side it may affect their marks.

If students hold the perception that “*their negative side may affect their marks*”, this could affect Chinese international students’ beliefs by potentially reinforcing feelings of inadequacy, lowering their confidence, and even impacting their willingness to participate in class. As the participant noted, even in a Western context, many Chinese students’ behaviours are affected by ‘face’ in terms of study and social life. Indeed, ‘face’ may have an impact on them, but the role of ‘power’ or ‘authority’ should not be neglected. Participants above noted that students may be afraid to ask teachers questions because they do not want to ‘lose face’, but this could also be due to their fear of the ‘power’ embodied by ‘authority figures’, such as teachers, in their perceptions and related to their previous experience of education in China. All my participants were female, and they were expected to be quieter and more obedient based on the social convention of China, in which teachers as ‘authority’ might and could influence Chinese international students’ identities and behaviours. Indeed, the fear of this “hidden symbolic power” (Blackledge and Pavlenko, 2001), may deepen Chinese young female’s unwillingness to engage in classroom discussions or challenge authority, thus reinforcing their sense of being undervalued and affecting their overall academic experience and the development of their identities. The fear of losing “face” may thus be hindering a student’s development and use of the English language in the classroom.

Participant 8 also noted that:

Even when I came here (the UK), I also can feel 'face', I want to impress others, to show my English is good even as a Chinese...I cared about my grade in school, I cared about how my parents looked at me, I cared about how my friends thought of me, it was very very stressful and tired.

This participant reflected that her awareness of 'face' results in a need to impress others and to show that her English is as good as native speakers. Moreover, as she experienced in China, grades continue to be important to her family and herself. This suggests that the impact of 'face' and the awareness of 'face' are a constant, even when Chinese international students come to study in a new environment, they can still feel the effect of 'face'. Participant 5 noted that:

'Face' did have an impact on me if I didn't get a high mark or I'm not top in my class, I'll feel not just lose my face but also my parents' face. I think my parents think the same... so I was always nervous about taking exams and the results.

Therefore, 'face' is a factor that makes the participant continually stressed, with implications for the participants' mental health. The identity of being "their parents' children" deeply affects Chinese international students, as it intertwines with the cultural concept of 'face'. This sense of responsibility to uphold family honour and avoid causing their parents to 'lose face' through their children's behaviour may cause significant pressure for Chinese international students. It can heighten anxiety around academic performance, as students strive to meet not only their personal expectations but also those perceived to be held by their parents. This pressure could shape their developing identity, making academic success a critical component of their self-worth and family reputation. This is echoed by Participant 1:

I was afraid to ask them to say it again, I didn't want them to sense that I didn't understand, and I didn't want to lose 'face', or let them think all Chinese students are bad at speaking English and lose all Chinese students' 'face'.

This participant's comment suggests that the impact of 'face' can not only hamper their confidence in speaking English or communicating with others but also it can affect Chinese international students' national identity and their confidence and pride as Chinese. Furthermore, the intercultural experience of studying abroad can bring changes to international students' "identity, relationship, routines, and ideologies about self, work, and family" (Ye 2006, p. 3). Indeed, Blackledge and Pavlenko (2001) suggest that people may hold certain expectations of others during their social interactions, which can lead to fixed opinions and stereotypes from a certain group of people, in this case, how Chinese students are viewed by others. The fear of 'losing all Chinese students' face' could affect their identity development and thus, their language skills may also be restricted. As Participant 3 explained:

Most Western people do not care about how others may think of them, and they are free and with an open mind... but as a Chinese, I find it hard to truly be myself, I still worry about others' judgements and what they may think of me...

This participant also reflected that the notion of 'face' leads to anxiety about other people's judgement of her ability as a student. Gill (2007) however noted that intercultural learning may lead to students' personal growth, especially in the way they perceive themselves and others.

Participant 5 further commented:

From my point of view, people here are confident, and they pay more attention to themselves instead of other people's views. I was worried about what others may think of me when I first got here, but now I do not feel others judge me, or I think I don't care that much anymore....

Before Participant 5 came to the UK, she was afraid of 'losing face' and disappointing her parents; she had a long-term awareness of 'face', which caused her anxiety and led to tension between her and her parents, hence her initial concern about other people's judgement of her. Chambers (1995) argues that people tend to speak in ways that align with societal expectations based on their class, sex, age, and region (pp.100 –101). This participant feels that social expectations affect her behaviours. As a young Chinese girl, she was concerned about how she talked, and the way she behaved in classroom, which could cause others to view her negatively and how these could be used against her. However, a person's awareness of the notion of 'face' can decrease with time, and a person's identity is not fixed but flows, as the participant noted above. This suggests that Participant 5 believed that the culture in the UK might place a higher emphasis on individualism and personal autonomy, which may be a different experience from what she learned and felt previously. In other words, people may focus more on their own thoughts, beliefs, and goals rather than being preoccupied with the opinions of others, which could create an environment where individuals feel more liberated from the fear of judgment and are more comfortable expressing themselves authentically. Gu, Schweisfurth and Day (2010), noted that international students' self-reflection changes after living and studying in the UK, and is related to social interaction, personal development, and academic progress. Therefore, learning in a different country or another culture may provide an individual with the opportunity to know oneself (Montuori and Fahim, 2004). This is echoed by Participant 6:

I'm not an independent student, I need teachers to supervise me, therefore, when I first come here, I don't know what to do and I can't follow up... but after the first semester I find it's easier and I can feel my development, not just with my study, but also with my personal life, I'm more independent now...

This suggests that Chinese international students learning in a new environment can develop self-awareness and an ability to reflect on their learning experience. This refers to 'the emergence principle' (Bucholtz and Hall, 2010), which relates to the fact that identity flows and emerges. Participant 6 identified herself as "a not independent student", however, with time and other potential factors, she felt that she improved herself in both her study and personal life. This is also a development of her identity as an English learner and speaker in the UK, which is also related to 'the partialness principle' discussed by Preece (2016), who claimed that the nature of identity formation is incomplete and ongoing. Gill (2007) also pointed out that studying in the UK can help Chinese international students develop academic confidence and independent learning ability. They may reconstruct their self-identity, and change their way of thinking, and their perceptions of themselves and others.

One of the challenges for Chinese students to successfully adjust to the new culture and learning methods may come from the pressure caused by 'face' from other Chinese international students. 'Face' as an unspoken rule exists in Chinese international students' social life, they feel the need to obey the rule of 'face' which may affect Chinese international students' behaviour. An example of Participant 4's experience:

I didn't feel the impact of 'face' during my study in Scotland, but I did have some experiences with 'face'...when my Chinese friends want me to do something or want me to pay the bills, I cannot say no, cause if I refused them I may 'lose face' or they may 'lose face'...

'Face' is related to an individual's social standing, reputation, dignity, and pride. It involves maintaining harmony and avoiding situations that might embarrass or humiliate oneself or others. Participant 4's comment suggests that she finds it hard to say no or refuse their friends' requests stems from a concern for preserving their friends' 'face' and avoiding any potential embarrassment or 'loss of face'.

Participant 2 further explained that:

I didn't feel 'face' impacted my study, but I can feel it affect my social life. As most of the time, I hang out with Chinese students. We are all aware of 'face', sometimes I don't know how to refuse my friends, or I don't want them to "lose face", I will pretend to enjoy something and be willing to do the things that I actually don't want to, just to 'keep their face'...

Participant 2 admitted that pretending to enjoy certain activities or agreeing to do things she does not actually want to do is to maintain their friends' face and avoid conflict. As these participants noted, 'face' has a connection to individuals' personal identity and social interactions. Blackledge and Pavlenko (2001) note: "Multiple identities are constructed and negotiated through language" (p.244). Participant 2 shifted and negotiated her identity through social contexts; when dealing with other Chinese students, she identified herself as Chinese and they shared the same awareness of 'face' culture. Some participants such as Participant 4 noted that 'face' seems to have a bigger effect on their relationships with other Chinese international students rather than on relationships with local students; perhaps it is because other Chinese international students are also continually aware of 'face'. This suggests that Chinese international students tend to pay extra attention to 'face' culture during the construction and shaping of their multiple identities, especially when they deal with groups of people from the same cultural backgrounds as themselves. They not only share very similar cultural backgrounds, where 'face' is an unspoken rule, they also share the same identity as Chinese international students in the UK, and it significantly impacts their behaviours and identity.

The concept of 'face' plays a significant role in interpersonal relationships and decision-making, and it can lead individuals to prioritize group harmony and the preservation of others' dignity over expressing their own preferences or boundaries, which seems to be the situation among the participants in this research.

However, Participant 2 suggested that studying in different learning environments and exposure to interactions with non-Chinese students was helpful:

Compared with students in China, they are willing to speak and share their thoughts, and teachers will not judge them or argue, which also drives me to express my ideas, I feel safe to speak my ideas without worrying about how others may think of me...

It implies that this participant may have experienced a different academic and social atmosphere in China where speaking up and sharing thoughts might be perceived as more challenging or even discouraged. This is in line with Gu's (2009) argument, which claimed that for Chinese students, in their unique intercultural environment of living and studying, the

evolution of their identities has become intertwined with their maturation and intercultural growth. It suggests that there might be cultural or educational factors in China that contribute to a sense of hesitation or fear of judgment when expressing ideas. Participant 2 felt encouraged by other students and teachers, as she commented “I feel safe to speak my ideas”, which suggests that the current setting fosters an open and inclusive environment that encourages active participation and values diverse perspectives, which reflects the positive side of learning in a new environment. The teachers’ non-judgmental and non-argumentative approach might create a safe space for students to freely express themselves. Teacher Participant A in the pilot study noted that:

The loss of face and... students may feel losing face if they speak publicly and even in small groups... they are quieter and certainly aware of face culture.

From the perspective of Teacher Participant A, Chinese international students tended to be quieter at the beginning of the semester and with an awareness of ‘face’ culture, however, Teacher Participant A further suggested that:

At the end of the year(semester), most of the students felt much more comfortable about speaking in the class and engage with their classmates...

This suggests that students could develop their self-confidence and their language skills through time and patient guidance from teachers. Studying in a new culture may also help international students enhance their tolerance and acceptance of new practices and values (Brown, 2009), valuing and respecting different views (Campbell & Li, 2008). It also highlights the potential impact of different educational cultures and cultural norms on students’ willingness and confidence to engage in a classroom or even social interaction and share their thoughts without worrying about ‘losing face’.

Clearly, there are mixed perceptions of the challenges and benefits for Chinese international students of studying and living in the UK, which will be discussed in detail in the next section.

5.4 Theme 2: teaching methodology

Data gathered suggests in this study that the majority of participants felt the teaching methods in the UK were significantly different from China. Shan’s (2020) research suggested that “teachers in the UK tended to inspire and encourage students to think and express their opinions, therefore many participants reported extensive opportunities to speak in the classroom, both in front of the class and in the group discussions (p.118)”. This partially supports the reported experience of the participants, some of whom prefer the UK teaching method, and feel it is novel and interesting; however, others struggled to adapt to the new method of classroom teaching. Participant 2 noted that:

Teachers here will not teach a lot or have lots of ‘formal’ textbooks, they were trying to help students to explore knowledge on themselves, but in China, teachers talk a lot and more details, they are the centre of learning, not students...

This comment by Participant 2 also highlighted that teaching methods in the UK tended to be student-centred, which is entirely different from Chinese teaching methods that were teacher-centred. Participant 2 described the UK teachers’ approach suggesting that they encourage students to take an active role in their own education. By promoting self-exploration and

independent learning, these teachers aim to develop students' critical thinking skills and ability to acquire knowledge on their own. In contrast, the description of teaching in China indicates a more traditional approach. In the Chinese teaching model, teachers are viewed as authority figures, they tend to provide detailed explanations and take a more prominent role in the learning process. Teachers in the UK, on the contrary, are more likely to guide students to think, rather than repeat and transmit knowledge directly to students. Participant 3 also noted that:

We learn things through sharing ideas and experiences...examinations in China are mainly objective questions, most of the questions have fixed answers, but here, we write essays and can be more subjective, independent learning is required...

This participant had become aware of the expectation to be more independent and to be a critical thinker; they were encouraged by teachers to communicate with their peers so that they could develop their own understanding of knowledge after discussing it in class. Participant 4 responded that:

I enjoy studying here because the education mode is more comfortable for me, the atmosphere of the class is relaxing...Teachers here pay more attention to the interaction with students and often encourage students to learn. Most of the teaching is in small classes size but in China, the teaching model is more 'fixed', which is mainly based on large class sizes...

Participant 4 noted that she was comfortable and relaxed which supports the research discussed above by Shan (2020), Brown (2009), Campbell (2010), and Gill (2007). This suggests that the teachers actively engage with the students, fostering a participating and engaging learning atmosphere. The encouragement to learn indicates that the teachers motivate and inspire students to take an active role in their education, allowing for more personalized attention, increased opportunities for interaction, and better feedback from teachers. It promotes a positive learning atmosphere where students feel comfortable sharing their views. The classroom environment and UK teaching models vary considerably from the Chinese model; the Chinese education system may have limited flexibility and less focus on individualized attention which may be due to the challenges posed by large classes as was described and appreciated by some participants, including Participant 5:

I enjoyed studying here because all the teachers are very erudite and professional. And I really enjoy the seminars However, it's quite different, especially the teaching style and assignment. There are many interactions between teachers and students, and between students and students which are rare in China.

The interactions between teachers and students have also been discussed many times by other participants, as well as among students themselves, in the UK educational classroom. This indicates that the environment encourages active participation, discussion, and collaboration. The evidence suggests that teachers play an important role in developing an effective nurturing learning space. Additionally, Participant 5 contrasts this with her previous experience in China, suggesting that such interactions were less common or less emphasized in the Chinese education system which is also discussed by many other participants in this study. Participant 5 further clarified:

Teachers won't deny the answers of students or point out any mistakes, even if they were wrong. Every student needs to get involved in the discussion and share their ideas

and thoughts...but in the educational environment I grow up if you speak non-standard English even Mandarin in school, you will get laughed at, So, in class, If I am not 100% sure about the answer, I will not raise my hand to answer it...

This also agrees with the literature discussed in Chapter 3 by Jiang, Yang, and Zhou (2017), and Liu (2013). Marzano (2003a) argued that the actions of teachers have an impact on students' achievement, which suggests that the important role of teachers cannot be ignored. Participant 5 seems to be surprised that there is no negative behaviour in class, and teachers do not directly reject or criticize students' answers or mistakes. This teaching approach encourages the sharing of thoughts and opinions in the classroom environment and creates a safe environment for students to express their thoughts and ideas without fear of judgment or 'losing face', which also supports the research by Shan (2020). However, this participant still carries a fear of losing "face" despite her awareness that the classroom environment and teachers' expectations in the UK differ from the educational experience in China. Participant 4 also noted that:

In the beginning, I had a hard time adapting to the teaching mode here, and there were also some difficulties and problems with language... my English is not very good, and I also could not understand others, others may feel the same about me...

Participant 4 and Participant 5 are both concerned about 'losing face', and they lack confidence. Teacher Participant B in the pilot study also suggested:

Chinese students come from China where face culture is a big thing... students are young and have little or no experience of teaching English, so they can be intimidated.

Indeed, it means that Chinese students, in general, have to negotiate many challenges related to language, learning, identity and even gender, however, for Chinese females, the challenges can be even bigger. Young female participants in this research expressed hesitancy to participate in class discussions or answer questions unless they were completely certain of the correctness of their responses. This fear of 'losing face' and their awareness of 'face' may lead the participants in this research to hesitate to use English in class or hold back their contributions in the classroom and hinder their own development identity as English learners and speakers. I, as a young Chinese woman, understand why my participants might feel that their English was not good enough, as this refers to how Chinese women are perceived in relation to expectations about how they behave in class, not just in the UK but also in China. This aligns with Butler's (1999) argument that society assigns certain roles, behaviours, and expectations to individuals based on their perceived gender. Indeed, Confucianism emphasizes hierarchy and gender roles (Wu, 2023), and under the significant impact of traditional Chinese culture, people hold different expectations of boys and girls, often resulting in girls being expected to be even more silent and compliant than boys. Chinese people generally believe that girls are better language learners than boys, which may be an additional pressure on young Chinese females. These cultural norms and expectations can significantly influence the behaviour and self-perception of Chinese young females, making them more likely to reinforce the belief that they should be quiet and obedient, both in educational settings and in broader social contexts.

Participant 6 further responded:

Teaching and learning are very different here and in China. There were no lectures and seminars in China. Teachers will upload lectures and you can learn online, then

you post your questions, like Q&A, here teachers expected you to be independent and have the ability to self-study.

This suggests that independent study is important in the UK, but that the role and expectations of teachers are also vital to effective learning. Participant 8 illustrated this in the following comment:

I had native speakers as my teachers in university back in China, but I still feel difficult to adapt to the pace of learning here. It is nice to learn in a different way, it opened my mind, and let me know that I need to think critically, which was new to me. In China, I just learned whatever teachers taught and never ask any questions to teachers, for me or most Chinese students...

This suggests that the pace of instruction or the overall learning approach is different, which has posed challenges for this participant, and it can be the case for other Chinese international students in the UK. Despite the initial challenges, Participant 8 considered that learning differently was positive; it opened her mind and gave her the opportunity for self-reflection. However, there are also participants who struggle with the UK teaching style. Participant 7 commented:

Sometimes, I feel I was forced to answer questions in the UK, because everybody was so excited to discuss or share ideas if I don't say anything, it seems odd and weird... and I don't want to be the one who ruins the atmosphere, which can be very stressful...I guess it is also a way to "give others face."

Participant 7 felt stressed and anxious because the enthusiasm of others in engaging in discussions can create a sense of obligation or pressure for her to contribute which as well may have had a negative effect on her learning process. Chinese international students in the UK tend to be passive learners, perhaps because of their previous learning experience in China and not being fully engaged in discussions or asking questions in class, because of cultural issues and language barriers (Shan, 2020). It may be the situation for other Chinese international students in the UK, as they may have concerns about not speaking up during discussions. They may feel that remaining silent may be perceived as strange or out of place, potentially disrupting the positive atmosphere of the discussion. This perceived pressure to actively contribute can lead to stress and anxiety for Chinese international students which may impact their learning process and developing identities. Moreover, the current study provides evidence that this passivity may be related to their constant awareness of 'face' and the risk of 'losing face'. The behaviour of keeping silent may be considered a form of respect or politeness in China. It can be seen as a way of showing consideration for others and allowing them to feel valued and acknowledged in China, which may not be understood or appreciated in the UK. 'Face' acts as a filter between students and their abilities to communicate in class. Participant 2 further explained that:

Sometimes I wasn't fully engaged in class, because when I cannot understand what others and teachers were saying, I can be very distracted and lose interest in listening, but I will not ask them to explain or repeat it because it will waste their time, and I want to be polite...

This reluctance to seek further explanation may hinder their ability to understand the content effectively. Additionally, the notion of politeness embedded in 'face' appears to affect students'

language development and learning process which may hinder Chinese international students' academic development. Meanwhile, this lack of understanding can cause distractions and diminish their interest in listening to the discussions or lectures. Despite this participant above's desire to ask for clarification, she hesitates due to a sense of politeness and follows the unspoken rule of 'face' and the concern about inconveniencing others.

The different teaching approaches are one of the themes raised in the interviews, while another theme is "China English". In the next section, Chinese international students' perceptions of 'China English' will be discussed.

5.5 Theme 3: Chinese international students' perceptions of China English

Another theme that emerged from the participant interviews is Chinese international students' perceptions of 'China English' (Kirkpatrick and Xu, 2002) which is related to their anxiety around 'face'. According to Kirkpatrick and Xu (2002), 'China English' is based on standard English, expresses Chinese culture, and has Chinese characteristics in lexical choice, sentence structure, and discourse; but does not show any L1 interference (p.269). In this research, participants' attitudes toward 'China English' were very different. Some of them consider 'China English' as a diverse form of English, while others consider 'China English' as an 'imperfect' English or Non-Standard English. There has been much discussion as to whether 'New Englishes' can be accepted as a target language for non-native speakers (Du, 2009). Du (2009) further notes that 'China English' has been widely accepted and recognized as a new variety of English in China. Furthermore, Bolton (2003) also argued that native English speakers can understand 'China English', and therefore, 'China English' can be learned and used both globally and in China. However, there is still some uneasiness among Chinese international students about using it in the classroom. Participant 1 noted:

It is a problem that many non-native speakers of English may have because the grammar system and expression habits of the native language will affect the output of English. I found it very common. Just like the accent problem, but if the listener can understand what you're trying to say then it is not a problem...English is for communication, to understand each other's ideas, rather than to express yourself without error.

Participant 1 felt comfortable using 'China English'. She saw 'China English' as a diverse form of English, just a tool for communication and so long as the listeners gave positive feedback then she felt confident to speak 'China English'. Chen and Hu (2006) also suggest that 'China English' as an emerging variety of English, is understandable in social interactions. However, social interactions are very different from classrooms; the stress of the learning environment might make it more difficult for students to use it in class. The fear of making mistakes, especially in their oral English, may lead to misunderstandings, and subsequent 'loss of face' may also affect Chinese international students. Participant 2 also suggested:

I know "China English" and I also speak it. My only concern is that others may not understand me, but I'm not worried about "China English" itself or the accent I may have, "China English" is also a diversity of English, just like 'Indian English' or other diversities. I'm not a native speaker, and I don't care if I speak like one or what others may think of me...

Participant 2 clearly held a positive perception of 'China English'; she was only worried about

whether she could be understood by others, rather than feeling that she ‘loses face’ when using it. This participant expressed her concern about potential communication difficulties if others did not understand the use of ‘China English’ or her accent. Student Participants from the pilot study of this research also shared a similar view: they both noted that their own perceptions of China English are very positive. Both use China English, and they recognise China English as a diverse form of English. They do not feel as if they are losing ‘face’ while using China English, but they will lose ‘face’ if someone points out their mistakes in public.

However, Participant 2 clarified that this concern lies with being understood rather than any inherent problem with ‘China English’. As this participant noted above, she did not care if she spoke English like a native speaker, ‘China English’ could be used as a communication tool with Chinese expressions in English, such as “Long-time no see”; which is echoed by Du (2009), “Chinese varieties of English have contributed to creating new norms of English” (p.22). Participant 2 prioritized effective communication over conforming to native speaker norms and was unconcerned about others’ opinions or ‘losing face’ in this regard.

Participant 5 responded:

I think we haven't changed our Chinese way of thinking instead we always translate Chinese into English before we speak English. Sometimes I will also speak “China English”, but I'm not worried about it...I'd love to be corrected if someone notices my “China English”, it helps me improve.

Participant 5 has recognised ‘China English’ as a communication tool, however ‘China English’ might affect her way of thinking and using English and inhibit natural communication. She also felt positive and valued corrections if others noticed occurrences of ‘China English’ in her speech. She saw it as an opportunity for improvement and growth in her English language skills. Participant 5 further explained:

I'm a little bit worried about “lose face”. Because in the future I will be an English teacher. If I speak ‘China English’, how can my students trust me? Also, sometimes my roommates or classmates cannot understand what I mean due to my ‘China English’.

This participant also reflected that the listener's reaction is very important; if the feedback is positive then she feels comfortable using ‘China English’, but if the response from listeners suggests negativity or causes misunderstandings then she feels a sense of “losing face”. Some of the participants in this research discussed how the perceptions of others could affect Chinese international students’ language learning and developing identities, and they further suggested others’ responses to their oral English during an interaction are highly important; if non-Chinese speakers gave positive responses, then Chinese international students felt confident to express themselves without worrying about making mistakes and ‘losing face’; if not, then Chinese international students might choose to avoid having interactions with other Non-Chinese people in both classroom and social contexts. This is lined with Forbes and Rutgers’ (2021) argument: language is how we recognize ourselves and others, more importantly, language is for communication and identity formation (Rymes, 2010). Therefore, it is essential to be aware of the role that language plays in the formation of identity, and for teachers in the UK to be aware of the subtle changes in the language used by Chinese international students, to help and support them more effectively.

'China English' may also affect her professionalism as a future English teacher, as this participant wants to ensure that her students trust her competence as an English teacher and her ability to effectively teach. Clearly, Participant 5 has been impacted by the awareness of 'face' which may also affect her behaviours and learning. This is also echoed by Participant 6:

My roommate sometimes says she cannot understand my English, but not because of the accent, but my expression, I think it is because of the mode of thinking, I tend to think in Chinese and translate it to English...

As Participant 6 noted above, 'China English' can be a problem when her expression uses "the Chinese mode of thinking", indeed Chen and Hu (2006) suggest that 'China English' is not only a communication tool but also represents Chinese culture and customs. However, the use of 'China English' may lead to misunderstandings in communication with people not familiar with Chinese culture. This indicates that there are practical consequences to her language choice, as it can hinder effective communication and understanding among peers. The fear of making mistakes and subsequently 'losing face' is often named as one reason why Chinese students find it difficult to interact with non-Chinese students (Forbes, 2019). In other words, Chinese international students may choose not to join a conversation or communicate with other non-Chinese students simply to avoid 'losing face'. Chinese international students may be too afraid of asking other non-Chinese students questions in case they cannot understand the response given. As a result, the fear of 'losing face' can hinder them from developing their spoken English. Participant 7 suggested that:

It is normal to speak 'China English', we are not native speakers, as long as I can be understood then it is ok for me. I couldn't tell if I'm speaking 'China English', maybe I wasn't aware of that? But it certainly affects my way of thinking, because I will be thinking in Chinese... but I'll change a different expression if I found out people didn't understand me...and I would use the words I'm confident with or I know the sentences are correct...

Participant 7 also notes that if she can be understood by others then 'China English' would not be a problem. Whilst the underlying potential impact of 'face' may be present, the participant chose not to refer to it, as she said: "I would use the words I'm confident with or I know the sentences are correct". This behaviour may however suggest she was affected by 'face', as otherwise, she would not need to have carefully chosen her words. In other words, if this participant realizes that she is not being understood, she is willing to adapt her expression and improve communication when necessary. This demonstrates her willingness to make adjustments during social interactions and choose words and sentences that she is confident and knows to be correct, which just implies she may be affected by 'face' subconsciously.

Participant 8 had a different perception of 'China English' and noted that:

I rarely speak 'China English', I may but I tried to control myself...I resist speaking "China English", I feel "lose face" to speak "China English". For me, I have always wanted to talk like a British, I considered British English is superior to "China English".

This comment suggests that she perceived the use of 'China English' in a negative light and felt she 'lost face' speaking 'China English'. This suggested that Participant 8 valued speaking English without the influence of her native language and considers it important for maintaining

a positive image which is referred to as ‘face’. Teacher Participant B also suggested that:

“Students try to avoid China English, they see China English as a bad thing...focus on grammar and oral English is their weakness... It is difficult for students to balance accuracy and oral fluency, so they say nothing if they are not sure about things.”

This is in line with Siegel’s (1999) argument, that non-native speakers tend to hold negative views of their own forms of English, viewing their home varieties of English as “imperfect” or “Non-Standard”. Participant 6 further answered with the following comment:

I was more anxious in China, nowadays if you do not speak “standard English”, people in China will criticise you, but in here... but here, basically all my classmates are Chinese, and they all speak “China English”, so I am not feeling ‘lose face’...

Based on what this participant suggests above, it seems that the anxiety around speaking English may come from societal pressures in China, as Siegel (1999) referred to, rather than factors experienced in the UK. The acceptance of ‘China English’ in the UK creates a more comfortable and less judgmental atmosphere for this participant. Participant 3 also had a similar concern:

I’ll afraid others may notice that, and “China English” make me feel ‘lose face’ because I’m Chinese, I’m afraid they may judge me, or have stereotypes that Chinese people are all bad at speaking English. If I sense others’ judgement, then I probably will not talk anymore... I’m bothered when I’m writing my papers or dissertations...

This participant also held a negative perception of ‘China English’, which might have affected her freedom to express herself, and certainly had an impact on her personal identity and behaviours. She felt that ‘China English’ was an indicator of her national identity which made her feel she may ‘lose face’ and was also a potential source of embarrassment. This fear of negative judgment and its potential impact on her self-confidence and willingness to communicate was a significant concern for Chinese international students, just like Participant 3. Furthermore, Participant 3 suggested that ‘China English’ could be a hindrance to writing papers or dissertations and might affect her future confidence as an academic.

Teacher Participant A also noted that:

China English may be the reason that some students are reluctant to speak out in class, they feel this variety of English is not as good as the English other students are using...

The perception that China English is inferior to other varieties of English can lead to a reluctance to speak out in class, as they might feel their language skills are inadequate compared to their peers. This belief that they are inferior linguistically can undermine Chinese international students’ confidence and willingness to participate in academic discussions, further affecting their sense of belonging and the development of their identity as learners.

Another issue raised in interviews is listeners’ reactions. Participant 1 explained:

If the listener can understand what I mean and give me feedback, then my goal is achieved. But if he/she doesn't understand, I will feel anxious, and afraid of ‘losing face’ or expressing my thoughts again.

As can be seen above, this participant suggested that the behaviour of listeners is important. If this participant cannot be understood by others, then the thought of being perceived as a poor English speaker can keep her from communicating naturally. The anxiety felt, and potential to 'lose face', by this participant is attributed to the fact that the listener is not able to understand her which is also echoed by Participant 2:

If someone points out my grammar mistakes, I will feel 'lose face' and afraid of speaking English publicly...

This participant suggested that the role of listeners' behaviour is important and contributed to her 'losing face', and subsequently affected her willingness to speak English. She worried that her language errors may be seen as a reflection of her language competence. However, Participant 5 noted that:

If they can point out my mistakes rather than laugh at me or judge me, then I'm fine with that.

Participant 5 was willing to learn from others and accept help if the listeners held a positive attitude and did not judge her 'China English'. In addition, Participant 3 answered:

I will not be worried about my 'China English', but if they cannot understand then I will feel stressed and not willing to speak English...

As this participant noted above, listeners' reactions are important and can affect her language output and her willingness to use English. Although participants hold different views of 'China English', the importance of listeners' reactions cannot be ignored. However, due to the restrictions related to the COVID-19 pandemic, participants in this study may not have had many opportunities to interact socially. Therefore, in the next section, participants' experiences of online learning related to 'face' will be discussed.

5.6 Theme 4: Chinese international students and online learning

As has been widely discussed, the Covid-19 outbreak has affected university courses (Parliament. UK, 2020); "The delivery of university courses differs across universities and individual courses, many students feel that their courses have suffered as a result of the Covid-19 outbreak" (p7). The survey conducted by the NUS shows that 20% of participants claim that they were unable to make full use of online learning (Parliament. UK, 2020). Participant 2 noted that:

I don't think the online study is effective. It's easier for me to be lazy in online courses, I don't even need to open my camera, and teachers won't see me, besides online study is really boring. People can't communicate properly, we have to speak one by one, or like me, I usually don't say anything, unless I was asked to...

This participant has clearly had a negative experience of learning online throughout the pandemic. Moreover, online learning has impacted her study and her behaviour; without the physical presence of a teacher or classmates, she may lack the external pressure or self-restraint that comes with a traditional classroom setting, and self-motivation and time management skills

become crucial. Therefore, online study for Participant 2 has not been effective. As Participant 2 noted, it may suggest that online learning, however, may have enabled her to save ‘face’ because she does not need to use the camera, during online meetings. Participant 8 agreed:

I prefer face-to-face study, online study is not efficient for me... I cannot feel the connections between people, because we are talking to the screen and camera... I don't know about others but I can't focus on what teachers are saying, because some classes are early, I woke up and may not change my PJ and even without eating breakfast, I just opened my laptop and fell asleep... but face to face is different, you need to get up early, and prepare yourself, wash face and get dressed, and go to the uni, so when you sit there, you will be fully awaked, it helps me focus...

Participant 8 sees the online study as a challenge: she may be disengaged during online classes, and she also has had a negative experience with learning online. Being seen by the teacher or face-to-face study may have its benefits, such as receiving immediate feedback from students and teachers being able to adjust content and delivery of courses based on student's responses. However, both these participants found online study may not be very effective. Participants in this study suggested that online communication is limited or hindered, possibly due to technical constraints or the absence of in-person interaction. This aligns with the discussion around the challenges related to the restriction of the Covid-19 pandemic:

We are acutely aware of the challenges facing all students but particularly disadvantaged students when moving from face-to-face learning to online and distance learning. In terms of how many students are unable to access online learning, it is not a binary thing that you either can or cannot. We understand that many students might, for instance, have weak wi-fi or not have the appropriate hardware or are not living in an environment where it is easy for them to work... It tends to be all manner of things coming together” (Parliament.UK ,2020, p.8).

Apparently, international students are facing many challenges related to online learning. According to the participants' responses in this study, students may not be able to get support in either technology or their learning needs from universities or teachers. Those students who had previous experience of face-to-face learning experience and moved to online learning may find it difficult to adjust to and fully engage in online learning. Furthermore, Participant 3 also commented:

I think face-to-face classes are more efficient, but it depends on the autonomy of the students. I haven't had the experience of online classes yet, so for me, face-to-face classes are more efficient than online learning...

As can be seen above, Participant 3 also found face-to-face study more efficient; she also suggested that students should take responsibility for their own autonomous learning. Participant 6, on the other hand, has not had much offline study experience since she came to the UK. As she responded:

Teachers and classmates may not really know me... because I have online classes, I barely had face-to-face classes, and we have over 100 students, so we do not really know each other very well... and I prefer face to face, cause I found myself more concentrate in the classroom...sure, online study is more relaxing because you don't need to open the camera, you don't need to be focused all the time, but there are also

problems, for students like me, (need supervision) I could be lazy, and learning efficiency is not high...

This participant noted that online study may be more comfortable and relaxing for her because she does not need to open the camera during online meetings, but she also found that online study may not be very effective for her. Indeed, online study can sometimes lead to decreased levels of engagement and interaction, particularly if students do not actively participate in discussions or cooperative activities. The absence of physical presence and real-time interactions may contribute to a sense of disconnection, just as Participant 6 suggested: “We do not really know each other very well...”, which can lead to fewer opportunities for exchanging ideas or building relationships with peers. Therefore, she held a negative view of learning online.

However, Participant 4 commented:

Online study benefits me more than face-to-face class study, I feel more comfortable speaking English online, I feel comfortable talking to the camera and less pressure, but I don't think 'face' affected my study, maybe it did affect me, but I didn't feel it...

This participant obviously felt more positive about online study, as she felt more comfortable without people watching her, and she did not need to worry about “losing face”. Moreover, it may help her develop her language skills since she feels more confident speaking to the camera. This is also related to Participant’s 5 answers:

Actually, I will feel more confident and relaxed to express myself online, but still, I can feel 'face' has an impact on me even during the online study, maybe I am not that confident in what I'm gonna say...

This quotation above suggests that Participant 5 found that online study helps her build confidence and provides a more relaxing environment than face-to-face learning. However, she can also feel anxiety, which means ‘face’ may have a constant impact on this participant’s involvement in class. In addition, Forbes (2019) argues that the pressure to avoid losing face may cause “one feels compelled to match, and even surpass, the achievements of others” (p.145). That can be the exact situation for Chinese international students in the UK, as the pressure related to ‘face’ could come from their parents or their classmates and peers. Chinese international students may have felt this pressure when they were in China but due to the constant impact of ‘face’, they may also feel the pressure of not losing face even when they are in the UK. Therefore, in the next section, the pressure on the participants in the study to avoid losing face will be discussed in detail.

5.7 Theme 5: Chinese international students’ perceptions of pressure related to face

‘Face’ is related to competition, which can be achieved by showing someone’s social status or success (Wang & Lin, 2009). As a result, for many Chinese students, “the competition to acquire face creates an often unwelcome yet compelling peer pressure” (Forbes, 2019, p.145). The desire to maintain or not lose ‘face’ can cause pressure on students, especially since we are living in a high-tech society in which people’s lives can be seen in detail all over the internet. Thus, in a closely connected society like China, the desire for people to compare themselves with others perhaps motivated by online exposure can be amplified, which provides the basis

for potential stress (Qi, 2017). Participant 3 commented:

When I took The National College Entrance Examination, my parents can really give me a lot of pressure, at this time 'face' is more important to them than ever, so the feeling of 'losing face' or the anxiety of 'lose face' is particularly obvious during high school entrance examination and the national college entrance examination... I don't want them to 'lose face' but I was so afraid I might fail them, which also made me want to escape... I didn't know how to face them.

The concept of 'face' or 'face culture' plays a significant role in shaping gender identity and power dynamics within certain societies, for example, those influenced by Confucian values such as China. As can be seen above, this participant is affected by 'face' which causes her a lot of pressure, and the fear of failure and the associated anxiety of letting parents down which comes from her parent's expectations can be overwhelming for her. This participant's parents prioritize expectations and put a heavy focus on her successful academic achievement which may lead to anxiety and fear of disappointing her parents, potentially negatively impacting the student's mental well-being and academic performance. Participant 7 answered:

My awareness of 'face' or "face culture" begins very young, it came from families... when families and my parent's friends were together having a meal... I would always be asked to perform something..., it can be dancing or singing or reading a poem... I was so embarrassed each time, I guess that is because I felt I was "losing face" ...

This participant responds that the pressure of 'losing face' may come from family, which may have lasting effects on her confidence, and self-image. Her parents wanted to show other people that she was successful, and this made her feel embarrassed and 'lose face'. The pressure to perform can contribute to her sense of her own identity. This can lead to internal conflict between personal desires and societal expectations. The 'power' possessed by her parents made her feel overwhelmed. In Chinese society, parents as an authority can hardly be challenged or spoken out against by their children. Such expectations from parents often differ by gender: girls may be expected to embody grace and modesty, and boys, on the other hand, are expected to be tough. This aligns with Notash, Mohammad and Soufiani's (2019) argument, who believe that feminine and masculine identities can be shaped through gender acts and language (Butler, 1999). Such power dynamics often leave no room for resistance, and children, especially girls, are expected to conform to these norms to uphold the family's honour.

In addition, Participant 5 noted:

I guess my awareness of 'face' or "face culture" begins at school and home and since I was a child, I can feel it, as I mentioned early, I've always been very competitive, and my parents have high expectations for me, too, so 'face' did have an impacted on me if I didn't get a high mark or I'm not top at my class, I'll feel not just lose my face but also my parents' face. I think my parents think the same... so I was always nervous about taking exams and the results.

The remaining pressure to avoid 'losing face' also affects Participant 5 who can feel the pressure imposed on her, as she has to work hard and be at the top of her class with high marks which leads her to stress eventually. The focus on academic performance and the link between academic success and 'face' suggests that 'face' culture places a strong emphasis on achievements and success on social status in China. This is also echoed by Participant 6:

I think 'face' is important to all Chinese people, for example, since we are just children if you had a high mark, your parents will make sure everybody knows, "make sure the world knows!" and if you are not well behaved in front of other people then you parents will consider you "lose their face" ... and your teachers will also accuse us of "losing her/his face" if our grades are not as good as those of other classes ... 'face' is everywhere... I have always been a person who values 'face' highly, even since I was a child... I'm one of the good students, my grades are always high, teachers and parents are proud of me, I'm "someone else's child" in other parents' eyes...so when I went to university, I was so proud, I think others are beneath me, teachers also praise me in public... I need to show others that "I'm a genius", and effortless... so I got cocky and lazy, when I was in my third year, my grades went bad...

This reinforces power dynamics where individuals (often women) must constantly navigate between personal identity and societal expectations. This dynamic is particularly pronounced in situations where authority figures control behaviours to maintain their own 'face'.

Participant 6 is clearly aware of 'face' and is also deeply affected by it; this can be understood from her words above that 'face' also has an impact on her study life as she understands that 'face' for a Chinese person is embedded in every aspect of society. This participant believes that 'face' is important to all Chinese people; she also values 'face' highly, and she feels superior to other students because of her high grades. This is related to research conducted by Forbes (2019) which suggests that: "thus, if one feels inferior to someone else, if they perceive another family is better or more successful or more stable than they are, then they will feel shame and a loss of face" (p.147); indeed, shame is a very strong word but appropriate to refer to the deep sense of pressure which is felt by all Chinese international students.

Qi (2017) argues how much people care about their 'face' is related to the pressure they feel. Indeed, Chinese students are often compared to their peers willingly or unwillingly which may lead to dissatisfaction, frustration, and 'losing face'. Another aspect of how 'face' is related to pressure is that Chinese international students often show unwillingness to ask or answer questions. In the UK, students ask questions in class which is rarely seen in a Chinese class (McMahon, 2011). In addition, Chinese international students are also afraid of being perceived as ignorant or foolish by others (Forbes, 2019). In other words, Chinese international students may also feel that they 'lose face' if they fail to answer questions in class. Moreover, the behaviour of asking questions can also be seen as foolish by other Chinese students, because it is not common practice in China and can then lead to students who ask questions 'losing face' among their Chinese peers. These can be the reasons that Chinese international students often lower their heads in class and are not fully engaged in group discussions. Chinese students may consider asking questions as foolish behaviour while other non-Chinese students, as well as teachers, may not understand it; those cultural differences could lead to Chinese students' vulnerability and uncertainty when they feel challenged in academic or social contexts (Marginson, 2012; as quoted in Wang, 2018). The pressure of losing face can hinder Chinese international students' study and language development as English learners and speakers.

Based on all data collected from participants, Chinese international students are aware of 'face', and 'face' may have a constant impact on them; it may still affect them even when they come to the UK. In addition, Chinese international students are also trying to adapt to the new teaching methods and build relationships with students from different backgrounds; they also need to face peer pressure and learn new cultures and social norms. This is also echoed by Shan (2020): "In the transition process, students' identities would be strongly influenced by their learning and living communities, as well as their practice and negotiation in the communities,

through which they understand who they are and what they are capable of” (p.12). In summary, the elements of gender, identity, power, and face culture and their connections, reveal a complex web of societal expectations and individual experiences. These elements collectively shape how individuals navigate their roles within their families and the broader society, often at the cost of personal expression and identity. Therefore, in the next section, the transformation of participants’ perceptions of ‘face’ and their identity as English learners and speakers will be discussed.

5.8 Theme 6: development of Chinese international students’ identity

A person’s identity is not only defined by themselves but also depends on how others describe him/her (Bakhurst, 2001; cited in Shan, 2020). In other words, people’s identities are reflected by others, but also by how people perceive themselves. In addition, people’s identities may change constantly with time (Wenger, 1998), which means, how people view themselves may change in terms of time and even with whom they are interacting in a specific context. In the context of this study, Chinese international students learn and live in a new environment where they may encounter challenges but also opportunities. Their identities as Chinese international students may also change in terms of time and space throughout their learning, therefore, in this section, Chinese international students’ development and changing identities in relation to the issue of ‘face’ will be discussed.

The sense of embarrassment, shame, or ‘losing face’ can impact one’s identity; one’s identity or how one perceives oneself and the way people perceive them will be questioned once a person feels shame (Bedford & Hwang, 2003). A person considers pride, honour, and dignity related to gaining face; guilt, anger, and shame are often linked to losing face; they will feel secure and relieved when they avoid losing face or so-called saving face (Zhu, 2003; Qi, 2011). The findings from the participants in this research suggested that when Chinese international students first come to the UK, they seem to be passive learners and most of them do not have the ability to learn independently. Nguyen, Terlouw and Pilot (2006) also pointed out that students expect teachers to have the right answers to all questions. Therefore, when Chinese international students come to the UK, there will be a phase where they need to adjust their learning patterns and adapt to the new one. Participants noted that this challenge in learning also had an impact on their self-identity, as Participant 3 said:

When I first came here, my oral English was not good and I was afraid to speak in class, I would question myself, if I’m not good enough...

This participant’s reluctance to speak English in class may also affect her adapting to the new environment and hinder her ability to build social connections and fully engage herself in the learning experience. Moreover, a lack of confidence can hinder Chinese international students’ ability to actively contribute to class discussions and communications with their peers, which may further hinder the development of their language skills and their identity as English learners and speakers. Participant 3 claimed that “I was afraid to speak in class”, and the fear may come from a desire to avoid embarrassment or negative judgments from others and avoid ‘losing face’.

Participant 6 shared a similar view:

I think my English is not so good even if I have already studied abroad. In China, even a little boy can speak smooth English if he is in an international school... I would feel that it is a waste of money and time for my parents to send me to study abroad...

This self-doubt can be a common experience for Chinese international students who are learning a new language, especially when they first arrive in an environment where that language is mainly spoken. After studying in the UK for a year, participant 6 felt the changes and development, she said:

Face becomes less important for me. Because caring much about 'face' cannot solve any problems but exhaust myself.

In this phase, Chinese students should experience personal growth which is also related to self-identity to some extent. Chinese international students' personal growth from an overseas study experience can be categorized into two-part dimensions which are intrapersonal and interpersonal (Pan, Wong and Ye, 2012).

5.8.1 Intrapersonal dimension

Thus, it is clear that Chinese international students have challenges not only related to their learning but also because they are so aware of the issue of 'face' and how they should behave which relates to interpersonal communication. There are three aspects of the intrapersonal dimension which are self-perception, intercultural competence, and academic competence (Pan, Wong and Ye, 2012). According to Brown and Brown (2009), international students who have completed studying abroad can be more independent, strong, and thoughtful than they were before studying in the UK, and also more confident in their skills, knowledge, and themselves (Campbell & Li, 2008). Participant 6 agreed that:

My view of values and the world has also changed a lot, I tend to be more relaxed... When I apply for jobs, I can talk about my professional knowledge and answer questions in confidence.

Participant 6 noted that she has grown in confidence, but she has grown in confidence in relation to a better understanding of 'face' and how 'face' inhibits her from studying and engaging in the classroom. In other words, she has become more self-aware because of a better understanding of 'face'. The research of Gu, Schweisfurth and Day (2010) also suggested that most international students became "organized in managing their time for studies; committed to their course of study; confident about using a great range of study skills; comfortable in small group discussion; and confident about managing independent study" (p.18); some students have developed an awareness of how 'face' might impact their studies and they became more focus on developing their language abilities. Chinese international students in the UK also developed academic confidence and competence in independent and creative writing; and reconstructed self-identity (Gill, 2007), as evidenced by Participant 4:

Because I'm Chinese, I'm afraid they may judge me, or have stereotypes that Chinese people are all bad at speaking English. I'm here as a Chinese international student, I represent myself and my country, my behaviours and acts are powerful.

As seen above, this participant had concerns about her being Chinese and that her identity as a Chinese international student may affect her language learning and speaking English. However, she took strength from the fact that she was representing her country. Therefore, in this case, 'face' is not threatening, it is powerful; she is not just herself but also has the responsibility of not losing Chinese people's 'face'. Triandis (1989) believed that the public self or others' views of self can be different in individualistic and collectivist cultures (cited in Shan, 2020). The

individualistic culture emphasises “autonomy, independence and self-reliance” while collectivists focus on “conformity to the other in public settings” (p.514); “the public self in collectivistic cultures is an extension of the collective self” (p.514). “Individuals feel more obliged to behave according to the expectation of the in-group members, acquaintances, and potential in-group members” (Shan, 2020, p.14). This may be the situation for Chinese international students in the UK. Their behaviour and actions are restrained, and they still feel obliged to behave according to the social norms, as Participant 4 noted above, “I represent myself and my country, my behaviours and acts are powerful.” Chinese culture is a typical representative of collectivist culture and even when Chinese international students study abroad, the idea of “not losing Chinese people’s faces” still affects them. Markus and Kitayama (1991) pointed out that the Western concept of self is described as a more independent self; however, Shan (2020) argued that “in a collective society, individual uniqueness is less valued and is not critical to defining the identities of a person” (p.14). In other words, the independent self is driven by a person’s inner desire, rather than seeing oneself as a part of a bigger group. Therefore, when Chinese international students come to the UK, they may experience changes that may also affect the way they perceive themselves, as Shan (2020) suggested: “When Chinese students enter the UK, where individuals tend to see themselves as independent rather than interdependent, and may unconsciously expect the newcomers to have the same self-perception, Chinese students may not be able to perceive and understand swiftly their new roles and manage to fulfil the new roles through practice in the new community”(p.14). Indeed, studying and living in a new environment may enable Chinese international students to self-reflect. Chinese students will need time to adjust to the new concept of self-identity, and this also contradicts what they have learned before which may affect their behaviours as international students. Participant 5 noted that:

Because in the future I will be an English teacher. If I speak ‘China English’, how can my students trust me?

Participant 5 wanted to be a teacher in the future. Therefore, she was worried that her future students may doubt her professionalism, hence her concern above. Montuori and Fahim (2004) also argued that: “Cross-cultural encounters can provide an excellent opportunity for personal growth by placing us in situations where our understanding of self and world, and of how we believe things ‘are’ or ‘should be’ is severely challenged” (p.244), which is what appears to be happening with some of the participants in this study.

This participant appeared to reflect on her identity as a Chinese international student but also as a future teacher. Participant 5 felt if she spoke ‘China English’, she might potentially break the trust of her future students, therefore, she felt negative about speaking ‘China English’.

These quotations from participants suggest studying in a different country, as Gill (2007) noted, can reconstruct students’ self-identity. The theme of this research is ‘face’, and according to participants’ perceptions that ‘face’ is an indicator of national identity and certainly has an impact on personal identity and behaviour.

5.8.2 Interpersonal dimension

International students reported that one of the benefits of personal development is that their interpersonal and communication skills improved (Gu, Schweisfurth and Day, 2010). Chinese international students may feel stress and anxiety in the new environment of the host country, but it is also a great chance for them to start new relationships and interpersonal networks in a

new cultural environment. As Participant 6 added:

A year later, I'm more willing to speak out my ideas and communicate with other students.

Participant 6 suggests that a year of learning and living in the UK has helped her build confidence and improve her language skills. Gu, Schweisfurth and Day (2010) found that interaction with people from different educational and cultural backgrounds can help international students improve their interpersonal skills, knowledge and attitudes and also enable them to function more effectively. Participant 1 noted that:

After a year of study here, I can feel I have become more confident than I first came here, I certainly feel my English is better, and I can understand more even with accents.

As this participant notes above, studying for a year in the UK, helps her build confidence, and certainly she can see the improvement in her English skills. Moreover, Participant 3 also responded:

Overseas learning experience gave me the courage to be myself and express myself.

This participant feels positive about her learning experience in the UK and the way in which she has developed her self-reflection. Durkin (2011) argued that when students come into a new learning environment, they should be able to “move on from this position to one where they recognize the multiplicity of viewpoints, uncertainty, and relativism and finally reach the stage where they make reflective judgements through problem-solving inquiry, based on contextual evidence” (p.18). In other words, Chinese international students are expected to be independent learners, however, it may not be easy for them to adapt to a new learning pattern or context as the above data from participants shows that this can affect students personally as well as academically. Moreover, other elements may also affect Chinese international students’ identity, for example, culture shock, which will be briefly discussed below.

5.8.3 Challenge or opportunity: culture shock

The definition of culture shock as discussed in the literature review, is referred to as “the transition period and the accompanying feelings of stress and anxiety a person experiences during the early period upon entering a new culture (Carley, 2006, p.159).” In addition, the experience of studying abroad is “a significant transitional event that brings with it a considerable amount of accompanying stress, involving both confrontation and adaptation to unfamiliar physical and psychological experiences and changes” (Cushner & Karim, 2004, p.292, as quoted in (Wang, 2018)). Indeed, this seems to be the situation for Chinese international students in the UK; they need to adjust to a new environment and adapt to different teaching methods. From the participants’ data above, it is clear that it can be very challenging but also full of opportunities for Chinese international students; and certainly, they may need to embrace those changes in order to live and study more effectively which accords with Wang’s research (2018) which suggests that “international students’ behaviours can be changed actively or passively” (p.18). As in the participants’ data above, some of them do not want to ‘lose face’ and they feel living and learning in the host community is difficult and are even afraid of using the language which may lead to communication barriers. If language learners cannot use or learn the target language of the host country, communication barriers will appear (Xia, 2020). Xia (2020) further argues that “these setbacks will lead to a sense of

cultural deficiency, which may aggravate the negative effects of culture shock” (p.337). It appears participants in this study experienced what could be referred to as culture shock, not only in the academic environment but also in the social context; it also becomes a potential trigger for the development of a student’s identity (Wang, 2018).

5.9 Gender, Identity and Face Culture

Although this thesis did not set out to examine gender-related issues, all participants were female in this study and were in the TESOL master’s programme at two universities. This data enabled further discussions on the relationship between gender and identity. Hwang and Francesco (2002) suggested that Chinese international students have come from a particular culture and Chinese institutions, and their related language has constructed them as silent, and obedient. Participants in this research also discussed this and suggested that in many Chinese cultural contexts, authority figures, including teachers, are highly respected and their opinions are seldom challenged. This face-related respect for teachers and the fear of authority can significantly influence the experiences and identities of Chinese international students, as they have to live their lives under the expectations of society, rather than living according to their own values. First, Chinese students might hesitate to engage in classroom discussions or ask questions due to fear of challenging the teacher’s authority. This can result in poor class participation and missed opportunities for academic growth and interaction. The fear of making mistakes in front of an authority figure can be heightened, leading students to avoid taking risks in their learning. This can hinder students’ critical thinking ability, as students might prefer to stay silent rather than risk being incorrect. Moreover, it can affect their academic identity, making them feel less confident in their abilities, which can lead to a negative self-image and a belief that their contributions are less valuable than those from other students. Specifically, for female students, who may already be socialized to be more obedient and quieter, the fear of authority can be even more pronounced. This dynamic can further inhibit their participation and reinforce traditional gender roles.

It appears that being female is never just about gender identity but more about the situation that women are in. These women are stuck in an invisible dilemma, and societal doubts and external ‘voices’ may damage their sense of self-value. Their multiple identities—for example, being a Chinese international student, their parents’ children, someone’s girlfriend, wife, or mother may overwhelm them, leaving these young Chinese women feeling lost and confused.

As a young Chinese woman, I related deeply to my female participants. I learned that while, theoretically, males and females are equal, and in my understanding and experience, they are equal. However, the reality is that we, as women, constantly encounter moments of inequality. This inequality often seems so small and inconsequential that we even feel ashamed or ‘losing face’ to talk about it, and yet we can feel it so clearly and intensely. For example, anyone can give “kind and nice advice” about the way we should dress, our behaviours in and out of the classroom (Participant 5), and even our private life. Women may feel embarrassed to bring up these issues, fearing they will be dismissed or judged, which can extend silence and acceptance of these inequalities. Participant 3 noted:

When I came here, to the UK, I found that most Western people do not really care about how others may think of them, they pay more attention to their own ideas, and they are free and with an open mind. It is great, that we should be able to be who we are... but as a Chinese, I find it hard to truly be myself, I still worry about others' judgements and what they may think of me... and of course, there must be people who care about "face", for example, you can see there are some gentlemen and ladies dressed well and fancy. Here "face" should be a complimentary term, representing a sort of etiquette and elegance.

Participant 3 felt she could not be herself: as a young Chinese woman, she worried about how others might see and judge her. She clearly admired the way that the UK people dress and the way they choose to live their lives, however, 'face' culture and her identity as a Chinese international student seem to be a hindrance. Participant 3 could feel the additional pressure to conform to Chinese societal expectations even if she was in the UK. This suggests that females may possess a strong awareness and sensitivity to gender-based injustices, even when they are not openly acknowledged.

Gender, identity, and 'face' culture are intertwined elements that profoundly shape my participants' lives within various cultural and social contexts. Gender as a social construct is not simply a biological category but covers roles and behaviours, associated with societal expectations. These gendered norms are deeply embedded in cultural practices and influence individuals' identities from a young age as discussed by participants in this research. Chinese international students, especially women, navigate their own multiple identities shaped by their gender, ethnicity, and personal experiences, which form a unique sense of self. Gender identity is deeply connected with 'face' culture, as individuals' obedience to gender norms often serves to maintain 'face' for themselves and their families; women are often expected to represent traits such as obedience, and selflessness to uphold family honour and maintain 'face' as discussed by participants in this research. Furthermore, power dynamics within families and communities play a significant role in enforcing gendered expectations. Authority figures, such as parents and elders, carry significant influence in shaping individuals' behaviours and identities. The pressure to conform to these expectations and maintain 'face' can have profound emotional and physical consequences for individuals. Feelings of shame, guilt, and inadequacy may arise when individuals perceive themselves as failing to meet societal standards in terms of face culture and its associated norms. Understanding the deep relationship among gender, identity, and 'face' culture has significant implications for any interventions to help and support Chinese international students in the UK.

5.10 Conclusion

The data collected from participants in this study suggested that 'face' plays an essential role in many aspects of Chinese international students' studies and lives. Participants in this research suggested that they could still feel the consistent impact of 'face' even when they came to the UK. Forbes (2019) also noted that most participants in his research are also aware of the effect of 'face' and hope to resist it, but 'face' still influences their lives. This research

analysed issues related to ‘face’ as discussed by participants who referred to both the challenges and opportunities of studying abroad.

The issues around Chinese international students’ independent learning were discussed. Students in the UK are expected to think independently, interact with their peers and also have the ability to develop knowledge by themselves (Shan, 2020). Indeed, participants noted that teaching methods here are very different from those in China; teachers in the UK usually help students discover new knowledge by themselves, and guide them to explore their learning; however, teachers in China tend to use test-based methods which rely on textbooks. However, different teaching methods in the UK also brought challenges as well as opportunities for Chinese international students. There are two challenges that have been raised by the participants, one is critical thinking, and the other one is learning autonomy. In China, critical thinking is rarely required, and teachers focus more on students’ skills in reading, writing, and exams which is also in line with Shan’s (2020) findings, and which suggests that it can be a big challenge for students who have been used to memory-based classroom learning and exams. These findings also discussed Chinese international students’ perceptions of ‘face’, ‘China English’, and their developing identities; the pressure related to face has also been discussed which reveals how ‘face’ deeply affects Chinese international students to a greater extent.

Therefore, through exploring how ‘face’ impacts Chinese international students’ developing identity as English learners and speakers, this chapter has developed important knowledge to add to the existing literature on these related topics. In the next chapter, the conclusions to this study will be discussed, in relation to how the research questions have been answered, and how the findings have helped to answer the research questions. This research will also consider the implications of these findings which lead to recommendations delivered in the final chapter.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

6.1 Introduction and Overview

This research aims to examine the impact of ‘face’ culture on Chinese international students’ studies and lives in the UK. It discussed and analysed Chinese international students’ perceptions of ‘face’ culture and associated notions of politeness and examined the developing identity of Chinese international students as English learners and speakers. In this chapter, summaries of all previous chapters are presented, and the research questions and associated aims are reviewed and discussed with reference to the Findings. In addition, this section will also present a summary of this research and implications of the Findings, limitations of this current research, as well as recommendations and suggestions for researchers who may plan further study in this area. The reflection on both the academic and personal growth of this researcher will also be presented. Moreover, reflection on the potential impact of the research and recommendations to universities in China and the UK will also be given.

6.1.1 Chapter summaries

Chinese international students learning in the UK and their transformative experiences of education have been widely discussed by researchers (Zhang, 2020; Forbes, 2019; Shan, 2020) in current literature. However, ‘face’ culture and the impact of ‘face’ on Chinese international students have not been a focus or have been overlooked in previous studies. Chapter One examines and presents Chinese international students’ perceptions of the impact of ‘face’ by uncovering their experience of studying and living in the UK and identifying and discussing any challenges they may have encountered. Chapter Two discusses the concept of ‘face’ culture in both the Chinese and the UK contexts, and the differences in an understanding of ‘face’ and its use among Chinese and Western contexts. In addition, the challenges related to ‘face’ culture that Chinese international students have met during their study and living in the UK were also discussed and presented. Chapter Three discussed the literature around ‘face’ culture, the concept of politeness, China English, and Chinese international students’ identity as English learners and speakers in the UK, all of which underpinned this study. Furthermore, relevant studies around Chinese international students’ study and living experiences in the UK were also discussed and analyzed. Chapter Four set out a qualitative research design that arose from Goffman’s (1967) concept of ‘face’ combined with Brown and Levinson’s (1978, 1987) politeness theory; the work of Mao (1994) was also discussed and focused more on the Chinese context than Goffman’s concept of ‘face’. To understand the issues underpinning this research, a pilot study and in-depth semi-structured interviews were used as the research tools to enable the researcher to collect rich data. In addition, this research also presents the reasons for choosing Goffman’s concept of ‘face’ and Mao’s (1994) concept of ‘face’ as the theoretical frameworks; that is, these concepts define ‘face’ culture from both Chinese and Western views which is central to the focus of the research. Furthermore, a discussion of these concepts helped participants and other researchers have a clear understanding of the key issues within this research, and as a result of this understanding, participants were more able to provide clearer responses during interviews. Chapter Five set out the analysis of the main themes that arose from the data collected from the interviews in this research which included Chinese international students’ perceptions of ‘face’ culture, and their suggestions and recommendations to improve the learning experience in UK universities.

6.2 Overview of research questions and findings

The research questions arose from an analysis of the literature and an intention to fill the existing gap in the literature review; these are set out in the introduction to this thesis. Each of the research questions will be discussed in turn and will be examined as to whether and how they were answered with reference to a discussion of the Findings in Chapter Five.

In what ways do Chinese international students perceive Chinese ‘face’ culture?

This research question aimed to explore ways in which Chinese international students perceive Chinese ‘face’ culture. This question was answered by the responses to the interview questions which are in Appendix 5.

The participants in this research were asked whether they were aware of the term ‘face’ or “face culture”, whether they understand it and in what ways did they become aware of the notion of ‘face’. The Findings show that all participants from the interviews were aware of ‘face’ and ‘face’ culture; and participants explained that they have developed their understanding of ‘face’ and ‘face’ culture from their parents, families and also teachers. ‘Face’ is deeply rooted in Chinese people’s lives and thoughts; parents will blame their children for ‘losing face’ of their own as well as their parents if children do not behave as their parents want; teachers will also blame students for ‘loss of face’ if their marks or exam results are not good.

Moreover, in order to explore how students perceive ‘face’ culture, the participants were asked whether they feel that ‘face’ has had an impact on them in social or academic areas of their lives in the UK. The Findings uncovered that all participants could feel the impact of ‘face’ in their social and academic areas in China and even when they come to the UK. Some of the participants noted that their understanding of ‘face’ also developed when they came to the UK; they further explained that they feel most people in the West do not know about Chinese ‘face’ which referred to how other people may perceive Chinese international students. Participants explained within the Findings chapter, their concern with ‘loss of face’ and how it could hinder their learning and social communication.

Chinese international students in the UK can still feel the impact of ‘face’ on their academic and social life. Participants noted that if they cannot be understood by others or they cannot understand others then they will feel a ‘loss of face’, and an example of this is that they did not feel confident to ask questions during the class or while communicating with other non-Chinese students. In other words, ‘face’ is a challenge or a hindrance for Chinese international students’ learning and living in the UK. However, some participants suggested that they do not care about ‘face’, as they come to the UK to learn, and they believe they can only improve and develop by making mistakes and using English. In summary, the data collected which informs a response to the question has been discussed in full in the Findings and therefore serves as a response to this research question.

In what ways does the role of ‘face’ culture contribute to the developing identity of Chinese international students as English learners and speakers?

The participants in this research were asked three questions with two sub-questions on this subject during the interviews. The Findings show that all participants came to the UK in order to study in the MEd TESOL programme which lasts around a year and a half and that they all enjoyed and were satisfied with their studies here. Most participants suggested that teachers

and other classmates are kind and supportive, and they were willing to share and help Chinese international students. However, some of the participants found it hard to engage or communicate with other non-Chinese students, and most of them tended to remain with their Chinese peers both inside and outside the university when socializing. They further suggested that as they became familiar with other non-Chinese students, they started to be less afraid of 'losing face'. Some of them feel positive about themselves as Chinese international students and also as English learners and speakers because they feel confident and safe sharing their ideas in class without worrying about what others may think of them.

In addition, they feel that they are encouraged by teachers and have been given the opportunities to improve their language skills by studying in the UK and also to learn about other cultures. However, there are also participants who feel negative about themselves. These participants further answered that they are Chinese international students and their behaviours and acts, or words, represent China, so they must be very careful not to 'lose face'. Thus, the anxiety around Chinese people 'losing face' can hinder their language development and affect Chinese international students' national identity, as discussed in the Findings chapter. Some of the participants noted that they do not want to communicate or discuss issues with other non-Chinese students in class, because they do not want to say something wrong or make mistakes, as they believe misunderstandings and mistakes can lead to 'losing face'; however, after a year learning in the UK, the participants claimed that they have rebuilt their self-identity as Chinese international students. They now feel that even though they are aware of 'face', they feel much more comfortable and confident studying in the UK.

Most of the participants noted that after a year of study in the UK, their language skills improved, and they became more confident. They hold positive attitudes about their future study and jobs, they believe that their experiences of studying in the UK helped them build confidence and also to become more independent learners.

To what extent does 'face' culture affect Chinese international students' perceptions and use of language in both academic and social contexts while studying in the UK?

In order to answer this research question, participants in this research were required to share their "face-culture-related" experiences in both academic and social contexts. They noted that independent learning and critical thinking are the two main challenges they met during their study in the UK. As Parris-Kidd & Barnett (2011) argued, Chinese international students are more focused on a results-driven education system, but the Western teaching system emphasizes developing students' independent learning and critical thinking skills (Reyes & Zhang, 2020). Indeed, the Findings showed that all the participants in this study felt confused about what critical thinking actually is and how can they be critical in their classwork. This approach to studying is unusual for Chinese students because most teaching modes in China are based on rote memorization and repetition (Huang and Turner, 2018).

The participants in this research suggested that teachers in the UK expect students to be more independent, however, Chinese students expect teachers to tell them what to do. In addition, other non-Chinese international students were familiar with this teaching method; and Chinese international students, according to the participants, were afraid to ask teachers or other students to explain. Indeed, because they do not want to be seen as "foolish", Chinese international students, according to participants in this research, believe that they appear foolish by asking questions and this also leads to "losing face". Most of the participants noted that they tend not to share their thoughts and ideas because they do not feel comfortable in interactive

classroom activities. Chinese culture focuses on harmony, and 'face' culture also emphasized 'giving others face' which promotes harmony; if you present an opinion that is contrary to the others, then it is seen as not 'giving other's face' or making other's 'losing their face'. In other words, Chinese students do not want to cause any conflict by appearing to make another student 'lose face'. These Findings showed that Chinese international students can still feel the impact of 'face', and they tend to follow the rules of 'face' even in the UK. The participants noted that 'face' culture impacts their confidence as English learners and speakers in both academic and social contexts, and also affects their language input and output.

Moreover, the Findings suggest that 'face' also brought pressure from others who have the same cultural background; 'face' has a big effect on their relationships with other Chinese international students as well as with local or other non-Chinese students. The reason is that they share very similar cultural backgrounds, and they are all aware of the rules of 'face' which impact their behaviours and actions.

The Findings also reflected that some of the participants claimed their awareness of 'face' results in a need to impress others and the awareness of 'face' is constant which makes participants feel continued stress and anxiety. These participants also believe the impact of 'face' leads to anxiety about their position among their classmates and the way they perceive themselves and others; it also affects their ability to learn. The Findings also reveal that according to participants in this research, the experiences of learning in a different country provide Chinese international students with an opportunity to know about themselves and also to reflect on their changes in social interaction, personal, development, and also their academic process. The Findings also show that participants in this research developed self-awareness, and their perceptions of 'face', of themselves and other students also changed and developed. Therefore, it appears from the participants' responses, that 'face' culture affects Chinese international students' perceptions and use of language in both academic and social contexts while studying in the UK to a large extent, as discussed in the Findings, and so, this research question is fully answered by the Findings.

How do Chinese international students perceive the diversity of language and especially their perceptions of 'China English' when they are in the UK?

One question with three sub-questions was asked in order to answer this question in the participant interviews, and the responses of Chinese international students' perceptions of China English can be found in the Appendix 5. The Findings clearly suggest that most of the participants in this research tend to see China English as a diverse form of English. Most of the Chinese international participants appear to feel positive toward China English and most of them are aware of themselves using China English. They recognise China English as a tool of communication. However, some participants feel negative about speaking China English. They consider speaking China English as 'losing face', 'imperfect' and 'Non-standard' English. Participants suggested that 'losing face' can affect their willingness to speak English. Furthermore, participants also noted that China English can be a hindrance to writing academic papers which affects their confidence as academics; they responded that China English can be a problem when they are engaged in academic discussion, which means that their thinking can be affected by China English, and it may not be as clear as academic English; they may tend to translate their ideas from Chinese to English in their head.

Moreover, the Findings show that according to participants in this research, listeners' feedback or reactions are essential to Chinese international students when they speak China English during interactions both inside and outside the university. Those participants in this research

who see China English as positive also noted that if the listeners do not respond or misunderstand them, then they do not feel confident, and this results in a 'loss of face'. The Findings also suggest that casual social interactions put less pressure on participants than classroom interactions, as Chinese international students can have more natural communication when they are relaxed and in a social context. However, interactions in class are more complex. As it is a more formal environment in comparison with social situations, Chinese students may feel nervous about using China English in class, because they are discussing specifically Chinese issues, so they may choose not to speak when they do not feel completely correct or confident about what they are going to say. They may not want to take the risk of 'losing face' in front of everyone, and this may affect their English learning and speaking, which may also have an impact on their identity as Chinese international students.

The researcher found that Chinese international students can have both positive and negative perceptions of China English. On one hand, they see China English as a tool for communication and a diverse form of English. On the other hand, listeners' reactions towards China English are very important, as Chinese international students can be highly affected by listeners' responses, and contexts that are, where China English is used are also important for Chinese international students. It is suggested in the Findings that they prefer to use China English in a more relaxed and informal environment.

Due to the recent pandemic, Chinese international students had limited opportunities to attend social events and minimal experience in face-to-face learning. Most of them hold positive views towards online learning: they believe online learning was more relaxing and comfortable than face to face learning environment; they feel more confident sharing their ideas online than in classrooms. However, other participants suggested that online study was a challenge for them, they found it to be inefficient and hard to engage with the learning process because it required them to be autonomous learners which was a new study approach, in which they had limited competence. Therefore, this research question has been answered.

6.3 Contribution to knowledge from this research

This thesis contributes to the understanding of the 'face' related experiences of Chinese international students in the UK and has implications for academic practice development within higher institutions broadly.

The theoretical framework used in this study is different from that used by most other researchers in related fields. Literature adopted in this research along with Goffman's (1955,1967) work on 'face', the politeness theory of Brown and Levinson (1978,1987), as well as Mao's (1994) work on 'face' culture, enabled me to explore and acknowledge the 'face'-related challenges that may be encountered when Chinese international students are studying in an international educational environment and provide strong support for the view that universities are failing to acknowledge potential benefits of having Chinese International students.

This study gives a thorough understanding of the face-related changing cultural development of China, and interviewees' perceptions towards it. It starts with the individual's experiences of learning in a new environment from both social and academic levels. Then it explores Chinese international students' educational backgrounds, and the associated social, cultural and gender factors, and analyses the factors that may affect their learning and living experiences,

specifically, young Chinese women's experiences, extending from participants who had just entered university to participants who already graduated. Thus, this study explored and revealed the current learning situation of Chinese international students, along with the 'face' culture-related challenges that they might have encountered, especially young females with their developing identities as English learners and speakers in the UK.

The contributions from participants in this thesis demonstrate the role of 'face culture' in developing Chinese international students' multiple identities. The Findings proposed in this study aimed to explain Chinese international students' academic and social experience in the UK and indicate specific needs among various elements of their experience, such as the ability to think critically, and issues around 'face' and culture, their developing identities. However, universities in the UK, especially the two universities used as contexts in this research, seem not to be dealing well with challenges and issues around Chinese 'face' culture that Chinese young students may encounter. Universities in both the UK and China were certainly not offering proper help and support for Chinese international students based on participants' responses in this research. Therefore, this research may contribute to an understanding of this issue and provide guidance and basic knowledge of 'face' culture, enabling staff and lecturers even the universities to better support and help Chinese international students.

The updated findings from this study, including the unique and challenging period of the Covid-19 pandemic have provided a more comprehensive understanding of Chinese international students' experiences. These findings offer valuable insights such as students' shifting and complex developing identities as English learners and speakers in the UK. Additionally, the study explores their perceptions of online learning during this time and also makes a comparison with face-to-face classroom settings, in order to allow students to have a more efficient learning experience.

During the conduct of semi-structured interviews in this study, I began to think and wonder: when I interviewed the participants, were they also observing my responses and giving answers they thought would 'give me face'? The reality is that their willingness to be open and honest and speak the truth of their hearts could be significantly influenced by my attitude and reactions towards them. Therefore, I constantly reminded myself to remain as objective as possible and to be aware of my attitude and behaviour throughout the whole interview. Offering my participants respect and no judgment of their experiences is the most important step to ensure the successful completion of interviews. This awareness and approach can also be beneficial to other researchers. When they deal with Chinese interviewees, they may need to check and look for the sign of whether participants given answers are influenced by the culture of 'face'. This is especially important when the researchers hold a higher social status and authority than the interviewees, such as in situations when the interviewees are students, and the researchers are teachers.

6.4 Limitations

Despite the amount of data and information collected from the participant interviews, there are still several limitations to this research. First of all, the selection of one research context was not ideal; this study would have been much more explicit and detailed if there had been the opportunity to contact and research in more than two Scottish universities, however, it would be much longer. With the limited time for PhD study, I was able to examine and recruit

participants from two universities in Scotland which resulted in some useful data. Secondly, it was conducted during the Covid-19 pandemic, which means I was not able to meet the participants face-to-face. I had to recruit and interview all participants online and found it challenging at times so had to re-interview the participants for clarity on two occasions. It might have been easier, and it might have made the participants more relaxed if I could have met them face to face. Furthermore, with the restrictions of the pandemic, I also had to meet supervisors and other PhD students online, which at times made it challenging to discuss issues in full. Thirdly, I also belonged to a previous MEd TESOL cohort, which was the target group for participants. As discussed in the Methodology Chapter, I knew some of the participants, so I could be referred to as an ‘insider’ researcher as discussed above. For an ‘insider’ researcher, it was easy to communicate and establish a close relationship with participants which might have allowed them to share their thoughts in a safer and more comfortable environment; however, it can also be considered to be a limitation, since I might have had similar experiences and might influence my objectivity and the results of this research. Although I was in the position of ‘insider’, I aimed at all times to maintain an objective stance, by ensuring that all information that informed the study reflected and represented the participants’ own ideas and views, as discussed in the methodology chapter. Furthermore, as I have discussed in both the Literature Review and Methodology Chapter, my participants were all young Chinese females, and the lack of male participants, therefore, means that gender as an important element may be a limitation. That is, this research cannot offer males’ experiences with ‘face’ culture, and the data may not be able to represent all Chinese international students in the UK. This research does not aim to explore the specific topic of gender, other than to acknowledge the complexity of gender within a broader context of identity.

6.4.1 Research context

The research context is considered one of the limitations as discussed above. The study would have been more detailed and thorough if there were more than two universities in the UK. However, the researcher considered the data collected from these two universities to be rich and in-depth.

The aim of this research is to uncover Chinese international students’ perceptions of ‘face’ culture and to examine the impact of ‘face’, also their perceptions of China English and the development identity of English speakers and learners. Therefore, by conducting this study, one outcome of the study is that the results would help non-Chinese students and teachers in the UK to understand Chinese international students and understand ‘face’ culture, in order to help them in their work with Chinese international students. The results of this study would improve the confidence and learning skills of Chinese international students by making them aware of the importance of ‘face’ culture. Although data collected from two universities in the UK may not reflect the whole of the Chinese international student community’s perceptions of ‘face’ in the UK, I managed to overcome the challenge of using two research contexts by discussing and analysing the Findings of each research question which were informed by the participant interviews. The participants’ responses were discussed in detail, and in order to clarify participants’ answers, additional questions were asked, as part of the semi-structured interviews, for clarity. Therefore, I considered that this challenge did not affect the outcome of this study.

6.4.2 The researcher’s positionality

The positionality of the researcher can be seen as an ‘insider researcher’ which was discussed

in the methodology chapter. Although the researcher's positionality as an 'insider researcher' might have influenced the design and the research data Findings (May & Perry, 2017). I created a more comfortable and safer environment during the interviews and gave the participants less pressure to respond through casual conversation in Chinese to relax the participants before the online interviews which were conducted in English.

Due to the positionality of the researcher, it was important to be reflective throughout the entire research process. In order to remain objective during the interviews and also data analysis, I made no assumptions before the interviews and used open questions and gave the participants time to respond. Therefore, the data was trustworthy, and carefully analysed by the researcher.

6.5 Reconsidering the research

If there was a chance to reconsider the research, I would have recruited participants from other subject areas rather than focusing on MEd TESOL. It might have allowed me to explore other Chinese international students' perceptions of 'face' culture and China English, also whether 'face' culture has an impact on them; comparing their subject areas with TESOL, their spoken language skills may not be such a priority for these students, however, their academic writing would be as equally essential. However, the data has already provided in-depth and rich information for this research. Therefore, I believe that involving more participants from different universities and majors in the UK will not be a necessity.

I would also like to undertake some further research. Due to the COVID pandemic, according to the data from participants in this research, some of the participants suggested they lacked the experience of face-to-face interactions with other non-Chinese students both inside and outside the university. In other words, as there were lockdowns and restrictions policies, participants in this research suggested that they were unable to have offline classes or meet other students; and since this research focused on Chinese international students' experiences related to 'face' culture, it might have affected the quality of this research if the participants lacked interactions or communications with others. In addition, it may also allow participants to compare and reflect on their previous learning experiences to the learning experiences after the pandemic.

6.6 Autobiographical reflection

6.6.1 Academic growth

The original plan of this research was to uncover whether 'face' culture and the notion of politeness have an impact on Chinese international students' authentic use of English. Then I realized this topic was too big to discuss, as the topic of the authentic use of English is too wide and it is very hard to explore in a short time. With the help of my supervisors, also by reading relevant academic articles and books, I changed the topic to uncover Chinese international students' perceptions of 'face' culture and also focused on their development as English learners and speakers in the UK. I also read widely about Chinese 'face' culture and had a better understanding of how other researchers examined Chinese international students in this related field.

The current literature focuses on discussing Chinese international students' learning motivation and their identity growth but topics around 'face' culture in the UK are rarely discussed in the existing literature. Therefore, I decided to discuss how 'face' culture affects Chinese international students in both academic and social contexts; The research aims to discuss how

to help local or non-Chinese people understand Chinese international students. I belonged to a previous MEd TESOL cohort and during the study, I realized many Chinese international students tended to keep quiet and lacked confidence when they did presentations in class. This made me wonder why they did not share their ideas, and how I or the universities could help Chinese international students. In addition, reading and researching related literature enabled me to clarify the concept of ‘face’ in order to help non-Chinese understand the term ‘face’.

6.6.2 Personal growth

I recognised my language skills had developed to an academic level through the research which also enabled me to identify my own strengths and weaknesses. I began to use more formal terms and academic words by understanding and reading other academic articles. However, due to the recent pandemic, I did not have any opportunity to attend conferences which I preferred to attend in person, which might have helped to improve my academic English by listening to others’ presentations as well as sharing my research with others. However, I’m already looking at the 2023 IATEFL Conference which will be taking place at Harrogate this spring. I believe this conference will bring some fresh ideas for me and help me improve my own research. I felt much more confident after presenting my work at the PhD transfer event where other PhD students and academic staff gave me feedback on the research.

I, as the researcher, have not always been confident in my writing skills. However, I feel that my academic writing level has significantly improved. In addition, when I came to the UK in 2017, the Scottish local accent was initially a huge challenge for me. I found it difficult to understand others both inside and outside the university. It was a challenge for me to be fully engaged in class because of the language barrier. In addition, I also found it hard to think critically and be an independent learner, sometimes it was even difficult to express my own ideas. With the help and support of my supervisors and classmates, I feel more confident and willing to share my ideas with others. Therefore, I feel my English writing skills along with oral English have improved significantly.

6.6.3 Challenges of the Covid-19 pandemic

This research was conducted during the Covid-19 pandemic which means that I did not have the opportunity to go back to China and interview participants in China. Participant recruitment and interviews took place during the lockdown which meant that I was restricted by laws at the time; because of the pandemic, a lot of Chinese students chose not to come to the UK but took online courses. Therefore, it was a challenge for me to recruit potential participants and carry out the interviews online rather than in person. In addition, due to the longer lockdowns of the Covid-19 pandemic, I had difficulty accessing the full extent of the library resources as the campus was temporarily closed. Moreover, planned meetings with other PhD students were also limited due to restrictions enforced during the pandemic. Relevant academic articles were accessed from the UWS library website and from my supervisors. With the help of my supervisors and in line with the Ethics policy at UWS, I was able to recruit enough participants who wanted to be part of this research. In addition, I managed to contact participants via Wechat and Teams to check their responses after the interviews, with their permission, which resolved this limitation.

In addition, the challenges of the Covid-19 pandemic were particularly rare and unusual, and it was especially difficult for Chinese international students to be so far away from their beloved friends and families. Most of the time, I just stayed alone like many of the other

Chinese international students in the UK, trying so hard to adjust to completely different ways of finding food and the restrictions of social interactions.

Moreover, the Covid-19 pandemic also brought huge economic pressures for both students and parents. Chinese students were not able to find part-time jobs to cover their costs and their parents were able to work because of the restrictions and laws in China, not to mention tuition fees and accommodation fees are considerably high. With all the negative news about Covid-19 and constant worrying about testing positive and getting affected by Covid-19. It has been a very difficult time for me and other students in the UK and certainly, it brought huge changes to all humans, but it also allowed me to become stronger and better at negotiating the issues which the Covid-19 pandemic brought. The learning experience for the research was also impacted by the personal challenge of coping with being restricted to home study. Staying at home for months had a negative impact on my mental and physical health. To cope with these challenges a daily routine was followed, which included set study time, eating well, regular exercise and frequent contact with family and friends in China via social media and video calls. The impact of the Covid-19 pandemic was huge and life-changing, but it also gave me plenty of time to be more reflective on my studies and improve my academic writing and learning skills.

6.7 Recommendations

6.7.1 Recommendations for academics in the UK

The Findings of this research suggest that university teachers in the UK do not have enough understanding of Chinese ‘face’ culture and how it impacts Chinese international students. Chinese international students may not have the opportunity to give feedback on their learning experiences in the UK. This study provides the Chinese international students’ comments on teaching methods and feedback in order to improve the learning process and experiences in the UK. It is important for teachers in the UK to have a better understanding of how to help Chinese international students develop their language skills and learning competence. That is to say, teachers in the UK should develop more awareness of the Chinese ‘face’ culture in order to help Chinese international students adapt to the UK teaching model better. Moreover, John (2016) argued that UK universities should provide all incoming staff and students with the opportunity to establish close links with existing students or staff in order to take full advantage of cross-cultural exchange. This means that universities should offer a platform to encourage and motivate international students and local students to interact in both academic and social contexts.

Therefore, to improve the effectiveness of Chinese international students’ learning, it is recommended that teachers in the UK encourage students to reflect on their learning and evaluate it so that the teachers have an understanding of the challenges. In this research, as a result of participants’ responses, it is recommended that teachers may need to adjust their expectations of Chinese international students, as many of them tend to be passive learners and not familiar with the teaching methods used in the UK. It is also important to remind UK teachers of Chinese ‘face’ culture and especially how it informs classroom interaction for Chinese international students.

6.7.2 Recommendations for Universities management in the UK and China

Based on the Findings of this study, the recommendations for universities in the UK and China are presented as follows:

6.7.2.1 Pre-sessional English courses

According to the participant's responses to the Findings of this study, they suggest that the teaching methods in the UK are very different from those in China as they found it hard to think critically and learn independently. Therefore, it is recommended that the universities in China should provide courses and funding to support students who want to study abroad. It is recommended that universities in the UK should also provide courses for Chinese international students to become familiar with the teaching style in UK university classrooms. This could be done in a separate area of PSE courses and could focus on Chinese international students, specifically on what criticality is and how it can be developed through peer work, group work and how that will inform academic writing. However, it can be very controversial: on one hand, classifying Chinese students separately might reinforce certain stereotypes, such as the notion that they need extra help to adapt to Western educational methods; on the other hand, creating a separate category for Chinese students might help them build a supportive community with their peers who are experiencing similar challenges, especially 'face'-related issues that may not be understood by other international students. These need to be carefully weighed against the potential negative consequences. Therefore, the real question should be whether the West fosters an educational environment beneficial to East Asian students to enable them to develop and demonstrate their abilities. Chinese students who are segregated might feel that they are being viewed as "different", negatively impacting their self-perception, as they may feel they are treated "differently" because of their identity as Chinese learners. This could result in decreased self-confidence, and even affect their academic performance and social interactions. Indeed, each student's learning background and ability to adapt can be different, and Western education approaches might not effectively meet their specific needs. Universities are important places for fostering diversity, and it may be better for every student to find their own pace, instead of expecting them to adapt to the new teaching methods and creating confusion. A more effective approach might be to provide broad support services ensuring all international students have equal opportunities to receive the help they need to adapt; students should be free to choose the PSE courses on which they learn, and all international students can have the opportunity to choose whether they want to stay with their own community or have a more cultural diversity group.

6.7.3 Recommendations for International students' support office

One of the Findings of this research suggested that participants did not know where they could get help with their studies. They further suggested that although universities in the UK have both Student Support Services and may have international support staff to help students solve their difficulties, some students are not aware of this when they first come to the UK. Participants in this research also suggested that some students may feel uncomfortable asking for help from Support Services, as they lack confidence in their ability to communicate fluently in English. Therefore, one recommendation is that staff be trained in how to interact with the international students, in particular, that they are made aware of 'face' culture. In addition, guidance and information should be given before students leave their own country, and support should also be offered by universities in the UK in terms of assisting students with personal issues. Therefore, it is recommended that this may take the form of a Mandarin / Chinese speaker who is employed specifically for this purpose. Because even though students may have

the required level of academic English skills, it may be much easier to access a discussion around the management of classroom behaviours.

In addition, Chinese international students often do not integrate well with other non-Chinese students ((Spencer-Oatey, Lifei, Dauber and Jing, 2017). Participants in this study also suggested that they lacked confidence in speaking English and making friends with other international students, and the COVID-19 pandemic made it even harder to go out and meet people. Therefore, if Chinese international students have more opportunities to communicate with other international students at the events held by universities in the UK, they may feel much more confident when they speak English in class with other non-Chinese international students. It can also give non-Chinese students opportunities to understand and learn about Chinese culture and Chinese international students. Understanding, support, and respect are thus essential to enable Chinese international students to negotiate such potential challenges around identity successfully, despite any intercultural differences and lack of understanding that may emerge. Universities can encourage the formation of student groups where Chinese students can connect with each other and with students from other backgrounds. These groups can provide a sense of community and belonging, as well as opportunities for cultural exchange and mutual support. Moreover, regular feedback mechanisms should be applied in order to understand the needs and concerns of Chinese students: surveys can provide valuable insights that help universities tailor their support services more effectively.

6.7.3.1 Mental health of students

Due to the recent pandemic, students may have felt isolated and lonely, according to the response of participants in this research; because of the lockdowns, they were not able to go out as they used to do. Universities in the UK should pay attention to Chinese international students' mental health since they are far away from home, and many are alone here. As discussed above, Chinese international students are impacted by 'face' and along with the pressure of 'loss of face', this may lead to issues with mental health. Therefore, universities and staff need to give Chinese international students emotional support and help when they have issues with their mental health, and it is also important that university staff direct them to support services when or where appropriate.

6.7.4 Recommendations for Language Support Opportunities

The participants of this research identified challenges with language as a barrier to their studying in the UK. The responses of participants in this study suggested that Chinese international students often have difficulties in communicating with other students, and with academic writing. Therefore, the Findings of this study recommend that opportunities and funding are offered to improve students' language skills by providing short-term study in the UK, which can give students a chance to be familiar with English usage in both academic context and social contexts. The Findings of this research also suggest that some Chinese international students had no previous experience of higher education in the UK, which means they need to adapt to the new learning approaches but also learn in a second language environment. Therefore, a further recommendation is for teachers to be aware of the different learning methods in order to help Chinese international students develop their confidence in speaking and academic writing.

6.7.5 Recommendations for Academics in China

Knowing little about the UK and the teaching methods is another common hindrance for Chinese international students in this study. Many of the participants claimed that there were no institutions in China that provided them with suggestions and advice for studying in the UK before they went abroad. Most of the teachers have no experience of studying abroad themselves, which does not help students prepare for their life in the UK. Therefore, it is recommended by this researcher that teachers in China should be offered opportunities to go abroad and the international education department of the Chinese university should also have teachers with experience in studying abroad to help students with their applications.

6.7.6 Recommendations for Chinese Universities

The Findings of this study show that the Chinese learning environment is different from the UK learning environment. “Chinese students often memorise textbooks to ensure accurate recall of information to cope with examinations” (Su, 2010, p.211), which reveals that Chinese students lack critical thinking skills which were also discussed by the participants in this study. Moreover, students learn English in order to pass the exam rather than using it authentically (Su, 2010); they do not have enough opportunities to speak English and practise their speaking skills. The Findings also suggested that participants in this study found that speaking English can lead to a loss of ‘face’ if they cannot be understood, which does not support the development of their confidence. Therefore, it is recommended that the Chinese pedagogical system needs to make changes and universities in China should focus on improving students' speaking skills rather than focusing only on exam results, and more importantly, helping students build confidence in speaking authentic English.

6.8 Suggestions for further research

This study highlights how ‘face’ impacted Chinese international students in both social and academic contexts. By discussing Chinese international students’ learning and living experiences in the UK, this study has provided potential directions for other researchers who may be interested in Chinese face culture. Participants in this research were unable to fully experience UK learning and social life, due to the restrictions of the recent Covid-19 pandemic. In order to have a better understanding of how face impacts Chinese international students in both social and academic contexts, there are suggestions for future research to have a deeper and more extensive analysis of this current research subject.

6.8.1 Changing cultural values in China

Most of the participants in this study suggested that ‘face’ had an impact on their social and study context, however, there were a few participants in this study who tended to be younger and implied that ‘face’ was no longer as important as it used to be. The younger generation of Chinese students may be more open and fearless about being themselves and are unlikely to be affected by the old traditional cultural values. In addition, there are more and more Chinese international students who come to the UK to study at a very young age, for example, Chinese students who attended high school in the UK, and years of study in the UK may change their perceptions. It would thus be important for further research to focus on the new generation, the changing cultural values in China, and Chinese students who came to the UK at a younger age.

6.8.2 Expanding the scope of the research

Although the data collected from this research was in-depth and rich enough for the current study, it would be important to collect data from a wider sample of Chinese international students across the UK to ensure that the Findings can be generalised and representative of this population of students. In particular rather than limiting recruitment to students from MED TESOL who will have a particular bias toward the importance of language and communication, which may influence their perception of Chinese ‘face’ culture, it would be vital to include students from a variety of academic disciplines and courses, as their views and perception of Chinese ‘face’ culture may differ from the participants in this research to the views of the current sample. In addition, future studies could also investigate how university teachers in the UK feel about Chinese face culture, whether they are aware of it, and how this influences their interactions with Chinese international students. Teachers’ attitudes toward Chinese international students and face culture should also be considered as one of the factors that may improve Chinese international students’ learning experience.

6.8.3 The impact of face culture on Chinese international students in different countries

As this study was focused on Chinese international students in the UK, Chinese international students in other countries may encounter the same challenge of ‘face’ as well. Different countries have different cultures, so if Chinese international students study in other Asian countries, for example, Japan and Korea, where they share very similar cultural values and Chinese international students may be understood better, because the concept of ‘face’ is embedded there. Even Chinese international students in other Western contexts, such as the USA and Canada, will likely have very different experiences from those in the UK. Future research, examining whether and how ‘face’ impacts Chinese international students in other countries and different environments would be helpful in understanding whether the current Findings are trustworthy and can be applied to all Chinese international students. In addition, future research could explore whether ‘face’ is unique in Chinese cultural values or if it also impacts other Asian students.

6.8.4 Face and disability support

As has been discussed above in section 7.6.2.4, Chinese international students may encounter problems with their mental health while studying in the UK, but they may also have learning disabilities. Reading comprehension can be a challenge for Chinese international students and especially for students with learning disabilities, “many students with learning disabilities struggle to comprehend text in school” (Hall-Mills & Marante, 2022, p.55). Although every university or college has a disability advisor or learning support coordinator who can help students with learning disabilities in higher education in the UK (Disability Support at college, 2022), this may not be the case in China. “While international standards have influenced the new regulations, China still imposes discriminatory obstacles for children with disabilities to be placed in mainstream schools” (Human Rights Watch, 2017). This may lead to a situation where learning disabilities, such as dyslexia, among Chinese international students may not have been identified before they went to study abroad. The Chinese educational system in which the emphasis is on rote learning will also contribute to the masking of any learning disabilities such as dyslexia, with individuals developing strategies to mask their difficulties, but which no longer work when they are faced with the demands of study at a UK university. Both Chinese students and university staff may think that they are not coping with their studies

because of language barriers when the actual problem may not be their grasp of the English language, but underlying learning disabilities. The students may find it hard to ask for help as they may feel a “loss of face” by letting others know about their learning disabilities and worry that they will be discriminated against. Further research should consider the impact of ‘face’ culture on Chinese international students with learning disabilities.

6.8.5 Face and Gender

As has been discussed in the Literature Review and Methodology Chapters, I was not able to find current literature specifically on how Chinese face culture and gender are linked. Therefore, this would be an area of interest for me and any further research. Gender and face culture may influence communication styles, and indeed, people’s behaviours in diverse cultural settings. Exploring specifically how Chinese ‘face’ culture operates for different genders and how face culture reinforces, or challenges, gender roles and expectations can help in understanding social dynamics and especially can help address gender discrimination. The focus on gender would provide more insights into how individuals develop and build their identities and position themselves in both academic and social contexts. This may enable Chinese international female students to speak out and serve as an addition to increasing the ‘face’- related feminist research studies in international education settings.

6.9 Conclusion

This research focused on the impact of ‘face’ culture on Chinese international students’ developing identity as English learners and speakers by discussing their learning and living experiences in the UK. In-depth and rich data was collected from semi-structured interviews and participants’ responses were analysed in detail and presented above.

In addition, in this concluding chapter, I also discussed the limitations of this research and ways to improve future research. The improvement and development of the researcher’s personal and academic life have also been discussed. Based on the Findings of this current study, implications from the Findings and recommendations for the universities and teachers in both the UK and China have been given in order to help Chinese international students’ need for a better learning experience and their own development. I intend that this study and the links to the academic resources provided will inspire future research into this topic.

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Appendices

Appendix 1 Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Name of department:

School of Education and Social Sciences, University of the West of Scotland

Title of the study: The impact of ‘face’ culture on Chinese international students’ developing identity as learners and speakers of English

Introduction

My name is Ximingle Liu, and I am conducting research for a PhD thesis at the University of the West of Scotland. I would now formally like to invite you to take part in my research study, but before making your decision, please take time to read this information sheet. If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact me. My contact detail are as follows:

- Email: [REDACTED]
- Telephone: [REDACTED]

Supervisor’s contact details:

- Dr Margaret Allan
- Email: [REDACTED]
- Telephone: [REDACTED]

What is the purpose of this research?

This study plans to analyse what 'face' culture is and the ways in which it can affect Chinese students’ developing identity as English learners and speakers. It aims to investigate how Chinese international students perceive ‘face’ culture in the context of Scotland.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been chosen because you fit the criteria of the participants I would like to interview. As you are a speaker of both English and Chinese and have the experiences of studying in the universities of Scotland, you would be an ideal participant.

Do you have to take part?

You do not have to take part in the study, and even if you do agree to take part, you may withdraw at any time. If you decide to withdraw, rest assured that any data collected up to the

point of your withdrawing from the study will be destroyed. Taking part or not taking part in the study will not impact your relationship with me in any way. If you decide to take part in this study, then you should let me know by **April 23rd, 2021**.

What will you do?

If you agree, you will be asked to take part in an interview with me which will be audio recorded. The interview will take place during the months of **April-May 2021**. You can be interviewed at a time and place that suits you. The interview will last approximately 45 minutes- one hour, and you will be invited to talk to me about:

- Your experiences of studying in Scotland.
- Your perceptions of ‘face’ culture and whether or not it affects your developing identity as learners and speakers of English.

What happens to the information?

The findings from this study will be included in my PhD thesis and may be published in the form of a report or article. However, your name will never be mentioned, and all participants will remain anonymous. The information that you provide me with will be kept for up to 10 years to allow for potential publication from the thesis at a future date. You are free to contact the researcher and withdraw your data up to the point of anonymization.

Who has reviewed the study?

The study has been reviewed by the Ethics Committee of the School of Education, UWS.

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

What happens next?

If you are happy to be involved in the study, then please let me know by the **23rd of April 2021** using the contact details provided above.

If you do not want to be involved in the study, then I would like to thank you for your attention.

After the study has been completed, a report of the findings will be available in electronic form. If you wish to receive a copy, please let me know and I will email it to you.

What if there is a problem?

Any complaint or concern about any aspect of the way you have been dealt with during the course of the study will be addressed; please contact Ximingle Liu Principal Investigator on [REDACTED]. In the first instance, you can also contact my supervisor Dr Margaret Allan at [REDACTED] Personal details withheld.

Will my taking part in the study be kept confidential?

Yes. Your details will be held in complete confidence, and we will follow ethical and legal practice in relation to all study procedures.

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet.

Appendix 2 Participant Consent Form

Consent Form: Participants (interview)

Name of department:

School of Education and Social Sciences,
University of the West of Scotland (UWS)

Title of the study:

The impact of ‘face’ culture on Chinese international students’ developing identity as learners and speakers of English

- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above study and the researcher has answered any questions to my satisfaction.
- I understand that taking part is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.
- I understand that I can withdraw my data from the study up to the point of anonymization.
- I understand that any information recorded during the study will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.
- I consent to being a participant in this study.
- I consent to being audio recorded as part of the study.

(PRINT NAME)	Hereby agree to take part in the above study
Signature of Participant:	Date

Appendix3

Interview Protocol and Interview Questions - Lecturers

Title of the study:

The impact of 'face' culture on Chinese international students' developing identity as learners and speakers of English

Introductory Statement for Online Zoom meeting:

We are now recording. Thank you again for agreeing to participate in this individual interview. Please remember that anything you say will be made anonymous in the transcription process and that you are free to stop participating at any time, and without giving explanations. You can also decline to answer questions. There is no penalty for declining to participate. I've also sent you Participation Information and this contains information about who to contact if you have any concerns or comments about today's interview.

Engagement

#	Questions:
1.	How long have you been teaching at this university? <ul style="list-style-type: none">• What programme do you teach on?
2.	Do you think that your students enjoy studying here? <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Why? Why not?

Exploration

#	Questions:
3.	Have your students commented that studying here is different from studying in China? <ul style="list-style-type: none">• If so, in what ways do they think is it different?• Tell me about any differences they have noticed in<ul style="list-style-type: none">– the teaching styles– the way students are involved in the lesson?
4.	Are there any challenges your students have met while studying here? <ul style="list-style-type: none">• If so, what are the challenges?
5.	Are you aware of the term "face" or "face culture" and do you understand it? <ul style="list-style-type: none">• If so, do you feel that "face" has an impact on your students in social or academic area of their lives?• Have you, or students, experienced any challenges related to "face culture"?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do you think that your students feel the impact of “face” while living and studying in Scotland?
6.	<p>How do your students feel they are perceived by you, as a teacher, and by their classmates?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do they feel positive about themselves as English learners and speakers? - Why? Why not? Do you expect them to engage in class, for example with you or other students? -If so: in what way(s)? -How do they feel about that?
7.	<p>Do you think studying Online benefits your students more than face to face class study?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If so, do you think they seem more confident expressing themselves online? Do they feel “face” has an impact on them during online study? Why do you think they are affected in this way?
8.	<p>Are you aware of the use of different languages among Chinese students?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do you know what “China English” is? -If so, what do you think of it? Do your students speak “China English”? Has “China English” affected their study or social life and is it related to “face”? -if so, in what way(s)?

Exit

#	Questions:
9.	What help would you like your students to have in order to enhance their studies in English both here and in China?
10.	Referring back to the title and aim of this survey, are there any other points which you would like to add which have not been included?

Thank you very much for your contribution today.

Appendix 4 Interview Protocol and Interview Questions- Students

Title of the study:

The impact of ‘face’ culture on Chinese international students’ developing identity as learners and speakers of English

Introductory Statement for Online Zoom meeting:

We are now recording. Thank you again for agreeing to participate in this individual interview. Please remember that anything you say will be made anonymous in the transcription process and that you are free to stop participating at any time, and without giving explanations. You can also decline to answer questions. There is no penalty for declining to participate. I’ve also sent you Participation Information and this contains information about who to contact if you have any concerns or comments about today’s interview.

Engagement

#	Questions:
1.	How long have you been studying in Scotland? <ul style="list-style-type: none">• What programme you are in?
2.	Do you enjoy studying here? <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Why? Why not?

Exploration

#	Questions:
3.	Is studying here different from studying in China? <ul style="list-style-type: none">• If so, in what ways is it different?• Tell me about any differences in<ul style="list-style-type: none">– the teaching style– the way students are involved in the lesson
4.	Are there any challenges you have meet while studying here? <ul style="list-style-type: none">• If so, what challenges have there been?
5.	Are you aware of the term “face” or “face culture” and do you understand it? <ul style="list-style-type: none">• If so, do you feel “face”has had an impact on you in social or academic areas of your life?• Have you experienced any challenges related to “face culture”?• Do you feel the impact of “face” while living and studying in Scotland?
6.	How do you feel you are perceived by your teachers and classmates? <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Do you feel positive about yourself as an English learner and speaker?

	<p>- Why? Why not?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are you expected to engage in class, for example with the teachers or other students? <p>-If so: in what way(s)?</p> <p>-How do you feel about that?</p>
7.	<p>Do you think studying Online benefits you more than face to face class study?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If so, do you feel more confident to express yourself online? • Do you still feel “face” has an impact on you even during the online study? <p>-If so, why do you think your study is affected in this way?</p>
8.	<p>Are you aware of the use of different languages among Chinese students?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you know what “China English” is? <p>-If so, what do you think of it?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you speak “China English”? • Has “China English” affected your studies or your social life and is it related to “face”? <p>-if so, in what way(s)?</p>

Exit

#	Questions:
9.	In future, what help would you like to enhance your studies in English both here and in China?
10.	Referring back to the title and aim of this survey, are there any other points which you would like to add which have not been included?

Thank you very much for your contribution today.

Appendix 5 Coding Categories

Pilot Study Results

T1= Pilot study participants1

T2= Pilot study participants2

S1= Pilot study participants3

S2= Pilot study participants4

Pilot Study Teachers' Data:

Participants	Selected Quotes	Themes	Subthemes
T1	Some students are initially confused by the way/teaching methods/organizing...set up in a different way here.	Different teaching methods as challenges to learning, language development and students' self-confidence	- Different class set up in here and China
T1	Students are expected to interact with teachers but also with each other... students are surprised that they are expected to contribute to the classroom	Challenges to learning and language development	- Chinese international students are used to being to be passive learners
T1	Students feel embarrassed and don't want to contribute to the class... working with peers or groups... maybe because of the levels of language?	Challenges to learning and language development	- Chinese international students tend to be inactive learners
T1	The loss of face and... students may feel losing face if they speak publicly and even in small groups... they are quieter and certainly aware of face culture	Challenges to learning, language development and self-confidence	- 'Face' has an impact on their study and students worry their lack of interaction may reflect on their marks. - Students' levels of spoken language is low because they do not want to engage, and their spoken language may suffer
T1	At the end of the year(semester), most of the students felt much more comfortable about speaking in the class and engage with their classmates	Essential factors for learning and self-development and language development	- Develop self-confidence - Results in positive feedback from the other Chinese students -Develops their language

T1	China English may be the reason that some students are reluctant to speak out in class, they feel this variety of English is not as good as the English other students are using...	Challenges to learning, language development and self-confidence	-Lack of confidence in their spoken English -Confidence in this variety of English which is related to 'face'
T1	There should be a course before they leave China to help students and prepare them to develop their language skills...to engage in the class and why 'face' culture is so important to Chinese students	Support for learning and self-confidence and language development	-Pre-sessional courses are essential - More attention should be given to understanding face culture – in both Chinese International students and staff at the host institution (staff training?)
T2	Students without previous experience of studying in the UK can be surprised by the teaching methods here, they expect me to give the answers... the expectations are different	Challenges to learning and language development	-Different teaching approaches and expectations of those approaches -Students feel frustrated and lack experience of studying in English-speaking countries.
T2	Encourage students to apply the knowledge to real-world contexts	Efforts for students' development (what students need to do) / (students' work to develop learning, language, and self-confidence)	-Opportunities to build confidence - Practise authentic language
T2	Students can be very scared with teaching practice and doing presentations...it is easier to just hang out with other Chinese students	Challenges to learning and language development and self-confidence	-Afraid of losing 'face' -Lack of confidence

T2	Ask students to reflect critically... that is when 'face' is really important to Chinese students... they are worried if they show the teachers their negative side it may affect their marks	Efforts for students' development (what students need to do) / (students' work to develop learning, language, and self-confidence)	-Chinese international students lack the ability to reflect critically and to be self-aware -Face has an impact on their study; their anxiety may impact their learning
T2	Chinese students come from China where face culture is a big thing... students are young and have little or no experience of teaching English, so they can be intimidated	Challenges to learning and language development and self-confidence	-Understanding of 'face' is important, there are risks of losing face -Students are negative about the experience of teaching practice
T2	Chinese students and non-Chinese are not mixed sometimes, and Chinese students can be very insecure, I offered to help and explain things a little bit more, they accepted...	Efforts for students' improvement (what students need to do) / (students' work to develop learning, language, and self-confidence)	-Chinese international students tend to be passive learners - Support from teachers can help (teachers need to be reflective, too?)
T2	Online study can be easier to hide, it is easy to avoid losing face than face to face teaching but it is hard for teachers to notice things and see things...	Challenges to learning and language development and self-confidence	Online study is a hindrance: -To students, who can avoid losing face -To teachers, as they may not be aware of the difficulties students may have
T2	Students try to avoid China English, they see China English as a bad thing...focus on grammar and oral English is their weakness	Challenges to learning and language development and self-confidence	-Variety of English (China English) can be a pressure for Chinese international students - Self-confidence (perceptions of language status)
T2	It is difficult for students to balance accuracy and oral fluency, so they say nothing if they are not sure about things	Challenges to learning and language development and self-confidence	-Students are insecure and afraid of losing face
T2	If before they come to the UK, there can be more help that focuses on oral fluency, speaking, and listening skills, that will be very beneficial.	Support for the development of learning, language, and self-confidence	-Need for pre-arrival courses -Help Chinese international students feel confident of learning in Scotland

Pilot Study Students' Data:

Participants	Selected Quotes	Themes	Subthemes
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S1	Study here in Scotland, we don't have too many classes, lecturers won't tell you what to do, what not to do, we need to be independent, studying in China was on the contrary... I did not know it before I came, and it is hard to say what one is better...	Challenges of different teaching methods	-Students' independence in learning is needed in Scotland but not in China
S1	I believe that every Chinese international student is aware of the concept of 'face', and I don't know about others but it sure did has an impact on me. We have been living in a country where your parents will compare you with other children, and in school, your teacher will compare you with other students, and not mention the whole society... no one ever talks about 'face' but their actions and behaviours do.	'Face' as a challenge to Chinese students in the UK of developing identity as English learners	- 'Face' has an impact on Chinese international students -Students have a lifelong awareness of 'face' -The impact of "face" deeply rooted in students' identity
S1	I can feel 'face' has an impact on my social life, but not much on my study. When I came here, I was afraid of making friends with other students who are non-Chinese and I did not go to any parties where I may need to speak English ... I'm worried that other English speakers may find out my English is poor and I may make mistakes, so as to not to lose 'face', I chose not to communicate or interact with other non-Chinese students here... cause we do not need to speak English or worry about making mistakes...	'Face' as a challenge to Chinese international students	-Lack of confidence in their spoken English caused by the awareness of 'face'. -The implications of 'face' hinder students from speaking and developing English - The implications of 'face' also hinder students' social life, self-confidence and self-identity.
S1	I was not engaged too well in class, because my English level is low, I cannot fully understand lecturers and other students... and I only ask help from Chinese students if I had any questions... most of the time, I only listen to others' ideas but not speak... because I was showing politeness and giving them 'face', even I have different opinions, I won't say it, cause I don't like conflicts or arguments. Besides, If I'm wrong, I will lose my 'face' in front of the whole class... I'm not quite positive in class, if lecturers do not ask me questions then I will not share my opinions willingly.	'Face' as a challenge to learning, language development and self-confidence	-Chinese international students tend to be passive learners - A reluctance to ask for help from the teacher or other non-Chinese students - The notions of politeness and 'face' also hinder students from sharing their opinions.
S1	I will use China English, I think it is easy for non-Chinese to understand and also for other Chinese to understand, I feel very positive about this English diversity... if no one points out my mistakes right away in public and make me lose 'face'.	The importance of recognising China English as a diverse form of English	-Some of the students are comfortable using China English - The impact of 'face' causing students' anxiety about using 'imperfect' English

S1	<p>When Chinese students first came here, they can be divided into even small groups for discussion, for example, 1V1 or 1v2, so they may not feel that much pressure and they can force themselves to talk since there only two/three people in a group... cause you do not need to worry about losing 'face' in public, small groups give more privacy than bigger groups, it makes me feel like a casual small talk rather than a formal debate, because sometimes in a big group, other students may have different opinions and may lead to arguments...</p>	<p>Support for students' development (what students need to do) / (students' work to develop learning How students can support their own language development (what lecturers and universities need to do to help students develop their learning) 'Face' as a challenge for Chinese international students' language development, learning and self-confidence</p> <p>The notions of 'face' can be a challenge to students' learning</p>	<p>-Opportunities to build confidence - Authentic language environment can help students develop their language skills</p>
S1	<p>After years and years of studying here, I can feel my English is better than I first came here. But still, even now sometimes, I will worry about losing 'face', I still do not want to have communication or interact with locals even just small talks, because I do not want to make mistakes and lose 'face', especially when they know I have been here for a long time, but my English is still not good enough.</p>	<p>'Face' as a challenge to Chinese international students' language development, social life and self-confidence, self-identity Language development after time in the UK</p>	<p>- The impact of 'face' has been deeply rooted in their consciousness, even studying abroad for years, they still can feel the impact</p> <p>-Students recognized the development in their language after a time</p>
S2	<p>I like studying here, compare to China, I feel less stressed(mark, rank, jobs) and you can exactly learn something rather than just pass the tests... because in China, your mark, school, job and your state represent you, you are consistently compared with others, if you are not good enough, you will lose 'face' and your parents and families also will be affected.</p>	<p>The positive impact of studying in the UK on Chinese international students 'Face' as a challenge to Chinese international students' development, self-identity</p>	<p>-Develops their language and learning -Less pressure on behaviours and involution ("a race to the bottom")</p>

S2	In China, lecturers are the centre and most of the time, students are not expressing their ideas, but here is completely different, in Scotland, lecturers expect students have their own thoughts... there is no absolute right or wrong... I prefer the way here because it allows me to share my ideas without worrying about causing others(lecturers) to lose 'face'... in China, if your idea is different from lecturers or you find your teacher was wrong, then you need to keep it to yourself because of the notion of politeness, you cannot point it out and make lecturers lose 'face'...it may reflect on your mark.	'Face' as a challenge to learning and language development 'Face' as a challenge to students' critical thinking	-Different teaching approaches and expectations of those approaches - Expectations of students' behaviours and students' independent thinking
S2	When I first got here, I cannot 100% or fully understand lecturers and other students, and the way we do homework or assessments are different from China... how to communicate with group members and how to write dissertations... it was overwhelming at the beginning, I did not know where to start, it was stressful, but it did get better... and I was worried about losing 'face' at first because other students (Non-Chinese) seem to know what to do, but we don't ...	'Face' as a challenge to learning and language development Different methodologies in China and the UK	-Students lack experience in studying in English speaking countries - Students do not have experience in understanding lecturers; and different expectations can cause stress
S2	I think every Chinese knows about 'face', I can feel 'face' has an impact on study but not my social life, for example, choosing a famous university and major... your mark and rank... before I came here, my parents and I were discussing which university/major is better, the rank of the university and I think these all connected and related to 'face'... to make me and my family look "good".	'Face' as a challenge to learning and language development and self-confidence 'Face' as a challenge to learners' identity	- Students afraid of losing 'face' - 'Face' affects student's choices related to learning and their behaviours
S2	I love communicating with others and online study has its' limitation... some students may not feel comfortable opening the camera, so I cant see their body language and other things... but I didn't have much experience on online learning, because I'm doing my PhD research, I don't really have classes.	Challenges of online learning and language development	-Negative experience of learning online - The communicative clues that assist interaction in-person conversation are missing - Online learning may allow students to save 'face' because they choose not to use the camera
S2	I feel positive about China English, it's a diversity of English, I don't feel China English affects my life, maybe sometimes	The importance of recognising China English as a	-Positive perceptions about China English

	I used China English and I didn't notice it but others(locals) may notice that... but I don't care if I make mistakes, if you don't speak English, you will never learn... Of course, I was worried about losing 'face' at first, but the reason why I'm here is to learn English if I don't speak it or use it in an authentic way then what am I doing here, so I speak it anyway...	diverse form of English 'Face' as a challenge to students' language development, learning and self-confidence	- Losing 'face' can affect students' willingness to speak English
S2	Before students come to the UK, there can be more help on their speaking, and when Chinese students come here, hope other local students can be patient and kind to them...	Support for Chinese international students' development (what lecturers, other non- Chinese students and universities need to do to help students develop their learning)	- Need for pre-arrival courses - Need for more support to enable students to feel confident learning in Scotland - The assumption that help will be needed in the understanding of other variety of English

Discussion

In this pilot study, two students were interviewed, and the researcher has coded their interviews, please see Appendix 5. There are two main themes generated from the coding process of students' interviews which are '*face as a challenge, the positive nature of China English and supporting students.*' The themes and subthemes that were based on this study's research questions are discussed as followed.

'Face' as a challenge to learning, language development is the most discussed theme that underpins several subthemes discussed by students. Two students suggested that several challenges caused by 'face' prevent them from learning, language development, self-identity development and build self-confidence, as Participant 3 said: "so as to not to lose 'face', I chose not to communicate or interact with other non-Chinese students here...and Participant 4 said that "I was worried about losing 'face' at first because other students (Non-Chinese) seem to know what to do, but we don't ...". However, two students shared different experiences about the ways 'face' affected them. Participant 3 emphasised that 'face' has an impact on her social life but not on studying. Participant 3 suggested that the fear of making mistakes while speaking English made her lose 'face'. The anxiety of losing 'face' hindered the participant from making friends with native speakers and other non-Chinese students. The other participant emphasised that 'face' affected her study but not on social life. In order to not lose 'face', Participant 4 worried about the rank of the University, and her grades and marks, and a good job after graduating. In China, your status is a way to give yourself 'face'; if your status is considered low then you will feel like losing 'face'. Moreover, they both mentioned that their perceptions of China English are very positive. Both of them use China English, and they recognised China English as a diverse form of English, they do not feel losing 'face' while using China English, but they will feel lose 'face' if someone points out their mistakes in public.

In addition, they both highlighted that the teaching method is very different here from China; students are expected to be more independent and show critical thinking. They both agree that universities and lecturers here and in China can do more to help students from China studying in the UK, in terms of pre-arrival courses.

As for the lecturers' pilot study, two lecturers were interviewed. There are three main themes generated from the coding process of lecturers' interviews which are "*challenges to learning and language development and self-confidence; essential factors for the development of learning, language and self-confidence; and support for students' improvement.*" The themes and subthemes arose from this study's research questions and are discussed as followed.

"*Challenges to learning and language development and self-confidence*" is the most discussed theme that underpins several subthemes discussed by lecturers. Two lecturers discussed several challenges that prevent students from learning a language and build self-confidence in class. For example, class set-up, different teaching approaches. Participant 1 suggested that "students are expected to interact with lecturers but also with each other... students are surprised that they are expected to contribute to the classroom". Participant 2 said that "students without previous experiences of studying in the UK can be surprised by the teaching methods here, they expect me to give the answers... the expectations are different." Chinese international students tend to be passive learners is discussed by the two lecturers as noted in the subtheme. They also discussed that Chinese students lack confidence in their oral English, they are worried about their English level which makes them reluctant to engage in classroom and group discussions. The two lecturers also highlighted that losing 'face' and Chinese 'face' culture hinder students from group discussions and presentations. Moreover, they both discussed that Chinese international students tend to see China English as a bad thing, participant 2 suggested that "Students try to avoid China English, they see China English as a bad thing... focus on grammar and oral English is their weakness.", which can be one of the reasons that Chinese students appear not to be engaged and reluctant to speak. Further discussions suggest that China English can be a pressure for Chinese students in the classroom, they may not engage in class or group discussions just to avoid speak China English.

This pilot study helped the researcher to better explore the aim of the study and also to reframe the research questions. It helped the researcher assess the feasibility of these questions and identify potential problems. This pilot study aimed to test the possibility of the researcher's initial focus on 'face' culture, the notions of politeness and students' attitude towards 'China English', rather than achieve any substantive findings (Peat et al. 2002). The results of this pilot study were encouraging, which helped the researcher identify key themes and subthemes for the main research. Some questions did not function as well as respected and did not allow students to fully disclose the thoughts and experiences of the participants. Hence, the researcher amended some questions based on the answers of the participants in order to explore more information.

Furthermore, although the discussions in the pilot study were encouraging and very interesting, the researcher still found that participants were not able to provide all answers to these questions, because they lacked relevant experiences, for example, the interview question which asked about lecturers to talk about students' social life. Similarly, in-depth qualitative interviews are needed to probe participants' thoughts on the culture of Chinese 'face' and 'Chinese English'.

The results of the pilot study enabled the researcher to narrow the research questions for this study, and also to explore participants' perception of 'face'. This pilot study also allowed the researcher to realize that the semi-structured interview can impede the expressive capacity of participants; participants (students) would be more engaged if they saw the interviews as informal conversations.

Interviews conducted as part of the pilot study confirmed that this was an appropriate method for developing responses to the 'face' culture questions; as well as for providing guidance and exploring questions in depth.

Reference

Peat, J., Mellis, C., Williams, K. and Xuan W. (2002) Health Science Research: A Handbook of Quantitative Methods, London: Sage.

Interview Results

S1=Participant1 (University A)

S2=Participant2 (University A)

S3=Participant3 (University A)

S4=Participant4 (University A)

S5=Participant5 (University B)

S6=Participant6 (University B)

S7=Participant7 (University B)

S8= Participant8 (University B)

Participants' Data- University A:

Participants	Selected Quotes	Themes	Subthemes
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S1	<p>The teachers and staff here are very friendly and helpful, and the learning environment is very relaxing, the course is of medium difficulty. Some of the classes were interesting, not boring, and group learning provided me with more opportunities to connect with people from different countries.</p> <p>In China, teachers are the centre, but here students are the centre of study, teachers expected students to be independent and have their own ideas. In class, teachers want to hear more different ideas rather than we all agree on just one idea.</p>	<p>Different teaching methods as opportunities.</p> <p>Challenges to students' independent learning</p>	<p>-Different teaching methods in the UK and China</p> <p>-Group study offered further opportunities</p> <p>-Participant1' independence in learning and critical thinking is valued.</p>
S1	<p>When I first came here, because of the high level of internationalization, people from different regions spoke different English in class, including the tutor. It took me some time to get used to the accents. But I was afraid to ask them to say it again, I didn't want them to sense that I didn't understand, I didn't want to lose 'face', or let them think all Chinese students are bad at speaking English and lose all Chinese students' 'face'.</p>	<p>'Face' as a challenge to Chinese students in the UK.</p> <p>The impact of "face" is deeply rooted in students' identity</p>	<p>-'Face' has an impact on Chinese international students' study and social life</p> <p>-'Face' as an indicator of national identity</p>
S1	<p>Yes, of course, I'm aware of 'face'. I believe 'face' is something that we can experience every day in our daily life, school or home, it is common. To me, the whole concept of 'face' including 'lose face' or 'gain face' is very personal, and it is an internal feeling, it doesn't need other people to emphasize it.</p> <p>For me, I feel 'face' had an impact on my social life more than my study. In terms of study, I don't feel much about 'face'. Some people may feel that they will 'lose face' if they fail to answer questions in front of many people or fail to pass the exam, but in my opinion, these are very normal phenomena. But in everyday social life, 'face' does have a big impact on me. For example, when I go shopping, and I have trouble communicating with others, even after the staff explained many times and I still cannot understand it, that is one of the situations I feel 'lose face'. I also feel embarrassed and 'lose face' when I'm late for class, because those things will affect other people's opinions about me.</p>	<p>'Face' is embedded in Chinese students' interactions</p> <p>'Face' as a challenge to Chinese international students' social life, language development and self-confidence, self-identity.</p>	<p>-Participant1 has awareness of 'face'</p> <p>-The implications of 'face' may hinder students from speaking and developing English, also their developing identity as English Language learners in the UK.</p> <p>-The awareness of 'face' may affect students' self-confidence and their ability to communicate in English; and in social contexts</p>
S1	At the beginning of the first semester, I	'Face' as a	-Chinese international

	<p>wasn't familiar with my classmates and these teaching methods, so I tend to be quiet and passive, so I won't make mistakes and 'lose face' but after a time, I started to express myself and my classmates were willing to do group works with me, cause I'm here to study, if I don't speak English or engage I can never learn anything.</p> <p>I think group discussion is very good. However, there can be a problem, that is, over time, these few group members tend to form a small group, it is easy for me to be 'lazy', as members of the group know each other very well and expect those who speak English better to speak more, so I do not need to speak or even to engage. Thus, I think random groups may be better than fixed groups.</p>	<p>challenge to learning, language development and self-confidence</p>	<p>students tend to be passive learners in a new environment, but this may change after a time.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The notions of 'face' may also hinder students from sharing their opinions and engaging in class; it may also change their behaviour
S1	<p>Yes, sometimes I may speak China English, but I think this is very normal. It is a problem that many non-native speakers of English may have because the grammar system and expression habits of the native language will affect the output of English. I found it is very common. Just like the accent problem, but if the listener can understand what you're trying to say then it is not a problem.</p> <p>English is for communication, to understand each other's ideas, rather than to express yourself without error. When I speak China English, I probably don't realize that. If the listener can understand what I mean and give me feedback, then my goal is achieved. But if he/she doesn't understand, I will feel anxious, afraid of 'losing face' or expressing my thoughts again.</p>	<p>The importance of recognising China English as a diverse form of English</p>	<p>-Participant1 is comfortable using China English</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It can affect students' output - It can demand more of the group members; this has implications for the teacher in setting up group work who should try to involve and encourage better group interaction? The 'importance of a listener paying attention - The behaviour of the group participants is important <p>- The impact of 'face' causing students' anxiety about using 'imperfect' English</p>
S1	<p>I think the most important thing about this learning experience here is that the teacher will guide us to express ourselves with confidence. Don't care about right or wrong or 'face', just say</p>	<p>Support for students' development (what students need to do) / (students'</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Importance of the role of the teacher -The notions of 'face'

	<p>what you think. Although you may make a lot of grammar mistakes or speak China English in public speech, no one in the class would laugh at you, teachers also shared many stories with us to encourage us to continue learning.</p> <p>As far as I am concerned, listening is very important, because in many cases, I cannot fully understand the whole sentence said by others, which will lead to my misunderstanding, so I have to make sure again and again, also, different accents also make it harder for me to understand. This process of repeating words again and again, makes me feel less confident, which will make me 'lose face'. I hope there can be courses to help me develop my listening and help me get used to different accents, especially Scottish accents.</p>	<p>work to develop learning How students can support their own language development (what teachers and universities need to do to help students develop their learning) 'Face' as a challenge for Chinese international students' language development, learning and self-confidence</p>	<p>can be a challenge to students' learning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Authentic language environment can help students develop their language skills but studying in a multilingual context can also be a challenge. -it is important for students to overcome this, with the help of the teacher
S1	<p>I think a lot of Chinese students tend to cluster together in class and only speak Chinese, so they won't 'lose face'. In my opinion, they are avoiding learning English and are afraid to face English communication, which exacerbates the 'China English' speaking phenomenon...</p> <p>After a year of study here, I can feel I have become more confident than I first came here, I certainly feel my English is better, and I can understand more even with accents.</p>	<p>'Face' as a challenge to Chinese international students' language development, social life and self-confidence, self-identity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The impact of 'face' even when they came abroad, they can still feel the impact of 'Face' on their social life and study - China English as a source of embarrassment; 'accent shame' - Complicating impact of 'face' on students' return to China <p>-Students recognized the development in their language after a time</p>
S2	<p>I really enjoyed studying here, because I met a lot of new friends and most of them are Chinese, teachers are very patient with me, students here are more active and positive compared with students in China, they are willing to speak and share their thoughts, and teachers will not judge them or argue, which also drives me to express my ideas, I feel safe to speak my ideas without worrying how others may think of me, but sometimes I still have the concern of 'losing my face', especial when I cannot fully understand what others were saying.</p>	<p>The positive impact of studying in the UK on Chinese international students</p> <p>'Face' as a challenge to Chinese international students' development.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The learning environment is very relaxing which encouraged students to develop their language and learning -Importance of the role of the teacher -Potential embarrassment

S2	<p>Teachers here will not teach a lot or have lots of ‘formal’ textbooks, they were trying to help students to explore knowledge on themselves, but in China, teachers talk a lot and more details, they are the centre of learning, not students...sometimes I wasn't fully engaged in class, because when I cannot understand what others and teachers were saying, I can be very distracted and lose the interest of listening, but I will not ask them to explain or repeat it because it will waste their time, and I want to be polite...My classmates and teachers are extremely kind and patient with me, even though I do not speak English very well, they are all willing to understand me and help me express my thoughts... but I will feel embarrassed because I don't want to bother others...</p>	<p>‘Face’ as a challenge to learning and language development.</p>	<p>-Different teaching approaches in UK and China</p> <p>- Participant1 does not have experience in understanding teachers and other international students</p> <p>-The notion of politeness embedded in ‘Face’ may affect the development and learning of students</p> <p>- Importance of the role of the teacher in developing a nurturing learning space</p>
S2	<p>I didn't feel ‘face’ impacted my study, because my classmates and teachers will not judge me and they all try to help me with my study... but I can feel it affect my social life, as most of the time I hang out with Chinese students. We all came from the same cultural background, we are all aware of ‘face’, sometimes I don't know how to refuse my friends or I don't want them to ‘lose face’, I will pretend to enjoy something and willing to do the things that I actually don't want to, just to ‘keep their face’... for example, sometimes I feel tired and just want to stay at home, but my friends ask me to go shopping, I will still go with them.</p>	<p>The positive impact of studying in the UK on Chinese international students</p> <p>‘Face’ as a challenge to social life</p>	<p>-The students received help and encouragement from teachers and classmates</p> <p>-The perception that teachers ‘judge’</p> <p>-The ‘face’ pressure may come from others who have the same cultural background (other Chinese students) in their social life.</p> <p>- Impact on personal identity and behaviour</p>
S2	<p>There are some situations I may feel the impact of ‘face’... When everyone seemed to be listening to me, I would worry that I cannot speak well and delay everyone's progress and time... I will feel ‘lose face’ because my ability to speak English is low... so I prefer to learn by myself rather than speak out and share my ideas with other students.</p>	<p>‘Face’ as a challenge to learning and language development and self-confidence</p>	<p>- Afraid of losing ‘face’ and the notions of politeness</p> <p>- ‘Face’ affects student's choices related to learning and their behaviours</p>

S2	I don't think the online study is effective. It's easier for me to be lazy in online courses, I don't even need to open my camera, and teachers won't see me, besides online study is really boring. People can't communicate properly, we have to speak one by one, or like me, I usually don't say anything, unless I was asked to...	Challenges of online learning and language development	-Negative experience of learning online - Online learning may allow students to save 'face' because they may choose not to use the camera - impact on students' behaviour
S2	I know 'China English' and I also speak it. My only concern is that others may not understand me, but I'm not worried about 'China English' itself or the accent I may have, 'China English' is also a diversity of English , just like 'Indian English' or other diversities. I'm not a native speaker, and I don't care if I speak like one or what others may think of me... When teachers kindly correct my usage of English, I'm fine with it... but if someone points out my grammar mistakes, I will feel 'lose face' and afraid of speaking English publicly...	The importance of recognising China English as a diverse form of English The level of losing 'face' may affect students' language development, learning and self-confidence	-Positive perceptions about China English - The importance of the role of the teacher - Losing 'face' can affect students' willingness to speak English
S2	Through my own experience, the help and understanding from my classmates and teachers are really important, they encouraged me to be more active and willing to speak English. I would suggest a pre-arrival course for students to adapt the teaching methods here. From my point of view, I suppose other students from Europe may have similar teaching approaches, but we as Chinese international students weren't familiar with those... Studying abroad especially in western countries are becoming more and more common for Chinese people, but it seems the western world still does not have a better understanding of Chinese people and Chinese culture. Maybe there are also needs for both sides to communicate and understand each other...	Support for Chinese international students' development (what teachers, other non-Chinese students and universities need to do to help students develop their learning)	- Need for pre-arrival English and English culture courses - Need for more support for students to feel confident learning in Scotland - Implications for teachers of Chinese International students - The assumption that help will be needed in the understanding of each other's culture

Participant Data – University A:

Participants	Selected Quotes	Themes	Subthemes
S3	I enjoy studying here. Campus facilities are perfect, the environment is quiet and comfortable, suitable for students to study, also teachers are patient to	Different teaching methods as	-Importance of the role of the teacher in developing a nurturing learning space

	<p>answer students' questions, care about students...not just care about their study, but also care about the difficulties you may have in your life.</p> <p>In China, the courses are very focused on details, for example, the English major has English listening, reading, writing, and grammar, speaking classes, almost covered everything... but in the UK, most courses are focused on the big picture, we learn things through sharing ideas and experiences, such as the course 'Global Language in the World'. Taking English major as an example, examinations in China are mainly objective questions, most of the questions have fixed answers, but here, we write essays and can be more subjective, independent learning is required, and you can write basically whatever you want.</p>	<p>opportunities.</p> <p>Importance of the role of the teachers</p>	<p>-Different teaching methods in here and China</p> <p>-Students' independence in learning is expected</p>
S3	<p>When I first came here, my oral English was not good and I was afraid to speak in class or public, maybe it is because I don't want to feel embarrassed, and that 'embarrassment' is probably what our Chinese people called 'lose face'. I am not familiar with the course arrangement, and especially for some 'professional' courses, I need to preview. I also have some difficulty understanding what teachers have taught, part of the reason is that my English skill is poor, but also some of the courses is a little bit difficult for me...</p>	<p>Challenges to Chinese international students' learning</p>	<p>-'Face' may have an impact on students' learning and confidence</p> <p>- It can affect students' input and output</p>
S3	<p>I think I'm always aware of the concept of 'face' even I'm just a child, cause you can hear people talk about it or 'feel' it and also your families may talk about it... but the first time, I ever feel 'face' is when I'm in primary school as a teenager when teachers asked you to answer questions if I gave the wrong answer, I will feel embarrassed and 'lose face'... when I'm a teenager, or younger, I have strong self-esteem, and I will feel lose my "face" because of my poor exam results or teachers criticize me in class... but when I get older, I care less about those things, and the sense of shame or 'lose face' is getting weaker and weaker, that is what they say 'thick face'... especially, when I took The National</p>	<p>'Face' as a challenge to Chinese student</p>	<p>-The impact of 'face' may cause students' anxiety.</p> <p>- Long-term impact and awareness of Face</p> <p>-The impact of 'face' may impact their confidence and even their identity</p> <p>- The notion of Face can decrease with</p>

	College Entrance Examination, parents can really give me a lot of pressure, at this time "face" is more important to them than ever, so the feeling of 'lose face' or the anxiety of 'lose face' is particularly obvious during high school entrance examination and the national college entrance examination... I don't want them to 'lose face' but I was so afraid I may fail them, which also made me want to escape... I didn't know how to face them		time/time spent in a non-Chinese environment -The impact of the "face" can also cause stress between parents and students. - the impact of "face" on students' emotions
S3	When I came here, to the UK, I found that most western people do not really care about how others may think of them, they pay more attention to their own ideas, and they are free and with an open mind. it is great, we should be able to be who we are... but as a Chinese, I find it hard to truly be myself, I still worry about others' judgements and what they may think of me... and of course, there must be people who care about "face", for example, you can see there are some gentlemen and ladies dressed well and fancy. Here "face" should be a complimentary term, representing a sort of etiquette and elegance.	'Face' as a challenge to Chinese students	-'Face' may have an impact on personal identity and behaviour -'Face' also has a positive side.
S3	As for the study, we are here to learn, we should break the 'face', and speak English as often as we can. Those mistakes can help us develop, and how can we learn a language without using it? I think group study is a good way to learn, 3 or 4 people as a small group, and make sure everybody has the right to talk, the exchange of ideas leads to more ideas, we may never have the changes to talk to people from different countries and learn different culture, and sharing interesting exciting experiences, it will make you have an open mind, and willing to embrace everything... I'm lucky, my teachers and classmates are good listeners and nice to me. I really cherish the learning experience here in the UK, it is an experience I never had before in China...	Opportunities for Chinese international students	-Participant3 was aware of 'face' but refused to let 'face' affect the study and social life. -The behaviour of the group participants is important -Importance of the role of the teacher
S3	I think face-to-face classes are more efficient, but it depends on the autonomy of the students. I haven't had the experience of online classes yet, so	The importance of recognising China English as a diverse form of English	-Participant3 feels comfortable using China English

	<p>for me, face-to-face classes are more efficient than online learning... For me, sometimes I will worry about my China English, but as long as the listeners understand then it is fine, it is a tool for communication and China English is a diversity of English, so if I can be understood, then I will not be worried about my China English, but if they cannot understand then I will feel stressed and not willing to speak English...but no, I don't feel 'lose face' using China English, I will be carefully and cautiously using my words in an academic environment or checking my grammar during writing, but in social life or daily life, I'm cool with it...cause English is not my first language, people will understand that, as long as they know what I'm saying, then that's fine...</p> <p>However, China English can affect my study, when I wrote papers and dissertations, I still want to write Chinese first and then translated it into English and some of my expressions are very Chinese, which may cause my teachers confused about what I'm trying to say. I had to explain myself, it usually took a long time to explain, and also it was an embarrassing and 'lose face' moment ...</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It can affect students' output - Importance of a listener's reaction <p>-China English may affect Participant3' way of thinking and cause misunderstandings</p>
S3	<p>Yes, after studying here, I see 'face' in a different way, people here pay attention to politeness and their behaviours, but they rarely worried about 'lose face' or how they were perceived... which gave me the courage to be myself and express myself, I'm still trying to do that, as I was raised differently, my parents are very strict with me, so that is also why I chose to continue my study here. I think communication is important, for students who have the intention of studying here, I suggest you express yourselves, don't hold back, from my experiences, teachers here won't judge you, they genuinely care about you and want to help you and also classmates are willing to make friends with you, so you need to not judge yourself, it is ok to make mistakes.</p>	<p>Opportunities for Chinese international students</p> <p>Support for Chinese international students</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Positive perceptions about 'face' -Need for self-confident - Implications for teachers of Chinese International students - The importance of the role of the teacher

S4	I enjoy studying here because the education mode is more comfortable for me, the atmosphere of the class is relaxing... learning here is quite different from studying in China. Teachers here pay more attention to the interaction with students and often encourage students to learn. Most of the teaching is in small classes size but in China, the teaching model is more 'fixed', which is mainly based on large classes sizes...so at the beginning, I had a hard time adapting to the teaching mode here , and there were also some difficulty and problems about language... my English is not very good, and I also could not understand others, others may feel the same about me...	Importance of the role of the teachers Different teaching methods as opportunities and challenges.	-Importance of the role of the teacher in developing a nurturing learning space -Different teaching methods in here and China -Language could be a challenge
S4	I learn 'face' and 'face culture' online... I'm always aware of it but I'm not sure I fully understand it, so I go online, and also my families will talk about 'face'... but I don't feel 'face' have an impact on my study life or academic areas, but it has a small impact on my social life. I didn't feel the impact of 'face' during my study in Scotland, but I did have some experiences with 'face'... when my Chinese friends want me to do something or want me to pay the bills, I cannot say no, cause if I refused them I may 'lose face' or they may 'lose face'...	'Face' as a challenge to Chinese student	- Participant 4 is aware of 'face', but only feels the impact on a social context... - 'face' could have an impact on the student's social life
S4	I feel positive about myself; I think I'm confident to express myself if I'm not confidently, how can I expect others to listen to me carefully? Also, my teachers and classmates are really kind to me, they helped me in many ways, I'm lucky, and I'm grateful... in China, the classroom size is bigger, and more students than here, so there is not really any opportunities for me to practise my English, also we did have group talks or presentations that much, but in here, in an authentic environment with students from different countries, I can feel my English improving, I'm more confident to speak English... For me, online study benefits me more than face to face class study, I feel more comfortable speaking English online, I feel comfortable talking to the camera and less pressure, but I don't	Opportunities for Chinese international students	-Need for self-confident - Group study and presentations can help develop language skills and build confidence - - Authentic language environment can help students develop their language skills - Online study is more comfortable for participant4

	life here...		
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Participant Data – University B:

Participants	Selected Quotes	Themes	Subthemes
S5	I enjoyed studying here because all the teachers are very erudite and professional. And I really enjoy the seminars. However, it's quite different, especially the teaching style and assignment. There are many interactions between teachers and students, and between students and students which are rare in China. Teachers won't deny the answers of students or point out any mistakes, even they were wrong. Every student needs to get involved in the discussion and share their ideas and thoughts.	Importance of the role of the teachers Different teaching methods as opportunities.	-Importance of the role of the teacher in developing a nurturing learning space -Different teaching methods in here and China -Students' independence and thinking is expected
S5	For me, some literature is too difficult to understand and writing essays are also difficult to get high marks, I've always been very competitive with my marks in China and also here, and to be frank, I have always been top of my class in China, but in here it is hard, which is quite frustrating and for me is "lose face"... In China, I'm not sure about other places, but in the education environment I grow up if you speak non-standard English even mandarin in school, you will get laughed at, So, in class, If I am not 100% sure about the answer, I will not raise my hand to answer it...	Challenges to Chinese international students' learning	-'Face' may have an impact on students' learning and confidence - It can affect students' input and output
S5	I guess my awareness of "face" or "face culture" begins at school and home and since I was a child I can feel it, as I mentioned early, I've always been very competitive, and my parents have high expectations for me, too, so "face" did have an impacted on me if I didn't get a high mark or I'm not top at my class, I'll feel not just lose my face but also my parents' face. I think my parents think the same... so I was always	'Face' as a challenge to Chinese student	-The impact of 'face' may cause students' anxiety - Long-term impact and awareness of

	<p>nervous about taking exams and the results.</p> <p>But in here, Not really(feel the impact of “face”). From my point of view, people here are really confident and they pay more attention to themselves instead of other people’s views. Therefore, I was worried about what others may think of me when I first got here, but now I do not feel others judge me, or I think I don’t care that much anymore...</p>		<p>“face”</p> <p>-The impact of ‘face’ may impact their confidence</p> <p>- The notion of “face” can decrease with time/time spent in a non-Chinese environment</p>
S5	<p>I don’t really feel very positive about myself, I think my English is not so good even if I have already studied abroad. Nowadays, in China, even a little boy can speak smooth English if he is in an international school in Beijing or Shanghai or other big cities... so it makes me questioned myself sometimes, why on earth did I come abroad, and still not so well at English, while even children can speak better English than me...</p> <p>But I think “face” to some degree, has a good impact on me, I pushed myself harder... and all my potentials, I become even harder working on my study, so that I don’t need to “lose face”. I’m more self-disciplined.</p>	‘Face’ as a challenge to Chinese students	<p>-‘Face’ may have an impact on personal identity and confidence</p> <p>-‘Face’ also has a good impact on participant’s studies and life.</p>
S5	I like group work and discussions, I feel very good because everyone can share their ideas as well. My classmates and groups are very supportive and nice to me, I learned a	Opportunities for Chinese international students	<p>-The behaviour of the group participants is important</p> <p>-group can be supportive</p>

	<p>lot from them, teachers are also very patient and guide us...</p> <p>Actually, I will feel more confident and relaxed to express myself online, but still, I can feel “face” has an impact on me even during the online study, maybe I am not that confident in what I’m gonna say...</p>	<p>‘Face’ as a challenge to Chinese students</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the role of teachers is also important <p>The online study helps build confidence and provided a relaxing environment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -“face” can still have an impact on participant5’ class performance
S5	<p>Yes, I think we haven’t changed our Chinese way of thinking instead we always translate Chinese into English before we speak English. Sometimes I will also speak “China English”, but I’m not worried about it, first English is just a tool of communication, and it doesn’t matter only if others can understand me. Second, I’d love to be corrected if someone notices my “China English”, it helps me improve, so if they can point out my mistakes rather than laugh at me or judge me, then I’m fine with that.</p> <p>A little bit worried about “lose face”. Because in the future I will be an English teacher. If I speak China English, how can my students trust me?</p> <p>Also, Sometimes my roommates or classmates can not understand what I mean due to my China English. For example, It should be “turn on the light” instead of “open the light”. It could be one of the awkward moments for me, which I think can be seen as “lose face”?</p>	<p>The importance of recognising China English as a tool of communication</p> <p>China English can lead to “lose face”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Participant5 feels comfortable using China English - China English may affect Participant5’ way of thinking and using English <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Importanc e of a listener’s reaction - “China English” may affect participan t5’ profess ionalism as a further teacher - China English may cause misunderstandings and “lose face”
S5	<p>Yes, after a year and a half of learning in Scotland, “face” becomes less important for me. Because caring</p>	<p>Opportunities for Chinese</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Build self-confident

	<p>much about “face” cannot solve any problems but exhaust myself. I put more focus on myself instead of other people’s views. I tend to enjoy real life instead of making much money. My view of values and the world has also changed a lot, I tend to be more relaxed, I am so proud of my Alma Mater and also my major. I’m also so grateful to my teachers and classmates, they have offered nothing but their general hearts. When I apply for jobs, I can talk about my professional knowledge and answer questions in confidence. I think if I want to acquire authentic English, I must watch English dramas, books or movies and also talk with native speakers, if in China and here we can have those classes that we learn English through movies and native-English teachers can analyze those movies or books for us that will be better...</p>	<p>international students</p> <p>Support for Chinese international students</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implications for teachers of Chinese International students - The importance of the role of the teachers and classmates
S6	<p>Teaching and learning are very different between here and in China. There were no lectures and seminars in China. Teachers will upload lectures and you can learn online, then you post your questions, like Q&A, here teachers expected you to be independent and have the ability to self-study. I’m not an independent student, I need teachers to supervise me, therefore, when I first come here, I don’t know what to do and I can’t follow up... but after the first semester, I find it’s easier and I can feel my development, not just with my study, but also with my personal life, I’m more independent now..</p>	<p>Importance of the role of the teachers</p> <p>Different teaching methods as opportunities and challenges.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Importance of the role of the teacher in developing a nurturing learning space -Different teaching methods in here and China
S6	<p>I think “Face” is important to all Chinese people, for example, since we are just children if you had a high mark, your parents will make sure everybody knows, “make sure the world knows!” and if you are not well behaved in front of other people then you parents will consider you “lose</p>	<p>‘Face’ as a challenge to Chinese student</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participant 6 is aware of ‘face’, and also deeply affected by “face”

	<p>their face"... and your teachers will also accuse us of "losing her/his face" if our grades are not as good as those of other classes ... "face" is everywhere... I always been a person who values "face" highly, even since I was a child... I'm one of the good students, my grades are always high, teachers and parents are proud of me, I'm the "someone else's child" in other parents' eyes...so when I went to university, I was so proud, I think others are beneath me, teachers also praise me in public... I need to show others that "I'm a genius", and effortless... so I got cocky and lazy, when I was in my third year, my grades went bad...</p>		<p>- 'Face' could have an impact on the student's study life</p>
S6	<p>So when I want to practise oral English, I noticed my roommate is also practising English, but her grades are not as good as mine, and I know my oral English is bad, cause where I grow up was not considering oral English important, schools more valued other aspects (exams, writing, grammar...)...so I did want to practise English in our accommodation, cause I did not want my roommate to hear me speaking English and that will make me "lose face", cause they all think I'm good... then the results are my roommate is better and I'm worse...</p> <p>When I came to Scotland, I found people here are more open, people will not judge you and you are "normal" people, even you wear weird cloth or you got tattoos all over your face, no one will think you are weird, but in China, you may feel people can't stop looking at you... so when I speak English, people here will also encourage and praise me, and also my teacher will say "oh, your English is great", therefore, I became more and more confident.</p>	<p>Opportunities for Chinese international students</p>	<p>'Face' could have an impact on the student's oral English and output</p> <p>- Authentic language environment can help students develop their language skills</p> <p>-Need for self-confident</p> <p>-The role of teachers is very important</p>

S6	<p>Teachers and classmates may not really know me... because I have online classes, I barely had face to face classes, and we have over 100 students, so we do not really know each other very well... and I prefer face to face, cause I found myself more concentrate in the classroom...sure, online study is more relaxing because you don't need to open the camera, you don't need to be focused all the time, but there are also problems, for students like me, (need supervision) I could be lazy, and learning efficiency is not high...</p>	Online study as a challenge to international students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Online study is more comfortable for participant 6 - Online study can also be not effective - A negative experience of learning online
S6	<p>I speak China English, my roommate sometimes says she cannot understand my English, but not because of the accent, but my expression, I think it is because of the mode of thinking, I tend to think in Chinese and translate it to English...and I was more anxious in China, nowadays if you do not speak "standard English", people in China will criticise you, but in here... but here, basically all my classmates are Chinese, and they all speak 'China English', so I am not feeling 'lose face', everybody says 'China English'... sometimes, when I have a conversation with my roommate, and I cannot remember the word or I don't know how to express, I will describe the thing or the words, and my roommate will help me out, I don't feel her judge me or considered my English is bad or despises me...</p>	'China English' as a diversity of English	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The anxiety of speaking English may come from China rather than here - The listeners' reaction is important
S6	<p>Teachers here do not care about your accents or your oral English, especially we learn TESOL, teachers here have lots of experiences with students who are not native speakers, so we don't really need to be anxious about our English... and teachers will compliment you even you just made a little progress...and it helps build your confidence... Here, grades are confidential, you do know others' grades, which is great,</p>	Opportunities for Chinese international students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Impact on participant's output -The role of teachers is important

	and no one will ask about your grades... and I'm more independent, when I first came here, I cried every day at night, because I cannot follow up, I don't know how to check my email, which classroom I'm in, but others seem to know it all, I can't find the material...courses are difficult for me, that moment I'll feel "lose face" and very stressful and questioned myself...	'Face' as a challenge to Chinese student	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop students' self-confident -Independence is needed here -“face” can affect personal identity
S6	I hope there can be a group for students who have questions or an office here to help students, and also relevant courses can introduce the life and study here. Also, learning English in a good English environment is important, teachers here always compliment you but teachers in China will not, maybe teachers in China can encourage students to be more confident so when students came here, they feel ok to speak English, rather than consider their English not good enough. However, there is one teacher of mine, will only praise you when your answer is the answer, he wants to hear... which is unusual in the UK... most teachers are great, they will make you feel good about yourself, but there are teachers who are very strict and serious which may make me lose the motivation of study... I hope teachers can be more supportive...	<p>Support for students' development</p> <p>Importance of the role of the teachers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need for pre-arrival English and English culture courses - Need for more support for students to feel confident learning in Scotland - Implications for teachers of Chinese International students

Participant Data – University B:

Participants	Selected Quotes	Themes	Subthemes
S7	Studying is quite different here, especially the teaching style and methods. We will have a lot of presentations and essays here but in China, we have more like “tests”... Besides, there are many discussions between teachers and students , and between students and students which are rare in China. Every point of the materials needed	<p>Importance of the role of the teachers</p> <p>Different teaching methods as opportunities.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Importance of the role of the teacher in developing a nurturing learning space -Different teaching methods in here and China

	<p>to be discussed, everyone needs to share their ideas, their opinions, which is very new to me, cause in China, we are rarely been asked about our ideas, so I was lost and confused, I did not have any ideas... I realized I was never thought about these, I just learned what teachers taught without thinking...</p>		<p>-Students' independence and thinking is expected - Develop students' self-reflection</p>
S7	<p>Sometimes, I feel I was forced to answer questions in the UK, cause everybody was so excited to discuss or share ideas if I don't say anything, it seems odd and weird... and I don't want to be the one who ruins the atmosphere, which can be very stressful...I guess it is also a way to "give other face"... In China, there will be students who raise their hands, if teachers picked them, and heard just one answer, they will rarely pick another one...so I didn't feel I have to answer it... Then about learning (language)... I will need more time and effort to learn the materials, compared to native speakers, I also need time to react to what teachers say during the class, I need time to understand and translate to Chinese, also my expression may not be accurate, it can be frustrating and sometimes "lose face" and do dare to speak English if I cannot be understood by others...</p>	Challenges to Chinese international students' learning	<p>- 'Face' may have an impact on students' learning - It may cause stress and anxiety - It can affect students' learning motivation - also has an impact on students' input and output</p>
S7	<p>My awareness of "face" or "face culture" begins very young, it came from families... when families and my parents' friends were together having a meal... I would always be asked to perform something.., it can be dancing or singing or reading a poem... I was so embarrassing each time, I guess that is because I felt I was "losing face"...</p>	'Face' as a challenge to Chinese student	<p>Long-term impact and awareness of "face" -The impact of 'face' may impact their confidence - The notion of</p>

	<p>When I came here, I noticed that most Chinese students are not willing to speak English or expressing their ideas, their heads are always low, afraid of teachers may ask them to answer questions, and they may not have the “right” answer, and I was one of them... also people here will say hi to each other, even they don’t know each other when I first got here, I didn’t understand...cause in China, strangers would not say hi even they were in a closed space, now when I look back, I felt I was rude... but I’m more open now, I would try to fit in and speak as much as I can, and considered less about if I’m “losing face” when I did some silly or awkward things...</p>	<p>Opportunities for Chinese international students</p>	<p>“face” can decrease with time/time spent in a non-Chinese environment</p>
S7	<p>In my opinion, Chinese students tend to hang out together, I guess that is because we all speak the same language, and similar background, it can never go wrong, it is a safe choice...but making friends with people from a different country can bring some “problems” or “misunderstandings”... I will have to explain my behaviours, or my habits and accept the differences we have, trying to understand each other, that is a lot of work to do and also something I tried to avoid...I know that the whole point of going abroad is to meet different people and cultures, learn different things, but it was very very hard for me, at the beginning... However, “face” did have a positive impact, I will feel very satisfied or happy if my mark or grade is better than native students, it is what Chinese may call “gain face”... therefore, I will work hard and feel encouraged!</p>	<p>‘Face’ as a challenge to Chinese students</p> <p>Opportunities for Chinese international students</p>	<p>-‘Face’ may have an impact on students’ behaviours and choices</p> <p>- it may also be due to students’ personality</p> <p>-‘Face’ also has a good impact on participant’s studies and life.</p>
S7	<p>In class, when someone tells a joke, I may not get it, due to accents or just because I don’t understand, I will laugh along with others, cause</p>	<p>‘Face’ as a challenge to Chinese students</p>	<p>-‘Face’ can have an impact on</p>

	<p>I didn't want others to find out I did get it, I will feel "lose face"... I'm glad that my classmates and teachers are very kind and patient, they will encourage me, I do not feel people hold discriminations against me...so I feel more confident than I was before... I'm more willing to speak out my ideas and communicate with other students, but to be honest, I still can feel "face", especially when I do presentations...</p>	<p>Opportunities for Chinese international students</p>	<p>students' behaviours</p> <p>-The behaviour of the group participants is important -group can be supportive - the role of teachers is also important</p> <p>-“Face” can still have an impact on participant7</p>
S7	<p>In China, “face” is an “unspoke rule”. In a good way, people will not make each other “lose face” unless they were on purpose, therefore, the relationships in China like the sea, which seems quiet and peaceful on the surface, but down there are not... so you cannot really have proper communications or solve the problems between you two, no one will say “no” to each other, especially for those people you are closed with... which is bad, because no one is happy in the end... In here, I feel don't need to follow the rule of “face”, I can say “no”, I can be angry about my roommates having parties all night, I can say “no”, I don't want to hang out, I'm tired.... This is a good thing for me, I can have some “me” time, without worrying about how others may think about me...</p>	<p>'Face' as a challenge to Chinese students</p> <p>Opportunities for Chinese international students</p>	<p>-“Face” may have an impact on participant7's behaviours</p> <p>-Study here has a positive side for participant7's emotions and life</p>
S7	<p>I'm not fully engaged in class, it depends on whether I'm interested in the class content or teachers...I'm also very passive, I</p>	<p>'Face' as a challenge to Chinese students</p>	<p>-Participant 7 tends to be passive and self-aware.</p>

	<p>will need teachers and my classmates to lead me...</p> <p>It is normal to speak China English, we are not native speakers, as long as I can be understood then it is ok for me. I couldn't tell if I'm speaking China English, I guess I did? But I wasn't aware of that? So I didn't feel "lose face". It certainly affects my way of thinking, because I will be thinking in Chinese... but I'll change a different expression if I found out people didn't understand me...</p> <p>I didn't feel China English has an impact on my social life or my study, cause every time I speak or write an essay, I would use the words I'm confident with or I know the sentences are correct...</p>	<p>The importance of recognising China English as a tool of communication</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implications for teachers of Chinese International students - China English may affect Participant7' way of thinking and using English - China English may cause misunderstandings - It can be a potential impact of "face" but the participant wasn't aware of it
S7	<p>I feel people here can be themselves, they don't care what other people may think of them, I was looking forwards to be one, and I'm still trying, it is just not easy...study here really build my confidence...I'm now feeling comfortable talking to native speakers...</p> <p>If universities or teachers can organize more interesting activities, let everyone get familiar with each other, then it may be better for Chinese students to blend in, even just parties or movie nights, things like that... cause Chinese students can be very shy, they need someone to push them, so if universities can prove opportunities like these, it may help Chinese students to speak English more confidently.</p>	<p>Opportunities for Chinese international students</p> <p>Support for Chinese international students</p>	<p>-Build self-confident</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implications for universities and teachers

S8	<p>Teaching and learning are different between here and in China. I had native speakers as my teachers in university back in China, but I still feel difficult to adapt to the pace of learning here. Luckily, teachers here are generously want to help you and support you. It is nice to learn in a different way, it opened my mind, and let me know that I need to think critically, which was new to me. In China, I just learned whatever teachers taught and never ask any questions to teachers, for me or for most Chinese students...</p>	<p>Importance of the role of the teachers</p> <p>Different teaching methods as opportunities and challenges.</p>	<p>-Importance of the role of the teacher in supporting new students</p> <p>-Different teaching methods in here and China</p>
S8	<p>“Face” is important to me, I was aware of “face” when I was a child. I am a person with very high self-esteem, so “losing face” is unacceptable to me, I cared about my grade in school, I cared about how my parents look at me, I cared about how my friends think of me, it was very very stressful and tired. I had to pretend to be someone else so that everyone will love me, be a good student, be a good girl, be a good friend... so even when I came here, I also can feel “face”, I want to impress others, to show my English is good even as a Chinese, and of course, I’ll need full A for my study... I don’t know if it is a good thing or a bad thing, on one hand, I do feel happy when people are impressed, or I got a high mark, but on the other hand, the process is painful...I'm struggling with it</p>	<p>‘Face’ as a challenge to Chinese student</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participant 8 is aware of ‘face’, and also deeply affected by “face” - ‘Face’ could have an impact on the student’s study life and social life - “Face” can cause anxiety and affect participant’s identity and behaviours
S8	<p>I’m loosed up now, I tried to balance my life. In Scotland, I think there is less competitive pressure, unlike in China where you have to work a hundred times harder to catch up, I learned to enjoy my life, to relax, not just learning all the time... for me, the positive side is with the learning environment I can feel my oral English is better and better... In China, my English is also great, but only with writing and</p>	<p>Opportunities for Chinese international students</p>	<p>- Authentic language environment can help students develop their language skills</p>

	reading but not listening and speaking, so yeah, I can still feel “face” has an impact on me, sometimes, I'm not sure about the usage of English, I will choose not to say and looked it up later without just simply asking other people about it... I suppose because I don't want to “lose face”...		‘Face’ could have an impact on the student’s oral English and output -Need for self-confident
S8	I prefer face to face study, online study is not efficient for me... I cannot feel the connections between people, cause we are talking to the screen and camera... I don't know about others but I can't focus on what teachers are saying, because some classes are early, I woke up and may not change my PJ and even without eating breakfast, I just opened my laptop and fell asleep... but face to face is different, you need to get up early, and prepare yourself, wash face and get dressed, and go to the uni, so when you sit there, you will be fully awaked, it helps me focus...	Online study as a challenge to international students	- Online study can also be not effective - A negative experience of learning online
S8	I rarely speak China English, I may but I tried to control myself...I resist speaking ‘China English’, I feel “lose face” to speak “China English”. For me, I have always wanted to talk like a British, and in China when I do presentations, I will try to speak like a “British”, I want to be better than my classmates, somehow, I considered British English is superior to ‘China English’. However, when I came to Scotland, especially Glasgow, I was shocked and realized what I have watched (movies, TV shows) in China was nothing like here... that is when I first realize accents or even ‘China English’ is a thing, so it was hard for me to understand what people were saying and even harder for me to pick up the “British sound”... I was quite frustrated but came to	‘China English’ as a challenge	-The anxiety of speaking English may come from China rather than here - “China English” can cause “lose face” for participant8

	Glasgow is my own choice... except the accents, Glasgow is really a nice place, people are kind and lovely and I'm glad to be here, I even now try to imitate a Scottish accent, it is fun... and my attitude towards "China Englis" also changed, it is ok to speak CE as long as you can be understood by others...		-The attitude towards "China English" can be changed with time
S8	Teachers here will not judge your accents or your oral English, they will encourage you to speak more, even during class if you are a Chinese international student, some teachers will pick you up to answer the questions, and always gave positive feedback, so I don't anxious about my English... it helps you feel confident about yourself and your English skills... I'll feel "lose face" and very stressed if my grades are not well, or things not going well with my study, cause I know my parents gave up a lot to just get me to go abroad and sometimes I feel not strong enough or independent, I will miss my family and homesick...	Opportunities for Chinese international students 'Face' as a challenge to Chinese student	-Impact on participant's output -The role of teachers is important - Develop students' self-confident -Independence is needed here - "face" can affect emotions - "face" can potentially bring pressure
S8	I hope there can be a place for students to talk about the problems and difficulties or meetings and I hope teachers can be more supportive... during this covid-19 situation, I really felt isolated and very depressed... It will also be nice to know more students from other countries even we are not in the same major or classes, it will help students adapt to their study faster.	Support for students' development Importance of the role of the teachers and universities	- Need for more support for students to feel confident and comfortable learning in Scotland - Implications for universities and teachers of Chinese International students